

score

D9.3- Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities

DATE OF DELIVERY - 30/06/2025

AUTHOR(S) – Laura De Nale (EUR)
Maëva Voltz (EUR)
Rochelle Caruso (ERINN)
Casey Borklund (ERINN)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534

DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS

Project acronym	SCORE
Project title	Smart Control of the Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities
Starting date	01.07.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-LC-CLA-2020-2
Grant Agreement No	101003534

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	D9.3
Work package number	WP9
Deliverable title	Final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities
Lead beneficiary	Euronovia
Author(s)	Laura De Nale (EUR), Maëva Voltz (EUR), Rochelle Caruso (ERINN), Casey Borklund (ERINN)
Due date	30/06/2025
Actual submission date	30/06/2025
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision table			
Version	Name	Date	Description
V0.1	Laura De Nale (EUR), Rochelle Caruso (ERINN)	04/06/2025	First draft
V0.2	Maëva Voltz and Laura De Nale (EUR), Rochelle Caruso and Casey Borklund (ERINN)	24/06/2025	Updated draft
V0.3	Attilio Vaccaro (MBI), Mar Reira (ENT)	26/06/2025	Internal peer-review
V0.4	Maëva Voltz and Laura De Nale (EUR), Rochelle Caruso and Casey Borklund (ERINN)	27/06/2025	Updated draft after peer-review
V1.0	Salem Gharbia (ATU)	30/06/2025	Final version and submission

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCLL	Coastal City Living Lab
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Approach
EC	European Commission
FP7	Seventh Framework Programme
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KMS	Knowledge Management Strategy
KO	Knowledge Output
KOQ	Knowledge Output Questionnaire
KOT	Knowledge Output Template
KT	Knowledge Transfer
KTP	Knowledge Transfer Plan
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Project Results
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

All information in this document only reflects the author's view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city living labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Oarsoaldea, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

This deliverable is the final report on the project exploitation initiatives and related impacts on innovation, including dissemination and communication activities. It is divided into 3 sections:

1. Chapter 1 includes a description of all communication and dissemination materials and activities developed and implemented during the project lifetime, including publications, events, notable activities and outputs (such as webinars, MOOCs and publications), and activities engaging stakeholders with a specific focus on CCLLs and a section on impact assessment;
2. Chapter 2 outlines the methodology used to identify SCORE's exploitable outputs;
3. Chapter 3 focuses on the presentation and description of the Key Exploitable Results and the actions deployed to maximise their impact.

The document is jointly drafted by Euronovia (WP9 leader) and ERINN (leader of the Knowledge management, transfer and exploitation of results), with inputs from all partners.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

WP9 is a transversal work package integrating the results of all the WPs in the dissemination and exploitation process: it will ensure that the outputs and learnings arising from all the activities and all WPs of the project are visible to a wide audience and that these can be learned from and implemented on a European scale.

Figure 1: WP9 in relation to other WPs

WP9 collaborated with all work packages to ensure sufficient and successful dissemination and exploitation.

Notably, WP9 worked particularly closely with WP2 across the tasks to ensure CDE activities were targeted to specific stakeholders and implemented to have optimal impact on local/regional stakeholders. As an essential aspect of WP9 knowledge transfer activities, further details are provided throughout.

WP9 activities are also linked with a number of other work packages and associated deliverables, as outlined below:

□ **WP2:**

- D2.4: *CCLLs Knowledge and Lessons learned*. The deliverable offers practical guidance drawn from the ten SCORE Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) on how best to create, implement, and evaluate a Coastal City Living Lab. While rooted in Coastal City Living Lab contexts, the recommendations are broadly relevant to any Living Lab focused on public engagement and resilience.

□ **WP4:**

- D4.1: *Citizen Science Playbook* (M48). This deliverable reports on **the stakeholders' networks built in each CCLL** as part of the WP2 activities to identify champions in each CCLL, which will be the SCORE ambassadors with the local communities.
- D4.4: *Citizen science activities press-release* (M30). **Press releases and media actions** related to the various co-monitoring activities in CCLLs. These activities are mentioned under 2.5.9.2 of this report.
- D4.5: *Citizen science activities in CCLLs* (M36). This deliverable presents a series of the **citizen science activities and workshops** carried out with the collaboration of WP2 in all the CCLLs. Some of these activities are mentioned under 2.5.10.1 of this report.

□ **WP6:**

- Task 6.5: Decision-support **guidelines for policy makers** (M30-44); closely linked with the knowledge transfer methodology and the update of residual coastal risk management guidelines by local/regional policymakers. A specific section on policy makers considerations and engagement is available in 2.4.3 of this report.

□ **WP7:**

- D7.5: Policy guidelines aimed at different levels of governance, supported by evidence-based adaptation planning tools and use scenarios (M47). A set of 3 **policy guidelines / policy briefs** (2-4 pages each) aimed at different levels of governance and policy making, and in a variety of coastal management contexts, containing evidence on coastal ecosystem services and their adaptation costs and benefits, as these have emerged from the SCORE project (especially its success stories). A summary of the first policy briefs published by the project is available in 2.5.9.3 of this report.

□ **WP8:**

- D8.10 (M24): *Early Warning and Spatial Digital Twin Assessment Plan* and D8.11 (M48): *Early Warning and Spatial Digital Twin Assessment Report*; links the **Impact Assessment** to the **knowledge transfer methodology** and developing the knowledge transfer plans for the Early Warning System and Digital Twin.

□ **WP10:**

- D10.2: *Networking and synergies between EU project* (M48) reports on the **networking and synergies with other EU projects**, whose involvement is summarised in 2.5.11 of this report.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES.....	11
1.1. Branding_____	12
1.1.1. Logo and Visual identity	12
1.1.2. Templates	12
1.2. Communication materials_____	14
1.2.1. One page project description	15
1.2.2. Flyer	15
1.2.3. Poster and roll-up banner	15
1.2.4. Infographics	16
1.2.5. Brochures.....	18
1.2.6. Audio-visual material and YouTube channel.....	19
1.3. Website_____	21
1.4. Social media and online presence_____	22
1.4.1. SCORE's social media accounts	22
1.4.2. Partners' social media accounts and websites.....	25
1.5. Publications_____	25
1.5.1. SCORE bi-annual newsletters	25
1.5.2. Press relations and media coverage.....	25
1.5.3. Media appearances	26
1.5.4. Relevant non-scientific publications	27
1.5.5. Scientific publications.....	28
1.6. Events_____	28
1.6.1. Organisation of project events.....	28
1.6.1.1. EbA Training Schools and citizen science activities	28
1.6.1.2. SCORE international workshops	32
1.6.1.3. Final event	32
1.6.2. Participation in external events.....	33
1.7. Notable activities and outputs_____	34
1.7.1. Webinars series	34
1.7.2. Geostories.....	34
1.7.3. MOOCs.....	36
1.7.4. Policy briefs	37
1.7.5. Synergies with other projects & initiatives	39

1.8. Monitoring and assessment of KPIs	40
1.9. Impact assessment of activities at CCLL level	42
1.9.1. Sligo	42
1.9.2. Dublin	43
1.9.3. Vilanova i la Geltrú	44
1.9.4. Benidorm	44
1.9.5. Oarsoladea	45
1.9.6. Oeiras	46
1.9.7. Massa	47
1.9.8. Piran	48
1.9.9. Gdansk	49
1.9.10. Samsun	49
2. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND TRANSFER METHODOLOGY	51
2.1. Knowledge management and transfer overview	51
2.2. Knowledge management and transfer for SCORE	52
2.2.1. Cross Cutting Principles	53
2.2.2. KT Training and Support Activities	54
2.2.3. Knowledge Transfer Impact Assessment	55
2.3. Knowledge management & Transfer Steps and Protocols	55
2.3.1. Collect & Understand	56
2.3.2. Analyse & Validate	57
2.3.3. Transfer & Exploit	59
3. PRIORITISED KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	61
3.1. Co-Creation & Living Labs	63
3.2. Increasing Data Availability	87
3.3. Green & Technological Tools for Climate Adaptation Strategies	107
3.3.1. Digital Twin & Data Visualisation	133
Conclusion	158
Annex 1 – KPI analysis	159
Annex 2 – List of publications	160
Annex 3 – List of events	168
Annex 4 - Knowledge Outputs	174
Annex 5 – Impact readiness levels	194

INDEX OF FIGURES

Figure 1: WP9 in relation to other WPs.....	5
Figure 2: SCORE project logo	12
Figure 3: Power Point template.....	13
Figure 4: Deliverable template	14
Figure 5: Agenda and meeting minutes template.....	14
Figure 6: SCORE flyer	15
Figure 7: SCORE poster and roll-up	16
Figure 8: SCORE Infographics.....	16
Figure 9: SCORE CCLLs infographics regarding prioritised EBAs.....	17
Figure 10: Infographic to promote Financial Resilience Strategies	17
Figure 11: Infographic templates to promote EBA selection & implementation.....	18
Figure 12: Cover and inside pages of the SCORE final brochure	18
Figure 13: Example of CCLL material developed at the CCLL level.....	19
Figure 14: Homepage of the SCORE YouTube channel	20
Figure 15: Homepage of the SCORE website.....	21
Figure 16: SCORE website visitors by country	22
Figure 17: SCORE LinkedIn and Twitter accounts.....	23
Figure 18: SCORE Facebook and Instagram accounts	24
Figure 19: SCORE final media press kit and press release.....	26
Figure 20: SCORE partners at the Bright Night Researchers Night in Pisa, Italy	29
Figure 21: Kids participating in the SCORE Minecraft workshop in Dublin, Ireland.....	30
Figure 22: Local activities in Benidorm and Gdansk during the third training school.....	31
Figure 23: SCORE Final event at ECCA2025	32
Figure 24: Hazard maps developed in WP1 as displayed in the Massa CCLL Geostory	35
Figure 25: The Piran CCLL has displayed their most impactful citizen engagement activities in their GeoStories as a GeoCarousel, making it interactive for readers.....	35
Figure 26: The Oeiras CCLL has described and displayed information about their sensor deployment activities in their municipality on their GeoStory	36
Figure 27: SCORE Full Knowledge Transfer Pathway and Methodology	56
Figure 28: SCORE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Collect and Understand	56
Figure 29: Methodology: Analyse and Validate.....	58
Figure 30: SCORE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Transfer and Exploit.....	59

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 1: Communication and dissemination tools, materials and activities planned and related KPIs.....	11
Table 2: Most visited pages of the SCORE website	22
Table 3: Overview of media appearances by country and type	27
Table 4: European projects participating with SCORE in the Adapt4Coast Cluster	39
Table 5: Distribution of KPI evaluation scores.....	40
Table 6: List of relevant definitions for knowledge management and transfer.....	51
Table 7: Overview of Knowledge Outputs for SCORE.....	61

1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Different tools and materials were planned to reach the SCORE objectives and to ensure proper project visibility and impact, as detailed in the Description of Work and summarised in the Table 1 below.

Table 1: Communication and dissemination tools, materials and activities planned and related KPIs

Visual Identity	The project branding helps all partners communicate about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner. The project branding includes project logo , visual identity , written identity including tagline and key messages and templates for Word and PowerPoint.
Communication materials	A communication package (M6) containing the main elements of the project is available as: a PPT presentation, poster, roll-up banner and a Word document (one-page project description, objectives, impacts) including logo, visual identity materials and templates. - 1 flyer (M6), 1 final brochure (M48), 1 timeline infography (M12), 1 motion design video promoted through the EU audiovisual channels and YouTube (M33), Partners interviews (M36) will be integrated into video for wide online dissemination - Liaise with the different partners' communication departments for wider dissemination of these materials using the partners' existing communication channels
Website	The public website contains information targeted for the general public (description of the project, the WPs, the partners, basic information on the technology) as well as specific information targeted towards the different types of stakeholders linked to the project (training materials, scientific papers, environmental impact).
Social networks and online presence	- Social web-based media (creation of 1 LinkedIn page, 1 Facebook page, 1 Instagram account and 1 Twitter account) targets the general audience as well as more technology related stakeholders - All project partners regularly re-share content from their personal and institutional social media accounts to direct their audience to SCORE's channels and website, following an agreed-upon schedule. In doing so, the consortium will reap the benefits of the partners' combined audience base, while building a strong brand that is able to live beyond the 4-year project and thus have an extended impact on cultural heritage transformation. By adding relevant hashtags (such as #H2020, #EBA) SCORE's reach is further amplified.
Press relations	- At least 2 press releases (M6 and M42) and 1 final media press kit to be done at the end of the project and disseminated to the press - 8 newsletters (every 6 months), - Public relations and media coverage (national/international press, communication to citizens and authorities) in partnership with the press department of the partners. - 2 articles in specialized magazines (Y3 and Y4)
Scientific publications	30 scientific publications in science, industry and social science journals to widely disseminate the project outcomes and results.
Events	- Organisation of several events: 3 training schools , 10 workshops , 2 webinars and 1 final infoday targeted at the general public and other non-experts - Participation in 10 scientific conferences and 3 exhibition fairs to present the project activities and outcomes. - At least 1 participation/exhibition in science popularization events , the EU researcher's night, the national science festivals existing in the partner countries

The different dissemination and communication activities, as well as the tools created and implemented during the project lifetime, are presented below.

1.1. Branding

1.1.1. Logo and Visual identity

The project branding, created right at the start of the project, helped partners to communicate about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner: it includes the project logo, project identity and style guide, templates for Word and PowerPoint documents.

- The **SCORE logo** consists of a clear and modern font and of an icon representing a wave composed of different shades of blue. This icon symbolizes both the water element typical of the coastal cities as well as the specific challenges tackled by the project, such as the increase of sea levels, coastal erosion, and extreme weather events. This logo will be used in all communications (written deliverables, journal papers, presentations, invitations etc.) to ensure project recognition and visibility.

The project logo and symbol are available for download on the project dedicated space in the SharePoint platform, with access restricted to project partners.

Specific guidelines on how to use the logo both on a white and dark background, as well as indications on its placement, font and colours have been described in a specific brand manual created in the first months of the project.

- The **project's graphical identity** includes fonts, colours and texts directly derived from the project logotype. Such visual identity is defined by the project logo and is being used in all dissemination tools and printed materials. For more detailed information on the project graphical identity, please see [deliverable D9.5](#).

Figure 2: SCORE project logo

1.1.2. Templates

Based on the project graphical identity, several **templates** were produced during the first months of the project and are used by all partners whenever needed:

- A template for deliverables;

- A template for deliverables' review reports;
- A template for a meeting's agenda;
- A template for a meeting's minutes;
- A template for PowerPoint presentations.

Additional templates were also produced for specific purposes, such as a template for infographics (see section 1.2.4) were prepared by ERINN and Euronovia to help CCLLs illustrate the main hazards they are facing and the EBA that were selected as solutions to better protect them. Also, a template for policy briefs was prepared by the project coordinator to help the different CCLLs in preparing relevant recommendations to reach local and regional stakeholders.

Figure 3: Power Point template

Figure 4: Deliverable template

The deliverable template consists of two main pages. The left page is a cover page with a blue background featuring a circular graphic and the SCORE logo. It includes the text 'DX.N-Title of document', 'DATE OF DELIVERY - DD/MM/YYYY', 'AUTHOR(S) - NAME(S)', and 'INSTITUTION/COMPANY NAME'. The right page is a table of contents with two main sections: 'DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS' and 'VERSION MANAGEMENT'. The 'DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS' section includes a table with fields for Project acronym, Project title, Starting date, Duration, Call identifier, and Grant Agreement No. The 'VERSION MANAGEMENT' section includes a table with columns for Version, Name, Date, and Description, listing versions V 0.1 through V 1.0. At the bottom right, there is a footer with 'SCORE_Dx_n_Version number' and '2/12'.

Figure 5: Agenda and meeting minutes template

The agenda and meeting minutes template consists of three main pages. The left page is a cover page with a blue background featuring a circular graphic and the SCORE logo. It includes the text 'Name of the project meeting', 'DATE OF THE MEETING', and 'PLACE OF THE MEETING'. The middle page is a table of contents with two main sections: 'DAY 1' and 'DAY 2', each listing a schedule of activities with times and descriptions. The right page is a table of contents with two main sections: 'DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS' and 'VERSION MANAGEMENT'. The 'DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS' section includes a table with fields for Identification, Title, Author(s), Related work package, Beneficiary responsible of delivery, Date of release, Number of pages, Summary, Dissemination level, and Repository. The 'VERSION MANAGEMENT' section includes a table with columns for Version, Name, Date, and Description, listing versions V 0.1 through V 1.0. At the bottom right, there is a footer with 'Title of document - SCORE_{meeting name} minutes' and '2/6'.

1.2. Communication materials

During the first six months of the project, a communication pack with printable communication materials was prepared by EUR and distributed to project partners in order to ensure effective communication and increase public awareness of the project. It included a one-page project description, a flyer, a poster and a roll-up banner. These tools were used by partners for events in which they participated to promote the project and its early results.

1.2.1. One page project description

An information sheet/consent form translated into different languages was prepared by ATU at the start of the project for distribution to participants in any project-related activity where necessary (scientific research, user requirements and socio-economic studies, and system testing). This document contains a simple description of the SCORE project and its objectives, as well as a Consent Form that participants were requested to sign, in some cases, before the start of specific research activities.

1.2.2. Flyer

A **project flyer** with general information on the project and the 10 CCLLs was created at M6. The flyer was distributed to partners who printed and distributed it when organising or attending external events. The flyer is available for download at: https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Score_Flyer_web.pdf.

Figure 6: SCORE flyer

About SCORE

SCORE is an EU-funded project aiming to develop a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLLs) addressing water and climate related hazard to enhance coastal city climate resilience through an Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) and smart technologies.

28 partners | 12 countries | 4 years | 01.07.21-30.06.25 start-end | 10M euros budget

FOLLOW US ON SOCIAL MEDIA

SCORE H2020 Project | @SCORE_EUproject | score-eu | score_H2020

www.score-eu-project.eu

The SCORE consortium partners

Partners include: IHS, UCC, Universitat d'Alacant, Universitat de Alicante, LaMMA, naider, mbi, OERIS VALLEY, UCB, REZ, Diputació Barcelona, dlr, euronova, ZRS, ERIN, IST-ID, and others.

PROJECT COORDINATOR
Dr. Séamus Charabá - ATU Sligo, Ireland
contact@score-eu-project.eu

Smart control of the climate resilience in European coastal cities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

Project concept

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities.

To tackle these challenges, SCORE will develop and deliver a new generation of tools, technologies and methodologies, as well as validated EBAs, to enable exploration of different reintegration actions and risks.

CHALLENGES

INTEGRATED SOLUTIONS

Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs)

CCLL is one of the main concepts behind SCORE: it is a new approach that expands the living lab concept in coastal cities to address climate change adaptation and resilience issues through Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBAs) and smart technologies.

These CCLLs are evenly distributed across Europe to make sure that any solution we come up with to increase climate resilience is suitable to be replicated anywhere else.

CCLL Locations: Sligo (Ireland), Dublin (Ireland), Odzisek (Poland), Piran (Slovenia), Basque country (Spain), Benidorm (Spain), Province of Barcelona / Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), Massa (Italy), Samsun (Turkey), Oeiras (Portugal).

The CCLLs will directly involve citizens, scientists, policy makers and other stakeholders in the design process of EBA solutions through low-cost sensors for citizen science activities in order to raise their awareness of EBAs. The objective is to provide local authorities and citizens a framework and tools for continuing their engagement after the end of the project. If you would like to be involved in our activities, contact us through our website: www.score-eu-project.eu

1.2.3. Poster and roll-up banner

A project **poster** template and a **roll-up banner** were created in the first months of the project to be printed and used during external conferences and events attended by the consortium to promote and present the results arising from the project. The poster was easily editable by project partners in order to include their latest results.

Figure 7: SCORE poster and roll-up

1.2.4. Infographics

A timeline infographic was created by Euronovia to illustrate the key activities of the project throughout its duration. It was widely distributed online (SCORE website, social media) and through the project newsletter. It is available for download at: https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Timeline_Infographic-SCORE.pdf.

Figure 8: SCORE Infographics

Additional infographics were developed by ERINN, with support of the CCLLs and WP7 (Figure 9), in their relevant local languages, to illustrate the main hazards they are facing and the EBA that were selected as solutions to better protect them. These were developed to support the knowledge transfer of the MCA process with local stakeholders, in particular those stakeholders who attended the CCLL collaboration sessions to highlight the results of the session and the ongoing work in the CCLL. These were developed in coordination with KO 7.2. To overcome language barriers,

communication and dissemination materials were consistently translated into the local language, facilitating the transmission of key messages.

Figure 9: SCORE CCLLs infographics regarding prioritised EBAs.

In addition, UCD developed a catalogue of infographics templates that the CCLLs could utilise to share the outputs from the CCLLs, including research results across the technical work packages, to disseminate key messages in a simple and digestible form for their stakeholders. These had several uses: they were shared on social media, sent alongside a policy brief as a concise explanation, shared with colleagues prior to meetings to set the scene, amongst many others.

ERINN and RedRisk developed infographics for WP6 frontrunners (Oarsoaldea, Massa and Vilanova) and summary documents of their financial risk assessments in their respective native languages (Spanish, Basque and Italian) to allow for each dissemination with policymakers. Further, a general version was developed with broad recommendations for the fellows to share with their local policymakers. The template was made available to partners, allowing them to translate as necessary.

Figure 10: Infographic to promote Financial Resilience Strategies

Lastly, these infographics were also created in postcard formats by EURO to be easily distributed at events. These strategies were implemented alongside the CCLLs activities and workshops with the support of the Innovation Board, to ensure the continual engagement of stakeholders and citizens in SCORE activities.

Figure 11: Infographic templates to promote EBA selection & implementation

1.2.5. Brochures

A **final brochure** (12 pages) was created at M48 by Euronovia, with inputs from all WP leaders. It presents the main results and achievements of the project, targeting a specialist audience. This brochure was shared through the project contact database, the website, social networks, and in the June edition of the [MIP4Adapt newsletter](#).

Printed versions were distributed during the SCORE final event and exhibition booth at the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference in June 2025.

Figure 12: Cover and inside pages of the SCORE final brochure

Other **brochures and promotional materials were developed locally** by the CCLLs for distribution to local stakeholders in different languages. For example, the Piran CCLL prepared a 20-page brochure 'Results of the Piran Coastal City Living Lab from the SCORE project' in English, Italian and Slovenian and a limited edition of a 129-page book 'Piran-

specific SCORE results which combines the relevant Piran-results from the SCORE WPs, as a gift for the core CCLL organisation representatives. They also prepared note blocks with SCORE/Piran specific pages featuring a map of Piran's old town intended for users to mark EBA/ NBS interventions and highlight relevant areas on the map.

Figure 13: Material developed at the CCLL level in Piran

1.2.6. Audio-visual material and YouTube channel

Different types of audio-visual materials were planned during the project duration. **Videos** were posted on the SCORE **YouTube** channel and promoted on the social media accounts of the project and the partners:

- A [SCORE presentation video](#) and a [podcast](#) were produced by ATU at the start of the project.
- A [video message](#) was recorded by the Irish Minister for Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science, Mr Simon Harris, to support the launch of the project and displayed to all partners during the SCORE Kick-off meeting. The video received almost 2k views on Twitter.
- A [video presenting the project activities and tools](#) in an attractive and dynamic way was produced by Euronovia and published in March 2024 (M33). While the voice-over of the video is in English, subtitles are available in all the nine languages of the partners (English, Spanish, Basque, Catalan, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Slovene and Turkish). It currently has 510 views on YouTube.
- [10 partner interviews](#) were posted online, including interviews of members of the CCLLs in different languages. Interviews were recorded by Euronovia during consortium meetings or during events attended by partners.
- The [recordings of the 10 SCORE webinars](#) organised from March 2022 to May 2024 to present the main outcomes from each Work Package are available in the SCORE YouTube Channel (see section 1.7.1).
- The recording of the [SCORE final event](#) which took place on 17 June 2025 in Rimini, Italy, during the European Climate Change Adaptation conference
- Short **promotional videos** illustrating the 'Behind the scenes' of partners' participation to internal and external events were created and disseminated online by Euronovia;
- Videos illustrating the **Minecraft workshops** and activities performed under Task 9.6 were developed by UCD and posted online. As an example, short videos (see for example:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072153643923185664> and <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7069243553868083200>) were produced and disseminated online to promote the Minecraft workshops organised as part of the first and second editions of the SCORE Climate Adaptation Training School (see 1.7.1.1) . On 7 June 2023, the game was also livestreamed for 6 hours on the SCORE YouTube channel for people to follow the players' quest and discover the SCORE Minecraft world.

- IHS, with the support of ERINN and the Innovation Board, have developed a [“How-To” video](#) for the Co-create your City Toolkit (KO2.1) which is being highlighted in the Horizon Results Platform.
- ENT recorded a [video to present the functioning of the SCORE EbA catalogue](#) presenting a set of nature-based solutions to address climate change hazards (e.g., sea-level rise, flooding, coastal erosion, storm surge) related to coastal and climate change adaptation and mitigation.
- NAIDER prepared a [video presentation of the Pilot Operation Plan \(POP\)](#) designed to direct the development and implementation of a Living Lab.
- ENoLL developed the [Living Lab Integrative Process video series](#) to introduce the key principles of Living Labs, their integration of research and innovation, and the Quadruple Helix Model—where public, private, academic, and citizen stakeholders collaborate for impactful change (9 videos).
- ERINN developed [two videos](#) to accompany the deliverable D2.4 Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 CCLLs. One video focuses more generally on the lessons learned by the CCLLs, while the second gives practical advice for how to integrate Living Labs into EU-funded projects.
- On the SCORE Online Learning Platform, 23 video compilations were made of CCLL partners in conversation with ERINN Innovation during the Lessons Learned collection interviews. These videos were created to illustrate the points made in the MOOC [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#).

To gather all these different project videos in one place, a SCORE **YouTube channel** was created in March 2022 (https://www.youtube.com/@SCORE_EUproject/about). At M48, this YouTube channel contains **40 videos** (as listed above) obtaining **5428 views** and **109 subscribers**.

Figure 14: Homepage of the SCORE YouTube channel

1.3. Website

The project website was launched in October 2021 at the following address: <https://score-eu-project.eu>. It is of crucial importance to enhance the visibility of SCORE as it serves as the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project activities, deliverables, and outcomes.

Together with social media, the website is a key tool for reaching out to a wide audience, communicate about the project and its results. The website provides essential information on the project, such as its concept and objectives, workplan, partners, activities, technology to be developed, information on the CCLs, news, publications, and more. More information on the content and structure of the website can be found in [deliverable D9.6](#).

The website was regularly updated, with new content and updates on CCLs activities, news articles, deliverables, publications, and many other resources. **168 news articles** have been published. New pages were created, when needed, to increase the dissemination of key project results, such as:

- [“Tools and platforms”](#) which lists and provides information about the different tools and platforms developed by the project and made available to the public
- [“Other publications”](#) which gathers all the SCORE policy briefs as well as other key reports in which SCORE is referenced.
- [“Key achievements”](#) which presents in the key results of the project organised by the three key themes of the project: 1) Co-Creation & Living Labs, 2) Increasing Data Availability and 3) Green & Technological Tools for Climate Adaptation Strategies.

Figure 15: Homepage of the SCORE website

Since June 2024 the SCORE website offers several accessibility tools: it is now possible to increase or decrease the size of the text, apply grayscale or higher contrast, and more options. This feature is visible on the left-hand side of the screen where a blue square with a person is visible.

The impact of the website is monitored using Google Analytics. Since its launch in October 2021, the website was visited by **30,627 visitors**, with **123,597 page views**.

The website received an excellent worldwide coverage, with visitors spread over all continents (**178 countries** mapped), demonstrating a worldwide interest in the project. The top-10 countries of origin of the website’s visitors are: the United States, Spain, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, France, Portugal, the United Kingdom, Germany and Finland.

The presence of the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany and Finland in this top-ten clearly demonstrates that the project is reaching well outside the borders of the project partners' countries. On the other hand, the countries of the CCLLs (Ireland, Spain, Portugal, Italy, Slovenia, Poland, and Turkey) account for **39% of all users** which proves that we are reaching the right locations, as well as gathering interest from additional places.

Figure 16: SCORE website visitors by country

The most visited pages, after the homepage, are the pages describing the SCORE team, the project concept, and the news & events. Notably, the page describing the first edition of the SCORE Climate Adaptation Training School is very high on this list. This shows that the important efforts made in terms of communication to promote this important event were very fruitful and contributed to make it visible.

Table 2: Most visited pages of the SCORE website

Page	Views
Homepage	29,411
Our team	4,057
Project concept	3,734
News & events	3,698
Deliverables	2,947
Partners	2,922
CCLLs	2,835
Tools & Platforms	2,141
SCORE Climate Adaptation training school – First edition	1,957
Work Plan	1,719

1.4. Social media and online presence

Social media have been used by the consortium to inform and connect with professionals, policymakers, and the scientific community as well as to reach out to the general public (students, citizens, local communities).

1.4.1. SCORE's social media accounts

A [LinkedIn page](#) and a [Twitter/X account](#) were created before the start of the project, in June 2021, in order to inform researchers, stakeholders and similar EU projects of the launch of the project:

- The **LinkedIn** account is managed by Euronovia and ATU with the aim to disseminate official project information among a professional audience. Partners and CCLLs regularly contribute to write posts on LinkedIn using their personal/institutional LinkedIn accounts: this way they are able to raise awareness of the project among their contact networks, and the consortium reaps the benefits of the partners' combined networks to reach a wider audience. The account has reached **1747 followers** with an average monthly increase of 6%, and **297 posts published**.
- The **Twitter/X** account is managed by Euronovia, in a more informal way, especially to retweet partners and tweets coming from CCLLs' members to keep the followers updated on the work undertaken daily by each partner. The account has reached **414 followers** and **407 tweets** were published (statistics are no longer available for free but up to June 2023, the account had an average monthly increase of followers of 6%).

Figure 17: SCORE LinkedIn and Twitter accounts

A [Facebook page](#) and an [Instagram account](#) were created by Euronovia in September and October 2021 respectively to primarily target students and the general public, with content focused on educating the public on climate change and its effects on coastal cities:

- The **Instagram** account is run by each CCLL for 1 week/month on a rotational basis: they publish stories and posts with updates on their work within the project. Additionally, project level content is published by Euronovia. The account currently has reached **287 followers** and **168 posts** and **24 stories** were published.

- The **Facebook** page is managed by Euronovia, ERINN and ATU who feed it by reposting relevant LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram publications from partners and CCLLs. The page has reached **186 followers** and **157 posts** were published.

Figure 18: SCORE Facebook and Instagram accounts

A **social media strategy** and calendar were created around M12 to ensure an efficient and coordinated contribution from all partners and CCLLs. This strategy was available in the project's SharePoint to guide all members of the consortium and reminders were sent regularly by Euronovia. The content shared on the SCORE accounts is a mix of project level and local news from the CCLLs, as well as more generic information on SCORE's topics of interest (e.g., climate adaptation and resilience, ecosystem-based approaches).

The different social media accounts contributed to the continuous development of a community of people interested in how the project is tackling climate change and its effects on coastal cities, and to raising awareness on the project and its objectives while allowing for more interaction with related initiatives.

The **impact of these tools was monitored monthly** through the tools listed below in order to identify the best performing content both in terms of **impressions** and **engagement**:

- Statistics on the use of Twitter were analysed through Twitter Analytics which, as of June 2024, was no longer available for free
- Facebook Insights provides useful information on how the content is resonating with the audience, how the page is growing and performing;
- Statistics of the LinkedIn page is accessible by the page administrators;
- Statistics for Instagram are available through the Instagram business feature.

The KPIs analysis, included those related to social media, is available in Annex 1. More detailed statistics by month (page views, clicks, impressions, etc.) for each social media channel are available upon request to Euronovia.

1.4.2. Partners' social media accounts and websites

In addition to the SCORE official accounts, project partners used their own personal and institutional websites and social media accounts to raise awareness of SCORE and to disseminate the activities taking place within the project to their networks. This contributed to expand the reach of the project to those people who are interested in the coastal and climate adaptations but who are not necessarily part of the SCORE community.

At M48, we have registered **173 news** published by partners in their institutional websites and **479 posts** published on their social media accounts.

Lastly, three CCLL have chosen to set up their own social media accounts in order to reach their communities in their own languages and publish more local news about their different activities:

- Gdansk (Polish): [Twitter](#) and [Instagram](#)
- Dublin (English): [Twitter](#)
- Benidorm (Spanish): [Twitter](#)

1.5. Publications

1.5.1. SCORE bi-annual newsletters

8 newsletters (twice a year) were sent out to the newsletter subscribers during the duration of the project in January and July 2022, January and July 2023, January and July 2024, January and June 2025. These include the latest project news with links to the website to drive more traffic. They are available on the project website (<https://score-eu-project.eu/newsletter/>) and have been disseminated on social media, as well as sent by e-mail to relevant networks of project partners to increase the size of the dissemination list, which includes 595 contacts. More information about the SCORE newsletters can be found in deliverable D9.12.

1.5.2. Press relations and media coverage

Important efforts were dedicated to press relations to ensure a good media coverage about the SCORE project, both at the European/national level and at the local/regional CCLL level:

- **2 press releases** were published by ATU: in July 2021 to officially communicate the launch of the project (this was translated into French, Spanish and Italian and distributed by the project partners to their contact networks and widely published through their institutional websites and social networks. ATU also sent their press release to all regional press in the Northwest of Ireland); in March 2024 to communicate about the different citizen science activities in place to involve local communities in innovative co-warning and co-monitoring activities for improving resilience to extreme weather events. The full document is available at this link: https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/SCORE_Press-release-SCORE-innovative-citizen-science-activities-to-tackle-climate-change-in-coastal-areas.pdf.
- UCD and ATU published a press release about the citizen science activity “Smart Pebbles” in their CCLLs (<https://lero.ie/news-and-events/news/dublin-and-sligo-students-release-%E2%80%98smart%E2%80%99-pebbles-track-climate-change-impacts>)
- Oarsoaldea sent out a press release in June 2023 about the first EBA training school (<https://oarsoaldea.hitza.eus/2023/06/02/klima-egokitzapena-lantzeko-hiru-egun-antolatu-dituzte/>)

- A **final press release** was drafted by Euronovia and included in the final media press kit for wide distribution. The press release has been also distributed as an individual document on the [website](#), social media and by project partners to their networks (https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/2025-06-12_Press-release-dates.pdf).
- A **final media press kit** (20 pages) was created by Euronovia with contributions from all the CCLLs. It targets a non-specialist audience, in particular the media and general public. It focuses on CCLL outputs, highlights, and key achievements, and provide key numbers and information about the project. This press kit was distributed through the website, social media, and during the final event. It was made available to the partners for local distribution (https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Press-Kit-2025_SCORE-Web.pdf).

Figure 19: SCORE final media press kit and press release

1.5.3. Media appearances

SCORE partners were very active with the media at regional, national and European levels. At M48, we have identified:

- **105 media appearances** including videos and interviews broadcast by local and regional TV and radio channels have been recorded since the start of the project, including:
- **3 articles** have been published in the SiliconRepublic Irish, a **specialized magazine** for science and technology news: one in August 2021 about the project launch, one in September 2023 about the "smart pebbles" activity to track coastal erosion and one in April 2024 on SCORE citizen science activities.

Among these, we highlight:

- The publication of the article "Using nature and data to weather coastal storms" featuring the SCORE project, that was published in Horizon, the EU's Research and Innovation magazine, on 11 August 2022.

- The video interview with the project coordinator that was broadcast by the RTE News (Ireland’s National Public Service Media) in June 2021 to promote the coastal living labs approach in Ireland (<https://www.rte.ie/news/connacht/2021/0930/1250003-sligo-coastal-study/>).

Several other videos and interviews have been broadcast by local and regional TV and radio channels in Slovenia and Italy. The full list of media appearances is available upon request to Euronovia.

Table 3: Overview of media appearances by country and type

Country	Media appearances
Turkey	1
Ireland	16
Slovenia	25
Italy	41
Spain	19
Europe	3

Type	Media appearances
Online article	68
TV	11
Radio	11
Print article	14

1.5.4. Relevant non-scientific publications

Through various collaboration activities, SCORE was also featured in a number of external publications, among which we highlight the following:

- The **blog article** “[Nature Will Guide You: NbS in European Coastal Cities](#)” was published on the Urbanet website by SCORE project partners ERINN and IHS to present the innovative approach of SCORE that focuses both on NbS and living labs to address societal challenges through a participatory approach.
- SCORE was featured in the “[Sea’ties Regional Report – Adapting Coastal Cities and Territories to Sea Level Rise in the Mediterranean Region, Challenges and Best Practices](#)” where the SCORE project and its Coastal Cities Living Labs (CCLLs) are one of two case studies presented (see page 26-27). This report was published with the support of the City of Marseille, Plan Bleu and MedECC and was presented on 12 November 2022 during the COP27, both online and at the Mediterranean Pavilion.
- Following the project’s contributions to the COP27 (see section 1.6.4), SCORE was highlighted as a **featured project** by CINEA: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/featured-projects/score-coastal-city-living-lab_en.
- SCORE is featured in the [CORDIS’ projects info pack entitled “EU missions to address climate change in cities and regions”](#) published in June 2024 (see pages 22-23) alongside other EU projects supporting the work of the EU Mission Adaptation to Climate Change.
- The Sligo CCLL contributed to submit a [recommendation paper to the UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights](#) in 2024, as part of the Northwest Human Rights Advocacy Network of Ireland. SCORE is cited in this document in the section on Nature Based Solutions.
- Nature Based Solutions Platform: SCORE has been shared in [SCORE Feature](#) on the [Nature Based Solutions Platform](#) to disseminate key results to peer learning networks. The CCLLs’ vision, main hazards addressed and EbA prioritised have been included in the NBS platform. Additionally, the wider outputs of the SCORE project were featured on this group’s [LinkedIn group](#) in three separate posts, which has over 46,000 current followers.

Lastly, SCORE produced or contributed to a certain number of policy briefs, see more details in section 1.7.4.

1.5.5. Scientific publications

The consortium actively disseminated its results through several scientific publications. The KPIs set at the beginning of the project (**30 scientific publications** in Scopus Indexed peer-reviewed journals, **one special issue/ collection** in a peer-reviewed journal, and **10 conference proceedings**) have been reached and far exceeded:

During the project lifetime, partners have published **95 scientific publications**, including:

- **56 journal articles** and 1 preprint in **33 different journals**: Atmosphere, Catena, Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health, Documents d'Anàlisi Geogràfica, Environmental Development, Environmental Policy and Governance, Environmental Science and Policy, Futures & Foresight Science, Geomatics Natural Hazards and Risk, IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine, IEEE-Transactions on Geoscience and Remote-Sensing, International Journal of Engineering Research in Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IJERMCE), Journal for Geography, Journal of Environmental Management, Journal of Marine Science and Engineering, Marine Geology, Marine Georesources & Geotechnology, Marine Policy, Miscellanea Geographica - Regional Studies on Development, Modeling Earth Systems and Environment, Natural Hazards, Ocean & Coastal Management, Remote Sensing, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Science of the Total Environment, Sensors, Sustainability, Sustainable Futures, Turkish Journal of Remote Sensing, Urban Climate, URSI Radio Science Letter, Visions for sustainability, Water.
- **6 conference abstracts and 28 conference papers** following participation in 24 different conferences.
- **2 editorials and 1 book chapter**
- **1 special issue**: the SCORE project cooperated with the special issue “Rain Sensors” of the open access journal Sensors, published by MDPI and co-edited by the SCORE partner Filippo Giannetti (University of Pisa, Italy) and Luca Lanza (University of Genoa, Italy): 4 papers authored by SCORE researchers were published in this special issue.

The full list is available in Annex 2.

All SCORE publications have been uploaded in the **SCORE Zenodo community** that was set-up in June 2023 by Euronovia: <https://zenodo.org/communities/score-eu-project>. This has been used as a project repository where all project publications and datasets have been uploaded for long-term preservation.

1.6. Events

During the project duration, partners have organised and have participated in several public events to promote SCORE and disseminate key results of the project, as detailed below.

1.6.1. Organisation of project events

1.6.1.1. EbA Training Schools and citizen science activities

During the project, 3 editions of the EbA training school were organised with the 10 CCLLs. They were renamed “SCORE Climate Adaptation Training School” for an easier dissemination. The training schools were successfully organised by UCD, ERINN, Euronovia, ATU, Naider, and with the participation and involvement of all CCLLs, engaging various stakeholders through lectures, workshop, and interactive activities. The Training schools not only piloted the tools developed by the consortium but also served as foundation for the knowledge share and testing.

All editions followed a 3-day format:

- Online lecture with a first part common to all attendees in English, and a second part with a focus on each CCLL in their local languages;
- A workshop session focusing on gamification jointly organised with all CCLLs;
- Several local-level citizen engagement activities organised in the CCLL as in-person, online, or hybrid events. The format and content were decided by each CCLL depending on their priorities and capacity. The activities were organised during a wider time range to ensure better participation.

The first pilot activities (e.g., Minecraft workshops) for the EBA Training Schools were organised online in September 2022, as part of Dublin Climate Action Week (CCLL Dublin), and in person during Bright Night Researchers' Night in Pisa, Italy (CCLL Massa).

Figure 20: SCORE partners at the Bright Night Researchers Night in Pisa, Italy

First edition: 2023 Training School

The 2023 training school, part of the EU Green Week, included a series of online and in-person activities across CCLLs, focusing on community engagement and education:

- **An online lecture** on Climate Adaptation (6 June, 2023): SCORE experts discussed nature-based solutions, ecosystem-based adaptation, citizen science, and smart cities. This session, that was attended by 160 persons, was followed by parallel talks by SCORE experts on approaches to climate adaptation. Presentations were held by CCLL representatives on different topics (including nature-based solutions/ecosystem-based adaptation, citizen science, and smart cities) and were held in different breakout rooms with participants being able to select the room of their choice based on location and language.
- **Online Minecraft workshop** (7 June, 2023) aimed at designing environmentally friendly solutions for coastal cities. Players

collaborated to address the threats facing a coastal city using ecosystem-based approaches. The session was also available in livestream on YouTube.

- **Local activities** organised by the CCLLs (May-June 2023). The format and content of these events was decided by each CCLL depending on priorities and capacity.

The first edition of the SCORE Training School was attended by over 500 participants. More details on this event are available at: <https://score-eu-project.eu/2023/05/11/score-climate-adaptation-training-school-first-edition/>.

Figure 21: Kids participating in the SCORE Minecraft workshop in Dublin, Ireland

Second edition: 2024 Training School

The second edition of the training school in 2024 followed a similar format as the previous year:

- **Online lecture** on Community-Based Coastal Monitoring (March 20, 2024): This session involved SCORE experts discussing citizen science activities and ecosystem-based approaches, with 7 parallel sessions in multiple languages led by CCLLs.
- **Online Minecraft Youth Engagement** (March 21-28, 2024): This week-long event allowed young players to collaborate on tasks related to climate adaptation of coastal cities. The server was open for a full week, and a livestream on YouTube allowed others to follow the progress.
- **Local activities** organised by each CCLL (March-April 2024). The format and content of these events was decided by each CCLL depending on priorities and capacity.

The second edition of the SCORE Training School was attended by over 550 participants. More details on this event are available at: <https://score-eu-project.eu/2024/05/14/a-look-back-at-the-2nd-edition-of-the-score-training-school>.

Third edition 2025 Training School

The third and final edition of the training school in 2025 followed a similar format as the previous years. The third edition consisted of:

- **An online lecture** was held on 11 February on various approaches to climate adaptation, covering topics such as nature-based solutions, ecosystem-based adaptation, citizen science, smart cities, the SCORE legacy, and innovative strategies for coastal climate resilience.
- As part of this, the **GeoDesign Game**, developed by UCD, was piloted with all the CCLLs as a stakeholder decision making and engagement tool (February 2025 – April 2025). The game resources were shared with all CCLLs, and the game itself is open-source and available on GitHub.
- In addition, each CCLL organised its own **local activities** as part of the training school (February 2025 – April 2025). The format and content of these events were tailored to the specific priorities and capacities of each CCLL.

The final edition of the SCORE Training School hosted 18 activities and events and was attended by **1750+ participants**. More details on this event are available at: <https://score-eu-project.eu/a-look-back-at-the-3rd-edition-of-the-score-training-school>

Local level activities organised in the CCLLs of these Training Schools included sensor workshops, and awareness-raising events like local walks/guided tours and Minecraft workshops. In Dublin and Sligo, Ireland, workshops focused on Minecraft and low-cost coastal sensors. Gdańsk, Poland, hosted mapathons, creative classes, and guided tours on climate change. Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm, and Oarsoaldea in Spain organised awareness events and workshops. Piran, Slovenia, conducted focus groups and field tours for sustainable mobility. Massa, Italy, held sensor information sessions, while Samsun, Turkey, ran surveys and events with farmers and kindergartens. Oeiras, Portugal, engaged primary school students in climate change activities.

Figure 22: Local activities in Benidorm and Gdansk during the third training school

In addition, many citizen science activities were organised in the 10 CCLLs throughout the project duration, reach a total of **105+ activities** and involving close to **7000 participants**. Information about the citizen science activities can be found in [deliverable D4.5](#).

Lastly, some CCLLs have also decided to organise local final events in their cities. For instance, Vilanova, together with the Benidorm and Oarsoaldea CCLLs, celebrated the end of the project on 22 May. The event was entitled “Adaptation to climate change in coastal areas: Challenges and solutions”.

Piran CCLL organised its final event on 30 June 2025 to present and discuss the overall results and especially the Piran CCLL achievements.

1.6.1.2. SCORE international workshops

SCORE has organised three international workshops:

- “Lessons learned from the Living Labs established to tackle Climate Change and Ocean Literacy” on 22 September 2023 as part of the Open Living Lab Days in Barcelona, Spain.
- “Smart Technologies and Community Engagement with EBA for Climate Resilience Actions” on 24 September 2024 as part of the Littoral 2024 "European Coastal Challenge Summit" in Constanta, Romania.
- “Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures” on 10 October 2024 as part of the European Week of Regions and Cities in Brussels, Belgium.

Detailed description and information on these three workshops are available in deliverables [D9.9](#) and D9.10.

1.6.1.3. Final event

On 17 June 2025, the SCORE project held its final event, titled **“Innovative Solutions for Climate Change Adaptation in Coastal Areas: When Green and Digital Tools Meet Living Labs”**. It was organised as a side event of the ECCA 2025 conference, Europe’s leading forum on climate change adaptation, held in Rimini, Italy.

This event marked a wonderful opportunity to reflect on and celebrate the results of four years of collaborative work, bringing together project partners, Coastal City Living Labs, and external stakeholders.

During this 2-hour event, divided into two sessions, we highlighted the legacy of the CCLs, showcasing how the project has contributed to empowering local communities, improving knowledge-sharing, and fostering collaborative solutions for coastal resilience. The event also focused on the evaluation of nature-based solutions and the integration of digital tools to better anticipate and manage climate risks in coastal cities.

Figure 23: SCORE Final event at ECCA2025

A key part of the final event was the opportunity for each CCLL representative to present their achievements, offering valuable feedback on the practical solutions implemented, the local partnerships developed, and the technical implementation of co-created solutions within their cities. These presentations provided a rich overview of both the successes and challenges faced on the ground, offering valuable lessons for future projects.

At ECCA we were also present with a **booth** where we showcased the main tools and solutions developed by our partners to tackle climate change, to enhance citizen participation, improve climate monitoring and projections and facilitate knowledge sharing.

Presentations and video recording of the event are available on the [SCORE website](#). For more information, see deliverable D9.11 about the SCORE final infoday.

1.6.2. Participation in external events

The targets set at the beginning of the project regarding the number of participation in external events were all beyond achieved: during the 4-year project duration, the SCORE consortium participated in **120 external events** for project promotion and scientific dissemination, where partners presented the work done within the project. Among these: **52 scientific conferences, 5 exhibition fairs in technology and open innovation events, 18 international forums, 31 national/regional/local events, and 19 science popularisation events** (not organised by the partners themselves). The full list of events is available in Annex 3.

Attendance at national, regional and local events

Several partners, in particular representatives of the CCLLs, have participated in local, regional and national events to present the project and to raise awareness of SCORE's approach to address climate change adaptation and resilience issues in coastal cities. Their objective was to engage local stakeholders and policymakers and have an impact at the local level as much as possible. On these occasions, presentations were done in the local language, making it easier for locals to understand the challenges and benefits of the proposed actions.

Attendance at strategic conferences, fairs and international forums

In each version of the SCORE PEDR (D9.1 - v1, v2, v3, v4) we provided a list of targeted events that partners identified as important venues for dissemination of project results. This list was originally quite extensive, and it was not intended that partners would participate in all the events. Therefore, not all the targeted events were ultimately attended, for several reasons: in some cases, participation was upon selection by the organisers (session or paper), in other cases timing was not ideal to disseminate a certain result, or partners turned out to be already busy with other activities, or had to reconsider their participation due to budget or other internal constraints. Internally, we monitor attendance at these target events using an online living document that partners continuously update with information on their participation and with new relevant events identified.

This strategy was updated for the last reporting period (RP3), based on reviewers' feedback: instead of including a long list of conferences in the field, that we were not sure partners would be able to attend, it was decided to highlight only a limited number of strategic events, where most efforts would be put towards, and where an application (session or abstract) were already submitted by SCORE partners to the organisers.

A total of 78 target events (in the categories conferences, exhibition fairs, and international forums) were listed in the different versions of the SCORE PEDR (D9.1) and in the internal tracking document. By the end of the project (June 2025), the partners have attended 33 of these events, representing 42% of the number of identified events in this time period.

42 additional events (i.e., not listed in the documents mentioned above) were also attended by the SCORE partners, including some important events upon invitation only, some technical events or other events that partners hadn't initially included in the list. In conclusion, a **total of 75 events** were attended by 30 June 2025 (2 more events will be attended in early July 2025). More details can be provided by EUR to the EC upon request.

1.7. Notable activities and outputs

1.7.1. Webinars series

A **series of webinars** was developed by Euronovia with the support of all WP leaders. Thought as an efficient tool to reach a wider audience and showcase the project's activities, tools, and methods, 9 webinars were organised from November 2022 to May 2024, each focusing on the activities of one WP. A first webinar had also been organised at the start of the project to introduce the Coastal City Living Labs concept, thus bringing the total of SCORE webinars to **10 webinars**.

In addition to project partners, external guest speakers were also invited to participate in several webinars to extend their reach and share useful insights about their work. Alongside website news and social media posts, the webinars were systematically shared through several relevant mailing lists at European and international levels (e.g., coastal list, Climate Adapt) and with other EU projects (including the Adapt4Coast cluster) to ensure wide dissemination. All webinars were clipped and incorporated into relevant MOOC curriculums by ERINN.

Recordings of the webinars are available on the project's YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLUoJeHsSUIVGMgUmCqBktOkDO8HRUuKrR> and the speaker's presentations are made available on the SCORE website

A dedicated section on the project website was created to make them more easily findable and accessible by the website users: <https://score-eu-project.eu/videos/>

1.7.2. Geostories

During the October 2023 Innovation Board Meeting, following analysis of Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs) for several Knowledge Outputs (KOs), WP9 and the Innovation Board determined that a centralised dissemination resource for the CCLLs would be necessary to reach more local target users. As such, specific dissemination materials on the SCORE Platform have been developed to support targeted outreach to local and regional stakeholders.

Partners from WP9 and WP5 have co-developed with each CCLL a GeoStory on the SCORE Platform about the work going on in their lab. These GeoStories, intentionally designed for easy navigation, showcase SCORE activities and results tailored to CCLL's local stakeholders on a single webpage. Acting as a centralized highlight reel, they allow readers to view the most relevant and beneficial projects and activities in their area. See below examples of CCLL GeoStories highlighting local activities and outputs – such as the hazard maps in Massa (Figure 24), citizen science activities in Piran (Figure 25) and sensor deployment in Oeiras (Figure 26).

To co-create these GeoStories, ERINN developed templates to collect information and activities that were most impactful in each CCLL. Additionally, published deliverables, articles, policy briefs, and KOs were assessed for relevant

resources for each CCLL. The ERINN and WP5 teams then compiled this information into an online starting template, from which CCLLs could then adjust and manage as their own GeoStories.

The GeoStories were intended to be dynamic resources, with additional elements (activities, knowledge outputs, etc.) being periodically added throughout the duration of the project. Each CCLL team included the most relevant and interesting activities and outputs for local stakeholders, including citizens, local policymakers, and public administrators. To ensure accessibility, the GeoStories were developed in the local languages of the CCLLs. As such, the GeoStories have become a valuable tool for knowledge transfer.

Figure 24: Hazard maps developed in WP1 as displayed in the Massa CCLL Geostory

Figure 25: The Piran CCLL has displayed their most impactful citizen engagement activities in their GeoStories as a GeoCarousel, making it interactive for readers.

Figure 26: The Oeiras CCLL has described and displayed information about their sensor deployment activities in their municipality on their GeoStory

The most recent iterations of these GeoStories can be found here: platform.score-eu-project.eu. A link to each one of the GeoStories is included in the CCLL individual pages on the SCORE website, as well as in the Final media press kit.

1.7.3. MOOCs

As an element of *Task 9.6.3, Lectures and Materials as MOOCs*, ERINN was tasked with developing Massive Open Online Learning Courses (MOOCs) for the lectures and materials from the T9.6 EBA Training Schools. A MOOC is an open-online course for which participants from around the world can learn about a specific topic, utilising a variety of mediums, including videos, user forums, quizzes, reading materials, links to external supplementary materials and much more. MOOCs provide an affordable and flexible way to learn new skills and deliver quality educational experiences at scale. Participants require only a smart phone/tablet/computer and access to the internet – making these open-source courses an equitable opportunity for self-guided learning. The utilisation of the SCORE MOOCs enabled the project to reach a wider audience and provide valuable climate action skills/learnings to citizens in Europe and worldwide. A full description of the creation, validation and amendment process for the SCORE MOOCs is captured in Deliverable 9.4 – Lectures and Materials as MOOC (M30).

On the [SCORE Online Learning](#) platform, the courses are structured so that within each course there are several modules, and within those modules there are lessons. ERINN has designed each course to have a major overarching theme, such as understanding Nature-Based Solutions, or how to Implement Ecosystem-Based Approaches. Simultaneously, the modules within the course have a specific set of learning objectives that are then achieved through the lessons of text, videos, and knowledge checks. Each course is designed for various learner levels, from Introductory (Limited to no pre-existing knowledge of subject matter needed) to Intermediate (Established knowledge of subject matter needed) to Advanced (High level of knowledge needed, focus on application of knowledge).

Across all 5 courses developed for the SCORE Online Learning Platform, there are a total of 35 modules, 164 lessons, and 74 videos. Additional videos are currently in development for Course #5 Serious Games for Participatory Planning. The full impact of the MOOC and detailed description of its courses are summarised in Chapter 3, Key Exploitable Result 9.1. Courses Include:

1. What are Nature-Based Solutions? (available in English, Spanish, and Catalan)
2. Ecosystem-Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation
3. Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities
4. Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs
5. Serious Games for Participatory Planning

In establishing the [SCORE Online Learning](#) platform, careful considerations led to the selection of Thinkific as the preferred platform on which to host the SCORE MOOCs. Chosen for its user-friendly interface, multimedia capabilities, customizability, and community engagement features, Thinkific serves as a hub for knowledge dissemination. The course material itself draws insights from a variety of SCORE materials, notably the EBA Training Schools, SCORE deliverables, Knowledge Outputs, partner contributions, and the webinar series. As such, the MOOCs proved to be an impactful tool for knowledge transfer both during and beyond SCORE. ATU has agreed to continue paying for the platform beyond the SCORE project through synergising initiatives, meaning the MOOCs will continue to be available at least two years beyond the project.

1.7.4. Policy briefs

11 policy briefs have been published by the SCORE consortium during the project: 5 relevant at the European level and 6 targeting national and local policy-makers, including 4 developed by the CCLLs themselves (Sligo, Oeiras, and Samsun). These policy briefs are available for download on the SCORE website: <https://score-eu-project.eu/other-publications/>. While all policy briefs were promoted online and disseminated widely through the SCORE newsletter, by project partners to their networks, at events and through other EU projects, local policy briefs have been disseminated locally, targeting in particular local policy makers. As an example, the policy brief relevant for Sligo was presented to the Sligo County Council.

Task 7.5 focused on developing and issuing policy recommendations to assist decision-making in climate change adaptation at local, national and EU levels. Starting in July 2024, this task culminated in deliverable D7.5 in June 2025. This deliverable presents a set of policy guidelines tailored to various governance levels and coastal management contexts, demonstrating how public value is generated from adaptation measures designed and implemented in the SCORE project. In addition to this deliverable, 3 policy recommendations documents were produced by TERO. Each brief targets policy makers at a specific level: EU, national, and local.

At European level:

- When will a 2-meter rise in sea level occur, and how might we adapt: This policy brief was prepared together with the CoCliCo and PROTECT projects and presented at the COP27 in November 2022.
- ADAPT4COAST - Integrated strategies for climate resilience in EU coastal cities: This joint policy brief presents critical findings from the Adapt4Coast Cluster, aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal areas by using an integrated solution of smart technologies and nature-based solutions.
- Research findings offer crucial insights for government climate policy, spanning climate vulnerability assessments, climate modelling, coastal restoration, enhanced monitoring via low-cost sensors and satellite data, and stakeholder engagement through the living lab model.
- Joint Policy Recommendations on Climate Adaptation from European Coastal Cities: This brief was prepared as an outcome of the SCORE workshop at the Open Living Lab Days 2023, this policy brief highlights the most

important policy recommendations from each of the ten living labs, based on years of research, experimentation, and collaboration, in order to build sustainable and resilient cities/regions across Europe. It helps showcase the extensive reach of the research being conducted within SCORE and partner projects across ten diverse European regions, indicating the scalability of this research model.

- Adapting to sea level rise - Reshaping the future of our coastal cities: Enhancing Coastal Cities' Resilience through Nature-Based Solutions: This brief was developed in collaboration with the [Ocean and Climate Platform](#), following the participation of SCORE partners in an online workshop on NbS in April 2024. This brief aims to provide guidance to decision-makers on how to overcome the typical challenges of integrating NbS into adaptation strategies for coastal cities. It was distributed through the Ocean & Climate Platform gathering more than 100 members – research institutes, NGOs, aquariums, private sector, French institutions and international agencies, local authorities – as well as through the SCORE partners' networks.
- SCORE Guidelines – Policy recommendations for EU policy-makers: This brief, based on the Deliverable 'D7.5 SCORE Policy Guidelines' and distributed at the SCORE final event, offers practical policy recommendations for EU policymakers on integrating Ecosystem-Based Adaptation, participatory planning, living labs, and innovative tools into existing frameworks, based on SCORE's research and pilot projects in ten Coastal City Living Labs.

At national and local level:

- Building Climate Resilience in Sligo County through Ecosystem-based Adaptation, Smart Technologies, and Coastal City Living Lab: This brief was prepared for the Sligo County Council decision-makers based on the lessons learned from the SCORE results on building coastal resilience in the face of coastal hazards, sea-level rise and coastal erosion in Sligo County.
- Heatwaves in Portugal: Understanding, Mitigation, Adaptation: This policy brief summarises a comprehensive analysis of heatwaves in mainland Portugal from October 1980 to September 2021. The results emphasise the urgent need for effective adaptation and mitigation strategies to alleviate the negative impacts of extreme temperatures on public health, agriculture, energy consumption, and ecosystem functioning. Additionally, recommendations for climate capacity building and raising public awareness are highlighted.
- Red Flags on the Map: A Policy Brief on Exceptional Rainfall and Temperature Events in Portugal: This policy brief presents key findings and policy adaptation strategies based on a comparative analysis of exceptional weather events in Portugal. Over the past four decades, climate change has altered hydrological and temperature regimes in the country, leading to exceptional rainfall and temperature events. The findings highlight the urgent need for adaptation strategies and policymaking to strengthen resilience and climate governance.
- Under pressure: Climate change, flood dynamics and resilience in the Kızılırmak Basin: This brief highlights the results of a recent HEC-RAS 2D modeling study that simulates flood risk under historical data and future climate scenarios, offering key insights for evidence-based planning in the Bafra Plain (Turkey)
- SCORE Guidelines – Policy recommendations for policy-makers at national level: based on the Deliverable 'D7.5 SCORE Policy Guidelines', this brief provides practical policy recommendations for national policymakers on integrating Ecosystem-Based Adaptation, participatory planning, living labs, and innovative tools, based on SCORE's research and pilot projects in ten Coastal City Living Labs.
- SCORE Guidelines – Policy recommendations for policy-makers at local level: based on the Deliverable 'D7.5 SCORE Policy Guidelines', this brief offers local policymakers practical guidance on integrating Ecosystem-Based Adaptation, participatory planning, living labs, and innovative tools, based on SCORE's research and engagement across ten Coastal City Living Labs.

Lastly, within Task 6.5, a set of guidelines for the management of residual coastal risk were produced to assist coastal city decision-makers in designing a strategy based on the set of financial and structural interventions available to them, tailored to the specific characteristics of their city. RED produced Disaster-risk financing (DRF) guidelines for Massa, Vilanova and Oarsoaldea (the 3 frontrunners of WP6) as well as general DRF guidelines for all the 10 CCLLs.

WP9 worked with WP7 and WP6 to facilitate dissemination of these policy briefs to appropriate stakeholders. Dissemination had a prominent focus on the local level through the CCLLs while identifying opportunities for knowledge transfer at the European level through events, web channels (website, social media, newsletter) and contacts with other similar EU projects and initiatives.

1.7.5. Synergies with other projects & initiatives

In order to boost dissemination of project results and maximize impact, synergies were developed with other **EU projects and initiatives working on a similar topic/domain**.

A list of projects with which SCORE could have synergies was drafted early after the launch of SCORE, taking into consideration a similar scope, activities and topic (climate change / coastal areas). This list was regularly updated and progressively refined, to include only those projects with which effective synergies were developed. This list as well more details about our networking activities are **available in Deliverable D10.2 - Networking and synergies between EU projects**.

In this final report, we chose to highlight our collaboration with the [CoCliCo](#), [PROTECT](#) and [REST-COAST projects](#) (see Table 4) with which synergies were stronger, since together we decided to apply for the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) and to join forces to constitute a **project group called Adapt4Coast** aiming to improve coastal city climate resilience.

Table 4: European projects participating with SCORE in the Adapt4Coast Cluster

Project acronym	Project objective	Website
CoCliCo 2021-2025	Informing decision-making on coastal risk and adaptation, by delivering an open web-platform exploring dominant risk drivers, adjusting visualisation and analysis techniques to local decision contexts, and combining relevant and high-quality geospatial information layers.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101003598/
REST-COAST 2021 - 2026	The project will bring together 38 partners to assess ecosystem services from coastal marshes, seabed meadows and coastal dunes, to reduce erosion and flooding risks while enhancing biodiversity and blue carbon. REST-COAST will conduct nine pilots in the main EU regional seas (Baltic, Black, North, Atlantic and Mediterranean) with the aim of increasing the commitment of citizens, stakeholders and policymakers.	https://rest-coast.eu/
PROTECT 2020 - 2024	The project aims at leveraging innovation procurement to unlock the climate service market's potential. The initial focus will be on utilities, green cities, health, land use, marine environment and security. Eventually, PROTECT will provide decision makers at EU, national, regional and local levels, with practical recommendations and guidelines for climate action.	https://www.protect-pcp.eu/

As a cluster, we jointly developed a project video and factsheet, as well as a policy brief (<https://score-eu-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Adapt4Coast-Policy-Brief-Final.pdf>) including critical findings and valuable insights for government climate policy. We also organised a joint webinar on 24 May, 2024, in which representatives of the four projects presented some of the tools and platforms under development to help communities plan smart adaptation strategies and play an active role in tackling climate-related challenges.

The cluster was very successful in communicating and in disseminating the main outcomes of the projects involved, developing joint dissemination campaign on social media on different occasions. The impact of these activities is demonstrated by the attention received by the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change, which invited the cluster to present the Adapt4Coast poster during the Third Forum for the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change in Brussels on 23 May, 2024. The poster was presented by the SCORE coordinator on behalf of the cluster.

1.8. Monitoring and assessment of KPIs

Monitoring the impact of the different dissemination activities involved a systematic collection of data and reporting of information from all partners. This information served to deliver the final verdict on the success of the dissemination process undertaken by the project.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination efforts, a comprehensive Communication and Dissemination Plan was developed at M6. This plan ensured that all activities were properly scheduled and executed, and included **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** to assess the impact of each action. KPIs serves as measurable indicators to track the performance and progress of activities, messages, and tasks toward their intended outcomes. Multiple KPIs were defined for each communication activity to enable a structured and meaningful evaluation of their success.

The KPIs were used throughout the project to assess the performance of dissemination activities and to adjust the dissemination plan whenever targets were not met or the expected impact was not achieved. This ongoing evaluation allowed for timely reorientation of strategies to improve effectiveness. For instance, a mid-term impact assessment was conducted and documented in **Deliverable D9.2 – Mid-term Report on Communication and Dissemination Activities**.

The **table presenting the KPIs reached at M48 is available in Annex 1**.

The following scale was used to score each KPI:

- If the results are lower than 50% of the target, the result is considered as Low;
- If the results are lower or equal to 75% but above 50%, the result is considered as Moderate;
- If the results are lower or equal to 100% but above 75%, the result is considered as Good;
- If the results are higher than 100%, the result is considered as High.

Over 60% of our KPIs received a ‘High’ score, and over 80% are either ‘High’ or ‘Good’ (as reported in Table 5). The activities were thus well aligned with the work plan.

The comparison between the KPIs evaluation at M24 and at M48 shows an increase in the “High” category (+9%) and a strong decrease in the “Moderate” category (-13%). However, the “Low” category increased by 8%, which is mostly due to the introduction of two new KPIs at the end of the project (number of final brochures distributed and number of participants in the final infoday). An explanation for these numbers is provided below.

Table 5: Distribution of KPI evaluation scores

Score	High	Good	Moderate	Low
% of KPI at M24	52%	24%	21%	3%
% of KPI at M48	61%	19%	8%	11%

The **highest KPIs** are related to:

- Organisation of events: EBA training schools, citizen science activities and workshops in each CCLL, the SCORE international workshops, and webinars;
- Participation in events: Scientific conferences, exhibition and trade fairs, popularisation events
- Online activity: Visits on the SCORE website;
- Press relations: Press releases and media appearances;
- Publications: Scientific publications, conference proceedings, decision-support guidelines, policy briefs;
- Materials: Number of videos.

It is to be noted that, in addition to scientific conferences, popularisation events and open innovation events whose participation was planned in the GA, the consortium participated also in a number of international forums and local, national and regional events for which we did not set any KPIs in the initial PEDR because these were not planned. These events contributed to increase the visibility and impact of the project both at the international and the national/regional level.

The high results in terms of tools, activities and participation clearly show a strong engagement from all consortium members and their commitments to the communication and dissemination of the project.

The **lower-performing KPIs** are related to:

- Participants in the final infoday (target: >1000)
- Followers on social media (target: +3000 followers on LinkedIn, +2000 followers on Twitter/X)
- Distribution of printed materials (target: 2000 brochures and 2000 flyers distributed)

The first two can be explained as the KPIs set for these activities were very high from the start. The third one was rather related to the difficulty in tracking down the actual numbers of printed materials that were distributed. In addition, there has been a shift from printed materials in most events in recent years (mostly for environmental reasons) which have contributed to lower this number.

Additional efforts and new activities were put in place by the consortium to increase performance of the lower-performing KPIs.

In the mid-term report (D9.2), we highlighted:

- The creation and dissemination of additional videos, such as the project presentation video created to launch the project, partners interviews in different languages, videos related to promote the Minecraft activities, and the recordings of a series of 10 webinars presenting the activities implemented within each WP;
- The creation of a social media strategy to involve all project partners and CCLLs representatives in the creation of content to increase the number of posts and their dissemination to other external networks.

Both activities proved to be effective, as evidenced by the increase in video views, which reached a satisfactory level. Although the social media KPIs were not fully met, the active involvement of all partners contributed to achieving a solid follower base, notably on LinkedIn (over 1700 followers) and Instagram (over 280 followers). It should be noted that this does not even account for all the followers from the partners' accounts who were also sharing SCORE posts.

Lastly, in addition to quantitative KPIs, some **qualitative indicators** were taken into consideration to understand the impact of the actions carried out, for example the feedbacks obtained through satisfaction questionnaires sent to participants after project webinars and after the Green Week events: an average score of 4.6/5 was given by the

participants regarding the level of interest of the webinars and an average satisfaction score of 4.8/5 for the Green Week. Responses to these questionnaires can be provided to the EC upon request.

1.9. Impact assessment of activities at CCLL level

This compilation of impact assessments presents a comprehensive overview of the most impactful activities, achievements, and legacy planning of the ten CCLLs. Each CCLL operated as a hub for co-creation, citizen science, and the piloting of EbA solutions to address the diverse climate challenges facing Europe's coastal cities. The following summaries highlight not only the specific actions and outcomes achieved in each location but also the evolving strategies for sustaining CCLL methodologies beyond the life of the project.

1.9.1. Sligo

The Sligo CCLL has significantly advanced climate adaptation efforts in the region by embedding scientific research, stakeholder engagement, and community knowledge into actionable local policy and the wider Sligo Climate Adaptation Network. One of the most tangible outcomes of this work has been the direct integration of SCORE findings into [Sligo County Council Climate Action Plan](#) 2024–2029. Action No. 31 of the Plan specifically acknowledges the CCLL and commits to identifying mechanisms for sustaining its activities. The inclusion of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), such as dune system protection, reflects direct inputs from SCORE stakeholder workshops, research findings, and policy briefs co-developed by the CCLL. These contributions have ensured that climate adaptation is not only technically informed but locally grounded and supported.

It is estimated that about 120-150 stakeholders, including local authority engineers, community leaders, environmental NGOs, academic researchers, and students, participated in workshops, seminars, and meetings over the project's lifetime. In addition to periodically sharing key project results, the team also facilitated training sessions and MOOCs to ensure upskilling and increased awareness among these stakeholders, particularly in the county council. These efforts helped institutionalise climate knowledge across sectors and cultivated a long-term partnership between ATU and the local authority. A particularly impactful moment occurred during community outreach in Raghly, when satellite data analysis on coastal erosion, presented by ATU researcher Khurram, aligned perfectly with local residents' anecdotal observations, building trust in scientific methods and affirming the value of integrating local knowledge with technical research.

Engagement was further deepened through interactive citizen science and educational initiatives. CoastSnap stations installed in Enniscrone, Dunmoran, and Streedagh allowed local citizens to contribute to ongoing monitoring of shoreline changes and have shown to be very popular with locals. Similarly, the Smart Pebbles exercise at Raghly involved local schoolchildren in data collection, sparking curiosity and even inspiring one student to pursue environmental science at university. Presentations on storm surge modelling by researcher Tasneem were well received by both community members and technical staff, increasing awareness of climate risks and local capacities to respond. Additionally, the installation of water level sensors at Rosses Point, Mullaghmore, and Enniscrone not only supported real-time data collection but also invited ongoing public participation in environmental monitoring.

Beyond policy and education, the Sligo CCLL created new opportunities for local business engagement in the climate resilience sector. For example, the installation of the sand dune fencing EBA was carried out by a local contractor. The project exposed broader challenges in the sector, including a shortage of qualified contractors for nature-based adaptation work and increasing competition for construction services. Nevertheless, these pilot initiatives have helped raise awareness of the economic potential of environmental services, and SCORE's financial risk research led by Dr. Ananya Tiwari, who obtained her PhD through her work in SCORE, is expected to guide more strategic, cost-

effective allocation of public resources in future adaptation planning. This research will also support emerging green procurement practices, giving local businesses clearer pathways to contribute to climate resilience.

The legacy of the Sligo CCLL is being carried forward through its integration into EU-funded follow-on projects such as ProClimate and Pro-Coast, and new Horizon Europe proposals are currently in development to further expand its scope. The relationships and institutional ties established through SCORE between ATU, Sligo County Council, national stakeholders like NPWS, OPW, and Clean Coasts/An Taisce, and the local community, have laid a durable foundation for continued collaboration. In Sligo, the CCLL has become more than a project activity; it is now a functioning model for inclusive, science-based climate action that combines policy, education, community, and business in a shared mission for coastal resilience.

1.9.2. Dublin

The Dublin CCLL made significant strides in advancing climate resilience through the integration of EbA and citizen science into local planning and action. One of its most impactful outcomes was the successful inclusion of EbA recommendations into the [Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council's Climate Adaptation Plan](#), ensuring that nature-based strategies are part of future climate resilience efforts. Leveraging Dublin's robust data infrastructure, the CCLL conducted detailed mapping of climate hazards and impacts, enabling informed, data-driven decision-making at the local level.

Dublin CCLL was also a leading hub for citizen science innovation. Notable initiatives included the SMART Pebbles project and the development of the SCORE Sensor Map, which enabled the real-time monitoring of environmental conditions such as air quality, weather, and tidal activity. Smart Citizen Kits and weather stations were deployed at public buildings and private residences across the CCLL locality, while citizens and students assembled and launched Smart Pebbles to track coastal erosion and tidal flows. These tools were supported by training and onboarding workshops, and the collected data was visualized on the SCORE Geosurvey platform, allowing Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council and the public to monitor and interpret changing environmental conditions more effectively. The Dublin CCLL team has already secured additional funding for further SMART pebbles activities, embedding citizen science further into the area beyond SCORE. The Dublin CCLL will continue collaborating with UniPi to continue this work.

Key stakeholders engaged through the Dublin CCLL included local environmental groups like Dalkey Tidy Towns and Birdwatch Ireland, several local primary and secondary schools, and academic institutions. Through multiple workshops and hands-on activities, the CCLL fostered a collaborative network of citizens, students, and local authorities, strengthening climate awareness and empowering communities with the tools to take local action. Dublin CCLL hosted two final events, one specifically with people in the local authority to discuss how best to continue working together. The DLRCC recognised that through SCORE they first began their close relationship with UCD, and have already begun collaborating on another Horizon project.

The CCLL is now expanding into the use of Extended Reality (XR) tools to visualize climate data in immersive formats, enhancing public engagement and understanding of complex environmental processes. These innovations are supporting the ongoing application of SCORE tools in local climate adaptation strategies. The Dublin CCLL has successfully cultivated a strong, connected stakeholder ecosystem and established a foundation for continued innovation in nature-based adaptation, digital engagement, and community-led resilience. With the SCORE Geosurvey platform still active and ongoing use of sensor data in local governance, the CCLL is well-positioned to continue shaping Dublin's response to climate change in the years ahead.

1.9.3. Vilanova i la Geltrú

The Vilanova i la Geltrú CCLL made a significant contribution to the SCORE project by advancing digital twin innovation, financial risk tools, and EBAs. As a frontrunner for early development of SCORE's Digital Twin, Vilanova played a key role in modelling climate risks and testing user-friendly decision support tools. Initial efforts focused on compiling exposure data and risk projections, which were discussed during co-creation workshops with municipal stakeholders. These sessions highlighted the importance of translating complex climate and financial risks into accessible formats. Their input directly improved the usability of the SCORE Financial Decision Support Tool, making it a more practical asset for municipal planning and climate risk assessment.

Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) was at the core of Vilanova's co-creation process. Stakeholders collaboratively selected a wetland restoration project in Platja Llarga as the most relevant intervention, aligning ecological goals with urban resilience needs. Although full implementation was not possible within the SCORE project timeline, funds were secured to develop the executive project, ensuring that SCORE's insights and modelling will shape its design. Platja Llarga had long suffered from the impact of halted urbanisation and unmanaged dumping. Thanks to joint efforts by citizens and local politicians, construction plans were blocked and the area partially restored with support from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). With SCORE's added contribution, an additional permanent pond was installed, transforming the project from a purely conservation-focused initiative into a climate adaptation measure that protects both a vulnerable railway line and a nearby campsite, demonstrating the shift toward multifunctional, resilience-oriented EBA design.

The Vilanova CCLL also served as a platform for stakeholder learning and policy exchange. For example, their continued use of the SCORE MOOCs and translation of these resources into Spanish and Catalan have provided opportunities for upskilling on EBAs and climate-related challenges. In addition to planned SCORE activities, the team organised a final SCORE event on in May 2025 which brought together 60 participants, including political representatives, regional stakeholders, and neighbouring municipalities. Held as part of Vilanova's annual coastal governance workshop, this event showcased the CCLL's results and hosted a roundtable with members from Oarsoaldea and Benidorm CCLLs to discuss shared challenges in implementing EBAs and sensor monitoring. The CCLL Core Team partners presented project findings, while national and regional administrations highlighted funding and governance opportunities for climate adaptation in Catalonia's coastal zones. This format strengthened regional collaboration and aligned multiple levels of government around shared adaptation goals.

From an economic standpoint, SCORE activities in Vilanova supported new subcontracted opportunities in the environmental sector. The wetland restoration works were carried out by local companies contracted by the City Council. These activities contributed to job creation within the private sector and laid the foundation for ecotourism initiatives. For example, guided weekend tours at the restored wetland site offer new opportunities for local service providers. In parallel, the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) conducted on the restoration of the intermittent urban river, Torrent de la Piera, has laid the groundwork for an execution project that will be funded by the Catalan Water Agency, which will likely lead to interventions being implemented in the near future. Looking forward, Vilanova's CCLL is actively collaborating with SCORE partners on a PRIMA-Med proposal to continue advancing the Digital Twin and explore early warning systems.

1.9.4. Benidorm

Benidorm CCLL, featured a Core Team that included partners beyond the SCORE consortium, fostering a broader collaborative base. It was selected for in-depth coastal erosion analysis using the CoSMoS-COAST model, with a focus on projecting shoreline changes under climate change scenarios. This work informed the development of beach nourishment strategies in partnership with the City Council, some of which are planned for future implementation.

The construction of an urban dune to protect the coastline is planned for the three-year period 2025-2027, with funding of almost €500,000.

Benidorm CCLL was actively engaged with stakeholders, including an estimated over 20 stakeholder entities throughout the lifetime of the project: it was actively engaged with the tourism sector, establishing a formal collaboration with the municipal Tourism Department and the Association of Hotels and Restaurants (HOSBEC). This connection aims to align resilience strategies with the city's economic priorities and enhance the visibility of climate adaptation efforts within one of its most important industries. In this regard, hotels would allow the CCLL to install low-cost cameras for coastal monitoring. They would obtain valuable information for better business performance in exchange for being responsible for the equipment's maintenance. To increase awareness of EBAs and climate risks, the University of Alicante has used games developed within the framework of the SCORE project, such as Mapathon and the Geodesign Game, to engage high school and university students in the scientific method (citizen science) and to raise awareness of the impacts of climate change.

Benidorm is very active in EBA implementation, and Benidorm already had a Climate Change Adaptation Plan in place before the project began, so many of the EBAs selected during the workshops were already included in this document. The selection of EBAs during stakeholder events helped the City Council prioritize some EBAs over others. Looking forward, the University of Alicante is considering requesting funding for a new European project to continue the work carried out during SCORE, specifically the comprehensive management of beaches through sensors and technological tools.

1.9.5. Oarsoaldea

From the outset, Oarsoaldea CCLL built a strong strategy around the Pilot Operational Plan (POP), aiming to balance internal development with strong stakeholder engagement, and continues to utilise this resource. As a regional public entity, its primary goal was to raise awareness of climate adaptation needs and promote the use of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) among both local authorities and citizens. The team has estimated they have worked directly with over 90 stakeholders from 30 different entities over the course of the project, including stakeholders such as the University of the Basque Country (EHU), Don Bosco vocational training school, AZTI marine research center, or the Pasaia Port Authority, all of which now have stronger ties to the CCLL that will exist beyond the SCORE project. Additionally, the CCLL has periodically discussed the SCORE project within the Oarsoaldea Sustainability Table, which includes the four City Councils and the Oarsoaldea Development Agency.

A key component of the CCLL's efforts was clear, accessible communication to ensure all stakeholders understood the value of adaptation. Demonstration NBS/EBAs were implemented across four municipalities, protecting citizens from various risks associated with climate change, such as heat waves or floods, and providing them with services, such as creating more friendly and stimulating urban environments. Additionally, these NBS/EBAs are allowing the mobilization of funds beyond the SCORE budget and delivering a multiplier effect (around €280,000, compared to €42,000 of SCORE). These actions, combined with participatory events and the development of a combined MCA and CBA played a central role in conveying the economic and practical value of NBS, particularly for flood damage reduction. The evaluation exercise carried out on an EBA that currently exists in the territory, provided evidence of how this solution (the Bakea floodplain) generates annual economic benefits to the municipality by counteracting the risk of flooding that could occur in the built-up area in the absence of this park.

The CBA helped integrate findings from flood modelling, damage assessment, and economic loss projections, making the case for NBS investment in concrete terms. Priority was also given to citizen participation through the installation of sensors, both in schools with the installation of weather stations, and with the installation of water quality sensors in rivers and the bay, as well as the installation of panels for monitoring natural areas through photos taken by

citizens, fostering collective awareness and encouraging new practices at the local level. Oarsoaldea also contributed to a Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping study and a CBA evaluating a floodable park solution.

The CCLL culminated its work with a final stakeholder event, highlighting the most significant aspects of the project, such as the installed or developed EBAs, Citizen Science activities, MCA and CBA processes, Financial Resilience strategies, or the Living Lab methodology, and bringing together representatives from across the region (local, regional and autonomic administration representatives, academia representatives, citizens, students, associations, and private sector to show all the results and outputs developed within SCORE for Oarsoaldea.

1.9.6. Oeiras

As a key case study for real-time environmental monitoring, Oeiras CCLL established strong collaborations with its Civil Protection services. SCORE sensors were integrated into the municipality's digital platforms, strengthening early warning capabilities and supporting rapid responses to extreme weather events, such as heatwaves and flash floods. More than 70 stakeholders were directly engaged throughout SCORE's activities in Oeiras, ranging from civil servants, emergency responders, and academic partners to teachers and schoolchildren, but due to extensive communication and outreach strategies, it is possible the number of participants reached could be over 50,000.

Twelve co-creation events and participatory workshops held throughout the project lifetime helped build a common understanding of climate risks and adaptation needs. These included stakeholder alignment, co-design of sensor networks, classroom integration; university engagement, large-scale public awareness campaigns, knowledge exchange; and civil protection workshops, urban planning discussions, showcasing of SCORE results. SCORE resources, including webinars, MOOCs, and the co-creation toolbox, were disseminated through the municipality's official website and social media channels, with the dual aim of raising public awareness and building technical capacity across departments and within the community. The co-designed sensor network was tailored to local needs through these inclusive workshops, and installation sites were jointly selected by civil protection officers, technical experts, and school representatives. The installed hydro-meteorological sensors now feed data into the municipal Civil Protection's operational platform, informing daily decision-making and long-term risk assessment. Visual outputs from this system have already supported municipal planning and emergency response protocols. The Civil Protection department has committed to keeping SCORE sensors operational for ongoing early warning and territorial monitoring.

Additionally, Oeiras executed an effective communication strategy to raise awareness of climate change and the role of nature-based solutions. Approximately 300 students were reached across different education levels through interactive climate change quizzes and tailored outreach activities. Media engagement was extensive, including 16 articles on the municipal website (examples [1](#), [2](#), [3](#), [4](#)), 12 posts on *Oeiras Interativa* (examples [1](#), [2](#)), 14 Instagram updates (to ~57,000 followers on @municipiodeoeiras), 7 Facebook stories, 2 LinkedIn posts, and 1 Tweet, and coverage in *Oeiras Atual* ([Edition 269](#), [Edition 271](#)), the municipality's print journal. Even participants shared in this effort: for example the Camilo Castelo Branco School [publicised](#) the installation of a SCORE weather station for use in citizen science activities, directly linking education with environmental monitoring. The Oeiras CCLL established structures and partnerships that are set to endure well beyond the project's conclusion, including education and citizen science will continue under the *Oeiras Educa+* programme, particularly within school curricula.

Oeiras CCLL successfully influenced local policy by integrating SCORE results into the municipality's climate planning framework. Although EbA solutions such as green corridors (Eixo Verde e Azul) and urban gardens already existed in Oeiras, they had not previously been formally recognised or communicated using the EbA terminology. Through SCORE, these existing measures were framed and discussed as EbA during local workshops and public events, promoting a shared understanding of their role in climate resilience. The same municipal team that implemented

SCORE also led the development of Oeiras' *Energy and Climate Action Plan (PAECO2030+)*, ensuring knowledge continuity and institutional learning. This enabled the integration of key SCORE outcomes, such as the relevance EbA and co-monitoring methodologies, into the municipality's strategic planning instruments (e.g., explicit references to the SCORE project on pages 75 and 99 of the communication report, and the inclusion of EbA in Actions 5.2.1 and 5.3.1 of Volumes I and II of the PAECO2030+). Two local policy briefs ([Heatwaves in Portugal: Understanding, Mitigation, Adaptation; Red Flags on the Map](#)) were developed and disseminated to address urgent issues such as extreme heat and rainfall, informing both public discourse and municipal conversations. These efforts enhanced institutional learning and legitimised EbA within local policy, providing a solid foundation for future climate resilience initiatives. Oeiras is also exploring collaboration with other SCORE cities and the project coordinator on a new initiative to enhance citizen awareness of climate change.

1.9.7. Massa

The Massa CCLL made a notable contribution to the SCORE project through its focus on downscaled climate projections, flood hazard mapping, and Digital Twin development. As a key testbed for risk simulation and vulnerability assessment tools, Massa played a central role in developing digital and participatory approaches to climate adaptation, particularly for riverine and coastal flood risks. Stakeholder involvement in Massa was consistent and strategic throughout the four years of the project, and the team have estimated they have had direct engagement with about 150 stakeholders. Regular preparatory meetings, typically three to four annually, were held with key decision-makers, including the Mayor, City Councillors, and technical officials of the Municipality of Massa, showing the impact that the project had on the locality.

Beyond municipal officials, Massa CCLL also engaged higher education institutions, such as the Marble Institute in Massa and Carrara, bringing academic insights into the project. Civil protection volunteer associations were key partners, particularly in discussions on hazard monitoring and the use of the SCORE sensor catalogue. This multi-tiered engagement ensured that both technical expertise and community perspectives informed the adaptation strategies developed. Massa CCLL hosted several events to gather input and disseminate results: a major highlight was the two-day workshop in November 2023, held at Villa Cuturi, which brought together approximately 30 stakeholders, including local associations, public officials, and technical staff. Participants collaboratively identified priority EBA measures most suited to the territory. Through structured discussion, the group prioritised: Riparian reforestation / rehabilitation along riverbanks, bioswales, and filter strips. The impact of this session was clear, that the common goal of Massa was to reduce flood risk in a region highly exposed to riverine and coastal hazards. Massa also hosted the final SCORE EBA Training School event, where it presented key outcomes and demonstrated the potential of its Digital Twin and Geostory. This served as a capstone moment, showcasing the evolution of Massa's climate adaptation efforts under SCORE and sparking dialogue around future applications.

Massa CCLL was a leader in the development of a Digital Twin prototype that enables real-time flood simulation and risk mapping, offering a dynamic tool for assessing vulnerabilities and supporting emergency planning. To ensure its usability, several knowledge transfer sessions were conducted with local officials and system users. These sessions built the capacity of municipal staff and helped refine the tool's functionality to meet real-world needs. The SCORE sensor catalogue and the EBA catalogue were used in discussions with civil protection and technical staff to inform potential future interventions. While no EbA projects have yet been implemented by the municipality, the catalogues have served as critical planning resources. Massa's Geostory has been broadly disseminated and is being used to raise awareness and frame local dialogue around climate adaptation. Additionally, financial strategies related to hypothetical calamity scenarios were presented to municipal leaders, enhancing local understanding of the economic implications of climate risks and the value of proactive planning.

Building on the foundations laid during SCORE, Massa is preparing new initiatives that extend the impact of the project. Notably, a PRIMA Med proposal is under development to continue exploring digital tools and nature-based solutions for climate resilience in the area. Although no EbA measures have yet been implemented, the studies and data developed through SCORE are already influencing local planning, particularly in the area of flood risk reduction. The Municipality is actively considering how to apply SCORE outputs in future sustainability and resilience projects, with continued collaboration between the project team and local administration anticipated.

1.9.8. Piran

In Piran CCLL, the SCORE approach was taken as a continuation approach, and the team has expressed clear ambitions to scale up its work by transferring key concepts and practices to other coastal cities. The team prioritised co-creation with citizens, municipal staff, environmental experts, and community groups, embedding ecological knowledge into local planning. Particular emphasis was placed on aligning EbA strategies with cultural heritage conservation and sustainable tourism, addressing the spatial constraints of Piran's densely built historic centre.

Stakeholder engagement was a core strength of the Piran CCLL. A broad and lasting network was built, with informal one-on-one meetings proving the most effective for reaching diverse and sometimes hard-to-reach stakeholders. These early interviews, conducted before the second general workshop, helped build trust and generated a snowball effect that drew in more community interest. Later in the project, several invitations were received from local organisations to join community activities, reflecting strong mutual engagement.

In total, the team held approximately 15 EbA design meetings with the municipality, landscape architects, and cultural heritage authorities; 4 knowledge transfer sessions with local high schools; and 3 Valorization and Innovations of Traditional Architecture and landscape in Piran (ViTA) working group (a citizen-led initiative focused on preserving Piran's traditional architecture and landscape) meetings to address architectural and landscape conservation (including the revalorization of historic rainwater collectors). The team has also joined a working group dedicated to revalorising the natural landscape of Piran and have committed to two upcoming assemblies. Around 4 sensor selection meetings took place with civil protection services and the municipal environmental and waste management company. While both organisations provided input, only the latter had the capacity and land access to support proper sensor installation. Some privately owned sensors and those managed by the municipal company have since been integrated into the SIP, demonstrating continued commitment beyond the project's end and active engagement with local SMEs and the local economy. ZRS Koper also organised two international networking events, one on digitalisation in historical research and another on climate-adaptive coastal and marine research, where SCORE concepts were showcased, particularly traditional, co-designed adaptation approaches blending nature-based solutions with heritage infrastructure.

Additionally, Piran served as a best-practice site for applying Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA), contributing to the *Navigating Living Labs* guide and the associated MOOC. Its EbA strategies centred on traditional green infrastructure: water-permeable stone pavements, dry-stone walls, terraced gardens, and historic rainwater collectors. These solutions targeted urban heat, freshwater scarcity, and flash flooding, while enhancing biodiversity and public space, all while always being in accordance with cultural and environmental protection regulations. Although a plan to renovate the city's terraces is ready for implementation, it awaits funding. Political obstacles have temporarily stalled progress, as the municipal spatial plan, aligned with SCORE recommendations, was rejected by ministerial authorities. Nonetheless, the groundwork laid by the Piran CCLL has positioned the city to act quickly when new opportunities arise.

Looking ahead, several initiatives will carry forward the momentum of SCORE in Piran. All Piran-specific SCORE outputs, including MCA results, prioritised EBAs, CBA, and risk maps, are being compiled into a printed results book

for the locality. Additionally, the Citizen Science Playbook is being translated into Slovenian to support integrated Living Lab engagement and climate adaptation learning. The newly funded NATURGO project (2025–2028), coordinated by ZRS Koper's MIOS department, will integrate NBS into urban water governance, with the Piran team as an associated partner to advise on prioritised NBS/EBAs for early implementation. Building on the successful CBA of historic rainwater collectors, ZRS Koper and the municipality are also planning a non-invasive survey of cisterns in collaboration with OGS Trieste to assess their capacity and condition. In parallel, the VITA working group will continue promoting traditional EBA methods beyond SCORE. Additionally, a postponed exhibition on traditional rainwater systems with the Piran Maritime Museum remains under consideration, pending funding and institutional changes. Finally, the urban terrace renovation plan will require skilled landscape architects and dry-stone wall masons, helping to revive traditional craftsmanship while supporting broader adaptation efforts. These next steps aim to deepen local resilience, reinforce cultural identity, and ensure long-term impact from SCORE.

1.9.9. Gdansk

The Gdańsk CCLL focused on understanding and addressing the city's vulnerability to urban flash floods and torrential rain events. A historical analysis of these events laid the foundation for their MCA workshop, which identified key Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) priorities: water parks and retention ponds, green spaces, and tree plantations. These findings have informed future planning and will guide the city's strategy for flood resilience. While no new EBAs were implemented during SCORE, the CCLL conducted thorough analysis and recommended feasible options for future action. A notable collaboration with Gdańsk Waters has resulted in plans to relocate a key measurement station to the University of Gdańsk and grant the CCLL access to a comprehensive dataset from the city's hydrometeorological monitoring network dating back to 2018.

Stakeholder engagement was central to the Gdańsk CCLL approach, with particular emphasis on educational outreach. Students and academic staff participated in workshops using the GeoDesign tool to evaluate potential EBAs. A robust Citizen Science programme targeted children and youth of all ages, including those with disabilities, through guided tours, STEM activities, and climate education, reaching nearly 400 participants over the course of the project.

Gdańsk is committed to continuing its role as a CCLL beyond SCORE. The CCLL has joined the Horizon Europe ProClimate project and has recently hosted a joint event with the NightMission project in June 2025, including a final workshop and lecture for 180 students. Further stakeholder meetings are scheduled for late June to reflect on key results and future directions. These ongoing efforts signal a strong commitment to maintaining and scaling up the CCLL model for sustainable and inclusive urban climate adaptation in Gdansk.

1.9.10. Samsun

The Samsun CCLL made substantial contributions to EbA and climate resilience during the SCORE project, particularly in response to growing flood risks, saltwater intrusion, and coastal erosion. The CCLL carried out extensive flood risk modelling using HEC-RAS 2D, producing hazard maps that directly informed [local policy briefs](#) and prioritised EbA measures such as floodplain enlargement, dune restoration, and bank naturalisation. These solutions were co-designed with local authorities including Ondokuz Mayıs Municipality and the State Hydraulic Works (DSI), and in some cases, such as the dune restoration and traditional floodwall construction, implemented during the project. In salt-affected farmland, real-time water sensors were deployed to support ecological dyke planning and adaptive responses, reflecting a strong focus on practical climate resilience.

The Samsun CCLL developed strong, lasting connections across stakeholder groups, including local farmers, fishermen, academics, government agencies, and students, building trust and a shared commitment to action. More

than 500 individuals were engaged over the four years through beach cleanups, school workshops, citizen science activities, co-creation events, and EbA planting campaigns. Primary and secondary schools, along with Samsun University, were key partners. For example, the laurel tree planting project involved local children, women's cooperatives, and farmers in germination, cultivation, and planting along a 1-kilometer coastal stretch, integrating education, ecological restoration, and future economic opportunities.

Samsun's CCLL approach inspired broader regional action. It directly supported the launch of a second non-SCORE Living Lab in Sinop through the SinoP project and strengthened ties with Başakşehir LL, one of Türkiye's most active labs. Moreover, Samsun University developed a new undergraduate course on nature-based solutions, submitted for curriculum approval, demonstrating institutional commitment to long-term capacity-building. Efforts to institutionalize the CCLL are ongoing. Samsun has applied for official certification from ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs), receiving highly positive feedback. This recognition would solidify its position as a hub for innovation and knowledge-sharing in climate adaptation.

The Samsun CCLL team has also laid the foundation for future research and innovation. The Samsun CCLL was certified by the European Network of Living Labs as a full Living Lab in June 2025. As such, this means they are members adhering to all requirements as specified by ENoLL. A huge impact for the team, this means the CCLL will continue on for years to come.

Further, Samsun University is involved in multiple proposals that extend SCORE's work, including *NATURE WISE*, submitted under a multilateral STI call, focused on nature-based, decentralized wastewater treatment; *KADIM-SU*, a national proposal for AI-driven drought risk management in Konya; and an upcoming PRIMA project targeting integrated water-energy-food nexus policies using digital twin and early warning system experiences from SCORE. Additionally, Samsun will join as a mentor partner in a Horizon Europe consortium under the 2025 CLIMA call, further expanding its leadership role in coastal climate adaptation. Together, these initiatives ensure that the knowledge, practices, and partnerships cultivated through the Samsun CCLL will continue to thrive and scale well beyond the scope of the SCORE project.

2. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND TRANSFER METHODOLOGY

2.1. Knowledge management and transfer overview

To ensure SCORE maximised its impact by exploiting results the project employs a proven Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology. This methodology was originally developed in the FP7 MarineTT project (GA #244164) and further developed and applied by the H2020 COLUMBUS project (GA #652690 - www.columbusproject.eu). This methodology has been applied in many FP7 and Horizon 2020 funded projects such as AQUAEXCEL, AQUAEXCEL2020, Aqualnova, ARRAINA, COEXIST, COMMON SENSE, ECsafeSEAFOOD, MaCuMBA, MG4U, ParaFishControl, MATES, SIMBA, ERGO REvived water, RES4BUILD, SEALIVE, BIOGEARS, SEArcularMINE, TechOceanS and ESCAPE.

SCORE's Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology was designed in a way to compliment the aforementioned dissemination and communication activities and overarchingly, to ensure the continued targeted impact of all knowledge transfer activities and foster exploitation of SCORE's results.

All captured knowledge was assessed and recorded in line with the Consortium Agreement (CA), respecting privacy and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) requirements. This approach was essential to avoid unforeseen delays or obstacles related to confidentiality or competitiveness and to provide partners with the security they need to allow them to be transparent in their findings, enabling the project to quickly identify opportunities for exploitation. The objective was to ensure the fastest route for new knowledge to where it can add value and create impact.

Table 6: List of relevant definitions for knowledge management and transfer

Definitions
<p>Knowledge Management is the process of identifying, capturing, organising, analysing, and storing knowledge (project results and outputs) to ensure its availability to be transferred effectively to specific and relevant users.</p>
<p>Knowledge Transfer (KT) is the overall process of moving knowledge from knowledge sources to targeted potential users, focusing the research being conducted on the wider needs of society and industry. KT consists of a range of activities that aims to capture, transmit and exploit knowledge, skills, and competencies from those who generate them to those who will transform them into added value outcomes, thus maximizing impact. It can include commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, licensing, spin-off creation, researcher mobility, and publications. The ultimate end benefit of successful KT is the application and influence of knowledge on targeted groups with greater impact (short and long term) across academia, industry, and society.</p> <p>This methodology focuses on capturing all the project's 'Knowledge Outputs' (KOs) and, through a series of collections and prioritisation, identifying the 'Key Exploitable Results' (KERs).</p>
<p>Knowledge Outputs (KOs) are described as "a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a scientific project. It is not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge". Typically, such knowledge might be referenced as a small part of a published paper, potentially three to five years after the approach is pioneered in a research project.</p>

Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are the ‘tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature’ which have been deemed to be of high priority for project transfer actions. How KERs will be identified from KOs is described in Section 3 of the PEDR, but it is important to note that SCORE is not implying any sort of value judgement between KOs and KERs. Rather, the project is simply using this distinction to allow knowledge that is of the most direct impact to the project or is most feasibly transferrable by the project, to be prioritised when assigning resources for transfer. By focusing on identifying KERs and transferring them when they have been assessed as having potential application and impact, it is possible to fast track them, providing a faster impact on target- and end-users external to the project.

End-user(s) are the individual(s) who are identified as being in a position where they could feasibly apply a given unit of Knowledge (KO/KER) and by so doing create the desired eventual impact of that knowledge. The KO/KER may need to evolve in order to reach the end-user.

Target User is an individual(s) (organisations should be avoided where possible as specificity is crucial), whose position makes them a potential stepping-stone needed along the impact pathway for a KO/KER to progress towards an identified end-user and eventual impact. Target users are individuals with a specific mandate or responsibilities relevant to the specific KO/KER being evaluated. Target users should not merely be potential users of knowledge but should be individuals whose application of the knowledge is likely to advance it down the relevant Knowledge Transfer Pathway. There can be any number of target users in a Knowledge Transfer Pathway.

A **Knowledge Transfer Plan** (KTP) is an analysed stepwise plan for achieving the identified eventual impact of any piece of knowledge, regardless of whether this impact is achievable in the short, medium, or long term. In SCORE these will be applied to all assessed KERs. The KTP identifies the end-user capable of producing the desired eventual impact and outlines a specific series of transfer activities to intermediate target users that provide a feasible plan to reach them.

Eventual Impact is the ultimate end benefit of the application of the knowledge (KO/KER). It is defined as an overall enhanced situation, generally for society but it can also be research or industry specific. Eventual impacts can be the adoption of new technologies, products or innovation identified and refined within the project or a change in protocols.

2.2. Knowledge management and transfer for SCORE

The Knowledge Management Strategy (KMS) and Knowledge Transfer of KO/KERs was integrated into the project through WP9, specifically in T9.3. The KMS was based on regularly collecting project KOs through structured questionnaires and interviews with partners responsible for developing the results. Collected and analysed KOs were assessed by the Innovation Manager (MBI) and Innovation Board based on several criteria, including: their innovation capacity, relevance to the respective sector, adherence to the project and call objectives, relevance at the local/regional levels for the CCLLs, and overall expected impact. The Innovation Board also discussed the most suitable exploitation and targeted dissemination activities, as well as the most relevant target and end users to prioritise. The Innovation Board consisted of all project SMEs (MBI, RED SpA, EUR, ENT, TERO, and ERINN).

ERINN (T9.3 leader) monitored knowledge generated by carrying out regular collection rounds. These collections were iterative, involving questionnaires, interviews and rounds of reviews to ensure all information is clear and up-to-date. All Knowledge Outputs (KOs) collected were analysed with support from the IB and relevant partners, to identify the project’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and assess whether IP protection was necessary. For the identified KERs, ERINN developed initial Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTPs), detailing customised transfer activities for the target and end-user(s).

KTPs were then submitted to the Innovation Board and relevant partners for review and input, ensuring SCORE innovations were in line with the latest market needs and expectations and/or ensuring the KTPs were tailored to the CCLL's local contexts. The Innovation Board and KTPs considered the potential routes to maximize impact of the KO/KER for at both the European/national level and regional/local CCLL level. As such, the KOs/KERs were reviewed for both their relevancy, novelty, use and exploitation potential at a European level and at the CCLL/local level.

ERINN and Euronovia supported the KO/KER owners and CCLL core teams, in planning the implementation of KTPs (identifying relevant stakeholders, events etc.) and dissemination/exploitation activities needed for transfer. SCORE's KT methodology developed transfer plans that were tailored to the respective target user. This customised approach increased the likelihood that 1) KOs/KERs will be transferred and exploited successfully, and the result will be applied; 2) there is an increased potential for impact from the transfer; 3) it is possible to measure and demonstrate the impact of the transfer.

To support the successful engagement of SCORE partners with this methodology, an internal special workshop organised to deal with exploitation and the protection of results took place during the Sligo Consortium Meeting (June 2022) to showcase the methodology and provide a practical overview of the knowledge management methodology. Subsequently, collected KOs/KERs and practical reminders about the KTP methodology were presented at the Alicante Consortium meeting (2023) and the Gdansk Consortium meeting (2024), with a final update delivered at the final consortium meeting in Rimini (2025). This allowed ERINN to keep partners familiar with the process, aware of the project's KOs/KERs, and to ensure that all partners were aware of the need to protect any results with potential commercial applications. The KOs/KERs were presented to the consortium at the end of the project, and for KER owners the actions to fulfil their market potential were outlined. Upon conclusion of the project, all project results were summarised in an accessible spreadsheet for all partners, with a particular focus on accessibility for the CCLLs, to clearly see what results were relevant to their cases, where they could find the resource, and how to utilise it most effectively. Additionally, the [Key Achievements Page](#) on the SCORE website summarised all KERs for use by the public, with information on target users, impact, and links to the associated resources or contact information. The partners have access to the KOs, KERs and KTPs on SCORE's SharePoint and can review them at any point. All partners were made aware of [IP policy and the Code of Practice](#) concerning the management of IP as stated by the recommendation from the EC.

2.2.1. Cross Cutting Principles

SCORE was a highly integrated and complex project, and therefore the knowledge management process required a corresponding robustness. The project had been designed in such a way to ensure that knowledge management and knowledge transfer were cross-cutting activities across the project. Notably, ERINN as Task 9.3 leader, was involved in knowledge transfer and impact related tasks across three technical work packages and across WP9. Details are outlined below.

- Within **WP2** (Coastal City Living Labs Design, Implementation, and Evaluation), ERINN led Task 2.8 – “Knowledge Production & Exchange” (M6 – M48) and was actively engaged across the WP2 tasks, including the workshops involving local stakeholders. Within Task 2.8, ERINN regularly held “lessons learned” (LL) meetings with the CCLLs and technical partners to assess and reflect on the implementation of the living lab methodology and associated technologies. This ultimately led to the development of D2.4 (Final CCLL Knowledge Products and Lessons Learned). However, these interactions and engagement across WP2 supported the KT activities by allowing ERINN to better understand the CCLL priorities and their respective local contexts, engage with the CCLLs during the implementation of the Pilot Operational Plans, including providing guidance on the local dissemination activities. Further, ERINN worked closely with Naider on Task

2.6 - Learning exchanges, between frontrunner and follower CCLLs to ensure that not only are the results and experiences of the CCLLs disseminated and opportunities for exploitation were shared amongst the CCLLs, but that the best-practice principles and activities were documented extensively, to support the development of future CCLLs beyond SCORE's 10 CCLLs. Lastly, WP9 utilised the CCLL's stakeholder identification and prioritisation, climate action plan development and ENOLL's CCLL mentorship activities to support KT activities, to ensure sufficient impact and the long-term sustainability of the CCLLs contribute to the success.

- Within **WP6** (Strategies to increase the financial resilience of coastal cities), ERINN partners on Task 6.5: Decision-support guidelines for policy makers (M30-44). This ensured that ERINN was active in the development of financial resilience strategies that were tailored and specific for the WP6 frontrunners and in local languages.
- Within **WP7**, WP9 supported WP7 partners in the implementation of Task 7.5, which focuses on formulating policy recommendations to aid decision-making in climate change adaptation at local, national, and EU levels. This task aims to gather evidence on coastal ecosystem services and adaptation costs and benefits, sharing success stories to demonstrate public value from adaptation measures. WP9 assisted in the potential design of these policy recommendations and supported the dissemination of the outcomes to ensure effective policy uptake and implementation through the established KT methodology.
- Within **WP8** (Development of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin solution prototypes), ERINN partners on Task 8.4 (Integration and Deployment of GIS based Early Warning and Digital Twin Platform: M24-48) and Task 8.5 (Assessment of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin: M24-48). The KT methodology has been incorporated into the Impact Assessment for the digital twin (DT) and early warning system (EWS) implementation. The impact assessments include the development of KTPs for each CCLL as related to the DT and EWS which are presented below.
- ERINN has an active role supporting WP leader Euronovia in **WP9** (Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation), specifically ERINN is a key member of the EBA Training School Team and leads the development of the MOOC (Task 9.6 – EBA Training Schools: M6-48) to facilitate exploitation via the [SCORE MOOC platform](#) on a large European level and within the CCLL communities.

2.2.2. KT Training and Support Activities

The methodology of engaging the CCLLs in KT was a central part of WP9 and is consciously incorporated into the knowledge transfer methodology. In addition to the KT methodology, a number of supporting KT activities have been taking place to further engage the CCLLs.

At the CCLL/local level, ERINN has facilitated communication and dissemination strategy session with the WP2 Frontrunners, helping them to facilitate their KT strategies within their CCLL. These sessions took place for the WP2 Fellows in the Fall 2023. Overall, due to the presence of ERINN in WP2, the KT perspective is present throughout CCLL activities, including learning exchanges and lessons learned collections. Further dissemination trainings and KT knowledge sharing sessions have been facilitated at the CCLL Board Meetings and during the Year 1 & 2 Consortium, as well as developing and distributing Communication & Dissemination Guidelines and corresponding Knowledge Transfer Strategy Template for the CCLLs to utilise. Alongside these activities, ERINN has developed various infographics for the CCLLs, in their relevant local languages, to share the SCORE results with local stakeholders. Additionally, as ERINN led *Task 9.6.3 Lectures as MOOCs*, they were able to identify opportunities for learning materials from the CCLLs to develop the SCORE Online Learning courses. As the final KTPs were developed, the CCLLs were recommended to take on various knowledge transfer activities as recommended by the Innovation Board.

2.2.3. Knowledge Transfer Impact Assessment

Within the KTPs, KERs were assigned a current **Impact Readiness Level (IRL)**, and a target IRL to be achieved near or just beyond the end of the SCORE project as a measure of impact quantification. IRLs were first conceived by the EU-funded DANDELION Project in 2018 (GA: 693796) and have been adapted here to incorporate elements of the impact pathway model arising from the EU-funded RI-PATHS project. The Impact Readiness Level (Annex 5) provides an assessment of how 'actionable' knowledge is in the societal and policy context. Proxy indicators are used to reflect various types of stakeholder engagement along the impact pathway that are conducive to impact generation. These indicators acknowledge that pathways are not always linear, recognising that in many cases systemic and/or sustained engagement can be required to achieve a desired impact. The IRLs have also been mapped to the more widely recognised Technology Readiness Levels and Societal Readiness Levels for comparison.

IRL's have been selected as the mechanism to track the KER's impact and the holistic advancement of SCORE's knowledge. As such, SCORE's KTPs do not have a traditional quantification measure (i.e., reach x number of stakeholders or x number of downloads) as these actions, while fulfilling dissemination/exploitation criterion does not necessarily measure impact holistically, but rather measures the progress of one or two specific knowledge transfer activities. Certain knowledge transfer activities will be more impactful than others (i.e., having one-to-one meetings with a single local policymaker vs emailing a policy brief to 10 policymakers), despite the action equating to a lower KPI. Rather than selecting more traditionally quantifiable KPIs, which may assess the impact progression more narrowly, the IRL measures progress more holistically and is therefore the selected impact measurement for SCORE.

The progression of the IRL was supported by monitoring the knowledge transfer activities, accordingly each KTP included a number of KT activities to track to provide the KO/KER owners will guidance on what will support the progression of the KER up the IRL scale. The IRL levels were monitored over the course of the project to ensure that the knowledge moved along as anticipated/outlined in the KTPs. At the end of the project, the KERs were each summarised in a final Impact Assessment (see Chapter 3). For these assessments, the KTPs were assessed to ensure that the intended IRL was achieved through project work, and a clear pathway for further exploitation was decided upon at the conclusion of the project. This process included ERINN reassessing KTPs alongside KER owners and discussing activities that took place during SCORE project-specific activities, with external users through the lifetime of the project, and finally detailing next planned and recommended steps for each KER. In Chapter 3 below, these Impact Assessments are organised by the three key messages of the project, with relevant KERs detailed within each section.

2.3. Knowledge management & Transfer Steps and Protocols

This section outlines the stepwise process which were carried out within T9.3. This methodology saw KOs identified, collected, reviewed, and prioritised to project KERs with developed KTPs. Figure 27 provides an overview of the full knowledge transfer pathway. The following sections will explain specific steps of this methodology and demonstrate how each step contributes to the overall knowledge transfer process.

The Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology consisted of the following three overall phases and is further described in detail below:

- **Collect and Understand**

- Validate and Analyse
- Transfer and Exploit

Figure 27: SCORE Full Knowledge Transfer Pathway and Methodology

2.3.1. Collect & Understand

Phase 1: Capturing of KOs in an internal KO Questionnaire (KOQ).

Effective KT relies on careful identification and description of KOs to ensure that all key information is provided which will result in effective transfer (Figure 28). This phase aimed to understand the positioning of a KO to more efficiently carry out impactful KT activities. It intends to help clarify how the KO could be beneficial to different target and end-users. This step identifies potential applications, target and end-users and the eventual impact of a KO. The KOs were collected in a Knowledge Output Questionnaire and further clarified through engagement with the KO owner.

Within this phase, quality control measures were performed to ensure that the KO(s) could be clearly understood by others, including those who may not be experts in the relevant disciplines. Each partner treated information from other partners as confidential, unless otherwise stated, and did not disclose it to other parties unless the information was publicly available. All beneficiaries needed to note that KOs are not only the final results of research, but they can also be part of the methodology to obtain the final result, which could be an innovation for the whole research area. It should be noted that KOs, especially those collected early in the project, continued to develop throughout SCORE. Collected knowledge was periodically reviewed by ERINN and the relevant partners were asked to provide updates if applicable. An overview of the KOs was available on SharePoint, so partners could advise ERINN if a given KO/KER needed to be updated.

Figure 28: SCORE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Collect and Understand

PROTOCOL – Phase 1 Collect & Understand

1. ERINN sent the Knowledge Output Questionnaire (KOQ) to SCORE Task Leaders every 6 months beginning in M18, who are requested to complete it and update it as appropriate.
2. If the Task Leader thought another partner was better suited to provide the requested information, then they sent it on to the relevant person(s) or let ERINN know who this person was.
3. For all identified KOs from the questionnaire, ERINN arranged interviews with the KO owner(s) to better understand the knowledge collected and brainstorm potential uses and users of the KO.
4. After the interview, the KO owner(s) received an updated draft of the KO to check for accuracy following the discussion. KO owner(s) responded with any corrections or suggested additions/edits promptly. In particular, this review focused on:
 - 4.1. If the title of the KO(s) is sufficiently informative
 - 4.2. If the description of the KO(s) is sufficiently comprehensive for a non-expert to adequately understand the nature of the KO and to determine its possible application
 - 4.3. If the potential end-users of the KO, as well as the potential application by each of these end-users, is reasonable/desirable and if there are any other potential end-users
 - 4.4. If the KO(s) is publicly available or is subject to IPR protection, which would affect transfer mechanisms and next steps
5. Once the KO owner was satisfied with the accuracy of their KOs they were marked as “confirmed” in the Knowledge Output Template (KO).
6. KOs advanced to the validation and analysis stage.

2.3.2. Analyse & Validate

Phase 2: The collected KOs are reviewed and assessed for potential application and impact.

Once the KO had been signed off by the owner and ERINN, the KOs went through an internal review process with the support of the Innovation Board, whereby a more thorough evaluation of the KO and its applicability and readiness for transfer was investigated (Figure 29). Due diligence was undertaken so that any factors that could affect the transfer potential (confidentiality, competition, IPR) of the KO and ultimately the uptake and impact of the knowledge could be identified. Following, KOs were prioritised and those with the potential to have an impact went through to the next step. An essential step in the SCORE knowledge management and transfer methodology was the identification of KO applications, potential impact and respective end-users (e.g., applications could be in various areas and sectors not just the one in the research area of the project) for each KO which was assessed as having high potential application and impact.

Important aspects were prioritisation of high potential KOs, profiling target and end-users to gain valuable insight to inform successful Knowledge Transfer Plans, and identification of whether knowledge transfer should occur at the EU/national level, CCLL level or both. The identification of whether transfer should be prioritised at the EU/National level and/or CCLL level was a key step in the knowledge transfer process. Further, for those KO/KERs that were identified as priority for CCLL level knowledge transfer, the CCLLs that are frontrunners for that KO's work package were prioritised amongst the CCLLs for transfer activities due to an availability of results. For example, within WP6, Massa, Oarsoaldea and Vilanova were frontrunners, so any KOs developed within WP6 focussed on the transfer activities within those localities.

The prioritisation process which occurs was not a ranking of the KO's importance but rather a method to help SCORE identify where to focus transfer and exploitation efforts to ensure maximize impact. For those prioritised, the Innovation Board with support of relevant partners identified potential target users whose application of the knowledge would be of benefit in transferring it towards its eventual impact.

Those KOs that were validated and deemed to be of priority for the project were re-labelled as Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and progressed to the third phase. Any KO that was not made a KER continued to be periodically reviewed and updated as necessary. Any remaining KOs at the end of the project were still captured as evidence of impactful research for final reporting. The identification of target users in the analysis stage is critical to laying the groundwork for transfer and exploitation plans in the third phase. The exercises in this phase may also serve to identify potential stakeholder's worth connecting with, even in cases where the knowledge may not yet be ready for transfer.

Figure 29: Methodology: Analyse and Validate

PROTOCOL – Phase 2 Analyse & Validate

- ERINN organised KO and KER “expert analysis meetings” with the Innovation Board and when relevant, invited members of the consortium and advisory board following the completion of Phase 1.
 - The frequency and makeup of these meetings was determined in collaboration with the Project Coordinator (ATU) and Innovation Manager (MBI), as well as based on the current status of knowledge collection and management in the project.
- At the expert analysis meetings, the Innovation Board carried out a thorough examination and evaluation of the KOs (collected so far), their applicability and readiness for transfer, and assessment of whether IP protection is necessary. For each KO, the following was considered:
 - If the KO required an IP assessment
 - If the KO was best suited for EU/National level exploitation, CCLL level exploitation or both.
 - Identification of all likely target and end-users. We encouraged partners to be as specific as possible when determining potential end-users, and consider the following conditions:
 - Understand the user’s mandate or responsibilities
 - Consider their background knowledge, attitude and practice about the issue
 - Understand their knowledge needs
 - Understand what and who may influence their decisions
 - Be aware of their preferred sources of information and knowledge.
 - Identification of associated application and impact potential
 - The Innovation Board addressed the likelihood of transfer for each presented KO, by providing a ranking. The Innovation Board cumulative ranking (scale of 1 to 3, 3 = highest likelihood for transfer) indicated whether this KO has a high likelihood of transfer and determined whether or not it should be prioritised as a KER based on its current status.
 - The ranking included an assessment of whether or not transfer is most appropriate at the European level or at the CCLL level. If it is at the CCLL level, specific CCLLs would be identified (i.e., those CCLLs that are frontrunners in the WP corresponding to this KO).
- After each expert analysis meeting, ERINN adjusted the KO where necessary, including requesting clarification from the KO owners or progressing the knowledge (changing the KO to a KER).
 - If an IP assessment was deemed necessary by the Innovation Board during the expert analysis meetings, the generating partner was asked to complete an IP Assessment to be reviewed by the

Innovation Manager and appropriate board member(s) who guided as necessary until all relevant parties believe sufficient IP protection rules had been applied before the further dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the KO.

- Those KOs that progress to KER status underwent the activities outlined in Phase 3. For those KOs that were not ranked with a high-likelihood for transfer, this KO and associated results was reassessed in subsequent KO collection periods and the KO owner was requested to input further information assuming the result had progressed in the previous 6 months.

2.3.3. Transfer & Exploit

Phase 3: Carry out and report on Knowledge Transfer activities; whilst measuring the impact of both the activity and the application of the Knowledge by the User(s).

For each KER, Knowledge Transfer Plans (KTP) were developed. Implementing an efficient KTP that is tailor-made to the needs and capacities of specific target and end-users (profiled in phase 2) maximised the chance of successful transfer resulting in uptake and application. The key to success was achieved through fully understanding the target and end-user and developing the KTP around them. There were several steps included in the KTP, and there were different routes it could go down to reach its eventual impact. The final KTPs are the accumulation of numerous KT activities as represented in Figure 30.

Within the KTPs, KERs were assigned a current Impact Readiness Levels (IRL) and a target IRL to be achieved near or just beyond the end of the SCORE project as a measure of impact quantification or KPI. The Impact Readiness Level Model below provides an assessment of how 'actionable' knowledge is in the societal and policy context. The IRLs (Annex 5) have also been mapped to the more widely recognised Technology Readiness Levels and Societal Readiness Levels for comparison. The KER's IRLs were monitored throughout the project duration to assess overall impact.

The individual partner(s) and/or CCLL(s) within SCORE best positioned to conduct the transfer were identified and ERINN supported these partners to implement the KTPs. In this phase the impact of SCORE's KERs were measured at regular intervals using the assigned and target IRL. KERs were all showcased on the EC's Horizon Results Platform outlining the actions required to fulfil their market potential.

The work carried out in this phase was essential for impact generation, and supported by activities to ensure the accurate reporting of the knowledge transfer activities. Not every KTP was able to be reasonably executed during the lifetime of the project, but by delivering clear plans, the knowledge management methodology helped to establish how exploitation actions within the project could feed into the overall impact of the project as a whole and help achieve the societal goals of SCORE.

Figure 30: SCORE Knowledge Transfer Methodology: Transfer and Exploit

PROTOCOL – Phase 3 Knowledge Transfer Planning & Exploitation

ERINN, with the support of Euronovia and the Innovation Board, worked with all relevant partners and CCLLs to assist where possible to implement the KTPs into knowledge transfer activities to engage with the appropriate target and end-users.

For any knowledge that had been determined to be a KER:

1. ERINN collaborated with the Innovation Manager and Innovation Board and the owner(s) of a KER to develop a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) for each KER. It considered:
 - 1.1. The impact potential identified in the validation and analysis step ensures that a concise and compelling narrative for the opportunity/business case is developed.
 - 1.2. The technical level of the target user; the depth of information needed; and the style of the language most effective for communicating with them.
 - 1.3. The background knowledge of the target user.
 - 1.4. Any preconceived ideas that the target user may have relating to the area of interest.
 - 1.5. Ways in which to relate the knowledge to examples with which the target user is familiar, or ones they can easily envisage.
 - 1.6. The level of evidence or validation that the target user requires.
2. ERINN was responsible for drafting the KTPs, the nature of these knowledge transfer activities will be highly dependent on the KER, the target user(s), the transferring partner, timelines, and resources available.
 - 2.1. Once the KTPs had been drafted, they were reviewed by the coordination team, IB, generating partner(s) and when relevant, specific CCLLs for feedback. Following any necessary iterations, the KTPs were finalised.
3. The knowledge transfer activities themselves were then carried out within a range of externally focused tasks by the KER owner and/or relevant CCLLs.
 - 3.1. Any action points/knowledge transfer activities outline by the IB Board, KO owners and CCLLs were monitored and actioned by ERINN and EUR at monthly WP9 meetings.
 - 3.2. Support was provided to ensure the success of these knowledge transfer activities.

3. PRIORITISED KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

This section includes an overview of the prioritised KERs and the associated KTPs that have been developed for those high prioritised KERs. The KTPs are developed to have specific knowledge transfer activities outlined for each of the target groups per KO. The target users and end-users for the KO's are diverse in their needs and expectations and as such, personalised plans were developed for each KO target group. The KTPs are written in a concise and straightforward manner to ensure easy uptake by SCORE partners and beyond the project.

The KTPs are based on the KO's submitted to the ERINN and the Innovation Board. In total, **31 KOs were submitted to ERINN across 4 separate collection rounds** periodically conducted throughout the project. Table 7 below gives an overview of all KOs collected, along with their status as a Knowledge Output or a Key Exploitable Result.

Table 7: Overview of Knowledge Outputs for SCORE

KO #	Title	WP	Primary Owner	Status
KO1.1	Mapping of baseline exposure and risks of climate change impacts on Coastal Cities	WP1	UCC	Knowledge Output
KER1.2	Multi-hazard risk assessment methodology for climate change impacts on European Cities	WP1	UCC	Key Exploitable Result
KER2.1	SCORE Co-Creation Toolkit	WP2	IHS, ENoLL	Key Exploitable Result
KER2.2	Pilot Operational Plan (POP): A strategic framework for the establishment of living labs.	WP2	Naider, ENoLL, IHS	Key Exploitable Result
KER2.3	SCORE Coastal City Living Lab Framework	WP2	ENoLL, IHS, Naider	Key Exploitable Result
KER2.4	Coastal City Living Lab Monitoring and Evaluation Framework	WP2	IHS	Knowledge Output
KO3.1	Procedural Guide for Identifying and Using Climate and Marine Data Services and Datasets for Baseline Characterization and Projections	WP3	LaMMA, CNR, ATU	Knowledge Output
KER3.2	Package of downscaling analysis tools, data, and user document	WP3	LaMMA, CNR, ATU	Key Exploitable Result
KO3.3	Package for the statistical analysis tools, data and user-guide for urban-scale models	WP3	LaMMA, CNR, ATU	Knowledge Output
KER3.4	Methodology and Hazard Maps for Flood Risk Mitigation Assessment	WP3	LaMMA, CNR, ATU, SAMU, UA	Key Exploitable Result
KER3.5	Package of Statistical Tools & User Document for Coastal Erosion	WP3	LaMMA, CNR, ATU, SAMU, UA	Key Exploitable Result
KO3.6	Testing Package & User Document to Improve Coastal Hazard Assessment & Long-Term Shortline Evolution	WP3	LaMMA, CNR, ATU, UCD	Knowledge Output

KO3.7	Oeiras CCLL: Constructing Severity Heat Maps to Assess Temporal Changes in Extreme Rainfall (Portugal)	CCLL	IST-ID	Knowledge Output
KER4.1	SCORE Catalogue of low-cost sensors viable for citizen science activities	WP4	UCD, ATU	Key Exploitable Result
KER4.2	SCORE Citizen Science Playbook	WP4	ZRS	Key Exploitable Result
KER4.3	SCORE Catalogue of Citizen Science Games	WP4	UCD	Key Exploitable Result
KER5.1	SCORE ICT Platform (SIP)	WP5	UniPi	Key Exploitable Result
KO5.2	SensorThings Application Programming Interface (API) and Data Harvesters	WP5	UniPi, TERO	Knowledge Output
KO5.3	Visualisation Suite for Project Data Communication and Sensor Data Collection	WP5	UniPi, TERO, UCD	Knowledge Output
KO5.4	SCORE Citizen Science Sensor Data Uploader App	WP5	UniPi, TERO	Knowledge Output
KO6.1	Exposure database for frontrunner CCLLs Vulnerability curves for frontrunner CCLLs	WP6	Red Risk	Knowledge Output
KER6.2	Risk characterisation methodology for the development of semi-quantitative, comparable indices.	WP6	Red Risk	Key Exploitable Result
KER6.3	Risk Profiles and Decision Support Tools for (cost)-Effective Risk Management, with a focus on Oarsoaldea, Massa, and Vilanova CCLLs	WP6	Red Risk	Key Exploitable Result
KER6.4	Risk Assessment Tool	WP6	Red Risk	Key Exploitable Result
KER7.1	Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, databases, and studies addressing ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) and other adaptation strategies	WP7	ENT, IHS, ENoLL, TERO	Key Exploitable Result
KER7.2	Multi-Criteria Analysis of Ecosystem-based Adaptation Strategies in Coastal City Living Labs	WP7	ENT, IHS, ENoLL, TERO	Key Exploitable Result
KER7.3	SCORE Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Catalogue: An Educational Catalogue for Coastal Climate Adaptation using Nature-Based Solutions & Ecosystem-based Adaptations	WP7	ENT, ZRS	Key Exploitable Result
KER7.4	Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping of Public Perceptions of Climate Change in Irish and Spanish Coastal City Living Labs	WP7	ATU, ENT	Key Exploitable Result
KER7.5	Cost-Benefit Analysis of Ecosystem Based Adaptation measures in SCORE's Coastal City Living Labs	WP7	ENT, Naider, ATU, ZRS, TERO	Key Exploitable Result
KER8.1	SCORE Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System	WP8	MBI	Key Exploitable Result
KER9.1	SCORE Online Learning: Massive Open Online Courses	WP9	ERINN, UCD	Key Exploitable Result

3.1. Co-Creation & Living Labs

Climate change and climate adaptation strategies have too long been addressed by top-down processes, creating out-of-touch and disconnected solutions. SCORE overcomes this challenge through systematic collaboration and co-creation with local stakeholders. The following KER's help to meet this need.

KER 2.1 - SCORE Co-Creation Toolkit

Knowledge Owners: IHS, ENoLL

Current Status: Open Access, available on IHS webpage - [Co-create your City Toolkit](#)

Description: The SCORE Co-Creation Toolkit works as a collection of tools designed to help in facilitating multi-stakeholder processes. Co-creation is understood as a process that, based on the identified needs, aims to develop results that include knowledge flows and absorptive capacities from all actors involved across the entire economic and social environment.

Its generic nature allows for adaptation to diverse settings, including for use by anyone interested in integrated urban development, such as practitioners, trainers, facilitators, students, citizens, and individuals from the public and private sectors, academia, research, and civil society. Although anyone within the quadruple helix (government, academia, industry, civil society) can facilitate using the toolkit, effective utilization does require some level of facilitation skill.

The toolkit is structured around four categories based on the target of the co-creation activity (i.e., needs assessment, visioning, etc.). These categories mirror SCORE's living lab methodology. Users can select the tool to be used among the different categories. There is a series of selection criteria which can support users to choose the most appropriate tool within each category, such as the number of persons to be involved, the time required to be allocated for facilitation, or the materials needed for it.

Those categories are:

1. **Need Identification & Analysis:** "I would like to...reveal and identify my participants' goals and needs on a specific topic/issue." In this category, a user can find tools to help explore and uncover different needs, views, values, and goals participants may have upon a specific topic/issue, helping the facilitator to understand and analyse the present and thus plan better for the future. Example: Stakeholder Journey / Activities Canvas.
2. **Ideation & Visioning:** "I would like to...stimulate my participants' creativity and innovation." In this category, a user can find tools that will help stimulate participants' creativity in attractive and interactive ways, so as to get inspiring and innovative ideas and solutions. Example: Brainstorming / the 5 Why's.
3. **Strategy Development:** "I would like to...plan and strategize with my participants for the future." In this category, a user can find tools that will help participants plan concrete actions for the future, so as to achieve the goals of a project in the long run. Example: 5 Bold steps / Scenario Planning.
4. **Prototyping & Testing:** "I would like to...test in real life and experiment with developed solutions." In this category, a user can find tools that will help in experimenting with the developed, solutions or actions, testing them in a real-life setting. Example: Blink Testing / Journey Mapping.

The individual tools are written in a highly accessible way, and have different components, including methods, templates (digital and/or printable or online), and/or suggested software. Many of the instructions suggest amendments/personalisation that the users can utilise if the conditions do not fit their needs perfectly.

Impact & Application: Overall, the toolkit serves as an easy-to-access, ready-to-utilize resource. Its availability as an open-source tool on the IHS website reduces the need for other projects or initiatives to spend resources developing similar tools from scratch. The toolkit's open-source nature reflects core values like equality, equity, social justice, and the right of people to shape their local areas. The toolkit provides a useful structure for bringing together stakeholders from the quadruple helix and can be used in various workshop or urban development contexts, even outside the specific Living Lab framework.

The potential impact of deploying the Co-Creation Toolkit is significant, with the key expected outcome being the empowerment and education of local communities. By providing a structured means to engage diverse stakeholders, the toolkit helps in developing co-created solutions that are more locally embedded.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO2.2 Pilot Operational Plan, KO 2.3 Coastal City Living Lab Framework

Priority Target User A: Public Sector Facilitators

Public sector facilitators / practitioners interested in facilitating co-creation processes with multiple stakeholders. These persons might not be explicitly trained in co-creation but could facilitate a local session with their users. Some examples could include: public authorities (i.e., municipal departments), people working in academia, researchers, civil society organisations, non-profit formal organisations (i.e., NGOs), organised communities, interest groups.

- *Role:* includes public sector facilitators and practitioners interested in facilitating multi-stakeholder co-creation processes. These individuals work within roles that involve bringing together diverse stakeholders. They can be found in public authorities (such as municipal departments), academia, research, civil society organisations, non-profit formal organisations, organised communities, and interest groups. Their primary role involves facilitating activities related to urban development, or potentially other settings.
- *Key Message:* Co-created solutions are more locally embedded. This toolkit provides a useful structure to bring together the quadruple helix (citizens, government, industry, academia).
- *Awareness:* Public sector facilitators may not necessarily be aware of the specific SCORE Co-Creation Toolkit. However, they are generally aware of the broader concept and idea of co-creation as a methodology.
- *Level of Understanding:* Individuals in this group might not have received explicit training specifically in co-creation. While they can facilitate co-creation sessions, effectively utilizing the tools does require some level of facilitation skill. The individual tools within the toolkit are designed to be highly accessible and include suggestions for adaptation, which helps usability.
- *Interest:* While there have been no direct inquiries about the toolkit on the IHS website from this group, the toolkit has been shared or mentioned in various courses, and the response from participants has consistently been very positive.
- *Other Influences (if relevant):* Decisions for Public Sector facilitators can be influenced by the need for buy-in from regional authority or higher-ups, as well as requiring approval to run co-creation sessions. These activities are often undertaken based on the priorities of the specific region or community they serve. The increasing commonality of co-creation activities is expected to make adoption more manageable.

Priority Target User B: Other EU Projects and associated academics

Other EU / National projects utilising co-creation methods. Can link closely with the other projects using the Horizon Results Booster. Examples: EmpowerUs, WaterLANDS, CLEVER cities, REWAISE, GrowGreen, Nature4cities.

- *Role:* For those facilitating a multi-stakeholder process (including any target group across the quadruple helix) or activity related primarily to urban development (and other contexts such as rural, regional, national, etc.) within an EU project.
- *Key Message:* Provides an easy to access, ready to utilise toolkit, reducing the need for other projects to develop their own from scratch.
- *Awareness:* Consortium members of these projects are aware of the idea of co-creation, but not specifically aware of this toolkit.
- *Level of Understanding:* The toolkit should be quite usable for other academics/EU projects looking to co-create in urban settings – they have experience with these methodologies and/or experience implementing stakeholder activities.
- *Interest:* If co-creation is embedded within project design, but no specific task on developing their own toolkit, this could be highly useful for the Living Labs.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 4 - Implementation

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 5 – Uptake

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

The co-creation toolkit was developed iteratively through its use by SCORE CCLLs in workshops during the project, both internally (consortium meetings, sustainability sessions in autumn 2024) and externally (workshops with stakeholders). Specifically, general online workshop sessions were used to introduce the co-creation approach and explained the different categories of tools, including examples, for all CCLLs and SCORE consortium members. Then, during each WP2 in-person workshops (in each

of the 10 CCLLs) comprising activities only with CCLL team and sessions with CCLL + local stakeholders made use of selected tools from the toolkit. After each workshop round, a survey was distributed for both CCLL team and stakeholders asking for evaluation and feedback, helping to improve the output.

External Engagement

The Co-Creation toolkit was advertised at multiple SCORE events, including ENoLL OpenLivingLab Days (2023), EU Week of Regions and Cities (2024), SCORE Ecosystem Based Adaptation Training Schools (2023-2025), Capacity Building: promoted in training courses at ENoLL (2023-2025), European Maritime Day (2025), and the SCORE Final Event at European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025).

The toolkit is currently hosted on multiple sites, including the [IHS Webpage](#) for primary access as well as the [ENoLL Knowledge Repository](#). This was chosen to increase visibility to broader stakeholders as both organisations continuously plan related workshops and therefore would have an interest in the toolkit. A [“How-To” Video](#) was created to increase usability of the site, which has accompanied the toolkit throughout knowledge transfer measures and is embedded into the IHS website on [“About co-create your city.”](#) The video has been viewed directly on YouTube over 200 times, and the webpage has been visited over 3,000 times with over 1,400 active users.

The Co-Creation Toolkit has also been shared extensively through partner networks. IHS developed a blog article on the development of the toolkit which remains on the webpage: [About co-create your city | Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies | Erasmus University Rotterdam](#). The toolkit was also shared in ENoLL’s January 2024 and IHS’s February 2024 newsletters, with a total of over 31,000 recipients. ERINN and Euronovia targeted similar EU projects (WaterLANDS, EmpowerUs, among others) to share the toolkit via personal emails.

IHS regularly utilises the toolkit with their education, advisory and research activities. Promoted in capacity building training courses both at IHS and ENoLL. Finally, a social media campaign was conducted by all WP2 partners. This includes sharing on IHS social media channels periodically – Examples: [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Instagram](#), Twitter/X; and sharing via ENoLL social media channels periodically – Examples: [LinkedIn November](#), [LinkedIn November](#), [X November](#), [X January](#), [Facebook November](#), [Facebook January](#)

In addition to these activities, the toolkit has been promoted through SCORE activities including the webinar on [Co-creation and Co-design - Examples for Nature Based Solutions in Cities](#), [the Horizon Results Platform](#), and has been featured in SCORE Online Learning’s Massive Open Online Courses - [Ecosystem Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation](#), [Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities](#), and [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE’s 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#).

Finally, the CCLLs disseminated the toolkit to their networks as a useful resource, particularly within the CCLL municipality networks, through targeted emails, social media posts, and direct conversation at events. The toolkit has since been utilised for other activities, such as in Piran where multiple tools from the toolkit were used at multiple events with citizens, and Oeiras disseminating the Toolkit through the municipality’s official website and social media channels, with the dual aim of raising public awareness and building technical capacity across departments and within the community.

Future Impact and Opportunities

ERINN will identify future calls to advertise the use of the toolkit for future EU projects and initiatives. Some calls of interest specifically mentioning co-creation are: HORIZON-CL5-2025-06-D1-01: Climate simulations data and knowledge for optimal support of IPCC Assessments and International Policy; HORIZON-CL5-2026-02-D4-04: Innovative approaches for the deployment of Positive Energy Districts; HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-CIRCBIO-15: European partnership: Forests and Forestry for a Sustainable Future; HORIZON-CL6-2025-02-COMMUNITIES-03: Innovative solutions for resilient and climate-adapted coastal communities in the Atlantic; HORIZON-CL6-2025-02-COMMUNITIES-04: Creating urban co-creation spaces for driving sustainable food system transformation. There is an active effort to align the toolkit with potential funding opportunities in other EU projects through partner networking, specifically those advertising Living Labs. Of particular interest are calls related to Mission Soil’s goal to put in place a network of 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses by 2030.

The toolkit will continue to be used by partners beyond the SCORE project. ENoLL has committed to actively incorporate the toolkit into future trainings. IHS will iteratively develop the toolkit with future stakeholder engagement activities and future projects, specifically IHS has received funding for the NURISH Horizon Europe project, which will continue working on co-creation of nature-based solutions, through which this catalogue will further be exploited.

KER 2.2 - Pilot Operational Plan (POP): A strategic framework for the establishment of Living Labs

Knowledge Owners: Naider, IHS, ENOLL, ATU

Current Status: A Template and Guidelines and Instructions document are available on SCORE's website [Tools and Platforms Page](#)

Description: A Pilot Operational Plan (POP) is a structured guide that provides the required instructions for the development and establishment of a Living Lab (LL). The POP was developed to be used by Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) within the SCORE project to respond to climate-change-related hazards through the creation of LL sites. However, as POPs exist to be strategic planning tools for any LL, this tool can be utilised to create LLs in communities of any size and with any objective.

The POP exists as both a template for future LLs to establish their activities, and as a guide for living labs as they expand and continue their development.

Approach: The POP provides a required strategic overview around the definition and implementation process of a LL through easily digestible phases (outlined below) and includes the definition of specifically tailored activities for each locality. During the characterisation of the POP, relevant variables such as: WHEN, WHY, with WHO and HOW are explained. Within each phase, there are certain activities to take place, outlined in the figure below.

Phase 1. Empathise and define: *WHY and WHO:* The principal objective of this initial phase is to analyse the context of the area which can then be used to define the structure of the LL. This structure will focus on improving the current situation of the locality. Thus, the main needs and barriers faced by stakeholders will be identified. Examples of activities that could be conducted are SWOT analysis, baseline risk analysis and mapping, or stakeholder mapping.

Activities: 1) Scoping, 2) Planning, 3) Supporting, Protecting & Rewarding.

Phase 2. Ideate and co-design: *HOW:* The main aim of the second phase is to co-create and co-design the solutions to the problems identified in Phase 1, through iterative co-creation with stakeholders. Using the *Minimal Viable Product (MVP)* approach, the initial solution is defined by main stakeholders with enough enticing characteristics to trigger the interest of early adopters, who get involved in the solution development cycle to iteratively improve the solution. Examples of activities include; co-creation activities or socio-economic assessments of Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBAs).

Activities: Launching

Phase 3. Prototype and Pilot: *HOW:* The objective of this phase is to pilot the developed solutions to test their applicability and utility in the field. The solutions that have been designed in Phase 2 following the MVP approach by the LL are placed in real-life context. The evaluation of these proposed solutions will be carried out by small-scale pilots that will determine whether the needs expressed by stakeholders to solve the identified problems in Phase 1 have been answered or to what extent. Examples of activities that could be conducted are the implementation of the solution like EBA implementation, citizen science approaches like low-cost sensor selection and deployment for climate variable monitoring for testing the solutions or other testing methods (smart technologies)

Activities: Monitoring

Phase 4. Test and Evaluate: The objective is to test the developed solutions in a larger feedback group to ensure its utility. To activate this fourth phase, the results of Phase 3 should be conducted in a small and controlled context. If the users provide positive feedback and the solutions are considered as appropriate and are then tested with larger groups, the evaluation process can be concluded. Examples of activities that could be conducted are large-scale testing, full socio-economic assessment (Cost-benefit analysis), or impact evaluation of the implemented EBAs.

Activities: Learning Lessons.

CCLL Specific Outputs: Each SCORE CCLL utilised the POP to create and implement their CCLL throughout the project. These POP plans are confidential and available to each CCLL team to use beyond the project to continue implementation.

Impact & Application: To effectively implement and establish the POP within a living lab, it would require approximately 3 facilitators. It can be used by anyone interested in implementing a Living Lab, this would likely be those in the public sector or academia. For successful participation, representatives from all sectors of the quadruplex helix (public sector, private sector, academia and citizens) must be engaged in this process. The implementation of the POP thereby promotes the collaboration between all stakeholders to find solutions. The POP is designed so it can facilitate the development and establishment of a Living Lab, facilitating co-creation and co-design. As such, they can impact any kind of decision-making process, allowing for a solution that is approved by different experts and can be used by communities to address a variety of issues relevant to a local area. The methodology of the POP can be given to institutions interested in creating LLs to help facilitate this process. Additionally, with the rise of LLs in European projects, this is a relevant, user-friendly and novel tool that to support the strategic development of LLs.

Linked Knowledge Outputs:

To integrate monitoring and evaluation alongside the implementation of the POP, a user can engage also with KO2.4 – the Monitoring and Evaluation Framework.

Priority Target User A: Other EU Projects & associated academics

Other EU / National projects utilising Living Labs (and related concepts) with their project methodology.

- **Role:** Facilitation of local decision-making and collaborative joint processes within a community through the creation of a dynamic innovation centre in the form of a Living Lab.
- **Key Message:** The POP is designed so it can facilitate the development and establishment of a Living Lab, facilitating co-creation and co-design. The POP can support the decision-making process, allowing for solutions and decisions to be made that are supported by different stakeholders and can be used by communities to address a variety of issues relevant to a local area.
- **Awareness:** Aware of the idea of a Living Lab, but not necessarily an expert in all the steps necessary to create one. These users are likely aware that Living Labs are a novel intermediary for engaging with communities across the quadruple helix, and need support in how to create and implement a LL.
- **Level of Understanding:** The POP is relatively usable for other academics/EU projects looking to create Living Labs. The target user would benefit by having some basic understanding of what a living lab is and co-creation tools. Academics and associated project implementers are likely familiar with the terminology and general methodology present in the POP if this is part of their project methodology.
- **Interest:** There is a significant interest in developing Living Labs in EU projects, and a consistent increase in co-created outputs and activities, so the POP will likely be of interest to these target users. However, it is possible that they would be unaware that such frameworks exist as it is a novel output.

Priority Target User B: Public Sector Facilitators

Public sector practitioners are interested in the creation of a living lab as a medium to solve societal challenges and drive community engagement/collaboration. Examples: Public authorities (i.e., municipal departments), people working in academia, researchers, civil society organisations, non-profit formal organisations (i.e., NGOs), organised communities, and interest groups.

- **Role:** Likely these users will be working within a regional/municipal government, looking to address societal challenges and drive community engagement.
- **Key Message:** Public authorities need buy-in from multiple stakeholder groups to effectively address societal/wicked challenges. A Living Lab is a great medium to assess and address these challenges, and the POP allows for an easy-to-use strategy to create a Living Lab.
- **Awareness:** Likely this target user would have some background knowledge of co-creation or similar methodologies, however, the concept of a living lab itself may be unknown to them. It will be important for them to be aware of what a living lab is.

- *Level of Understanding:* Anyone falling within the quadruple helix can be an implementer/facilitator, with the exception of an individual citizen. The POP is written in a highly accessible way and should be able to be followed by this target user group.
- *Interest:* Based on conversations with these target users at ENoLL's OpenLivingLab Days, it was clear that there is a need to support EU-funded projects utilising living labs and providing necessary materials to do the implementation effectively and efficiently. As such, there is likely a large amount of interest in the POP for this target group to fill this gap.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 2 – Discovery

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 3 – Engagement

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

The CCLLs undertook various activities following this framework as the POP served as the guidelines for their implementation as a CCLL. During the first year of the project, each CCLL established and defined their individual POPs, which included specific phases and activities tailored to each city's context. This process involved establishing the CCLL methodology, assessing the cities' contexts through questionnaires, and conducting workshops.

In these workshops, guided by the POP framework, CCLL teams engaged in activities primarily related to Phase 1: Empathise & Define. These activities included:

- Analysing the local context to define the LL structure.
- Identifying main needs and barriers faced by stakeholders.
- Brainstorming and selecting specific problems to address.
- Defining their CCLL's vision and strategic goals.
- Identifying and mapping relevant stakeholders.
- Identifying potential barriers.

The completed POPs for each CCLL were produced and have been used by the CCLLs throughout the SCORE project as living documents. Fronrunner CCLLs (Oarsoaldea, Vilanova, Piran, Sligo) began implementing their plans in Phase 1 and progressed through co-creation and solution selection in Phases 2 and 3. Fellow CCLLs (Benidorm, Dublin, Gdansk, Massa, Oeiras) started their planning six months later, allowing them to benefit from the experiences of the Fronrunners. The learning process included four steps which facilitated knowledge exchange and increased impact:

1. Learning from Fronrunners – Fellows drew on the progress and lessons learned by the Fronrunners.
2. Learning among Fellows – Fellows shared experiences and challenges with each other as they moved through similar stages.
3. Joint Learning – Fronrunners and Fellows exchanged results and insights during the later stages of implementation.
4. Finalising Learning – All CCLLs consolidated the lessons learned and addressed any outstanding issues, particularly to support Fellows whose results were less advanced.

This staged and collaborative approach ensured effective knowledge transfer, mutual learning, and adaptive implementation across all CCLLs.

External Engagement

The [POP template](#) was developed with a sample POP for "Model City" to allow for future Living Labs to adapt the template to their own context, with examples. An accompanying [Instructions and Guidelines](#) document for how to utilise the POP was developed to walk a user through the template in an intuitive, phase-based manner. Finally, a ["How-To" Video](#) was created to increase usability of the POP, which has accompanied the template and guidance document throughout knowledge transfer measures.

The POP materials were disseminated by project partners at multiple events including ENoLL OpenLivingLab Days (2023), European Maritime Day (2025), and the SCORE Final Event at European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025).

The POP has been submitted to the [Horizon Results Platform](#). Stakeholder engagement workshops being facilitated by the POP are detailed in CCLL GeoStories, which give CCLL stakeholders insights into how the POP was implemented in their own contexts. Finally, the POP is detailed in the SCORE Online learning Massive Open Online Course - [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#). Here, the materials are described for future CCLLs interested in implementing their own Living Labs through a POP framework.

Future Impact and Opportunities

In addition to being hosted on the SCORE Tools and Platforms page, the POP will be linked on IHS, Naider, and ENoLL sites within 2025. The POP will be hosted on ENoLL's knowledge repository, and the resources will remain open access for the public as soon as the knowledge repository is fully developed by the ENoLL team and live on their website. Additionally, the POP will be included in ENoLL Living Lab Capacity Building courses as a useful tool for creating and implementing Living Labs, specifically within coastal contexts. Through these key actions, the POP will be shared periodically with members and trainees, maximising the exposure of the POP to large audiences interested specifically in creating Living Labs. Further, the POP will be featured in both ENoLL, Naider, and IHS newsletters within 2025.

CCLL Core Team members will still have access to their specific POP following the conclusion of SCORE, to continue to revisit their visions and plans as they continue implementing their CCLLs. Elements of the POP, such as the vision statement and associated workshop activities, are featured in the [CCLL GeoStories](#), allowing stakeholders to have access to elements of this process beyond the project's conclusion.

KER 2.3 – Coastal City Living Lab Framework

Knowledge Owners: ENoLL, IHS and Naider

Current Status: Open Access, available primarily in LLIP videos ([link](#)), MOOC: [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#), and also integrated into all CCLL activities

Description: A Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL) is a novel innovation intermediary which orchestrates an ecosystem of actors in a specific region to tackle specific climate change related challenges such as sea level rise, coastal erosion, and extreme events. CCLLs are solving wicked problems that are complex, specific and have many different causes. They address problems related to climate change, sustainability, societal behaviour, economic impact, and others. CCLLs are based on multi-stakeholder collaboration to address the identified problems by providing a set of human-centric tools and methodologies, which are crucial for developing solutions within a tailored approach city by city and their specific context.

Similar to other Living Labs, CCLLs are characterised by their emphasis on co-creation, experimentation, and multi-stakeholder engagement. CCLLs actively involve users, including citizens and local communities, but work specifically in the development and testing of strategies to enhance climate resilience in the face of water and climate-related hazards. SCORE's CCLLs use a Pilot Operation Plan as their strategic guide to develop and implement their Living Labs (KO2.2).

The CCLL methodology provides coastal cities with a framework that could be defined as a structured approach in setting up and running the SCORE Living Labs to build climate resilience, while taking first steps for the establishment and ensuring the sustainability of the Living Labs beyond the scope of the SCORE project. The CCLL methodology is based upon the Living Lab Integrative Process (LLIP), including eight phases (from the problem definition until the deployment space).

Novelty: The Living Lab Integrative Process (LLIP) framework (Figure below) is a validated methodology utilised by the European Network of Living Labs, to design and implement Living Labs. The LLIP process is broken down into three phases, the Problem Space, the Solution Space and the Deployment Space. The Problem Space focuses on understanding the challenge(s) faced by the Living Lab community and identifying the specific stakeholders needed to tackle said challenge. The Solution Space works on the co-development and testing of solutions. The final phase, the Deployment Space, focuses on the implementation and scaling up of the solutions. The CCLL Framework uses the LLIP as the guiding principle and has a focus on coastal cities and their challenges. The developed framework can be replicated in other scenarios and by Living Labs in any domain.

With the aim of having an integrative process for the SCORE project, the LLIP as developed by Mastelic (2019) was adapted and two more steps were added at the end of the process, to include the implementation and scale-up phase. In detail, the CCLL approach is based on the design thinking methodology and generates human-centric innovations within the coastal city context. It consists of eight steps, structuring the process from the problem space towards the deployment space.

Key elements of a CCLL:

Building Blocks: A CCLL is built on six essential building blocks that drive collaboration, innovation, and real-world impact:

1. **Orchestration:** Acts as a connector within a community, partnering with relevant stakeholders.
2. **Co-creation:** Innovations are co-developed with all stakeholders, increasing adoption.
3. **Active user involvement:** Stakeholders are engaged throughout the innovation lifecycle, ensuring feedback is integrated.
4. **Multi-stakeholder participation:** Involves actors from government, academia, industry, and civil society (Quadruple Helix).
5. **Real-life setting:** Innovations are tested in users' actual environments, not in isolated labs.
6. **Multi-method approach:** Activities are problem-driven, using methods tailored to each challenge and involving relevant stakeholders.

Core Team: A strong Core Team ensures effective management and impact. Living Labs require structured coordination to balance diverse interests and deliver results. Five internal roles include:

- **Living Lab Manager:** Leads operations and ensures long-term sustainability through strategic project development.
- **Panel Manager:** Connects internal and external stakeholders, coordinating communication and engagement.
- **Project Manager:** Oversees planning and execution of projects.
- **Human Interaction Specialist:** Designs and analyses user research methods.
- **Pilot Manager:** Manages technical implementation and scaling of innovations.

Quadruple Helix: Living Labs unite four key groups—academia, citizens, government, and industry—to co-create solutions:

- **Academia:** Offers research expertise and evidence-based methods.
- **Citizens:** Bring lived experience and ensure solutions are practical and relevant.
- **Government:** Provides policy support and aligns projects with strategic goals.
- **Industry:** Contributes technology, funding, and market insight to help scale solutions.

Impact & Application: The CCLL Framework offers novel guidance for Living Labs that can be applied by various stakeholders to enhance climate resilience in coastal cities. Its human-centric, multi-stakeholder approach ensures that solutions are tailored to local conditions, which can lead to more effective and sustainable outcomes. The framework's potential impact includes the development of innovative climate adaptation strategies, stronger collaboration between sectors, and the long-term sustainability of resilience initiatives.

The target users of this framework would be the CCLL Core Teams intending on creating and implementing a CCLL. In order to effectively implement and establish the CCLL, it would require approximately 3 facilitators to fulfil the necessary roles (i.e., CCLL manager, panel manager, project manager, pilot manager, human interaction specialist) to successfully implement. This would most likely be led by those in the public sector, other EU-projects or academia.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KER2.2 Pilot Operational Plan, KO2.4 SCORE CCLL Monitoring and Evaluation Framework.

Priority Target User A: Other EU Projects and associated academics working in coastal contexts

Other EU / National projects utilising Living Labs (and related concepts) with their project methodology.

- **Role:** Facilitation of local decision-making and collaborative joint processes within a community through the creation of a dynamic innovation centre in the form of a Living Lab.

- **Key Message:** The CCLL Framework offers novel guidance for Living Labs that can be applied to enhance climate resilience in coastal cities. Its human-centric, multi-stakeholder approach ensures that solutions are tailored to local conditions, which can lead to more effective and sustainable outcomes. The framework's potential impact includes the development of innovative climate adaptation strategies, stronger collaboration between sectors, and the long-term sustainability of resilience initiatives.
- **Awareness:** Aware of the idea of a Living Lab, but not necessarily an expert in all the steps necessary to create one.
- **Level of Understanding:** While it assumes a basic understanding of Living Lab principles, the framework builds on these by applying them specifically to climate resilience in coastal cities. Target users, primarily academics and project implementers, are likely already familiar with some of the terminology and methodologies it includes, especially if Living Labs form part of their project approach. A key knowledge transfer goal is to ensure the framework is straightforward and accessible for users to learn and apply.
- **Interest:** There is a significant interest in developing Living Labs in EU projects, and a consistent increase in co-created outputs and activities, so the CCLL framework will likely be of interest to these target users. However, it is possible that they would be unaware that such frameworks exist as a CCLL specifically is a novel concept.

Priority Target User B: Public Sector Facilitators, working in coastal contexts

Public sector practitioners that are interested in the creation of a Living Lab as a medium to solve societal challenges and drive community engagement/collaboration, specifically within coastal contexts and on climate-related challenges. Examples: Public authorities (i.e., municipal departments), people working in academia, researchers, civil society organisations, non-profit formal organisations (i.e., NGOs), organised communities, and interest groups. Particularly those involved in the SCORE project.

- **Role:** Likely these users will be working within a regional/municipal government, looking to address societal challenges and drive community engagement in a sustainable way.
- **Key Message:** Public authorities need buy-in from multiple stakeholder groups to effectively address societal/wicked challenges. A Living Lab is a great medium to assess and address these challenges, and the CCLL Framework allows for a strategy to create a Living Lab for addressing climate related challenges in a coastal area.
- **Awareness:** Likely this target user would have some background knowledge of co-creation or similar methodologies; however, the concept of a Living Lab itself may be unknown to them. It will be important for them to be aware of what a living lab is in order for them to understand the necessity for a Coastal City Living Lab for their context.
- **Level of Understanding:** Anyone falling within the quadruple helix can be an implementer/facilitator of the CCLL framework, except for an individual citizen. The MOOC will be developed in a way that any public sector facilitator could utilise the framework to begin creating and implementing their own CCLL.
- **Interest:** There is a need and an interest from the public sector to support EU-funded projects utilising Living Labs and providing necessary materials to do the implementation effectively and efficiently.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 1 – Conception

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 2 – Discovery

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

The CCLL Framework underpinned all work done in SCORE as it formed the basis for the establishment and implementation of each of the CCLLs. The framework's application during the workshops held by the CCLLs served as the baseline for most activities deployed by the SCORE project. The framework outlines consecutive phases for building a CCLL over time: (1) Empathize and define, (2) Ideate and co-design, (3) Prototype and pilot, and (4) Test and evaluate. Each phase includes specific activities linked to various WPs throughout the project.

- Phase 1 (Empathize & Define) activities included scoping (identifying problems, stakeholders), planning (defining structure, vision), and supporting/protecting/rewarding (administrative, legal, communication). Examples of activities included workshops to define the vision and structure of the CCLL, gathering user stories and specifications (WP8), collecting data on past climate events (WP1), gathering climate change perception (WP4), defining the CCLL strategy

and helpdesk (WP2), and reviewing legal requirements (WP2). This phase addressed the questions of WHEN, WHY, WHO and HOW to set up a CCLL.

- Phase 2 (Ideate & Co-design) activities focused on launching the process to ideate and co-design solutions for identified climate problems. Activities included workshops to co-create and co-design Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) solutions (WP2, WP7), conducting socio-economic assessments of proposed EBAs (WP7), and developing financial resilience strategies (WP6). This phase addressed the question of HOW the CCLL should address problems to adapt to climate change.
- Phase 3 (Prototype & Pilot) activities involved monitoring and implementing ideated solutions. Activities included prototyping and testing designed solutions or technology on a small scale to monitor locations, understanding and evaluating CCLL performance, identifying weak areas, analysing stakeholder participation, and monitoring goals. WP activities included introducing/testing climate sensors (WP4) and conducting the first interaction with the Digital Twin (WP8).
- Phase 4 (Test & Evaluate) activities focused on learning lessons, involving the final testing and evaluation of solutions at a larger scale. Activities included gathering useful outcomes, identifying barriers, evaluating the entire process (effort vs resources), and collecting stakeholder feedback. WP activities included running the overall evaluation (WP2), disseminating past events maps (WP1), running/participating in training sessions (WP3), evaluating citizen science platform performance/engagement (WP4), sharing guidelines for coastal risk management (WP6), sharing success stories (WP7), and assessing Digital Twin effectiveness (WP8). This phase was linked strongly with the KO2.4 – SCORE CCLL Monitoring and Evaluation Framework and D2.4 – Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE’s 10 Coastal City Living Labs.

Overall, the utilisation of the framework as the basis for these activities formed the major building block of the SCORE project. In turn, this validated the framework as an effective Living Lab methodology, and thereby increased the impact of its use.

External Engagement

The key output for dissemination was the [Living Lab Integrative Framework Video Series](#). These have been shared in a social media campaign via SCORE and ENOLL social media networks and are available on the SCORE YouTube channel. These videos have been incorporated into a free training in the ENOLL Living Labbers Academy ([link](#)), and the Framework and LLIP videos form the basis for [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE’s 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#), where the framework is detailed for future CCLLs to better understand best practices.

The value of utilising a Coastal City Living Lab has been shared at numerous high-impact conferences and events, including ENOLL OpenLivingLab Days (2023), EU Week of Regions and Cities (2024), SCORE Ecosystem Based Adaptation Training Schools (2023–2025), Capacity Building: promoted in training courses at ENOLL (2023–2025), European Maritime Day (2025), and SCORE Final Event at European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025).

The CCLL framework has been recommended to policymakers in the following materials:

- D7.5 Policy Guidelines ([link](#)) strongly emphasises the recommendation of using a CCLL as an intermediary to strengthen resilience against climate-related changes to coastal areas
- ADAPT4COAST Integrated strategies for climate resilience in EU Coastal Cities ([link](#))
- Building Climate Resilience in Sligo County Through Ecosystem-based Adaptation, Smart Technologies, and Coastal City Living Lab ([link](#))

The Coastal City Living Lab framework has been published in a number of high-impact articles, including the following:

- Quadros Aniche, L., Edelenbos, J., Gianoli, A., Enseñado, E. M., Makousiari, E., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., Caruso, C. and Zalokar, S. (2024). Boosting co-creation of Nature-based Solutions within Living Labs: Interrelating enablers using interpretive structural modelling, *Environmental Science and Policy*, 161, 103873, (First online 30 August 2024) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103873>
- Quadros Aniche, L., Edelenbos, J., Gianoli, A., Caruso, R., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., Wissink-Nercua, C. P., Undabeitia, A., Enseñado, E. M. and Gharbia, S. (2024). Contextualizing and generalizing drivers and barriers of urban Living Labs for climate resilience. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 34(5), 490–523, (First online 17 January 2024) <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.2097>

- Tiwari A, Rodrigues LC, Lucy FE, Gharbia S. (2022) Building Climate Resilience in Coastal City Living Labs Using Ecosystem-Based Adaptation: A Systematic Review. Sustainability, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141710863>
- Roberta Paranunzio, Iulia Anton, Elisa Adirosi, Tasneem Ahmed, Luca Baldini, Carlo Brandini, Filippo Giannetti, Cécil Meulenbergh, Alberto Ortolani, Francesco Pilla, Gregorio Iglesias, Salem Gharbia. (2024). A New Approach Towards a User-driven Coastal Climate Service to Enhance Climate Resilience in European Cities'. Sustainability, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16010335>

Finally, the CCLL Framework is hosted on the [Horizon Results Platform](#) and featured in webinar on Co-Creation: [Co-creation and Co-design - Examples for Nature Based Solutions in Cities](#). It also is detailed in SCORE Online Learning's Massive Open Online Courses of [Ecosystem Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation](#), [Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities](#), and [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#).

Future Impact and Opportunities

Accessible for future CCLLs: The framework itself and related materials (POP template, Co-creation Toolkit) will be promoted to other CCLLs beyond the SCORE project. The framework's application in SCORE allowed for the generation of lessons learned that are shared in "D2.4 Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs" and its associated MOOC and videos, all of which will be available beyond the duration of SCORE.

Further, it is the recommendation that ENOLL continues to share this framework via their knowledge repository and through capacity building courses for other LLs beyond the SCORE project. This provides a continued opportunity for other LLs to learn from the experiences of the SCORE CCLLs. Using results as best practice examples in future EU projects is an opportunity: for example, the CCLL methodology was brought to a newly created CCLL in Turkey (SINEP CCLL), showing the extended impact of this framework beyond SCORE.

Sustainable CCLLs: Multiple SCORE CCLLs have committed to continuing to work as a CCLL beyond the SCORE project and have already received funding to continue activities, including Gdansk and Sligo. Several CCLLs expressed ambitions to scale up the outcomes derived from using the framework, such as replicating results in neighbouring territories (Vilanova), exporting concepts to other coastal cities (Piran), or using developed methods for habitat protection elsewhere (Sligo). Through Sustainability Sessions organised in Autumn 2024, CCLLs were given training and support on how to extend their entities beyond the SCORE project.

Integrated into future EU initiatives: Accessing grants, and government funding programmes is seen as a potential financial source, and it is recommended to utilise the CCLL framework as an element of EU project bids as they have shown to be effective innovation intermediaries through SCORE. There is rising environmental and climatic concern and strong commitment from the EU to invest and support climate resilience for coastal cities, and the use of a CCLL framework aligns strongly with these priorities. The framework's focus on climate change adaptation, resilience, Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)/EBAs, and smart technologies aligns with potential future calls related to these themes, as well as calls specifically mentioning Living Labs will be targeted, including *HORIZON-CL6-2025-02-FARM2FORK-01: Additional activities for the European partnership on accelerating farming systems transition -agroecology living labs and research infrastructures* and *HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-BIODIV-01-two stage: Living labs co-creating innovative solutions for forests and freshwater ecosystems restoration*. Additionally, a Co-Creation workshop highlighting the benefits of using Living Labs is planned to take place in Ireland in September 2025 to showcase the results of SCORE alongside other EU projects (EmpowerUs, WaterLANDS, Prep4BLUE, etc.) to Irish policymakers and public sector actors to increase interest.

Policy: It is the recommendation of the Innovation Board that all CCLLs prepare a local-level policy brief to solidify their findings as CCLLs to policymakers. The basis for this is to recommend that local governments are encouraged to formally embed the CCLL model within their urban planning and climate adaptation strategies. It is also recommended through D7.5 Policy Recommendations that the EU Adaptation Strategy and related directives and Horizon Europe Missions should explicitly recognize Living Labs as formal innovation ecosystems. This policy brief also suggests that the EU should include CCLLs as a pillar of EU-funded programs to enhance citizen engagement in climate policy development and use the CCLL Lessons Learned materials to inform EU directives on participatory governance. It is the expectation that through these recommendations the CCLL Framework will extend its impact from the 10 SCORE CCLLs into new CCLLs across Europe in a more formalised way beyond the project to further impact policy.

Knowledge Owners: ZRS, UCD **Current Status:** To be published in July 2025 on SCORE website and elements are currently available in the course [What are Nature-Based Solutions?](#)

Description: The Citizen Science Playbook is a guiding tool on how to establish a climate adaptive (Coastal City) Living Lab, and how to engage with participants of the Living Lab in co-creative activities centred around an Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) approach and low-cost, do-it-yourself sensors. The Citizen Science Playbook provides general knowledge on all the basic aspects of addressing water and climate-related hazards to enhance coastal city climate resilience. This Playbook is useful to further enhance knowledge and learning materials for both moderators and participants of climate adaptation Living Labs. Additionally, the engagement framework is general enough to be of interest to general citizen science programmes or anyone interested in upskilling on basic knowledge of climate adaptation.

The Playbook contains a detailed engagement strategy and several brief learning modules to become climate literate. Further, it highlights useful tools and examples of the SCORE project's work in action, including: a compilation of the social innovation approaches, deliverables, videos, MOOCs and additional catalogues and tools developed throughout the SCORE project, each with a brief description and links to the available (publicly accessible) deliverables, additional literature, and an extensive 'climate action' glossary.

An overview of the Playbook:

1. Introduction
2. SCORE's CCLL climate adaptation through co-warning, co-monitoring and EBA approach
3. Engagement strategy methodology
4. Description of engagement strategy embedded in SCORE activities
5. Key considerations and purpose for engagement
6. The Why, Who, What, Where, and When of the engagement strategy
7. Introduction to the learning modules
8. Learning modules
9. SCORE outcomes and tools
10. SCORE online content

Impact & Application: The Citizen Science Playbook can be used as an introduction to climate adaptive co-creation and ecosystem-based adaptation approaches. As it provides definitions, glossary and links to various educational/awareness tools, it is a useful guide for those either interested in getting involved in citizen science activities or conducting them through an organisation or a project. Its use could improve citizen science programmes and therefore increase involvement of citizens in useful science projects, specifically related to climate resilience and monitoring.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO9.1 Massive Open Online Courses

Priority Target User A: Citizen science practitioners, including academics, and other EU-funded projects with citizen science and climate-adaptive living lab components.

Actors interested in conducting citizen science activities or projects: scientists and authorities, Living Lab facilitators, etc.

- **Role:** To use the listed catalogues and tools to make informed decisions on the best citizen science tools and activities for climate resilience projects, and gain knowledge/examples on past usage to educate future users/citizens.
- **Key Message:** The Citizen Science Playbook can be used as an introduction to climate adaptive co-creation and ecosystem-based adaptation approaches and acts as a useful guide for a practitioner conducting them through an organisation or a project.
- **Awareness:** This playbook targets users who would be very aware of citizen science activities but not of this particular playbook or of all the SCORE activities and tools suggested.

- *Level of Understanding:* The playbook targets users who likely has strong expertise in citizen science activities but may need additional ideas for how different tools can be utilised. The Playbook is easy to read and does not require training to use.
- *Interest:* Likely actively seeking information on citizen science and living lab programmes and would be interested in determining the best stakeholder engagement and interaction tools with options for their specific means or projects.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 2 – Discovery

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 3 – Engagement

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

Both the Engagement Strategy and Learning Modules and Glossary presented in this the Citizen Science Playbook were developed, finalised and approved November 2021 and early 2022 respectively to include principal knowledge needed to understand the objectives of SCORE from both climate change and social engagement perspectives. Such information was used to structure the engagement strategy followed by CCLL partners throughout SCORE. Then later in 2023, ERINN utilised the learning module content to develop the MOOCs (Task 9.6.3) for use by CCLLs during citizen science activities ongoing through the project.

External Engagement

The Citizen Science Playbook's learning modules have formed the basis for the course [What are Nature-Based Solutions?](#) and also featured in a few lessons in the course [Ecosystem Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation](#). The first course was translated into [Spanish](#) and [Catalan](#), increasing its usability to wider audiences. The SCORE MOOCs have been used by CCLLs before and during citizen science activities to provide stakeholders with introductory material to the SCORE project and its principles. As such, the playbook materials have been widely used by the CCLLs and distributed to their stakeholder networks through email, GeoStories, and in-person activities.

These MOOCs were also shared through a social media campaign targeting specific LinkedIn community groups including the Nature-Based Solutions community group. These were very successful, with engagement with target audiences reaching over 750 likes, 19 comments and 155 reposts. At present, the MOOCs have over 1,200 enrolments.

Future Impact and Opportunities

Upon finalisation in July 2025, the Citizen Science Playbook will be made available for download on the SCORE website. The Playbook's content will be available as an overview PDF and guideline for LLs, so it could be in printed form or on desktop machines for target users such as LL moderators, teachers, etc. ZRS Koper has also contracted translations of the Citizen Science Playbook in Slovenian for providing more optimal use to a wider public (schools, teachers, students, municipalities, etc.) in Slovenia. Finally, the Citizen Science Playbook will be featured on the Horizon Results Platform.

The Citizen Science Playbook is a good starting point for other projects to utilise when beginning citizen science activities as well as for initializing a living lab with a climate-adaptive focus. Future calls will be identified that are relevant to this resource and the playbook will be advertised on these via the Funding and Tenders partner search query. Some pre-identified call opportunities include:

- HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-BIODIV-02: Strengthening the capacity of citizen science in biodiversity observation
- HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-ZEROPOLLUTION-03: Environmental biotechnology applications in service of remediation of polluted ecosystems
- HORIZON-CL6-2025-03-GOVERNANCE-08: Effective environmental observing systems and associated governance

As the Citizen Science Playbook in full will be released in July 2025, a social media campaign is recommended to promote the resource on ZRS pages, Piran CCLL GeoStory, as well as by distribution through the wider SCORE consortium.

KER 4.3 - SCORE Game-Based Approaches to Enhance Community Participation in Spatial Decisions

Knowledge Owners: UCD

Current Status: The GeoDesign Game can be played here ([link](#)) and is available as Serious Games for Participatory Planning MOOC ([link](#)) and instructions are accessible through the GeoDesign Game instructions on the SCORE website ([link](#))

Description: This KO explores how game-based participatory approaches can enhance community engagement in spatial decision-making, focusing on the GeoDesign Game and EBACraft, a custom game adaptation in Minecraft. Both were tested by the SCORE CCLLs during SCORE Climate Adaptation training schools (EBA Craft in the first and second editions of the event and the GeoDesign Game in the third edition) to help communities co-create Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) solutions.

The two games are:

- **The GeoDesign Game** allows participants to propose, discuss, and vote on EBA strategies across multiple rounds, employing a simple and interactive online platform. It encourages structured collaboration between local authorities, experts, and residents, fostering inclusive decision-making. The gameplay is easy to follow and uses OpenStreetMap (OSM) and open source Leaflet maps as a base for players place EBAs within a defined area. In later rounds, they engage in discussions and vote on these solutions, refining the best strategies for implementation.
- **EBACraft** leverages the Minecraft immersive sandbox environment and geospatial data (e.g., OSM) to engage youth and non-experts in designing and visualising local planning solutions. This takes place in a custom environment inside of Minecraft and the players build is based on the objectives briefed by the facilitators. The players have the flexibility of designing, creating and crafting their environment within the guidelines provided by the facilitator. Unlike the GeoDesign Game, the EBACraft does not have an online platform: the game needs to be downloaded from the repository [here](#) and then can be adapted to the necessary context to play the EBACraft game - instructions are provided on how to do this in the guide.

Novelty: These approaches improve upon traditional spatial planning by gamifying decision-making, making it more accessible, interactive, and engaging. Unlike standard GIS-based tools, which often require expert knowledge, both games simplify complex data, allowing non-specialists to contribute meaningfully. By combining Serious Gaming and GeoDesign framework, these game-based approaches introduce an innovative, hybrid model that integrates real geospatial data with collaborative gameplay, offering a structured yet creative way to develop sustainable adaptation strategies.

Iteration: The GeoDesign Game and EBACraft have been refined based on participant feedback to ensure ease of use for diverse stakeholders, including non-experts. The games used iterative game design approach, where game is tested several times and improved based on user feedback. This feedback was achieved through the questionnaires that were answered by the players at the end of the sessions. These questionnaires helped to finetune the games further to make them more functional and interactive. As part of the EBA Training Schools, the SCORE CCLLs validated these tools in real-world settings, demonstrating their potential for community-driven spatial planning. Participants successfully used the games to co-create feasible adaptation solutions, strengthening dialogue among stakeholders across diverse age demographics.

However, challenges remain, including scalability and technical barriers for those unfamiliar with basic digital tools. Challenges such as lack of experience in interacting with ICT tools were highlighted by users in the GeoDesign Game, where it is recommended that facilitators familiarize themselves with the platform in advance. For Minecraft-based games, the primary barriers include accessibility, usability (keyboard, mouse handling), and hardware availability. These have been mitigated by setting up pre-configured game environments and providing necessary equipment and licenses when possible.

A common challenge across both platforms is localisation and language adaptation particularly with Minecraft, which requires tailoring content to different regional contexts. The MOOC directly address these issues, offering adaptable strategies to overcome contextual and technical barriers across diverse settings. The scalability of the game largely depends on the expertise of the facilitator. To strengthen their role and ensure effective facilitation, the MOOC that introduces the core framework of the games and prepares facilitators to lead productive sessions. Despite these challenges, the KO marks a significant step forward,

proving that interactive, game-based approaches can bridge knowledge gaps, foster collaboration, and support more inclusive, data-driven urban and environmental planning.

Game Outputs: The GeoDesign Game and EBACraft generate a range of outputs that help assess their impact on community engagement, spatial decision-making, and EBA planning. These outputs include game-generated data, participant feedback, and visual records of planning decisions, which provide insights into how different stakeholder groups interact with the tools and contribute to urban and environmental planning.

Impact & Application: Serious games as decision making tools offer practical applications for various end users, enabling more inclusive, data-driven, and collaborative spatial planning. Their successful adoption can lead to improved community participation, better-informed decision-making, and enhanced climate resilience strategies across multiple sectors.

Local & Regional Government Bodies: Municipalities, urban planners, and environmental departments can use these tools to engage communities in co-creating urban and environmental solutions, ensuring that EBA strategies align with local needs. The GeoDesign Game can serve as a negotiation and consensus-building tool, helping officials balance competing interests when implementing green infrastructure, flood management, or urban expansion projects. EBACraft is particularly useful for engaging younger populations, can be incorporated into public participation programs to visualise proposed urban changes. This can ultimately result in increased civic engagement, improved alignment of adaptation strategies with community priorities, and more sustainable urban planning processes.

Academic & Research Institutions: Researchers in urban planning, geography, and environmental science can apply these tools to study spatial decision-making, participatory planning, and digital GeoDesign framework, Universities can use the GeoDesign Game in coursework to train students in real-world planning challenges, while the EBACraft can serve as an educational platform for digital geospatial mapping and learning. These tools also provide structured data through debriefing recordings and CSV files, allowing researchers to analyse patterns in community decision-making and adaptation strategies. This can lead to a greater integration of participatory GeoDesign methods into research and education, fostering innovation in climate adaptation and urban resilience studies.

Community & Civil Society Organizations: Local community groups and NGOs can use these games to facilitate citizen-led spatial planning, empowering residents to advocate for green spaces, climate resilience measures, and sustainable land use. The GeoDesign Game enables structured discussion and co-design of adaptation strategies, while EBACraft provides a visual and interactive approach to engaging community members in reimagining their local environments. Ultimately, this allows for more inclusive community planning, strengthened advocacy for climate adaptation, and better integration of citizen-driven ideas into municipal strategies.

International & European Networks: Organizations such as UN-Habitat, ICLEI, and EU urban development initiatives can apply these tools to scale up participatory urban planning efforts, particularly in climate-vulnerable regions. The GeoDesign Game's structured decision-making process can be replicated across different cities, while Minecraft's immersive design environment can be used for youth engagement in urban development programs, allowing for greater global adoption of participatory GeoDesign, leading to data-driven, community-led policy recommendations for urban adaptation.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KER7.3 SCORE Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Catalogue, KER 9.1 SCORE Online Learning: Massive Open Online Courses

Priority Target User A: Academics, and other EU-funded projects engaging with citizens

Academics and practitioners working within the environmental research space, specifically those focusing on conducting citizen science activities or environmental or planning projects.

- **Role:** To use the games to gain insights from the public to make informed decisions on the best planning solutions for climate resilience projects. The aim is to empower researchers to utilise these tools with local authorities, educators, and communities for collaborative decision-making, bridging the gap between technical experts and the public.

- *Key Message:* These games can be used as an introduction to climate adaptive co-creation and ecosystem-based adaptation approaches to engage effectively across the quadruple helix. Its use could improve citizen science programmes and therefore increase involvement of citizens in useful science projects.
- *Awareness:* This target user would be very aware of the value of stakeholder engagement for spatial planning, but not necessarily aware of the potential of participatory games as an approach to engage with communities.
- *Level of Understanding:* This target user likely has strong expertise in citizen science activities but may need additional ideas for how different tools can be utilised. In academic and research institutions, these tools can support GeoDesign and urban planning researchers in studying participatory spatial decision-making and digital planning methods. Environmental scientists and climate researchers can explore how digital platforms facilitate community-led climate adaptation, while educators in geography, architecture, and GIS can use them to teach spatial planning, geospatial data analysis, and sustainable design in an interactive way.
- *Interest:* These target users are likely actively seeking insights from stakeholders would be interested in determining the best options for their specific means or projects. These gaming approaches improve upon traditional spatial planning by gamifying decision-making, making it more accessible, interactive, and engaging. Unlike standard GIS-based tools, which often require expert knowledge, both games simplify complex data, allowing non-specialists to contribute meaningfully. By combining Serious Gaming and GeoDesign framework, these games introduce an innovative, hybrid model that integrates real geospatial data with collaborative gameplay, offering a structured yet creative way to develop sustainable adaptation strategies.

Priority Target User B: Public sector, including municipalities and decision makers of the SCORE CCLLs

Municipalities, including those within SCORE CCLLs, such as Sligo County Council, Dún Laoghaire County Council, Vilanova Municipality, etc.

- *Role:* To use the games to gain insights from the public to make informed decisions on the best planning solutions for climate resilience projects. The aim is to empower researchers to utilise these tools with local authorities, educators, and communities for collaborative decision-making, bridging the gap between technical experts and the public.
- *Key Message:* These games can be used as an introduction to climate adaptive co-creation and ecosystem-based adaptation approaches to engage effectively across the quadruple helix. Its use could improve citizen science programmes and therefore increase involvement of citizens in useful science projects.
- *Awareness:* This target user would be very aware of the value of stakeholder engagement for spatial planning, but not necessarily aware of the potential of participatory games as an approach to engage with communities.
- *Level of Understanding:* Serious games are valuable tools for enhancing community participation in spatial planning and ecosystem-based adaptation. Their application can benefit multiple sectors, including local and regional government bodies, where city planning authorities and urban planners can use these tools to integrate participatory decision-making into land-use planning, urban resilience strategies, and infrastructure projects. Environmental and sustainability departments can incorporate EBA solutions into city adaptation plans, while municipalities and local councils can leverage the games to foster community-driven urban and environmental planning. This target user likely has not utilised serious games for planning decisions previously. The games are designed to be user-friendly for those unfamiliar with these programmes through instructions provided in the MOOC.
- *Interest:* These target users are likely actively seeking insights from stakeholders would be interested in determining the best options for their specific means or projects. These gaming approaches improve upon traditional spatial planning by gamifying decision-making, making it more accessible, interactive, and engaging. Unlike standard GIS-based tools, which often require expert knowledge, both games simplify complex data, allowing non-specialists to contribute meaningfully. By combining Serious Gaming and GeoDesign framework, these games introduce an innovative, hybrid model that integrates real geospatial data with collaborative gameplay, offering a structured yet creative way to develop sustainable adaptation strategies.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 3 – Engagement

- IRL 4 – Implementation

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

Throughout SCORE, the WP4 team co-designed and delivered these game-based participatory tools (GeoDesign Game & EBACraft) during 2023, 2024, 2025 SCORE EBA Training School weeks, engaging diverse stakeholders across all CCLLs and their partners. These were facilitated stakeholder workshops and training sessions where public authorities, local communities, youth groups, and academic institutions collaboratively explored EBA strategies using the games. This allowed for the teams to adapt complex geospatial data into accessible, gamified formats, enabling non-experts to meaningfully participate in spatial decision-making processes. The team further conducted questionnaire-based feedback loops during training schools to gather insights from players on usability, relevance, and accessibility, informing iterative improvements. Such identified barriers to digital access (e.g., hardware, technical skills) were considered by pre-configuring environments and providing tailored support to different user groups. The games were deployed and tested in real settings with CCLLs, allowing stakeholders to identify actionable EBA strategies based on game sessions also improve the climate perception.

As noted, the EBA Craft and GeoDesign games were both utilised during all three years of the EBA Training Schools. During these schools, each of the 10 CCLLs facilitated online and/or in-person events to use these games with their local communities. After these events, an EBACraft livestreams which took place in [2023 EBA Training School](#) and [2024 EBA Training School](#) were made available on YouTube for interested gamers to watch. Additionally, for interested CCLLs, the presentations on that took place during the EBA Training Schools were uploaded to YouTube and now are accessible on the CCLL GeoStories [here](#). Finally, a GeoDesign [post-event survey](#) was created to allow for iteration of the game.

The GeoDesign Game and EBACraft generate a range of outputs that help assess their impact on community engagement, spatial decision-making, and EBA planning. These outputs include game-generated data, participant feedback, and visual records of planning decisions, which provide insights into how different stakeholder groups interact with the tools and contribute to urban and environmental planning.

- For the GeoDesign Game, the primary outputs include recordings of debriefing sessions, where participants discuss their decision-making process, and CSV and JSON files generated at the end of each session, which logs all proposed solutions, voting patterns, and spatial planning decisions. Additionally, questionnaire responses are gathered to analyse the game's effectiveness in promoting collaboration and influencing real-world adaptation strategies.
- For EBACraft, key outputs include in-game recordings, screenshots, and saved world files, which document the players' interactions, spatial layouts, design choices, and adaptation strategies designed by participants. This data provides a visual record of how communities, particularly young people, envision and modify their environments using a geospatially accurate Minecraft model. Questionnaires had been used in SCORE CCLL events and EBA Training School week to assess participant engagement, learning outcomes, and the game's role in fostering civic participation.

All resources are available to CCLL facilitators and researchers for further analysis. Data, including CSV files, debriefing recordings, and Minecraft-generated content, will be collected by the CCLLs and they are at liberty to store and analyse the data in their local repositories. Facilitators will provide links and contact points for access to these materials.

Using the GeoDesign Game during Year 3 of the EBA Training School saw a number of unique activities taking place across each CCLL. Across the SCORE Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs), the GeoDesign Game served as an engaging and educational tool for involving local stakeholders, particularly young people, in the collaborative planning of ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) strategies. Each CCLL adapted the activity to its local context, ensuring the game reflected regional environmental challenges and social dynamics. The game not only introduced participants to nature-based solutions (NbS) but also encouraged critical thinking, role-playing, and consensus-building to identify climate adaptation priorities.

In Dublin, the pilot version of the GeoDesign Game was tested with 20 students from Holy Child School, Killiney. After an introductory session on EBAs and game objectives, students explored local coastal issues and potential NbS for their area. A preliminary test run helped students get comfortable with the interface and gameplay. Their strong local knowledge enriched the activity, making role-playing and decision-making more authentic. The session ended with a debrief where students discussed their choices and deepened their understanding of EBAs and climate resilience. In Benidorm, a similar session engaged secondary school students who worked in small groups to propose NbS for their city and the wider Alicante area. After a

contextual presentation by the local CCLL team, students debated appropriate solutions and reflected on how such participatory tools could inform municipal decision-making. Meanwhile, in Oarsoaldea, the GeoDesign Game was tested internally with the CCLL team and development agency staff, helping them evaluate the game's potential for future public engagement, to positive reviews by those involved.

In Gdańsk, two student groups from the University of Gdańsk, along with academic researchers, explored NbS options such as green roofs, water parks, and tree planting—solutions previously shortlisted in local multi-criteria analysis workshops. After casting votes individually, participants discussed their experiences with local flooding and the effectiveness of different EBAs. The session underscored the potential of participatory tools in fostering informed community dialogue around urban adaptation. Other CCLLs adapted the GeoDesign Game to suit their audiences. In Massa, students aged 10 to 18 played in mixed-age teams, encouraging peer-to-peer interaction. In Piran, students played two rounds of the game in rotating roles, followed by group discussions about their reasoning and the benefits of selected NbS. In Oeiras, the game focused on flood risks in the Rio Jamor area, with a diverse group of academic and public participants who voted on solutions like infiltration ponds and riparian reforestation. This session emphasized the game's utility in reflecting stakeholder values and advancing community-driven urban resilience planning.

External Engagement

For use by external target users, the Massive Open Online Course [Serious Games for Participatory Planning](#) is the key output used for dissemination of this KER. The MOOC will include a number of videos developed for the course by IHS, which are still being finalised by their videography departments. The videos and materials used in the MOOC are also available for users in individual formats, including the following: [EBACraft Tutorial](#) through Google Drive, [EU Green Week 2023 YouTube Live](#), and [EBACraft at the Climate Adaptation Training School second edition YouTube Live](#).

The GeoDesign Game also has been extensively shared at multiple events, including the Erasmus Sustainability Days in Rotterdam on May 21-22 2025, in collaboration with IHS. This session focused on Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), which encompass actions aimed at protecting, managing, and restoring natural or modified ecosystems. Through an interactive workshop utilizing a GeoDesign game, 15 participants from the conference collaboratively explored how to co-create local urban solutions, and filled out a post-event survey for the team to collect insights on how to improve the games for future iterations. The Game has also been shared at the International GeoGame Symposium June 9-10, 2025 at University College Dublin and through collaboration with the Dublin CCLL at the Dalkey Tidy Towns event in June 2025.

Additionally, insights from the SCORE GeoDesign and Minecraft-based participatory planning sessions have been incorporated into the policy briefs outlined in Deliverable D7.5. These findings highlight the value of documenting and sharing outcomes from such activities with policymakers to promote the adoption of digital participatory tools in urban and environmental planning processes. A key recommendation is to use participatory planning games to co-design adaptation measures alongside local communities. Cities are encouraged to integrate tools like the GeoDesign Game into public consultations and urban resilience workshops as a way to engage diverse stakeholders in scenario-based planning. The game fosters collaborative decision-making and raises awareness of nature-based solutions in the face of climate challenges. As part of SCORE's contribution, the GeoDesign Game was piloted across several Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs), tailored to reflect local geographical, cultural, and environmental contexts. Sessions were conducted in local languages and adapted to the needs of each city, demonstrating the game's flexibility and potential as a participatory planning instrument.

The GeoDesign Game is actively integrated with the Nature-Based Solutions Application Programming Interface (NBSAPI), developed by GeoDesignHub as part of the NBSINFRA H2020 project. This API offers a computational approach to Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in urban planning, facilitating data-driven decision-making within collaborative spatial planning, and is currently employed in real-world urban interventions. Integrating the GeoDesign Game into the API will expand its accessibility to a network of potentially interested users and ensure its inclusion in digital workflows for community-driven NBS co-design.

The GeoDesign game's code is available on GitHub, enabling collaboration and continuous improvement by the community. The repository will be made publicly available before the end of the project. This is an open resource and anybody can use this code and modify the code, we plan on having this under creative commons licensing, which means that the code can be modified but

cannot be used in its original form for commercial purposes by others. Finally, the two games are featured on the [Horizon Results platform](#).

Future Impact and Opportunities

API Development: The UCD team is actively collaborating with platforms such as GeoDesignHub to develop and refine the NBSAPI, enabling smooth integration with a variety of digital tools and platforms. This work supports the broader goal of streamlining data exchange and enhancing the functionality of participatory planning systems.

Playtesting and Adaptation: Continuous playtesting and iterative improvements to the GeoDesign Game, informed by user feedback, are ensuring that the tool remains adaptable, user-friendly, and effective across diverse geographic and cultural settings.

Heritact – NegoDesign Version: A specialised adaptation of the GeoDesign Game, known as *NegoDesign*, has been developed to support digital negotiation and collaborative reimagining of urban spaces through the [HeritACT project](#). This version is particularly suited to heritage-sensitive areas, promoting inclusive decision-making and fostering shared visions for community-oriented urban transformation. It is recommended to the UCD team to continue using these games to be adapted into new project spaces to expand the use of the games.

KER 9.1 - SCORE Online Learning: Massive Open Online Courses

Knowledge Owners: ERINN, UCD

Current Status: Open Online Free courses available at <https://score.thinkific.com/>

Description:

A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) is an open-online course for which participants from around the world can learn about a specific topic, utilising a variety of mediums, including videos, user forums, quizzes, reading materials, links to external supplementary materials and much more. MOOCs provide an affordable and flexible way to learn new skills and deliver quality educational experiences at scale. All participants require only a smart phone/tablet/computer and access to the internet – making these open-source courses an equitable opportunity for self-guided learning. The utilisation of SCORE's MOOCs enables the project to reach a wider audience and provide valuable climate action skills/learnings to citizens in Europe and worldwide.

Through the development of a central online learning platform, multiple MOOCs have been created to address different learning goals. Each course will serve one or more of the following overarching learning goals of the platform:

1. Increase knowledge of the CCLL concept and its functions.
2. Increase knowledge of the usefulness and effectiveness of Nature-Based Solutions and Ecosystem-Based Approaches for coastal cities.
3. Foster the utilisation and understanding of citizen science in climate change education.
4. Cultivate an appreciation for how digital and green solutions can be used in tandem to tackle climate change.
5. Raise awareness of the impact that the SCORE approach can have on local communities.

The SCORE Online Learning platform (<https://score.thinkific.com/>) is hosted on the Thinkific site and is user-friendly and well-branded to the SCORE identity. Each MOOC course on the site was developed following a set methodology to allow for appropriate identification of course material, validation of contents, and dissemination of the resource. To date, 3 courses have been developed and are live on the SCORE Online Learning platform.

Course #1: What are nature-based solutions?

Level of difficulty: Introductory

Target audiences: the general public, students, citizen scientists, municipalities / local policymakers, participants in CCLLs or living labs, and sustainability enthusiasts.

Objectives: The key learning outcome of this course is to provide learners with the necessary context to understand the role that Nature-Based Solutions and Ecosystem-Based Approaches can have in climate resilience. By the completion of the course, learners will have:

- Journeyed through the geologic past and uncovered how human activities have played a significant role in shaping the planet.
- Considered the essential workings of the water cycle, understanding that it has a profound impact on the health of the planet, influencing everything from climate patterns to freshwater availability.
- Gained a deeper understanding of the urgent need for sustainable solutions to safeguard our planet's delicate resources and ecosystems.
- Explored the concepts of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBAs).

Course #2: Ecosystem-based approaches: introduction to implementation

Level of difficulty: Introductory - Intermediate

Target audience: students, citizen scientists, policymakers, sustainability enthusiasts.

Objectives: The key learning objective of this course is to provide learners with a thorough understanding of what EBAs are and how they can be implemented into real-world scenarios. Through the completion of this course, learners will gain a comprehensive understanding of:

- What Ecosystem-Based Approaches are and how they are useful in creating sustainable, resilient, and adaptable communities in the face of a changing climate.
- The design, implementation, and evaluation of dynamic and collaborative Living Labs as a means to test and evolve various EBA solutions.
- The differences between co-creation and co-design, and how these processes are important to consider when developing solutions to climate challenges.
- Effective strategies for engaging with the public, including examples of citizen science and innovative uses of technology to reach new audiences.
- The importance of identifying and modelling disaster risk to inform more effective management schemes.

Course #3: Coastal monitoring for resilient communities

Level of difficulty: Intermediate - Advanced

Target audience: citizen science programme organisers, policymakers, technical teams within municipalities.

Objectives: The key learning objective of this course is to equip participants with the knowledge and skills needed to implement effective coastal monitoring strategies, leveraging innovative tools and community engagement to enhance climate resilience in coastal regions. Through the completion of this course, learners will gain a comprehensive understanding of:

- How to identify the key impacts of climate change on coastal communities to build resilience.
- Practical approaches for engaging local communities in coastal monitoring efforts.
- The latest tools and platforms for collecting, storing, and analysing coastal monitoring data.
- How technology can enhance both data accuracy and community participation in coastal resilience planning.

Course #4: Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs

Level of difficulty: Intermediate - Advanced

Target audience: Living Lab core teams, actors across quadruple helix interested in creating a Living Lab

Objectives: Navigating Living Labs offers practical guidance drawn from the ten SCORE CCLs on how best to create, implement, and evaluate a Coastal City Living Lab. Hear the valuable lessons learned by SCORE CCLs themselves, who share real-world insights, challenges, and successes for current and future Living Lab practitioners. By sharing these experiences, this course aims to contribute to the broader Living Lab community, providing actionable insights for those looking to establish, manage, or refine their own co-creation practices. While rooted in Coastal City Living Lab contexts, the recommendations are broadly relevant to any Living Lab focused on public engagement and resilience.

Course #5 Serious Games for Participatory Planning

Level of difficulty: Intermediate

Target audience: Researchers, Policy Makers, Urban and Environmental Planners, Community Engagement Practitioners

Objectives for learners:

- Understand the principles of Serious games and how they apply to participatory planning
- Learn how serious games can facilitate inclusive decision-making processes.
- Learn how to facilitate Serious games developed within SCORE, Geodesign Game, and EBACraft
- Explore how spatial data, stakeholder inputs, and scenario building are integrated in the GeoDesign Game and EBACraft

This course will be live by the end of July 2025, as it is waiting on final editing from the IHS teams for a video series collected for the MOOC.

Development

In developing each course, the key stakeholders' needs are considered to ensure that the modules created are tailored more appropriately to the intended audience. This in turn allows courses to maximise both generated interest and overall impact. Key identified participants and stakeholders are as follows:

- **SCORE CCLL stakeholders:** The CCLL stakeholders have an intense learning curve when participating in the project, and MOOCs can help empower them to feel engaged in this process by gaining more background information on what SCORE is doing and why. By fostering this education, the MOOC can enable the local stakeholders to continue implementing the SCORE approach beyond the project's end date.
- **Local municipalities & practitioners:** In local areas with an interest in increasing resilience to climate change, the MOOCs can provide practitioners and policy makers an opportunity to understand how SCORE approaches can be applied within their context, the materials and skillsets needed to implement, and the opportunities for change when applied. Further, introductory courses can provide these individuals with a simple, accessible way to gain the scientific and methodological background necessary to understand the proposed climate and community-based solutions.
- **Students & Teachers:** Developed MOOCs will allow students to educate themselves on a variety of relevant topics such as Nature-Based Solutions, co-creation and co-design, the development of living labs, and the role of technology in community engagement. A MOOC can achieve this through both theory and practical examples to provide a comprehensive understanding of key concepts, while highlighting the work done through the SCORE project. MOOCs can be a unique way for a student to engage more creatively with scientific content, making the courses a great addition for any teacher to add to their curriculum as primary or supplementary material.
- **Living Labs in other EU-funded projects:** Building competencies with the terminology and framework used in establishing a living lab takes a significant amount of time for stakeholders unfamiliar with the process. External EU projects establishing living labs and EBA/NBS could use these resources to allow their respective stakeholders the opportunity to learn about these concepts in the early stages of the project, thereby fostering a more productive living lab engagement process.

Citizens/General Public: For anyone interested in the SCORE approach, specifically Nature-Based Solutions, citizen science and climate change, the MOOCs will provide them with an introduction to these concepts, and if interested, they can continue to the more challenging modules to upskill in these areas. As such, the MOOCs are an excellent tool to engage with individuals that might not otherwise have access to educational materials on these subjects.

Throughout the development of any MOOC, target users were assessed by the MOOC Development Team, and course materials will be tailored to their background knowledge and learning goals. At least one MOOCs will be designed to be appropriate for each of the above identified target groups.

Impact & Application: With SCORE's focus on locally co-developed solutions, SCORE's MOOCs are a natural extension of the project's concept, allowing interested learners to equip themselves with the knowledge needed to build a more climate resilient coastal community. The aim was to capitalise on this potential by building Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), that through which the CCLLs can maximise stakeholder learning and engagement, while allowing other coastal communities or interested parties to easily learn about SCORE's approach, theory, and insights.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: All

Priority Target User A: General Public

This group could include any general public member: this might include SCORE CCLL stakeholders, citizen scientists, students and teachers, etc.

- *Role:* Anyone can access the MOOC for free online. As such, there is no barrier to use other than access to a computer or smartphone. Through increasing their knowledge on the themes within the courses, there could be subsequent opportunities to apply this knowledge within other settings, though it is not necessarily the objective of this KO.
- *Key Message:* With the MOOC # 1 What are Nature-based Solutions? introductory course, this user can explore the origins of our changing climate and discover how Nature-Based Solutions can help address environmental challenges.
- *Awareness:* Low to medium. The target user is likely aware of the key themes present in the MOOCs but not of the specific courses.
- *Level of Understanding:* The key purpose of this KO is to increase the target user's level of understanding on the course topic. As such, there is no training required to take up this KO. The platform is easily usable and includes a brief introduction lesson on how to navigate through the course.

For anyone interested in the SCORE approach, specifically Nature-Based Solutions, citizen science and climate change, the MOOCs will provide them with an introduction to these concepts, and if interested, they can continue to the more challenging modules to upskill in these areas. As such, the MOOCs are an excellent tool to engage with individuals that might not otherwise have access to educational materials on these subjects.

Developed MOOCs will allow students to educate themselves on a variety of relevant topics such as Nature-Based Solutions, co-creation and co-design, the development of living labs, and the role of technology in community engagement. A MOOC can achieve this through both theory and practical examples to provide a comprehensive understanding of key concepts, while highlighting the work done through the SCORE project. MOOCs can be a unique way for a student to engage more creatively with scientific content, making the courses a great addition for any teacher to add to their curriculum as primary or supplementary material.

The MOOC *Course #1 – What are Nature-Based Solutions?* is the recommended course for this target group. As this is an introductory-level course, it is adapted for learners with low understandings of Nature-Based Solutions, Ecosystem-Based Approaches, or the wider challenges of climate change.

- *Interest:* The target user would be actively seeking out information on these relevant themes. They would be interested in the KO for a number of reasons, such as being involved in citizen science projects, involved in an educational setting, etc.

Priority Target User B: Academics, researchers, living labs, and other EU projects

Those working in research or academia and working with EBAs or Living Labs.

- *Role:* The user would take the MOOC to upskill in order to be more knowledgeable about Living Labs or EBAs for their own projects. They'd likely have interest in incorporating these concepts into their research.
- *Key Message:* The SCORE MOOCs provide practical tools and knowledge on Nature-Based Solutions, Ecosystem-Based Approaches, and Living Labs to support research, EU projects, and climate action initiatives. The recommended courses are MOOC #3 Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities and MOOC #4 Navigating Living Labs.
- *Awareness:* This user would be familiar with the key terms and methods but would be interested in learning more about how to implement these ideas in their own projects or research.
- *Level of Understanding:* Building competencies with the terminology and framework used in establishing a living lab takes a significant amount of time for stakeholders unfamiliar with the process. External EU projects establishing living labs and EBA/NBS could use these resources to allow their respective stakeholders the opportunity to learn about these concepts in the early stages of the project, thereby fostering a more productive living lab engagement process. Recommended courses: MOOC Course #2 Ecosystem-based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation, MOOC Course #3 Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities, MOOC Course #4 Coastal City Living Labs
- *Interest:* Academics and researchers are often actively researching climate resilience, NBS, EBAs, and Living Labs. They would find SCORE's outputs valuable for evidence-based research, methodologies, and case studies. Living labs and EU-funded projects are likely seeking practical guidance and frameworks to establish and implement living labs or EBAs effectively. SCORE MOOCs provide foundational knowledge and examples that can streamline their processes.

Priority Target User C: Local municipalities and policymakers

Local decision makers or policymakers working with coastal monitoring or EBA solutions planning.

- **Role:** Role of the target user would be to be knowledgeable about potential coastal management or city planning solutions.
- **Key Message:** The SCORE MOOCs offer practical guidance on implementing Nature-Based Solutions and Ecosystem-Based Approaches to build climate resilience in local communities. The recommended courses are MOOC Course #2 Ecosystem-based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation, MOOC #3 Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities, and MOOC #4 Navigating Living Labs.
- **Awareness:** The target user may be familiar with the concepts present in the MOOC but not of the MOOCs.
- **Level of Understanding:** In local areas with an interest in increasing resilience to climate change, the MOOCs can provide practitioners and policy makers an opportunity to understand how SCORE approaches can be applied within their context, the materials and skillsets needed to implement, and the opportunities for change when applied. Further, introductory courses can provide these individuals with a simple, accessible way to gain the scientific and methodological background necessary to understand the proposed climate and community-based solutions.
- **Interest:** Policymakers and practitioners are actively seeking information related to climate resilience and sustainable solutions due to increasing pressures to address climate change impacts at local levels. The SCORE MOOCs provide actionable insights on Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBA), offering practical tools and strategies they can apply to develop policies, engage communities, and implement cost-effective climate resilience measures. Their interest is driven by: The need for evidence-based solutions to meet climate targets, The demand for tools to support local decision-making and stakeholder engagement, Opportunities to replicate successful approaches from other regions or projects.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 3 – Engagement

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 4 – Implementation

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

The MOOC was co-developed by the wider SCORE consortium. To create the MOOCs, a huge number of SCORE activities contributed material. For example, the Citizen Science Playbook learning modules formed the basis for MOOC #1 What are Nature-Based Solutions? Additional text was collected from relevant featured KOs, including the EBA catalogue, Sensors Catalogue, MCA and CBAs, Digital Twin, ICT Platform, etc. Finally, *Deliverable 2.4 Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs* formed the basis for Course #4: Navigating Living Labs.

Video Content Curation

Multiple videos from across the project have been incorporated into the MOOCs. In total, there were 74 clips/videos incorporated across the MOOC courses, from the following project resources:

Webinars

- Developing Coastal City Living Labs ([link](#))
- The potential of Ecosystem-based Adaptation in Coastal Cities ([link](#))
- Co-creation and Co-design – examples for Nature-Based Solutions in cities ([link](#))
- Risk modeling and its role in designing strategies to increase financial resilience ([link](#))
- Collecting and managing environmental data: the SCORE ICT platform ([link](#))
- From global to local scale: predicting the effects of climate change on coastal cities ([link](#))
- Engaging and empowering citizens with low-cost sensors for monitoring climate change hazards ([link](#))
- The SCORE digital twin: the application of smart technologies against climate change ([link](#))
- Mapping the baseline exposure and risk of extreme climate impacts on coastal cities ([link](#))
- Adapt4Coast Webinar: tools to enhance climate change adaptation in coastal areas ([link](#))

EBA Training School Lectures: EBA Training School Videos from Day One of the schools, including years one, two and three.

- First Edition: SCORE Project Manager, Iulia Anton (ATU Sligo), launched the training school with a presentation in English about the SCORE's approach to coastal climate resilience. Then, the participants were split into 7 parallel sessions according to their language preference and location where speakers presented different topics related to coastal climate-related issues and approaches with real-life examples from the project. The English session from the ATU team discussing useful smart technologies for engaging with communities was incorporated into MOOC #2.
- Second Edition: The SCORE Project Manager, Iulia Anton (ATU Sligo), launched the training school with an introduction to the SCORE's approach to coastal climate resilience, followed by a presentation of citizen science activities within the project by Saul Crowley (UCD). The participants were then split into 7 parallel sessions according to their language preference and location, in which speakers presented different topics related to community-based coastal monitoring. The English session facilitated by the ATU and UCD teams on smart technologies for coastal monitoring was incorporated into MOOC #3.
- Third Edition: Project Coordinator Salem Gharbia introduced the overview of the SCORE project, followed by talks from ENoLL and IHS team members on the SCORE legacy and innovative approaches to coastal climate adaptation. The English session by the ATU team was also incorporated into MOOC #3, where they discussed decision support tools and living Lab sustainability to inform climate policy-making.

ENoLL Living Lab Integrative Framework Video Series: 9 videos from the ENoLL team were incorporated into MOOC#4 Navigating Living Labs to detail how to create and implement a Living lab throughout the Living Lab Integrative Process.

Lessons learned: 23 videos were created from the Lessons Learned Interview Series which took place with each CCLL in early 2025. The clips were curated into compilations aligned with the various lessons learned chapters within MOOC #4, and feature speakers from across all 10 CCLLs in conversation with the ERINN team.

External Engagement

The MOOC has been advertised at multiple SCORE events, including ENoLL OpenLivingLab Days (2023), EU Week of Regions and Cities (2024), SCORE Ecosystem Based Adaptation Training Schools (2023-2025), Capacity Building: promoted in training courses at ENoLL (2023-2025), European Maritime Day (2025), and the SCORE Final Event at European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025). Promotional cards (see below) were handed out at these events, with over 50 copies being disseminated to interested learners.

These MOOCs were also shared through a social media campaign targeting specific LinkedIn community groups including the Nature-Based Solutions community group. These were very successful, with engagement with target audiences reaching over 750 likes, 19 comments and 155 reposts on the first post shared in November 2024. The Nature-Based Solutions communications team has already planned an additional post to advertise the final MOOCs, set for the first week of July. In addition to this, the MOOC has been shared extensively within partner networks and through social media campaigns. In June 2025, ERINN Innovation ran a [paid campaign](#) to advertise MOOC to its network of target users that might be interested in creating or implementing Living Labs. The post received over 121,000 impressions.

Finally, the CCLLs have widely disseminated and utilised the MOOCs when engaging with the public and CCLL-localised events, such as the EBA training schools. *MOOC #1 What are Nature Based Solutions* has been translated into Spanish and Catalan for dissemination to a wider audience. At present, the MOOCs have over 1,200 enrolments.

Future Impact and Opportunities

The MOOC courses are written to still be relevant following the conclusion of SCORE. As such, they can remain live well beyond the project given the platform receives funding. There was a large amount of interest in sustaining this site from UCD, ATU, and

ERINN's perspectives. Following discussions between ERINN, UCD, ATU, and ENoLL, ATU has agreed to continue paying for the platform beyond the SCORE project through synergising initiatives, meaning the MOOCs will continue to be available at least two years beyond the project.

Finally, additional plans to host the MOOC across partner pages are in motion. ERINN will host a blog about the MOOC as a key output for the SME within the project. The content from MOOC course #4 Navigating Living Labs will also be hosted on ENoLL's knowledge repository once the site is finalized.

#	Knowledge Output Title	Description
KO2.4	SCORE Monitoring & Evaluation Framework	The SCORE M&E Framework specifically designed for LL environments to strengthen climate resilience in European coastal cities. Its innovation stems from an integrated, participatory approach applied across diverse CCLLs, blending established evaluation methods with participatory principles. The framework provides a structured assessment with a dual focus on both the process (how initiatives are executed through phases like co-creation, piloting, testing) and the effect (outcome and impact) throughout the project cycle. Embedded stakeholder engagement fosters a more inclusive and context-sensitive evaluation process. While particularly suited for LLs focused on climate resilience and urban innovation, its flexible, principle-based design suggests it could be applied to any LL setting or other innovation/community-based projects beyond the LL model. Data is collected through online surveys, meetings, and workshops, structured across baseline, interim, and impact assessment phases.

3.2. Increasing Data Availability

To create effective climate mitigation strategies, high-quality local data is essential. However, many communities lack sufficient weather data needed to do so. As such, SCORE developed a suite of tools to expand the data pool available to the CCLLs.

KER 1.2 - Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment Methodology for Climate Change Impacts on European Cities

Knowledge Owners : UCC

Current Status: Open-Access as part of D1.4 ([link](#))

Description: This KER is a novel methodology to assess at a high level (i.e., high resolution), the risks faced by European cities due to the extreme impacts of sea level rise and climate-related events due to climate change. All potential climate hazards are included in this methodology, as it is tailored to be more general and not specific just to coastal cities. The methodology has been applied to SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) but can easily be adapted for other European cities.

The methodology utilises an indicator-based approach to assess risk related to climate-related hazards and climate change by relying on specific indicators. The approach involves selecting, calculating, and interpreting these indicators to make informed decisions, track progress, or identify trends. This process considers multiple climate-related hazards (i.e., including storms, sea-level rise, coastal erosion, coastal flooding, heavy precipitation, land flooding, landslides, heat waves, cold spells, droughts and strong wind). These hazards are then scored and weighted to calculate baseline risk within a locality.

The methodology includes or is based on:

- A systematic literature review on the extreme impacts of climate change on CCLLs.
- A comprehensive understanding of the key hazards and impacts of climate change on the CCLLs.
- The mapping of these key hazards.
- A high-level, semi-quantitative assessment of exposure and vulnerability on CCLLs.

- The calculation and mapping of coastal exposure and vulnerability indicators on CCLLs.

This methodology allows for a high-level, homogeneous and standardised comparison of baseline risk for current atmospheric conditions between CCLLs and other cities. This process is beneficial for several reasons:

- Such comparisons facilitate the development of uniform and effective policies.
- Cities can allocate resources more efficiently when they have standardised risk data. They can prioritise projects and investments to mitigate climate-related risks where they are most needed.
- Standardised data allows for simplified information sharing and collaboration between cities and stakeholders.
- Homogeneous data and standardised assessments make it easier to communicate risks and vulnerabilities to the public.

Novel approach: In general, there are a few existing methodologies with multi-hazard criteria, but they are limited to their geographical context and the number of climate-related hazards available for assessment. This methodology includes considerations necessary for coastal cities and subsequently gives a more holistic overview of the climate-related hazards. As such, it can be adapted to numerous contexts and can be applied to any city or region.

Notably, this methodology has been applied to each CCLL, with the results presented in D1.4. Local data and context were provided, which allowed for a higher degree of detail for each individual city.

CCLL Specific Outputs:

Each CCLL has specific outputs relevant to this KO that could be utilised at the local/regional level. The analysis includes the risk of all the CCLLs to the key climate-related hazards pre-identified. The analysis encompasses the risk of the population, the residential buildings, the industry, the commercial buildings, the agriculture, the critical infrastructure, the beach areas and the natural areas. The results are summarised in the form of maps and tables, depicting the scoring of risk and the hot spots of risk.

Impact & Application:

- **Potential Application:** Through the use of the broad methodology, and use of EU datasets and codes, this technology could potentially be used for ~1000 European cities to provide an overview of their risk assessment. The broad methodology can give numerical scores for technicians to then further develop maps for their own areas. Target users can then use these generated risk maps/risk assessments to aid in decision-making for a variety of purposes.
- **City planning:** With this methodology, one can assess risk for multiple cities and compare them for use in decision-making and budget allocation. The assessment of multiple hazards allows all to be included in consideration in both planning and subsequently in allocating resources. When several cities are considered at the same time, their risk can be leveraged and compared, which allows for the identification of which cities are more urgent to take action in.
- **Government/policymakers:** This methodology can assist in the development of coastal adaptation strategies/coastal resiliency plans. Risk assessments can provide scientific insights to assist European, national or regional government bodies or policymakers to compare risk between coastal cities and prioritise response actions in mid-timescales. For cities with a lack of baseline risk information (especially holistic multi-hazard risk assessments) or data inaccessibility, the application of the methodology can have a high impact on the development of climate change plans or legislation.

Linked Knowledge Outputs:

- KO1.1 - Mapping of baseline exposure and risks of climate change impacts on SCORE's Coastal Cities Living Labs
- KER 3.1 - Procedural Guide for Identifying and Using Climate and Marine Data Services and Datasets for Baseline Characterization and Projections
- Clustered KER 3.4 & 3.5 – Coastal Erosion & Flood Modelling for CCLLs
- KER 6.1 – Risk Characterisation Methodology for the Development of Semi-Quantitative, Comparable Indices

Priority Target User A: Academic or Industry Technicians

Academics, researchers, and scientists: civil engineers, survey engineers, and environmental scientists, e.g., Department of Environmental Engineering, Marine & Environmental Institutes, etc.

- *Role:* To conduct research broadly on climate-change, climate-change mitigation & resilience, impact assessments, etc.
- *Key Message:* In general, there are a few existing methodologies with multi-hazard criteria, but they are limited to their geographical context and the number of climate-related hazards available for assessment. This methodology includes considerations beyond those only specific to coastal cities, as it gives a more holistic overview of the climate-related hazards. As such, it can be adapted to numerous contexts and can be applied to any city or region.
- *Awareness:* Production of hazard maps is not a novel practice, as such, these target users are likely aware of methodologies to produce hazard maps. However, they will be unaware of the breadth/opportunities this KER offers in terms of the number of hazards and the wide-reaching geographies.
- *Level of Understanding:* To utilise this methodology, a high level of technical expertise would be required. The technicians will need access to specific technologies and will require some technical background. The methodology was developed with a combination of programmes - GIS software, Excel, and to access some databases (i.e., Copernicus), and use of Python code. However, anyone with relevant training should be able to understand and replicate this methodology.
- *Interest:* There is a growing need for this type of methodology for communities to best plan their responses to climate change – as this data is prepared for the larger European community, the interest should be high.

Priority Target User B: Public Sector Urban Planners

Urban planners, Environmental/Climate departments, e.g., Irish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection (Poland), Civil Protection (Oeiras), etc.

- *Role:* To support the city planning and environmental department in achieving environmental goals and associated requirements, and development of climate-change planning documents.
- *Key Message:* In general, there are a few existing methodologies with multi-hazard criteria, but they are limitations with their geographical reach and the number of climate-related hazards available for assessment. This methodology and dataset allow for any European city to be considered and their respective hazard map to be developed. With this methodology, one can assess risk for multiple cities and compare them for use in decision-making and budget allocation. The assessment of multiple hazards allows all to be included in consideration in both planning and subsequently in allocating resources. When a number of cities are considered at the same time, their risk can be leveraged and compared, which allows for the identification of which cities are more urgent to take action in. This methodology can assist in the development of coastal adaptation strategies/coastal resiliency plans. Risk assessments can provide scientific insights to assist European, national or regional government bodies or policymakers to compare risk between coastal cities and prioritise response actions in mid-timescales. For cities with a lack of baseline risk information (especially holistic multi-hazard risk assessments) or data inaccessibility, the application of the methodology can have a high impact on the development of climate change plans or legislation.
- *Awareness:* Production of hazard maps is not a particularly novel practice, as such, they are likely aware of previous methodologies to produce hazard maps. However, they will be unaware of the breadth/opportunities this KER offers in terms of the number of hazards and the wide-reaching geographies.
- *Level of Understanding:* To utilise this methodology and data set, a high level of technical expertise would be required. A target user will need access to specific technologies and will require some technical background. The methodology was developed with a combination of programmes - GIS software, Excel, and to access some databases (i.e., Copernicus), and use of Python code. However, anyone with relevant training should be able to understand and

replicate this methodology. Policymakers themselves would not understand the methodology and therefore require the advice/considerations of the urban planners & climate departments.

- *Interest:* With this methodology, one can assess risk for multiple cities and compare them for use in decision-making and budget allocation. The assessment of multiple hazards allows all to be included in consideration in both planning and subsequently in allocating resources. This methodology can assist in the development of coastal adaptation strategies/coastal resiliency plans. Risk assessments can provide scientific insights to assist European, national or regional government bodies or policymakers in comparing risk between coastal cities and prioritise response actions in mid-timescales (2030-204). For cities lacking baseline risk information (especially holistic multi-hazard risk assessments) or data-inaccessibility, the application of the methodology can have a high impact on the development of climate change plans or legislation.
- *Other Influences (if relevant):* The overarching climate-action plans (if available) and strategies of the region. The idea of targeting the planners and environmental bodies is that they are avenues through which we can reach the policymakers, as the policymakers themselves are unlikely to use this output, without the support of planners.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 1 - Conception

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 3 – Engagement

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

The CCLLs took part in a participatory process to identify key climate-related hazards. Local data was gathered through WP2 questionnaires, which supported a detailed baseline risk analysis for each city. This data allowed risk assessment to be tailored to each local context, covering impacts on people, homes, businesses, agriculture, critical infrastructure, beaches, and natural areas. The methodology was validated through **data, scenarios, and stakeholder feedback**:

- **Data and scenarios:** The risk analysis was based on a systematic literature review and utilized data collected from WP2 questionnaires and existing databases. It incorporated a high-level, semi-quantitative assessment of exposure and vulnerability on CCLLs. For instance, for Dublin CCLL, assessments of residential and commercial buildings under six Sea Level Rise (SLR) scenarios were used, drawing data from the Irish 20-m medium-scale resolution DTM. This also included potential insurance claims for Great Dublin under these SLR scenarios.
- **Stakeholder feedback:** The report itself is based on a participatory process involving the CCLLs. The CCLLs provided local data and context, which allowed for a higher degree of detail in the analysis. The CCLLs' perceptions indicated that the results and methodology were greatly appreciated and useful, particularly the graphical outputs for communication with external stakeholders. Their feedback also suggested avenues for further development of the methodology, such as including more study cases, refining risk weighting, and considering projections for some indicators.

External Engagement

Publications

- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2023). Extreme climate change hazards and impacts on European coastal cities: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 184, 113587. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113587>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2023). Scientometric review of climate-change extreme impacts on coastal cities. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 242, 106709. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106709>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2024). High-level characterisation and mapping of key climate-change hazards in European coastal cities. *Natural Hazards*, 120(4), 3623-3659. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-06349-4>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2024). Multi-hazard assessment of climate-related hazards for European coastal cities. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 357, 120787. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120787>

- Laino, E., Paranzio, R., & Iglesias, G. (2024). Scientometric review on multiple climate-related hazards indices. *Science of The Total Environment*, 174004. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174004>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2024). Beyond coastal hazards: A comprehensive methodology for the assessment of climate-related hazards in European coastal cities. *Ocean Coast Manag* 257, 107343. DOI: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2024.107343>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2025). Extreme weather events and environmental contamination under climate change: A comparative review of ten European coastal cities. *Curr Opin Environ Sci Health* 2025, 45:100606. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2025.100606>

Conferences:

- European Sciences Conference
- UCC PhD Workshop

Other Knowledge Transfer Measures:

- [SCORE Webinar](#) #8 – Mapping the baseline exposure and risk of extreme climate impacts on coastal cities
- Integration into the CCLL Story Maps for various CCLLs
- Publication on the [Horizon Results Platform](#)

Future Impact and Opportunities

This methodology is specifically designed to support the creation of coastal adaptation strategies and resilience plans. It offers scientific tools to help European, national, and regional governments compare climate risks across coastal cities and prioritize actions for the medium term (e.g., 2030–2040). It is particularly valuable for cities that lack baseline risk data or comprehensive multi-hazard assessments, as it enables more informed planning and policymaking.

By allowing consistent comparisons between cities, the methodology supports the development of harmonized and effective policies across regions. This makes it highly relevant for future policy or funding initiatives in climate resilience, urban planning, disaster risk reduction, and sustainable development at local, national, and EU levels.

Looking ahead, the final version of the methodology must be developed and widely shared. To ensure its robustness, the UCC team will continue refining the approach through additional case studies, further analysis of risk weighting, and improved projections for future climate risk. There is a clear ambition to automate risk calculations using platforms like Copernicus, enabling more frequent and standardized assessments across European coastal cities. However, this will require significant development and funding.

User-friendliness is also key. Future versions must be designed with non-experts in mind and co-created with end-users. For successful adoption at the policy level, collaboration with urban planners and climate/environmental departments is essential, as policymakers are unlikely to use technical outputs without expert guidance.

As part of the peer-review process, the UCC team expanded the methodology and applied it to additional cities: La Spezia (Italy), Bergen (Norway), Cork (Ireland), Klaipėda (Lithuania), Viana do Castelo (Portugal), and Varna (Bulgaria). It is recommended that the results and methodology be shared with the municipal bodies of these cities. In countries where existing CCLLs are active—such as Italy, Ireland, and Portugal—these municipalities should be connected with their national CCLLs to promote knowledge exchange and highlight the practical value of the methodology.

KER 3.2 - Package of downscaling analysis tools, data, and user document

Knowledge Owners: LaMMA, CNR, ATU **Current Status:** Open Access, as part of [D3.3 \(Package of downscaling analysis tools\)](#) and [D3.4 \(User document for the downscaling analysis tools and data\)](#).

Description: SCORE employs innovative methods to downscale climate data, transforming large-scale climate model outputs

into fine-scale, localized data tailored for urban-scale applications in our Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs). This process is integral for understanding and addressing climate change impacts at a local level, bridging the gap between global climate models (GCMs) or regional climate models (RCMs) and the detailed information required for urban resilience planning

Purpose of Downscaling in SCORE: By refining large-scale data (resolutions of tens of kilometres) into high-resolution datasets (resolutions of hundreds or tens of meters), this KO ensures that the resulting information is relevant to the specific geographic, topographic, and environmental contexts of each CCLL. Localised data enables the creation of sophisticated models for simulating flooding phenomena, assessing climate risks, and evaluating adaptation strategies that are used in later SCORE activities (D3.7/3.8 & KO3.4).

Challenges Addressed: Global and regional climate models often fail to adequately represent localized phenomena due to their coarse spatial resolution. Key limitations include:

- Inability to capture local features like vegetation, complex topography, and coastlines.
- Poor representation of extreme, localized events, such as convective precipitation or storm surges.

The KO works to overcome these limitations by **integrating dynamic and statistical downscaling techniques**, ensuring that localised impacts of climate change are better captured for urban planning and resilience-building efforts.

Innovative Capacity: These downscaling methods go beyond conventional approaches, notably by including and utilising the following:

1. **Unstructured Grids:** Models used, such as SHYFEM and WWIII (WAVEWATCH III), use unstructured grids to provide more **accurate representations of complex coastlines and bathymetry**.
2. **Neural Network Applications:** A convolutional neural network (CNN)-based statistical downscaling tool was used to refine rainfall data used in LISFLOOD (LISFLOOD hydrological model), significantly **advancing the resolution and accuracy of precipitation** estimates.
3. **Integration of Marine and Hydrological Data:** Datasets include atmospheric fields, sea levels, wave patterns, and hydrology. This comprehensive approach **enables accurate simulations of interactions between wave climate, storm surges, and river discharges**.
4. **Scenario-Based Projections:** The project uses RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios to evaluate both moderate and extreme climate change impacts, allowing for a **thorough analysis of future risks**.

The methodology employed is both user-oriented and scientifically robust:

1. **User-Oriented:** Open-source tools like SHYFEM, WWIII, and LISFLOOD are chosen for their accessibility, transparency, and relative ease of use, empowering end-users such as municipal authorities and researchers to apply these models to local contexts. This KO aims to provide a well-documented and comprehensive package of tools, including all the necessary information to download and use these downscaling models. This enables end-users, such as municipal personnel and researchers with sufficient knowledge and background, to replicate the process.

Scientifically Robust: State-of-the-art techniques such as finite element modeling (SHYFEM), spectral wave modeling (WWIII), and spatially distributed modeling (LISFLOOD) ensure high scientific accuracy in data generation and processing.

CCLL Specific Outputs: Downscaled data are available for Massa, Oarsoaldea, Vilanova, Sligo and Samsun are available to the SCORE partners.

Impact & Application: The methods and models outlined in this KO can be applied to coastal cities outside of the project, in line with the dissemination actions included in the project. To this end, the selection of models for the project primarily focused on open-source models, avoiding restrictions on their use.

The downscaled data and models developed are instrumental in supporting urban resilience strategies, including:

- **Flood Mapping:** Simulating urban floods caused by storm surges, extreme rainfall, and river discharges.
- **Coastal Erosion Analysis:** Assessing the impact of waves and sea-level rise on coastal infrastructure.

- **Ecosystem-Based Adaptation:** Evaluating nature-based solutions for enhancing climate resilience.

Expected impacts include improved disaster preparedness, reduction in economic losses due to climate hazards, and informed policy frameworks for sustainable coastal management.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KOs and KERs across Work Package 3 act in a cumulative manner and therefore are all relevant to each other.

Priority Target User A: Public sector entities, in particular Municipalities, tasked with developing and implementing climate adaptation strategies, like new urban plans or new infrastructures approvals. These entities play a crucial role in managing the impacts of climate change on urban areas and their communities.

Specific Examples.

- **Role:** The relevant roles and responsibilities of this target user group include seeking data-driven climate resilience strategies, participating in environmental departments and urban planning agencies, and acting as local authorities involved in policy/governance. Support urban resilience strategies, including flood mapping, coastal erosion analysis, and evaluating nature-based solutions, leading to improved disaster preparedness and informed policy frameworks.
- **Key Message:** This output is innovative because it provides newly downscaled climate data specifically tailored for urban areas within your CCLL, including atmospheric variables. It is beneficial as it provides the precise, localised climate data needed for data-driven climate resilience strategies and supports the development of detailed urban-scale models for simulating phenomena like urban floods and coastal erosion. This enables better assessment of climate risks and evaluation of adaptation strategies, including nature-based solutions.
- **Awareness:** Knowledge Transfer Sessions involving oral presentations have been held with relevant CCLL local stakeholders specifically within Massa, Vilanova & Oarsoaldea to transfer this KO, meaning some stakeholders will be aware through dedicated project activities, however saturation within the institutions is likely limited, nor did all CCLLs have these sessions.
- **Level of Understanding:** The target user group includes municipal personnel and local users, technicians, and scientists. While the KO aims to be accessible and usable by those with limited technical expertise, the process itself requires high technical expertise and powerful technology. The downscaled data *are* in netCDF format, which is a standard in meteorology but quite technical. As such, a technician would be needed to utilise these results.
- **Interest:** This target user is likely actively seeking information related to the KO because they need data-driven climate resilience strategies and require precise downscaled datasets for their roles in climate adaptation and urban planning. However, human resources to utilise and political will to implement such results will vary based on the regions.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 1 – Conception

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 3 – Engagement

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

Throughout the project, a range of activities were carried out across the Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) to refine, test, and validate climate adaptation tools. This began with in-person and online meetings with local stakeholders to gather in-situ data, sensor readings, and reports to tailor methods to each CCLL's context.

Knowledge transfer sessions were held in Massa, Oarsoaldea, Vilanova i la Geltrú, Sligo, and Benidorm, bringing together municipal staff and policy stakeholders. In Vilanova and Benidorm, municipal representatives saw strong potential for using the tool in science-based decision-making. Oarsoaldea's session included the local water management agency, while in Sligo, the coastal golf club owners showed strong interest, reflecting established local engagement.

The tool was tested locally in Massa, Oarsoaldea, Vilanova, Samsun, and Sligo, depending on the downscaled parameters. For wave-related data, testing occurred in all CCLLs. Validation used local sensor data—like hydrometric gauges and buoys—to calibrate models historically. EURO-CORDEX evaluation runs were used for statistical validation by comparing extreme value distributions across datasets.

This validation process, outlined in deliverable KO3.6, underpins the scientific integrity of the flood and erosion models. Though mainly for internal quality checks, it strengthens the reliability of the outputs. Interest from other cities, including Pisa, shows the broader relevance and potential for replication across European municipalities.

Publications:

- Preprint: [link](#)
- Tools and methodologies have been uploaded and made publicly available on Zenodo platform as part of [D3.3 \(Package of downscaling analysis tools\)](#) and [D3.4 \(User document for the statistical downscaling\)](#).

Conferences:

- Oral presentation: [link](#)
- Oral presentation: [link](#)

Other Knowledge Transfer Measures (webinars, social media, goestories, etc.):

- Geostories: <https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/catalogue/#/geostory/5851>
- Webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hg3zuZdhfR8&t=3618s>
- News: <https://www.voceapuana.com/attualita/2025/02/28/cambiamenti-climatici-massa-protagonista-del-progetto-score-soluzioni-innovative/86534/>
- News: <https://www.lanazione.it/massa-carrara/cronaca/cambiamenti-climatici-progetto-score-entra-9a9a62ff>
- Kickoff meeting of the AMIS project (<https://interreg-maritime.eu/web/amis>)
- CNR school seminars (<https://www.ibbr.cnr.it/ibbr/news/attivita-di-divulgazione-scientifica-cnr>)
- Publication on the [Horizon Results Platform](#)

Future Impact and Opportunities

LaMMA has taken key steps toward reaching Impact Readiness Level (IRL) 4, notably through the co-creation of the methodology in collaboration with local stakeholders. This participatory approach ensured the method was grounded in real-world needs and conditions.

Looking ahead, LaMMA plans to build on this KER by applying it to additional case studies. This will allow continued collaboration and knowledge-sharing among partners already engaged in the project. A concrete opportunity to apply this work is emerging through the PRIMA-MED call on water management in the nexus (<https://prima-med.org/submit-your-project/water-management-in-the-nexus/>). The high-resolution, context-specific data produced by this KER offers a scientifically robust foundation for assessing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), particularly in Mediterranean contexts. Several SCORE partners based in relevant regions are currently preparing applications for this call.

While the service enabled by this KER has wide-ranging potential, it is not a simple plug-and-play solution. In particular, the neural network component requires significant customization for different datasets. This makes it both technically and computationally intensive, challenges that many municipalities are not equipped to manage independently. To address this, LaMMA, as a core knowledge holder and contributor to several key outputs within Work Package 3 (specifically KOs 3.1 through 3.6), is exploring the development of a tailored service model. This service would offer climate risk assessment and adaptation planning support to public authorities, leveraging the methodologies, tools, and datasets refined during SCORE. By providing this expertise as a service, LaMMA could bridge the gap between advanced scientific tools and the practical needs of municipalities, supporting the uptake of data-driven climate resilience planning across Europe. More details in KER 3.4/3.5.

Clustered KER 3.4 & 3.5 – Coastal Erosion & Flood Modelling for CCLs

Knowledge Owners : LaMMA, CNR, ATU, SAMU, UA **Current Status:** Open – see below for links

[D3.7 Package of short-term hazard modelling](#)

[D3.8 User document for the short-term hazard modelling](#)

Title : Methodology and Hazard Maps for Flood Risk Mitigation Assessment

Background: Flood modeling is crucial in the context of climate change as rising global temperatures lead to more extreme weather patterns, including heavy rainfall and storms. These events increase the risk of riverine and coastal flooding, while rising sea levels further heighten the threat. Accurate modeling is essential for predicting and mitigating these impacts. Floods cause extensive damage to infrastructure, agriculture, and businesses, often displacing large populations. Urban areas are particularly vulnerable due to dense populations and impermeable surfaces. Effective flood modeling aids urban planning supports flood-resistant infrastructure and helps develop adaptation strategies like levees and drainage systems to reduce disaster impacts.

Description: This KO aims to describe the tools and procedures for the development short-term hazard models, where the main outputs are the hazard maps. This KO addresses the "last mile" hydraulic model, which is a high-resolution flood simulation that focuses on the final stage of a downscaling process, detailing localized impacts on urban areas, infrastructure, and drainage systems. It takes as input the climatic information produced by the hydrological model, sea level model, and wave model. These models are applied at the urban scale, incorporating digital terrain models and precise information at these scales. This model simulates different hazard scenarios, each representing a potential flood risk with a specific likelihood of occurring. The probabilities of these events are determined using statistical methods, such as the block maxima approach, which extracts the highest values from fixed time intervals (e.g., annual maximum flood levels) to fit a probability distribution and estimate return periods for extreme events.

The methodology enables the evaluation of both riverine and coastal flood scenarios, taking into account the contribution of river discharge, sea level rise, storm surge, waves runup and tides through the configured HEC-RAS hydraulic model with a simplified approach (compared to other methods) but in a computationally efficient way.

This methodology allows for the integration of a broader range of models used in the downscaling of global forcing conditions (Task 3.2, Deliverables 3.3 & 3.4), including:

- Wave modeling (WW3 - WaveWatch III) to assess offshore wave climate.
- Hydrological modeling (LISFLOOD) for precipitation-runoff processes and river discharges.
- Circulation and sea-level simulations (SHYFEM) to represent sea-level variability and storm surges.

Inputs: The methodology requires outputs from the downscaling procedure (D3.3 and 3.4), the extreme value analysis (D3.5 and 3.6) as boundary conditions of the hydraulic model.

Software/Computation Considerations: The hydraulic simulations were carried out with HEC-RAS (Hydrologic Engineering Center's River Analysis System) which is a widely used open-source hydraulic modeling software that allows users to perform one-dimensional (1D), two-dimensional (2D), and combined 1D/2D hydraulic analyses, making it a versatile tool for floodplain management. This methodology utilises a coupled 1D/2D approach. The 1D component was used to model the river stream, while the 2D component was applied to simulate the flooding area, with a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) of 2m resolution. Water can reach the flooding area either from the river, due to bank overflow, or from the sea, driven by the total sea level. For riverine flooding, the upstream boundary condition is defined by the river discharge, with values provided by the LISFLOOD hydrological model, and the downstream boundary condition is the sea level. In the case of coastal flooding, the total sea water level is calculated as the sum of storm surges, sea level, tides, and waves runup (from WW3 and SHYFEM outputs).

EBA Integration: The methodology has a focus on integrating Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBAs) into flood models to mitigate flood hazards, with particular emphasis on riverine floods, which have been identified as more prominent in our results, achieved via co-modeling sessions with the CCLs to ensure the design and implementation of EBAs were tailored to the specific

characteristics and needs of each city. Integrating EBA into flood management strategies, cities can reduce their vulnerability to flooding while promoting biodiversity, enhancing ecosystem services, and contributing to climate resilience.

CCLL Specific Outputs:

Oarsoaldea, Vilanova, Massa CCLL Case Studies: Using the simplified approach, short-term modelling was carried out for Oarsoaldea, Vilanova, Massa CCLLs, resulting in hazard maps available for different scenarios:

- historical (1956-2005)
- future (near future 2015-2065 and remote future 2045-2095)
- Hazard maps are created for two different RCP (Representative Concentration pathways): RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 and, for each scenario, coastal flood and riverine flood are modeled for 6 different return periods (5, 25, 50, 100, 200, 500 years), for a total of 60 maps for each frontrunner CCLL.

The results obtained from the model vary from one CCLL to another, highlighting the uniqueness of each city and emphasizing the importance of high-resolution urban-scale models:

- Vilanova: In Vilanova, while flooded areas show minor variations between scenarios, water depth is significantly higher in more pessimistic projections and increases with return periods. The city is protected from sea-induced flooding by a wall, but sandy beaches and their activities remain highly vulnerable to extreme coastal events.
- Oarsoaldea: In Oarsoaldea, future scenarios are associated with higher flow rates compared to historical conditions, and the RCP 4.5 scenario results in a more extensive flooded area than the RCP 8.5 scenario. Coastal flooding minimally affects the city, even under the highest return periods, due to the area's significant tidal excursions and the port's construction above mean sea level.
- Massa: Future scenarios suggest worsening riverine and coastal flooding, with RCP 8.5 showing a significantly larger flooded area than RCP 4.5. The urban area is especially vulnerable due to overflowing canals. Projections indicate that extreme coastal flooding could rival river floods, differing from trends in other cities.
- Samsun: The Samsun CCLL used a different methodology to that above. For consistency and simplicity, these activities will remain a separate entity. The Samsun CCLL tested the full adoption of the two "last-mile" models (HEC-RAS and XBeach) in the pilot area to develop flood maps. The downscaling methodologies in the Samsun case study differ from those used in the other three study cases as the others only used the HEC-RAS model.

Impact & Application: This output supports the development of flood management and climate adaptation plans by providing hazard maps for riverine and coastal flooding under various climate scenarios. These maps help local authorities identify high-risk zones, prioritize infrastructure, and implement zoning regulations. By using models based on future climate scenarios (RCPs), municipalities can plan more adaptive, long-term strategies. The integration of nature-based solutions (NBS) into hydraulic models offers practical, sustainable alternatives for flood mitigation, supporting more resilient urban planning. Consequently, the output may aid policymakers in securing funding and promoting ecosystem-based approaches. Its uptake can reduce the economic and social impacts of flooding while supporting sustainable urban environments. Environmental scientists and engineers benefit from the detailed data and maps, which can be used for spatial analysis, climate impact studies, and training programs focused on flood risk and resilience planning.

Title : Package of Statistical Tools & User Document for Coastal Erosion

- D3.9 - Package of models for the long-term evolution of the coastline: <https://zenodo.org/records/12598885>
- D3.10 – Users document for methods and models of the Long-Term coastline evolution: <https://zenodo.org/records/13960788>

Background : Understanding the long-term dynamics of the sea's impact on the coastline is crucial for effectively planning and managing coastal areas, particularly as climate change effects become more apparent. Shoreline retreat threatens economies, landscapes, and public safety, particularly on beaches with high seasonal populations. Coastal areas face multiple climate risks,

including sea level rise, extreme weather, and changing water quality. Sandy coasts are especially vulnerable, rapidly transforming due to storms and long-term shifts. Natural beaches act as buffers. Unfortunately, in many European coastal regions, their natural state has been significantly altered, leading to the loss of key coastal ecosystem components such as dunes and backshore vegetation. This degradation has heightened the vulnerability of coastal cities to erosion and storm-related damage. Assessing coastal erosion and the combined impact of storms over the coming decades is a complex challenge.

Solution: The SCORE project tackles this issue by utilising models that incorporate climate change scenarios generated through downscaling methodologies (D3.3 and 3.4). These scenarios are described by the variables downscaled to the specific location of interest, like water level projection or future wave height and direction. By leveraging these tools, the project seeks to deliver accurate and tailored predictions and develop effective adaptation strategies to reduce the impact of coastal erosion on urban areas. Long-term modeling, using downscaled dataset as initial and forcing condition, can improve disaster preparedness by assessing cost-effective adaptation strategies and supporting more informed urban planning to mitigate long-term climate risks. This KO aim to describe one aspect of long-term coastal modeling, which addresses shoreline evolution, both erosion or accretion, and identifies hotspots of coastal erosion, including the statistical tools & user-guide. The KO can enhance the coastal resilience, supporting the development of informed and collaborative strategies to address the complex challenges posed by coastal erosion and sea-level rise.

Challenges: Modeling coastal morpho-dynamic evolution (including erosion) over extended time scales presents significant challenges, notably:

- Drivers of coastal morpho-dynamic evolution:
- Coastal morpho-dynamics involve sediment transport and shoreline alterations.
- These changes result from hydrodynamic processes (like tides, waves, and currents) and geologic factors (such as cliff erosion, sediment supply, and fluvial inputs).
- Numerical Modeling Challenges:
- Achieving accurate simulations while managing computational effort is crucial.
- Increasing model resolution (more grid points) enhances accuracy but demands more computational resources. However, higher resolution also reduces the allowable time step for stability.
- Human Impact:
- Anthropogenic activities significantly affect coastal evolution. Hypothesis of future human actions are difficult to predict and to be included in a modelling system.
- Land reclamation, dam construction, and altered sediment supply impact ecosystems and morpho-dynamics.

Methodology: The methodology adopted in SCORE uses the downscaled wave data related to the different IPCC scenarios (namely RCP 8.5 and RCP 4.5) as input to coastal evolution models, which provide the shoreline long-term evolution. The latter is the most used indicator for monitoring coastal erosion and accretion, from present time to 2100.

Inputs:

- *Shoreline observations:* derived from existing surveys or remote mapping.
- *Wave hindcast and forecast data:* Wave height, period, and direction data come from the downscaling activities of the project (as reported in D3.3 and D3.4).
- No *bathymetric data* are required directly in the model, but a foreshore slope for each transect must be derived from existing bathymetric datasets of the study area.

Software: The software selected for this purpose is the COSMOS-COAST model developed by the US Geological Survey (USGS). COSMOS-COAST models coastal change due to a variety of oceanographic and terrestrial processes across a multitude of spatiotemporal scales. COSMOS-COAST is unique in the scientific community because it applies data assimilation to calibrate site-specific behaviour and characteristics into large-scale modeling applications.

In summary, the notable aspects of the model include:

- Accounts for long-shore and cross-shore sand transport and local trends

- Assimilation of historical shoreline observations to calibrate and validate the model
- Typically applied to project shoreline change on decadal to centennial time scales
- Run in an ensemble to better characterize uncertainty
- Model output is optionally .kml files, easily readable in Google Earth.

Outputs:

Fig.1 - In green 2020 shoreline position and transect along which the model evaluates shoreline erosion or accretion; In yellow modeled shoreline position in 2050; in red in 2100

CCLL Specific Outputs:

Benidorm, Massa and Dublin CCLL Case Studies (*selected because they have coastal erosion needs*): The overall methodology use open, state of the art software and tools. The ones created during the SCORE project, like pre or post-processing tools, are also open and reachable in the Zenodo platform (D3.9). Thanks to this, the methodology is scalable to the other CCLLs of the project, and in principle to many other futures cases. During the project this shoreline evolution tools were applied to the front runners CCLLs in this task, chosen by their vulnerability to the coastal erosion. This KO includes both the methodology and the specific CCLL results obtained.

Modeling the shoreline long-term evolution was performed in Benidorm and Massa CCLLs through COSMOS COAST model resulting in several shoreline maps at different steps for different scenarios:

- historical (1956 - 2005)
- future (2006 - 2100)

Shoreline future evolution has been modeled for two different RCP (Representative Concentration pathways): RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5. The results obtained from the model vary from one CCLL to another, highlighting the uniqueness not only of each city, but also of each single beach.

Benidorm: In Benidorm there are two different beaches (Levante and Poniente) which are quite different from one another. In 1991, a breakwater was constructed and 710,847 m³ of sand was artificially supplied through dredging on the east side of Poniente Beach to address the ongoing coastal erosion in the study area. This intervention resulted in a 70-meter increase in the beach's width and highly conditioned the natural beach dynamics. Nevertheless, the COSMOS-COAST model may be run in "continued accretion mode" to take into account the beach nourishments occurring during the calibration period, when the model performs the assimilation of the historical shoreline data.

In order to better model each beach, in the Benidorm area, two different models were tested, one for each beach. For Poniente Beach, 128 transects spaced approximately 20 meters apart were used, while 96 transects were used for Levante Beach. Since both beaches can be treated as closed systems, the first and last transects of each beach were considered as "cross-shore only" transects, to avoid accounting for long-shore transport to or from areas outside the beach. All other transects were treated as

"full model" transects, allowing for the evaluation of both cross-shore and long-shore transport. A baseline is set ("no-erodible" line) at the internal limit of the backshore, which can be set as a fixed line (shoreline can't cross it).

Benidorm CCLL data includes:

- Shoreline long-term evolution dataset and processing results,
- morpho-dynamic evolution model outputs.

On Poniente Beach, the western part appears to be the area most affected by future erosion. However, potential effects of diffraction at the ends of the beach, which have not yet been considered in this phase, may influence these results. Conversely, the eastern part shows a trend of accretion, but this could also be influenced by diffraction effects, warranting further investigation. For Levante Beach, the maximum expected shoreline retreat in the coming years is also projected on the western side. Despite these considerations, the results align well with the wave climate, as waves in this area are expected more frequently to come from the east.

Massa: At Marina di Massa, the area suffers from a systematic lack of sediment supply. The prevailing potential sediment transport, directed towards the south, is largely hindered by the presence of the port of Carrara and, more generally, from all the basins located further north. In recent years, an ongoing and costly beach nourishment program has been carried out annually since 2017, involving the addition of more than 400,000 cubic meters of sediment each year.

In the Massa area, two different implementations of the model were tested: one (a) focused on the southern coastal area with fewer coastal defenses, and the other (b) included the area with groins and breakwaters. Since the individual beach cells between two groins can be treated as closed systems, the first and last transects of each cell were considered as "cross-shore only" transects, to avoid accounting for longshore transport to or from adjacent cells. All other transects were treated as "full model" transects, allowing for the evaluation of both cross-shore and long-shore transport.

Available **Massa** CCLL data includes:

- Shoreline long-term evolution dataset and processing results,
- beach video surveillance data through webcam system,
- morpho-dynamic evolution model outputs

Despite some uncertainty, it is evident that the parameters associated with the transect in the area with man-made coastal defenses exhibit a more stable evolution compared to others. This stability is due to the reduced morphodynamic changes within the "cells" (areas between two groins).

The erosion trend observed outside the cells is characteristic of this coastal area, which is known for experiencing significant erosion. The long-term model indicates that this erosion trend will likely continue, influenced by the projected wave climate under the RCP8.5 scenario and the hypothesized Sea Level Rise (SLR).

Dublin: In the Dublin CCLL, a different approach has been adopted. A study of coastline changes in the Dublin area, stretching from Dún Laoghaire Harbour to the northern Dublin Bay has been carried out, aimed primarily to assess the contribution of satellite data processing algorithms within the GEE framework to advance understanding of these phenomena. The package includes coastal evolution modelling, satellite past analysis and related results.

The Dublin area experienced several coastal flooding events, which have caused severe impacts in the past. The future sea level in the North Atlantic and along the Atlantic coasts of the UK and Ireland is projected to rise by nearly 1 m under RCP 8.5 and, with a projected increase in the intensity and magnitude of extreme storms, this will increase coastal damage. Predicted changes in SLR will be the primary factors in magnifying the impacts of wave patterns and changing storm surges in urban coastal areas.

Available **Dublin** CCLL data includes:

- dataset and processing results

- Re: Shoreline evolution

Satellite imagery (Landsat and Sentinel-2) has been pre-processed and analyzed through Google Earth Engine's platform, ensuring accurate coastline detection. Water/land classification was performed through advanced algorithms classifying imagery into water, enhancing the accuracy change detection. Historical analysis for Dublin coastline presents 63% of transects classified as erosional shoreline (mainly in the northern part of the area) while 26% are accretional shoreline, altogether illustrating that the present focused area is suffering from erosion conditions.

Impact & Application:

This KO provides an analysis of the future trends of coastal erosion, starting from shoreline evolution of the recent years.

- This data gives a critical insight into the coastal erosion risk and may help local authorities and municipalities to prioritise infrastructures investments taking care of the most vulnerable areas in the present and in the future scenarios of coastal erosion risk.
- It allows to adequately evaluate the shoreline changes also considering the different conditions due to changes in sediment transport, river supplies, and sea-level rise, and make use of historical shoreline datasets, derived from satellite or from in-situ monitoring, which become an effective input in a long-term perspective.
- The KO also provides a way to evaluate if the planned measures may produce the desired effect in coastal erosion management in the long-term period.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: As the work within work package three is cumulative, all WP3 KERs and KOs are relevant to the overall story and potential of the knowledge outputs.

Priority Target User A: Public Sector Entities with the relevant CCLs

Public sector entities tasked with developing and implementing climate adaptation strategies. These entities play a crucial role in managing the impacts of climate change, particularly flooding and coastal erosion, on urban areas and their communities.

For the Flood Models, CCLs Massa, Oarsoaldea, Vilanova and Samsun are a priority:

- Massa: Municipality of Massa, Province of Massa Carrara, Authority of Bacino, ARPAT, Municipal Union, Regione Toscana
- Oarsoaldea: Oarsoaldea Development Agency Management Board, communications and tourism departments, Eusko Jaurlaritz - Basque Country government agencies (Emergency & Meteorology Manag./Euskalmet Meteo. Agency, URA - Water Agency), Gipuzkoako Foru Aldundia (province government) Environmental Department, Ministry of Environment Servicio Provincial de Costas de Gipuzkoa, Ministry of Transport and Mobility Pasaia Port authority
- Vilanova: Vilanova City Council, Calafell City Council, Sitges City Council, ACA - Catalan Water Agency, Barcelona Provincial Council, Catalan Climate Change Office, Natural Park of Garraf, Natural and coastal environment service (Garraf County Council), DG Coasts, Gencat, DG Coast and Sea, Ministry for Ecological Transition, Spanish Government
- Samsun: Samsun Governorship, Samsun Municipality, Samsun Provincial Directorate of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change, State Hydraulic Works Samsun Office, Provincial Directorate of National Education, Disaster And Emergency Management Presidency.
- Benidorm: Area Ingenieria Civil del Ayuntamiento (Town Hall Civil Engineering Area), Town Hall Beach Area, Local Police of Benidorm, Smart Office (Distrito Digital), General Directorate of Coasts
- Dublin: Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council, Smart Dún Laoghaire (Innovation Collaborator Group), Local Authority Waters Programme (LAWPRO), Dublin Bay Biosphere Partnership, Office of Public Works (OPW), Geological Survey Ireland (GSI), Irish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Ministry of Environment, Climate and Communications.

Specific Examples.

- *Role:* These entities are primarily responsible for urban planning, land management, coastal risk protection, emergency response, and the development and implementation of local climate adaptation and resilience plans. They are the decision-makers regarding infrastructure investments, zoning regulations, and guiding urban development, as well as managing natural infrastructure and advocating for funding for adaptation measures. They also manage various services such as water management, environmental protection, and disaster risk reduction.
- *Key Message:* These outputs provide scientific information and tools that directly assist in preparing and developing flood and coastal erosion management plans and local climate adaptation strategies in the short-medium and long-term. The KOs deliver critical insights through hazard maps and future projections, identifying high-risk areas under various climate scenarios. The flood hazard maps are essential for risk assessment and evaluation, while the analysis of future coastal erosion trends helps prioritize investments in vulnerable areas.
- *Awareness:* Knowledge transfer sessions have occurred with the CCLLs conducted by the technical leads within SCORE, however, widespread knowledge of these outputs will be limited.
- *Level of Understanding:* The outputs as developed for the public sector and municipal partners are relatively intuitive, but for meaningful implementation, the support of technicians within the climate and planning departments will be necessary.
- *Interest:* This target user is likely actively seeking information related to the KO because they need data-driven climate resilience strategies and require precise downscaled datasets for their roles in climate adaptation and urban planning. However, human resources to utilise and political will to implement such results will vary based on the regions.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 1 – 2 – Conception

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 3 – Engagement

Project Activities within SCORE that increased impact as it pertains to your KER

Local Engagement and Data Collection: Throughout the project, both in-person and online meetings were held with local stakeholders across several CCLLs. These interactions were crucial for gathering in-situ data, sensor outputs, and local reports, all of which helped refine the modelling methods and ensure local relevance. These engagements also supported co-creation efforts and fostered trust among stakeholders.

Knowledge Transfer and Stakeholder Engagement: Knowledge Transfer (KT) sessions were held in multiple CCLLs, including Massa, Vilanova, Sligo, Oarsoaldea, and Benidorm. These sessions brought together municipal policymakers, technical staff, and other CCLL stakeholders to introduce the tools, explain their applications, and discuss potential use in local planning. These KT events played a key role in contextualising the outputs and encouraging their future uptake.

Tool Testing and Validation: The coastal erosion model was applied in Benidorm, Dublin, and Massa, enabling site-specific analysis of shoreline change. The short-term hazard modelling component was tested in Massa, Vilanova, Oarsoaldea, and Samsun, using downscaled parameters tailored to local conditions.

External Engagement

The WP3 overarching results, particularly in the areas of coastal erosion and short-term hazard modelling, have been presented to external municipalities, such as Pisa, Italy, where the tools and findings received strong interest. This early engagement indicates significant potential for wider uptake of the methodology among coastal cities facing similar challenges.

Furthermore, tools and methodologies linked to this KER have been made publicly accessible via the Zenodo platform. Key deliverables such as [D3.7: Package of Short-Term Hazard Modelling](#) and [D3.8: User Document for the Short-Term Hazard Modelling](#) are now openly available for download and reuse, supporting transparency and knowledge sharing.

Publications:

- Peer-reviewed publication: [link](#)
- Preprint: [link](#)

Conferences:

- EGU General Assemblies 2024 and 2025 (EGU24, EGU25): Oral presentation: [link](#); Oral presentation: [link](#)
- The 52nd International Liège Colloquium on Ocean Dynamics

Other Knowledge Transfer Measures:

- Geostories: <https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/catalogue/#/geostory/5851>
- Webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hg3zuZdhfR8&t=3618s>
- News: <https://www.voceapuana.com/attualita/2025/02/28/cambiamenti-climatici-massa-protagonista-del-progetto-score-soluzioni-innovative/86534/>
- News: <https://www.lanazione.it/massa-carrara/cronaca/cambiamenti-climatici-progetto-score-entra-9a9a62ff>
- The Kickoff Meeting of the AMIS Project ([Interreg Maritime](#))
- Internal scientific seminars hosted by CNR, including activities coordinated by the CNR IBBR ([CNR dissemination portal](#))
- Showcase on the [Horizon Results Platform](#)

Future Impact and Opportunities

The methodology behind the KER, while powerful, is not a simple plug-and-play tool. It involves technically advanced modelling, neural network tuning, and high computational demands that most municipalities are not equipped to handle in-house. For this reason, it is more viable to offer it as a service rather than an open-source product. LaMMA, with its core expertise and role in developing several of SCORE's key outputs, is uniquely suited to provide this service through a professional and sustainable model.

To bring this vision to scale, additional funding, partnerships, and infrastructure will be essential. Upcoming opportunities like the PRIMA-MED call on water management are particularly well-aligned with this KER (a proposal is being developed by locally relevant SCORE partners). These collaborations not only provide strong foundations for case study expansion but also demonstrate proof-of-concept to new stakeholders.

A comprehensive service package is recommended to be built around four main components:

1. Provision of Highly Localised Climate Projections: Transforming coarse-scale global or regional climate data into fine-resolution outputs tailored for specific urban environments. Using advanced downscaling techniques, including dynamic, statistical, and neural network models, this service would generate highly granular climate datasets (e.g., sea level rise, rainfall, wave patterns) essential for evidence-based adaptation planning.
2. Urban Flood Risk Assessment and Mapping: Creating detailed hazard maps for riverine and coastal flooding under both current and future climate scenarios (e.g., RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5). These maps, based on simulations across different return periods, allow authorities to identify critical risk zones and prioritise investments, zoning changes, or infrastructure upgrades.
3. Long-Term Coastal Erosion Analysis: Using historical shoreline data and future climate projections, this component evaluates erosion and accretion trends up to 2100. With models like COSMOS-COAST and satellite data integration, municipalities can identify erosion hotspots and assess the long-term effectiveness of planned interventions.
4. Evaluation of Adaptation Measures, Including Nature-Based Solutions (NBS): Applying modelling tools to assess how various adaptation options, especially EBAs, would perform under different hazard scenarios. This supports evidence-based decision-making on sustainable flood defences and integrates ecological considerations into infrastructure planning.

To deliver these services, LaMMA could adopt several business model approaches:

- Project-Based Consulting: Tailored assessments and planning tools delivered as defined consulting projects for municipalities or regional agencies.
- Retainer or Subscription Models: Ongoing services like updated data delivery, periodic re-modelling, and access to online platforms for visualizing outputs.

- Training and Capacity Building: Structured training programs to upskill municipal staff in interpreting and applying climate and risk data.
- Strategic Partnerships: Collaborations with engineering firms, urban planners, and other research institutions to integrate climate risk insights into broader development strategies.

KER 7.4 - Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping of Public Perceptions of Climate Change in Irish and Spanish Coastal City Living Labs

Knowledge Owners: ATU, ENT

Current Status: Open Access publication: [Public Perceptions of Climate Risks, Vulnerability and Adaptation Strategies: Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping in Irish and Spanish Living Labs - ScienceDirect](#)

Description: As Europe faces 'extremely high' climate risks, being the fastest warming continent on the planet, it is crucial to invest in effective climate adaptation strategies to protect vulnerable communities. Despite this, limited studies have explored the effects of climate risks on human lives, due to the assumption that European countries have sufficient adaptive capacity and socioeconomic resources. This has hindered policymaking, as lack of data fosters uncertainty and inefficiency.

Using qualitative tools (surveys & Interviews), the KO explores the public perceptions of climate change in two Coastal City Living Labs (Oarsoaldea, Spain (97 participants) and Sligo, Ireland (68 participants)). Participants were selected based on their knowledge of climate change and/or their exposure to climate risks. The data collected was analysed using Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping and tools such as bubble plots, heatmaps, graphs, and representations of the qualitative data.

The objective of this research is to:

- Increase awareness about the increasing levels of climate vulnerability and inequality based on socioeconomic factors such as gender, age, education, income and nationality even in richer European countries
- Gather and share information on the levels of citizen awareness and engagement with existing local climate strategies, and how this effects their success, as well as methods to improve engagement.
- Improving understanding of the day-to-day impacts of climate risks, and understanding how this experience shapes eco-friendly behaviours, especially willingness to engage in climate action.
- Understanding the role of socioeconomic co-benefits associated with climate strategies, and whether these improve public willingness to try out new strategies such as NBS.
- Creating systematic maps of the complex socioeconomic relationships and illustrating how different factors affect each other, as part of a systems analysis to inform adaptation planning.

Outcomes: The socioeconomic vulnerability of the 2 CCLLs, yielded similar trends despite differences in regional socioeconomic conditions. Notable trends:

- Low-income groups, women, and minority groups tend to feel more at risk for climate change challenges (when compared to their peers)
- Local populations in both regions had limited faith in and awareness of local policymaking
- Local populations showed an increasing willingness to adopt nature-based solutions due their multiple co-benefits.
- Positive correlation was found between those who have experienced climate risks and a belief in climate change and willingness to engage in climate action. Notably, most respondents underestimated the willingness of their community to engage in climate action, but were willing to contribute resources and time to it.

Methodology: Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping

Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs) are a tool that allow the capturing and modelling the behaviour of qualitative system dynamics. FCM's illustrations integrates data from multiple stakeholders to develop an integrated and cross-sectoral understanding of complex concepts and societal dynamics as part of a larger comprehensive systems analysis. The figure below shows the key FCM illustration of this study.

Figure 12. Fuzzy Cognitive Map of Climate Adaptation (based on interviews from both regions).

The key recommendations are:

- Although large scale environmental models and government initiatives are working towards filling data gaps in our understanding of climate risks, **empirical knowledge based in community interactions has been limited**. Increased use of participatory and systems-based approaches can help fill this knowledge gap in adaptation planning.
- Within Europe, cross-region comparisons and causal analyses of community perceptions of climate policies have been limited. These comparisons can offer innovative insights on how different communities and regions cope with risk, adding agency to public policy.
- This research proves that statistical data on climate risks alone is not sufficient for effective policymaking, as personal human experience plays a huge role in shaping the way climate change impacts communities. Empirical knowledge is necessary to verify and complement numerical models, and policymakers must focus on gathering empirical data for effective policymaking.
- This research showcases that even in wealthy European nations like Ireland and Spain, certain socioeconomic groups (such as immigrants) are still more vulnerable based on factors like income, gender, nationality, age, profession, and education, and local policy must target these groups.
- Some livelihoods, and thereby sections of society, are more affected by climate risks. Respondents in Ireland felt more vulnerable as there was a greater number of citizens whose livelihoods or day-to-day lives were affected. In comparison, respondents in regions with statistically higher climate vulnerability (such as Spain in our study) felt less vulnerable since their livelihoods were not directly impacted and/or they have greater authority, resources, and knowledge to deal with climate risks. This showcases the importance of identifying and engaging with the most impacted and vulnerable communities. This also demonstrates the need to improve awareness and reduce uncertainty amongst and offer greater autonomy to affected communities. These issues must be prioritised in policymaking.
- Existing political systems and lack of political will makes it challenging for citizens to take meaningful action. Systems approaches considered in this study offer insights into these complex dynamics, illuminating the relationships between different elements as part of the larger picture, to improve adaptive capacity for vulnerable communities. The trends and insights highlighted as part of FCM can offer important policy implications.
- Better regional mapping of risks and contextualising adaptation issues is necessary to improve social justice. Developing strategies (i.e., Nature based solutions) that have socioeconomic co-benefits is increasingly important for effective adaptation.

- Local knowledge and experiences are pivotal to co-creating adaptation policies. Although this is resource consuming, statistical data has indicated the immense potential damage and loss expected without effective adaptation policy. Policymakers must prioritise this.

Impact & Application: The knowledge generated can be used during and after SCORE to improve resilience in the regions, improve stakeholder and citizen engagement, improve existing climate strategies and adaptation efforts, as well as improve data on the current experiences of climate risks as well as socioeconomic vulnerability.

The local municipalities in both living lab regions can use the results to improve engagement with the public on climate policy, and work on co-creating more effective climate policies. This data can also be used by local living lab teams as well as researchers in Spain, Ireland, and beyond to improve understanding of climate vulnerability and public experiences of climate risks in European and other regions.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: N/A

Priority Target User A: Academics and Researchers

Academics (Social science researchers; behavioural psychologists; environmental psychologists; NbS practitioners; researchers studying citizen/public engagement with climate policymaking or policy researchers; etc.) and environmental scientists focusing on climate change adaptation, as well as environmental researchers that could use this methodology in their own contexts.

- Role:** These target users are likely conducting their research on climate adaptation within communities. Any academics/researchers interested in understanding stakeholder perceptions for better implementation of NBS or climate strategies in general would find this methodology useful.
- Key Message:** This KO provides a step to better understanding the needs and perspectives of communities as they will be impacted by a changing climate. This understanding can in turn be used to improve resilience in the studied regions, improve stakeholder and citizen engagement, improve existing climate strategies and adaptation efforts, as well as improve data on the current experiences of climate risks as well as socioeconomic vulnerability. Overall, its insights provide an opportunity for academics to connect more meaningfully with communities.
- Awareness:** *Medium to high. There should be minimal need to educate academics who work within this field on how to utilise this KO. The content is readable and accessible, and the methodology is well known in academic space.*
- Level of Understanding:** Users should have the technical understanding of the challenges that local communities will be facing because of the changing climate. However, these researchers may not have a full understanding of the community's perspective on these issues. As such, this KO will provide them with an opportunity to appreciate that climate change will impact communities differently, and this can better inform their own research.
- Interest:** These users should have an interest in understanding public perceptions of climate risks, vulnerability and adaptation, and are interested in specifically learning about these regional case studies. They could also use this paper as an example if they are repeating this same methodology within their own contexts, as Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping is a methodology used commonly in this field.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 1 – Conception

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 2 - Discovery

External Engagement

This study is available as an open Access publication: [Public Perceptions of Climate Risks, Vulnerability, and Adaptation Strategies: Fuzzy Cognitive Mapping in Irish and Spanish Living Labs - ScienceDirect](#). The results from this work were presented at LITTORAL 2024 and at the Living Lab Health and Wellbeing Symposium (2024). Additionally, the results from the Sligo case study were presented to the Sligo County Council at an information session in November 2024, to present the key takeaways.

to the local decisionmakers and interested community members. Finally, this study has been shared on the [Horizon Results Platform](#).

Future Impact and Opportunities

The two CCLLs will be able to draw on the findings of this study to inform future research and policymaking efforts. In Sligo, the County Council plans to use the outputs to better understand the needs and perspectives of the public, sparking deeper discussion and collaboration that will help refine and strengthen local climate strategies. ATU is also building upon this work, using it to improve stakeholder engagement with the CCLL's objectives, both within and beyond the scope of SCORE. The influence of the research is already visible. The EU ProClimate project, which has also established a Living Lab in Sligo, is actively integrating these findings and will continue the Living Lab's activities after the conclusion of SCORE.

To support knowledge sharing and local engagement, the key recommendations and outputs should be made available as concise summaries for inclusion in the GeoStories of both the Sligo and Oarsoaldea CCLLs. It is also recommended that Oarsoaldea CCLL organise a dedicated session with its stakeholder networks to present and discuss the main findings, as was done in Sligo CCLL. Particular attention should be given to sharing the results with the University of Pais Vasco in Bilbao, which expressed strong interest in the study during its implementation. GAIA, as one of the research partners of key Oarsoaldea CCLL stakeholders, is already drawing on these results and is currently drafting a policy brief to support further uptake and application of the insights generated.

KO #	Title	Description
KO1.1	Mapping of baseline exposure and risks of climate change impacts on SCORE's Coastal Cities Living Labs	This KO is composed of several high-level (i.e., high resolution) baseline maps outlining the risks faced by each of SCORE's ten coastal cities living labs to the extreme impacts of sea level rise and climate-related events (i.e., coastal erosion, coastal flooding, land flooding, landslides, heatwaves, cold spells, strong winds, droughts, heavy rainfall, heavy snowfall) due to climate change. The methodology to develop these models is not novel or unique to SCORE, however, it is a necessary first step in the further development of climate adaptation strategies. The maps are used to outline climate-change-related hazards in an easily digestible way for each CCLL.
KO3.1	Procedural Guide for Identifying and Using Climate and Marine Data Services and Datasets for Baseline Characterization and Projections	This KO provides users with procedures and sample data on climate and marine conditions suitable for characterising current climate conditions and making future projections, with a specific focus on coastal cities. This Knowledge Output aims to support the SCORE project by identifying and recommending appropriate climate services and datasets across Europe. It outlines the key criteria for selecting relevant data—such as user needs, spatial and temporal resolution, accessibility, and available documentation—tailored to the needs of the CCLLs. In addition, it provides practical, step-by-step guidance on how to access and use these datasets through specific use cases. The document also includes a detailed overview of selected datasets, covering their usability, structure, interfaces, formats, and metadata to help users navigate and apply the data effectively.
KO 3.3	Package for the statistical analysis tools, data and user-guide for urban-scale models.	The package provides tools, procedures, and a user guide to generate tailored data for urban-scale models. These models simulate key aspects of city systems—such as infrastructure, environment, and population dynamics—and are essential for assessing urban vulnerability to climate change. Focusing on extreme value analysis (EVA) and hydraulic modelling, the KO supports flood mapping and risk assessments at the local scale. This makes it a valuable resource for disaster preparedness and coastal resilience planning.

KO3.6	Testing Package & User Document to Improve Coastal Hazard Assessment & Long-Term Shortline Evolution.	Coastal cities are at the forefront of climate change impacts that endanger their infrastructure, ecosystems, and communities. Rising sea levels, more intense storm events, coastal erosion, and urban flooding required immediate, data-driven solutions. Addressing these complex issues, predictive models and tools have been developed (in WP3 tasks) to analyse short- and long-term evolution of the coastline and flood scenarios. This KO integrates the developed findings, models, and tools to establish a final set of cohesive tools, aimed at testing and validating the models' effectiveness in simulating real-world conditions and supporting decision-making in coastal risk management.
-------	---	---

3.3. Green & Technological Tools for Climate Adaptation Strategies

Effective climate adaptation strategies must integrate green approaches with innovative technology. We need comprehensive solutions like those in SCORE that blend nature-based solutions, with tools to help us visualise and understand our adaptation options.

KER 6.2 – Risk Characterisation Methodology for the Development of Semi-Quantitative, Comparable Indices

Knowledge Owners : RedRisk

Current Status: Public, Open Access as part of D6.1
<https://zenodo.org/records/13960883>

Description: Cities are exposed to multiple natural hazards with different characteristics, intensities and frequencies, which makes it difficult to assess and compare the risk and impact associated with the various hazards. This KO addresses the need for comprehensive yet easily understood risk assessment frameworks capable of handling the complexities of these urban environments, which are exposed to a range of natural hazards. This KO's objective is to define a methodology to be used for a quick assessment of the impacts of risks in coastal cities and to provide a classification of the SCORE CCLLs in terms of their exposure to natural risks. The methodology combines different sources of information on hazards, exposure, and vulnerabilities to create semi-quantitative indices. Specifically, the indices are derived from the combination of several variables, notably the hazards, their probability and intensity, the assets they affect, and the locality's vulnerability to the hazard. The output is semi-quantitative indices that allow for comparative analysis among the cities (e.g., which CCLL/city has a high likelihood for heat waves), as well as an understanding as to why certain risks are prevalent (e.g., why is coast flood risk significant in this city). Index-based approaches are not new, but the novelty here is the comparability between cities and the ease through which they can be understood by both scientific and non-technical stakeholders.

Open Data Sources: One of the significant strengths of this methodology and indices is the utilisation of openly available data sources, making the methodology replicable and accessible.

Value: The methodology is relatively quick and straightforward, thus being suitable for a light, non-data-intensive risk assessment whose purposes are to define priorities and identify critical situations worthy of a deeper, more detailed assessment. This then can lead to more effective and tailored risk reduction strategies or resource (re)allocation.

CCLL Specific Outputs:

CCLL-specific data available as part of Deliverable 6.1: (In PDF format. The underlying geospatial data can be provided on request)

- Exposure maps: Population, land cover, road and railway networks
- Hazard maps: Fluvial flooding, coastal flooding, landslide, coastal erosion

- Risk scores for fluvial flooding, coastal flooding, extreme precipitation, landslide, heat wave, and coastal erosion (overall and disaggregated by exposure type when applicable)

CCLL-specific data not explicitly included in Deliverable 6.1:

- Potential impact index maps (for applicable perils): Population, residential buildings, economic activities, road and railway networks. Should CCLLs require additional visualisation pertaining to this data, they can contact RedRisk.

Impact & Application:

1. **Informed Decision-Making for Public Sector:** The primary impact is that it provides public sector with valuable insights into the risks/hazards associated with the coastal cities. This information enables more informed and data-driven decision-making. Public entities, for example, can use this data to allocate resources for risk mitigation and disaster preparedness effectively.
2. **Risk Management:** The report and methodology are essential tools for developing and enhancing risk management strategies. It allows stakeholders to identify high-risk areas, vulnerable assets, and specific hazards that need attention. This, in turn, helps in prioritizing risk reduction efforts and emergency response planning.
3. **Resource Allocation:** By understanding the risks, stakeholders can allocate resources efficiently. They can focus on areas with the highest risk profiles and direct funding and resources to measures that will have the most significant impact in reducing risks.
4. **Insurance and Financial Planning:** For insurance companies and financial institutions, this methodology can be used to assess the risk landscape and determine suitable insurance coverage and financial products. It aids in understanding potential liabilities and pricing insurance policies effectively.

Linked Knowledge Outputs:

- KO6.1 - Exposure database and vulnerability curves for the Coastal City Living Labs, Massa, Vilanova and Oarsoaldea
- KER 6.3 - Risk profiles & risk assessment tool for Oarsoaldea, Massa, and Vilanova Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL)

Priority Target User A: Public Sector / Policymakers (European coastal municipality, or regional authorities)

Local/regional authorities are central stakeholders in coastal cities as they are responsible for risk management, emergency response, land-use planning, environmental protection plans, etc. within their respective cities/regions.

- *Role:* Public authorities can better understand the climate-related risks and hazards facing their coastal cities, enabling them to make informed, data-driven decisions. This approach supports efficient resource allocation, ensuring that efforts are targeted where they will have the greatest impact in mitigating and managing those risks.
- *Key Message:* This approach equips public authorities with clear, data-driven insights into the risks and hazards facing coastal cities, enabling smarter, evidence-based decision-making. It supports the development of robust risk management strategies by identifying vulnerable areas and prioritising risk reduction and emergency planning. Ultimately, it ensures more efficient allocation of resources, directing investment where it will have the greatest impact on protecting communities and infrastructure.
- *Awareness:* It is unlikely that the target users are specifically aware of this specific methodology, but they likely will be aware of the need for risk characterisation as it relates to risk management and resource allocation.
- *Level of Understanding:* Likely the relevant departments (i.e., environmental planning, land use, etc.) within the local authority will have the technical knowledge to understand the methodology. Additionally, the final semi-quantitative indices are designed to be easily digestible by policymakers needing to make decisions on this topic and citizens wanting to weigh in.

- *Interest:* As climate change becomes increasingly impactful in our cities, appetite for such indices will become increasingly necessary and required by public sector planners. However, the political parties interests and views on climate adaptation may impact the likelihood for uptake.

Priority Target User B: Academics & Research Institutions

Specific Examples: Researchers and academics in fields such as environmental science, urban planning, and risk management are interested in the methodology and findings for further study and research. This data can contribute to advancing scientific knowledge

- *Role:* Using the methodology and findings for further study and research. The data and methodology are seen as contributing to advancing scientific knowledge and increasing the study and research area in relevant fields like environmental science, urban planning, and risk management. The novelty of KO 6.2, which lies in the comparability of risk indices between cities and the ease with which they can be understood by both scientific and non-technical stakeholders, makes it particularly interesting for academic study.
- *Key Message:* Providing opportunities for the public sector and policymakers to better understand climate-related risks in an easy-to-digest manner supports building a bridge between research and implementation. Researchers must consider the users and their needs so the work can be impactful.
- *Awareness:* Likely they are unaware of this specific KO, but the idea of developing risk indices is well known.
- *Level of Understanding:* Academics in relevant fields should have no issue understanding this output.
- *Interest:* We anticipate interest to be high due as climate adaptation is a high-priority research field.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 2 – Discovery

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 3 – Engagement

Project Activities within SCORE that increased impact as it pertains to your KER

- Activities within the CCLLs directly enabled the practical application and impact of the KO6.2 risk assessment methodology. By collecting and applying open-access hazard and exposure data, each of the ten SCORE CCLLs received tailored outputs, including hazard and exposure maps and risk scores across six climate hazards. Financial risk categorisation offered strategic guidance for managing fluvial and coastal flooding risks. The application of the methodology was conducted across all 10 CCLLs. The resulting risk scores and their analysis for each CCLL are presented as the outcome of this application.
- As part of WP6, dedicated Knowledge Transfer sessions were conducted with the frontrunner CCLLs to ensure a deep understanding of the methodologies, tools, and concepts developed, particularly around risk assessment and financial resilience. These sessions aimed to build capacity within the CCLLs, enabling them to effectively interpret, apply, and communicate the results in local planning contexts. Additional sessions with the fellow CCLLs, coordinated in collaboration with WP3, expanded the reach of these efforts by raising awareness of the benefits and applicability of such services and technologies. This strategic engagement helped foster a shared knowledge base across all CCLLs, supporting wider adoption and long-term impact.

External Engagement

Publications:

- Figueiredo, R., Rangel-Parra, R., Bussi, G., Ceresa, P., Coccia, G., and Martina, M. L. V. (2024). A semi-quantitative multi-hazard risk assessment framework for European coastal urban areas. *Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk*, 15(1). doi:10.1080/19475705.2024.2378994

Other Knowledge Transfer Measures:

- KT sessions with CCLLs have been completed.
- [SCORE Webinar: Risk modeling and its role in designing strategies to increase financial resilience](#)
- Development and sharing of CCLL Case Studies & testimony, disseminated via the SCORE website: [Smart Spending for Safer Shores: How Vilanova is Using Data to Boost Climate Resilience](#)
- Inclusion on the [Horizon Results Platform](#)
- Displaying CCLL-specific results on CCLL StoryMaps.
- CCLL partners are encouraged to directly email the outputs to relevant internal departments (e.g., Environmental Planning, Risk Management) within their local or regional administrations.
- Promotion on SCORE's social media channels.

Future Impact and Opportunities

CCLLs to distribute to priority stakeholders within their community. The priority stakeholders for Vilanova i la Geltrú, Massa, and Oarsoaldea CCLLs are primarily government organisations at the local, regional, and national levels. Here is a specific list of government organisations identified as stakeholders for these CCLLs:

Vilanova i la Geltrú

- **Local Level:** Gava City Council, Calafell City Council, Sitges City Council
- **Regional Level:** ACA - Catalan Water Agency [Agencia Catalana del Agua], Gencat, Barcelona Provincial Council [Diputació de Barcelona], Catalan Climate Change Office [Oficina Catalana de Cambio Climatico (Gencat)], Natural Park of Garraf [Parque Natural del Garraf], DG Coasts, Gencat, Natural and coastal environment service (Garraf County Council); Sustainable Development Advisory Council of Catalonia (SADS); Generalitat de Catalunya
- **National Level:** DG Coast and Sea, Ministry for Ecological Transition, Spanish Government

Massa

- **Local Level:** Municipality of Massa; ARPAT; Authority of Bacino; Carrara Municipality; Montignoso Municipality; Municipal Union; Port Authority; Province of Massa Carrara
- **Regional Level:** Tuscany Region Settore Difesa del Suolo

Oarsoaldea

- **Local Level:** Blas de Lezo (Vocational training school); Tknika - Vocational training school; Local government (4 municipalities); Oarsoaldea Development Agency Management Board, communications and tourism departments)
- **Regional Level:** AZTI - Marine Science & Technology; BC3 - Basque Centre for Climate Change; EHU/UPV - University of Basque Country; Aranzadi Zientzia Elkarte - Science Association; CEDEX - Public Works Studies & Experimentation; Tecnalia - Science & Technology; University of Deusto; Eusko Jaurlaritza - Basque Country government BASQUETOUR - Tourism Agency; Eusko Jaurlaritza - Basque Country government Emergency & Meteorology Manag./Euskalmet Meteo. Agency; Gipuzkoako Foru Aldundia (province government) Environmental Department; IHOBE - Environmental Agency
- **National Level:** Ministry of Economy Consorcio de Compensación de Seguros; Ministry of Environment Servicio Provincial de Costas de Gipuzkoa; Ministry of Transport and Mobility Pasaia Port authority; Naturklima - Climate Change Foundation

Knowledge Owners : RedRisk	Current Status: Open Access, linked with D6.4 – D6.7 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D6.4 Residual risk assessment report for the frontrunner CCLs • D6.5 Risk profiles for the frontrunner CCLs • D6.6 Historical 'as-if' cash flow diagrams according to all strategies developed • D6.7 Financial strategies selection tool
<p>Description: Coastal cities are particularly exposed to hydro-meteorological and climate-related natural hazards, particularly flooding. Flood risk reduction and management activities require adequate knowledge about the probabilities and potential consequences of flood events based on a probabilistic risk assessment framework, which encompasses models of flood hazard for different climate scenarios, exposed elements, and vulnerability.</p> <p>Risk Profiles & Risk Assessment Methodology:</p> <p>In this context, the KO provides quantitative risk assessments for coastal and fluvial flooding for Massa (Italy), Oarsoaldea (Spain) and Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain) Coastal City Living Labs (CCLL). The assessments are based on the state-of-the-art methodology for quantitative physical risk assessments, combining hazard, exposure, and vulnerability components. The risk assessments cover four types of exposed elements, namely population, buildings, roads, and railways, for coastal and fluvial flooding; associated with five different climate scenarios (i.e., historical baseline, and RCP (Representative Concentration Pathways) 4.5 and RCP 8.5 for two different timeframes).</p> <p>These risk assessments provide an overview of the impacts of pre-selected ecosystem-based approaches (EBAs) for the mitigation of fluvial flood hazard. Allowing users to understand the impact that climate change is expected to have on flood risk, and the influence that specific EBAs can have in reducing fluvial flood risk from a baseline to an improved infrastructural condition (i.e., residual risk) in these CCLs.</p> <p>Input Data Required: Hazard maps, exposure datasets, vulnerability models</p> <p>Novelty: The methodology follows the state-of-the-art, but the results are the novelty for the CCLs.</p> <p>Outputs (in PDF form):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimated affected population counts and economic losses for buildings and road and railway networks for all considered return periods. • Average annual affected population counts and average annual losses for buildings and road and railway networks. • Annual exceedance probability curves for population affected and economic losses. <p>The outputs are available for the five climate scenarios mentioned above, both for coastal flooding and fluvial flooding (the latter with and without EBA implementation).</p> <p>Risk Assessment Tool: In the field of climate resilience and strategy planning, there is always uncertainty regarding the magnitude and timing of these unexpected events. To develop comprehensive financial risk plans, probability simulations are run and multiple financial strategies can be outlined accordingly. The overarching goal is to minimise the cost of the selected financial resilience strategy and minimise the residual losses.</p> <p>Strategies refer to a set of financial tools defined with certain characteristics (limits, percentages, rates, etc.) to achieve a specific objective. In this work, the simulations consist of generating results towards the objective, by means of variations in the characteristics of the financial tools. Specifically, the strategy designed in this research consists of the interaction of two financial tools, reserve (retention mechanism) and insurance (transfer mechanism). Therefore, each result for each strategy represents variations in the characteristics of the two financial tools that are aimed at the defined objective.</p> <p>The KO contains two components:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. the Historical 'as-if' cash flow diagrams demonstrator & 2. the Decision Support System (DSS) tool. 	

The DDS tool (D6.7) is the visual-interactive representation of everything that was done in the Historical “as-if” demonstrator (D6.6). The solutions shown are the simulation results considered in a range where the cost-benefit is optimal.

The “as-if” cash flow diagrams were developed using a Monte Carlo probability simulation to estimate the outcomes of uncertain events using (1000 x 20-year realisations) 20,000 years of synthetic time series to simulate and optimise the strategies. The cash flow diagrams outline how the cash balance of a potential municipal disaster risk management fund would have varied had the hypothesised financial strategies been implemented.

Using the Decision Support System (DSS) tool, target users can visualise and explore the varied solutions and interact with them more easily to make informed decisions. This is executed through a set of Python commands that allow access to the Decision Support System tool. With this, target users can consider and prioritise other factors like the budget the city has to allocate to disaster risk, or what percentage of risk should be transferred to the insurance market. The tool allows us to explore the various possibilities and allow the cities to plan most accurately.

In the larger story of risk management, such financial strategies/methodologies are less known and less common as part of the risk management capabilities. The aim here is to maximise each euro that is put into disaster risk management as well as to reduce the costs of remaining uncovered damages.

Novelty: The methodology is based on well-established scientific concepts. The main novelty is in their usage to address type of problem at hand, and the development of a companion interactive decision support system tool specifically for this application.

Tool: Python is required for running the decision support system tool.

CCLL Specific Outputs:

Quantitative Risk Assessments & Associated Tools:

- Risk Profiles:
 - [Risk profile - Massa.pdf](#)
 - [Risk profile - Oarsoaldea.pdf](#)
 - [Risk profile - Vilanova.pdf](#)
- Cash Flow Diagrams & Decision Support Tool (D6.6 & D6.7)

Impact & Application: These outputs can be used to develop financial resilience strategies for the flood risk management and thereby risk management decision support guidelines for policy makers. Performing quantitative risk assessments such as the ones produced here is instrumental in supporting any risk reduction and management activity. Adequate knowledge on the risk to which a city is exposed in the cornerstone to taking actions of any kind to address it.

A city council member can select a solution knowing how much to put into a reserve per year, how much insurance to purchase, etc., thereby helping with budgeting and maintaining the desired performance. Target users will leverage the KO to:

- To help cities/regions better plan their financial risk strategies, making every euro put into risk management count and maximise the impact.
- Explore and compare different financial risk strategies using probability simulations.
- Optimise budget allocations for disaster risk management, ensuring efficient spending.
- Enhance decision-making capacity.

Linked Knowledge Outputs:

- KO3.1 Procedural Guide for Identifying and Using Climate and Marine Data Services and Datasets for Baseline Characterization and Projections
- KER3.2 Package of downscaling analysis tools, data, and user document

- KO3.3 Package for the statistical analysis tools, data and user-guide for urban-scale models.
- KER3.4 Methodology and Hazard Maps for Flood Risk Mitigation Assessment
- KER3.4 (KO3.5) Package of Statistical Tools & User Document for Coastal Erosion
- KO3.6 Testing Package & User Document to Improve Coastal Hazard Assessment & Long-Term Shortline Evolution

Priority Target User A: Local Public Sector Officials (including SCORE Partners) i.e., Climate Change Adaptation; Municipal governments and planning departments; Civil protection and emergency; Financial Planners; Urban Planners and Infrastructure Decision-Makers.

- *Role:* Local public sector officials play a central role in leveraging the financial resilience tools developed in WP6. These tools are designed to support departments and units responsible for planning, budgeting, and responding to flood risks—ensuring that climate adaptation strategies are both cost-effective and impactful. Climate change adaptation departments and urban planning units can use risk assessments and decision support tools to integrate flood risk into long-term development and zoning policies. Civil protection and emergency response units can use risk profiles to improve preparedness and target response planning in high-risk areas. These capabilities enable local governments to make informed, resilient, and financially sound decisions in the face of increasing climate-related risks.
- *Key Message:* The aim is to maximise the impact of every euro invested in disaster risk management while minimising the costs of uncovered damages. These tools offer municipalities solutions to strengthen climate resilience and manage flood risks effectively, helping cities understand the effects of climate change and the benefits of ecosystem-based approaches (EBAs) in mitigating risk. They also support the development of financial resilience strategies, guiding informed decisions on budget allocation and adaptation investments.
- *Awareness:* The CCLLs partners are aware of these outputs due to the knowledge transfer sessions, but broadly across their organisations, this will be more limited.
- *Level of Understanding:* There may be a lack of knowledge from municipalities in the field of financial strategies/methodologies for risk management.
- *Interest:* Municipalities are responsible for issuing reports of impact and vulnerability to climate change and are aiming to focus and prioritise adaptation measures, as such the demand for all types of risk assessments is increasing. The financial tool is considered as very useful to convince the political layer about the need for these adaptation measures.

Priority Target User B: Regional Public Bodies (including SCORE partners) – for example, Regional environmental and climate agencies, transport and infrastructure agencies (i.e., road and railway networks); economic and urban development bodies; environmental agencies and emergency services.

Specific Examples

- *Role:* Regional-level users play a crucial role in planning, implementing, and overseeing climate resilience and disaster risk management strategies across multiple municipalities. Their responsibilities encompass a broad range of activities, from infrastructure management and economic development to environmental protection and emergency response.
 - 1) **Overseeing Adaptation Strategies:** Regional environmental and climate agencies are responsible for overseeing the broader implementation of adaptation strategies across multiple cities;
 - 2) **Infrastructure Management:** Transport and infrastructure agencies manage road and railway networks that are vulnerable to flooding. Their role involves ensuring the resilience of critical infrastructure to climate-related hazards.
 - 3) **Guiding Investment and Policy:** Economic and urban development bodies use risk assessments to guide future infrastructure investment and policy decisions. They are responsible for making informed decisions about resource allocation and development strategies based on risk profiles.
 - 4) **Flood Risk Mitigation and Emergency Preparedness:** Those involved in flood risk mitigation and emergency preparedness at the regional level need financial risk simulation tools to optimise resource allocation and reduce residual losses

- *Key Message:* Maximise each euro that is put into disaster risk management as well as to reduce the costs of remaining uncovered damages, supporting strategic financial planning across regions.
- *Awareness:* There is mixed awareness of these types of outputs depending on the department. Specifically, the awareness of these specific outputs for Oarsoaldea and Vilanova is higher due to the linkages with Regional/Provinciinal partners within SCORE.
- *Level of Understanding:* Some may be familiar with climate change adaptation strategies and risk assessments, however, the financial strategies/methodologies for risk management may be less known. Likely regional policymakers will have a higher level of technical understanding than those at the municipal level. Technical Experts require the ability to run Python to operate the DSS tool.
- *Interest:* Regional public bodies are likely to be actively seeking information related to climate change adaptation, flood risk management, and infrastructure resilience. They would be interested in the KOs because they provide quantitative risk assessments, financial planning tools, and decision support systems that can help them make more informed decisions, optimise resource allocation, and comply with regulatory requirements. The potential to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of their adaptation and mitigation efforts would be a key driver of their interest.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 2 – Discovery

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 4 - Implementation

Project Activities within SCORE that increased impact as it pertains to your KER

Frontrunner Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) of Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova i la Geltrú carried out quantitative risk assessments for coastal and fluvial flooding, covering population, buildings, roads, and railways. They also co-developed financial resilience strategies and a Decision Support System (DSS) to help evaluate and select appropriate flood risk management approaches, incorporating local data and EBAs. These cities actively contributed throughout the risk assessment development, providing data, context, and feedback. The tools were tested through Knowledge Transfer sessions and surveys, where stakeholders assessed their usability and usefulness. Feedback led to refinements in both the risk profiles and the financial strategy selection tool. While many found the tools intuitive and valuable, particularly for justifying adaptation actions to political decision-makers, some highlighted the need for clearer visualisation, user support, and guidance materials to enhance accessibility and understanding.

External Engagement

Several non-partner stakeholders have expressed clear interest in the financial resilience tools developed through KO6.4. A representative from a regional public administration in Oarsoaldea described the financial tool as “very useful in order to convince the political layer about the need for these adaptation measures and especially the where and why,” underscoring its strategic value for policymaking and communication. Similarly, a CCLL manager in Vilanova (SME) noted that the DSS represents “a step further to advance adaptation and show the harm avoided,” highlighting its practical relevance for those involved in implementation.

Upcoming external dissemination activities include presentations at the SCORE Final Event, ECCA, EU Regions Week, and targeted workshops. Additional KT measures include a dedicated WP6 webinar, policy briefs, and the planned inclusion of the outputs in the CCLLs’ GeoStories.

Conferences & Events:

- SCORE Final Event & ECCA Conference
- Presentation at EGU General Assembly 2025

Other Knowledge Transfer Measures:

- Knowledge Transfer sessions have played a central role in disseminating the tools and risk profiles. Dedicated KT sessions between WP3 and WP6 took place in late 2024 and early 2025, focusing on tool usability and uptake; these were recorded for wider dissemination.
- Risk Modelling Webinar - [link](#)
- Development and sharing of CCLL Case Studies & testimony, disseminated via the SCORE website: [Smart Spending for Safer Shores: How Vilanova is Using Data to Boost Climate Resilience](#)
- Inclusion on the [Horizon Results Platform](#)

Future Impact and Opportunities

Tool Development & Improvements

- The development of KO6.3 and KO6.4 revealed several key barriers to tool uptake, including low familiarity with financial risk methodologies, technical limitations due to Python-based accessibility, and the need for clearer, more visual presentation of results. Despite this, the tools are viewed as highly valuable for policymaking and strategic planning. Planned deliverables (e.g., D6.8) will provide further guidance and documentation. Improvements to the DSS tool would be useful to increase its usability, with a more web-accessible interface, to enhance usability. European and regional funding should be explored by RedRisk to further develop these outputs and tools.

Increase Uptake

- RedRisk is positioned to support continued development and implementation of these tools for both fellows and new municipalities. Engagement in brokerage events and initiatives like EU Week for Regions and Cities is recommended to reach relevant stakeholders.
- Survey responses also flagged budget limitations as a barrier, local grants could support non-frontrunner CCLLs in replicating these tools.

Frontrunner CCLLs

- Frontrunner CCLLs are expected to disseminate outputs within their institutions, we recommend having additional knowledge transfer activities (emailing to key stakeholders, hosting meeting to explain the materials, sharing via the GeoStory platform)
- Spanish are encouraged to collaborate, possibly producing a Spanish-language opinion piece on the value of risk assessment and EBAs within Spain, leveraging the timeliness of the recent natural disasters in Spain.

Policy Considerations

- The KOs align with key policy frameworks, notably the European Floods Directive (2007), which requires risk assessments in vulnerable areas. The SCORE tools go beyond current standards, offering advanced methodologies that can directly inform and support compliance and strategic planning.

KER 7.1 - Synthesis Of Socio-Economic Assessment Methods, Databases, And Studies Addressing Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EBA) And Other Adaptation Strategies.

Knowledge Owners: ENT, IHS, EnoLL, TERO, ATU

Current Status: Open-access [publication](#) published in MDPI, available on [Zenodo](#)

Description: This KO corresponds to a systematic literature review of scientific studies performing socio-economic assessments of climate change adaptation in coastal areas to determine which socioeconomic assessments were used most often.

The review focused mainly on four types of adaptation strategies: hard (more relying on engineering-based solutions), soft (e.g., initiatives encouraging adaptation behaviour or focusing on coastal management and regulation), ecosystem-based adaptation

or, in short, EBA (green-oriented measures more relying on interventions implemented at the ecosystem level), and hybrid (resulting from the mix of the previous solutions) adaptation strategies.

The analysis aimed at answering the following general and specific research questions:

1. Which socio-economic assessment methods have been used to analyse adaptation strategies?
 - 1.1. Do these methods fall under Multi-Criteria analysis (MCA), Cost-benefit analysis (CBA), Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) or other types of assessments?
 - 1.2. To which extent are these methods expert-based or participatory?
2. In which adaptation context have these assessment methods been utilized?
 - 2.1. Which type of adaptation strategies have been utilized in the assessment?
 - 2.2. What climate change hazards do these adaptation strategies address?
 - 2.3. What climate change sectoral impacts do these adaptation strategies address?
3. Which monetary and non-monetary metrics have been used to assess these adaptation strategies?
4. How do these adaptation strategies perform?
 - 4.1. What were the results of the monetary and non-monetary metrics used?
 - 4.2. What final recommendations were provided?

The systematic literature review followed PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis) 2020 methodology to ensure consistency and quality of the results. After excluding duplicates, and studies not fulfilling eligibility criteria, 51 studies were finally included in the literature review analysis. From these studies reviewed, 23 were cost-benefit analysis (CBA), six performed multicriteria analysis (MCA), three combined MCA and CBA, two developed a CBA and cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA), and the remaining 17 fell under the category of 'other' types of methods (e.g., real-option analysis – ROA; economic impact evaluation, and risk assessment).

Amongst the main results, the review revealed that most of the selected studies addressed hybrid adaptation strategies. From these, hard measures such as dike constructions and seawalls were often considered for flooding and sea-level rise; soft-based actions like beach nourishment were at times presented as potential cost-effective measures to mitigate coastal erosion and flooding; and EBA relying on the regeneration of coastal ecosystems (e.g., mangrove forests, reefs, wetlands), or the implementation of green infrastructure options such as porous pavements or the expansion of green urban areas were sometimes considered for the mitigation of extreme heat events and flood run-off, along with other impacts.

The analysis contributed towards a better understanding of the effectiveness, cost-efficiency, and generation of co-benefits by EbA solutions (e.g., provision of ecosystem services, support to livelihood, health), but it also stresses the need for further research on these topics.

Conclusions of the literature review:

- Coastal areas are highly vulnerable to climate change and require appropriate climate adaptation strategies.
- CBA or MCA are the most used socioeconomic assessment models.
- Typically, these studies focused on hybrid adaptation strategies/solutions.
- There is a need for decision-makers to consider the adaptation strategies analysis results when developing policies and plans.

Impact & Application: This output will be highly relevant for decision-makers and planners, as it clearly outlines various socioeconomic methods for assessing adaptation strategies, highlighting their strengths and limitations. It also provides a comprehensive overview of hard, soft, Ecosystem-based, and hybrid adaptation options, and summarises the key climate hazards facing coastal areas. Among others, this output highlights the methods relying on stakeholder participation, the climate

hazard and sectoral impact addressed by the method, and the adaptation solutions implemented. As such, the deliverable presents the results of the different assessments in a way that is easily comparable to future research.

This allows for users to increase knowledge on existing socio-economic assessment methods to more accurately choose appropriate tools and approaches suited to their contexts. This in turn increases the likelihood of implementing sustainable and effective climate adaptation measures in coastal regions.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO7.2 Multi-Criteria Analysis, KO7.5 Cost-Benefit Analysis

Priority Target User A: Academics

Academics working in the climate adaptation/EBA sphere, including economists, sociologists, urban sustainability and climate change specialists, environmental scientists.

- **Role:** Those doing research on EBA approaches and other adaptation strategies and the focus on such socio-economic assessments within these climate change adaptation strategies.
- **Key Message:** This KO could be applied to obtain a general overview of the different socio-economic assessment methods most frequently used to assess the economic performance of EbA and other adaptation strategies in local and regional coastal areas. This KO highlights the methods relying on stakeholder participation, the climate hazard and sectoral impact addressed by the method, and the adaptation solutions implemented. The KO presents the results of the different assessments in a way that is easily comparable to future research.
- **Awareness:** *Likely aware of socio-economic methods but are interested in learning more.*
- **Level of Understanding:** There should be minimal need to educate academics who work within this field on how to utilise this KO as they have expertise in the field. The content is readable.
- **Interest:** At this stage there have not been citations but there is growing interest, and more research is needed on assessing the benefits and co-benefits that EbAs generate.

Priority Target User B: Public sector decision-makers

Public sector decision-makers, including city planning authorities, municipalities.

- **Role:** To implement climate adaptation strategies in their local municipality /region.
- **Key Message:** This KO could be applied to obtain a general overview of the different socio-economic assessment methods most frequently used to assess the economic performance of EbA and other adaptation strategies in local and regional coastal areas. Among others, this KO highlights the methods relying on stakeholder participation, the climate hazard and sectoral impact addressed by the method, and the adaptation solutions implemented. The KO presents the results of the different assessments in a way that is easily comparable to future research.
- **Awareness:** *Low: decision-makers and planners presumably, have a low awareness of this KO. However, further research could be done to confirm.*
- **Level of Understanding:** Low-medium: Decision makers and planners will understand the deliverable and it would be highly relevant as it outlines different socioeconomic methods for the assessment of adaptation strategies/measures, including some of their pros and cons; provides information of a wide set of hard, soft, EBA and hybrid adaptation options; and summarises the main climate hazards affecting coastal areas, with flooding being the most studied.
- **Interest:** Decision makers are increasingly being required (whether by policy mandates or the will of the people) to implement green(er) solutions in regard to climate adaptation, which also means conducting a socio-economic assessment in regard to the adaptation measures. This KO outlines the which socio-economic strategies are the most commonly used and the co-benefits associated with EbA solutions.

IRL at Project Start	IRL Achieved During SCORE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRL 1 – Conception 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRL 2 – Discovery
<p>Internal Activities Increasing Impact</p>	
<p>Within the broader umbrella of WP7, the aim of this output was to develop and implement a methodology for climate change adaptation strategies, with a focus on EBAs. The results of this foundational research activity for SCORE formed the basis for other WP7 activities, including the running of the MCA workshops (see KO7.2) and the CBAs conducted for frontrunner CCLLs (see KO7.5).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EbA catalogue: this deliverable set the foundations for the elaboration of the EbA catalogue. After completing the LR and in view of the elaboration of the MCA methodology, some partners agreed on elaborating this tools, not initially foreseen in the GA 	
<p>External Engagement</p>	
<p>Publications include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Riera-Spiegelhalder, M., Campos-Rodrigues, L., Enseñado, E. M., Dekker-Arlain, J. d., Papadopoulou, O., Arampatzis, S., & Vervoort, K. (2023). Socio-Economic Assessment of Ecosystem-Based and Other Adaptation Strategies in Coastal Areas: A Systematic Review. <i>Journal of Marine Science and Engineering</i>, 11(2), 319. https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11020319 D7.1-Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, databases, and studies addressing EBA and other adaptation strategies is available on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/11242253, and a simplified table with the selected studies from D7.1 will be uploaded to Zenodo in CSV format by July 2025 under the title Summary of studies selected in the literature review - SCORE WP7. This report has been shared on the Horizon Results Platform. 	
<p>This output was disseminated at the Developments and Challenges in Accounting Standardization, Teaching and research in January 2025. It is a conference co-organised by the University of Lleida and the University of Valencia. The presentation related focussed more on the CBA approach identified through this output, presented under the name "Cost-benefit analysis and the institutional exposure to climate change" to around 30 participants. It was also showcased at the SCORE Final Event at European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025) as a cluster of the greater WP7 story – from this assessment to the outputs of the MCA and CBAs in the CCLL.</p>	
<p>Finally, the D7.5 Policy Guidelines (link) references this deliverable by stating that socio-economic assessment methods are fundamental for making well-informed decisions regarding climate change adaptation, noting that effective decision-making relies on systematic information and data analysed by experts, as well as the incorporation of stakeholders' perspectives.</p>	
<p>Future Impact and Opportunities</p>	
<p>Future research could involve updating the literature review to incorporate the latest developments and insights. In addition, it may explore the selection and implementation of alternative socio-economic assessment methods identified in the review, beyond those applied in SCORE—namely, KER7.2 Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA). These research options could be supported by upcoming funding opportunities at the EU, national, and regional levels.</p>	

KER 7.2 - Multi-Criteria Analysis of Ecosystem-based Adaptation Strategies in Coastal City Living Labs

Knowledge Owners: ENT, Naider, IHS, ZRS, TERO, ATU, ENoLL, with support from CCLLs

Current Status: Both reports D7.2 *Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change* and D7.3 *Results from the participatory socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions*, are

available as open-access documents, and also available on CORDIS ([Link](#)), and Zenodo ([link](#)) and SCORE Website

Description: The contribution of this result is twofold: it presents main findings from the evaluation of Ecosystem Based Approaches (EBA) solutions through Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) across the ten SCORE Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs), and it outlines the key lessons learned from applying this method within this context.

The application of the MCA as a participatory assessment has been gaining prominence across different contexts, including climate adaptation across different geographical locations, spatial scales, and problem settings. This method offers stakeholders a relatively straightforward way to engage with complex topics. Decision makers, city planning authorities, and municipalities can use MCA to evaluate and select the most preferred adaptation interventions for implementation. The participatory-based nature of this method enables the collection of diverse stakeholder perspectives on the proposed adaptation measures, including those from citizens and citizens' groups, academia, NGOs, private sector, and public administration.

The MCA Process:

MCA is a structured, transparent, and iterative framework wherein the decision problem (i.e., which EBAs are most suitable for our community) is broken down into a process of multi-step, leading to a decision recommendation. MCA aids the assessment of different policies, measures, or actions (hereinafter referred to as options) against a set of multiple qualitative and/or quantitative evaluation criteria. With the involvement of multiple stakeholders, including thematic experts, MCA integrates both subjective and objective assessments.

MCA requires three key components:

- (1) a set of options which need to be ranked or scored;
- (2) a set of criteria measured in different units; and
- (3) a set of performance measurements for each option against each criterion (Hajkowicz & Collins, 2006).

All in all, the output of the MCA process is a 'single most-preferred option', a 'set of ranked options', a 'short list of options for further appraisal', or a 'characterization of acceptable or unacceptable possibilities' (Munaretto et al., 2014). The high-level overview of the steps to implement MCA are:

1. Understanding the local adaptation context
1. Identifying a list of preliminary options
2. Screening or feasibility assessment
3. Defining evaluation criteria
4. Scoring or assessment of options
5. Weighting of evaluation criteria
6. Ranking and Prioritisation of options
7. Sensitivity analysis

For a more detailed description of the methodology used, the report *Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change* (D7.2) is an easy-to-understand practical guide with the main steps required to implement MCA methods. Moreover, the report *Results from the participatory socio-economic assessment of EBA interventions* (D7.3) details the methodological adjustments made for the practical implementation of MCA across the CCLLs. It also presents the main results, and identifies advantages, limitations and opportunities for improving the application of this method in similar living lab contexts.

Impact & Application: The accessibility of the MCA makes it a valuable tool for evaluating adaptation options and supporting the decision-making process. Experts from various fields, such as economists, sociologists, urban sustainability and climate change specialists, environmental scientists, could implement the MCA method to assess a broad range of adaptation options,

incorporating perspectives from various stakeholders (e.g., citizens and citizens' groups; academia; NGOs; industry; public administration) for a comprehensive assessment.

The application of the MCA across the CCLLs contributed for a better understanding and evaluation of different types of EBAs and different stages of readiness (i.e., implemented, planned, or hypothetical), which can be analysed alone or in comparison with other types of adaptation strategies (e.g., hard, soft). With the implementation of the MCA method in the CCLLs, it was possible for stakeholders to collaboratively define the evaluation criteria and weigh the EbA based on their priorities. The workshops allowed participants to broaden their understanding the potential of EBA to be effective solutions to climate change and to provide additional ecosystem services, such as biodiversity improvement and social interaction benefits obtained from the existence and use of green spaces. Following participants' discussions, there were identified recommendations for extending EBA benefits to areas beyond workshop study areas, and in some cases, such as in Oarsoaldea or Gdansk, there were recognized synergy opportunities among organizations for climate adaptation.

Utilising an MCA similar to that followed by SCORE CCLLs offer several potential benefits. These include helping citizens better understand the local implications of climate change and potential adaptation through EBA; exploring collaboration opportunities in financing, developing and monitoring EBA solutions across private, public, and NGO sectors; stimulating academic discussions on the results and areas for improvement; and providing valuable insights to policymakers that could influence local and regional climate planning strategies.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO7.1 Synthesis Of Socio-Economic Assessment Methods, Databases, And Studies Addressing Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (Eba) And Other Adaptation Strategies, KO7.5 Cost-Benefit Analysis of Ecosystem Based Adaptation measures in SCORE's Coastal City Living Labs

Priority Target User A: Public sector actors and local/regional decision makers

Local and regional public sector entities would be the key stakeholders interested in utilising MCA as a structured methodology to assess and implement Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA) strategies within their own localities.

Local Public Sector entities could include:

- *Municipal Planning Departments – Responsible for urban planning, land use, and infrastructure development.*
- *City Environmental Agencies – Oversee local climate adaptation, green spaces, and sustainability initiatives.*
- *Coastal & Water Management Authorities – Manage flood prevention, coastal resilience, and water resources.*
- *Transport & Mobility Departments – Plan public transport and sustainable mobility strategies.*

Regional Public Authorities & Decision-Makers, such as:

- *Regional Climate & Energy Agencies – Support sustainable energy transition and climate adaptation.*
- *Metropolitan Governance Bodies – Coordinate planning and policy implementation across multiple municipalities.*
- *Regional Development Agencies – Oversee economic and environmental projects at the regional level.*
- *Environmental & Natural Resource Departments – Manage biodiversity, air quality, and ecosystem-based adaptation.*

- *Role:* The public sector decision-makers are the ones who are ultimately paying and determining which EBAs to implement and where.
- *Key Message:* Decision makers, city planning authorities, and municipalities could use the MCA methods to evaluate and decide on the most preferred adaptation interventions to implement. These tools should be used as part of the decision process when planning adaptation strategies to climate change. The participatory-based nature of an MCA allows to incorporate the perceptions of different stakeholders about the studied adaptation measures (e.g., citizens and citizens' groups; academia; NGOs; private sector; public administration).
- *Awareness:* Based on the experiences with the CCLLs, the utilisation of the MCA methodology is rather limited in public sector settings, and thereby awareness would be lower. However, they are likely familiar with the value of public

consultation and would be aware of this as a general practice to get public opinion on implementing various public projects.

- *Level of Understanding:* MCA is understandable for non-experts to implement and engage with, but some previous knowledge or training on what EBAs to analyse would be necessary. The KO (in the deliverable form) is relatively easy to understand once it has been explained, but ultimately, they would require someone with domain-level expertise to implement it.
- *Interest:* While EBAs are becoming more and more popular, largely the interest in the methodology will depend regionally. For those communities with an interest in EBAs, the methodology can support their decision-making process, including both stakeholder perspectives and a more technical assessment. Public opinion & governance/voting cycles ultimately impact the ability to implement EBAs and therefore use this methodology. The MCA methodology also requires these decision-makers to value the perspectives of the quadruple helix.

Priority Target User B: General public and civil society organisations (CSOs)

The public contributed to the MCA process, which would be facilitated largely by target users such as the public sector facilitators and decisionmakers. Some examples of these participants in the MCA process could be those working in climate action (such as climate action networks, youth climate action groups, environmental NGOs, etc.) or local community groups (environmental advocacy groups, biodiversity conservation organisations, neighbourhood associations, local cooperatives).

Further, the general public would be interested in the results of the MCA process if it was used within their area.

- *Role:* The general public and more importantly, CSOs can play a massive role in putting appropriate pressure on the public authorities/decision-makers, if they are educated about their options. They can advocate for the use of this methodology and/or the incorporation of the results of an MCA (such as the chosen EBA solutions) into their communities.
- *Key Message:* This target group should be influenced more broadly on the ideas of EBAs & co-creation, encouraging citizens to make active choices and engaging in their community's future. The MCA allows for facilitators to more accurately gain perspectives from local users on a selection of options. As such, this process is a great method for incorporating citizens into the local decision-making process, specifically in the area of climate action.
- *Awareness:* These target users are not likely to be aware of the MCA specifically but are likely familiar with the concept of co-creation or public consultation. Generally, there is a lack of awareness of EBAs, however, with an ever-increasing knowledge of climate change and communities actively feeling the effects of the climate crisis, there is an increasing receptivity towards these solutions.
- *Level of Understanding:* Some education is needed to explain both the idea of EBAs and/or MCA process. The idea that these can be co-created and locally embedded would need to be taught to this user group for them to appropriately engage in the process.
- *Interest:* Whilst the general public and civil society are large groups with diversity within, there are certain climate activists and climate change affected-people due to various climatic hazards (i.e., heat waves, coastal erosion, etc.). For the general public to engage in the MCA process, they must be informed about the potential options for implementation in their locality and the specific challenges these solutions aim to address. Therefore, raising awareness of climate challenges and Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA) solutions is crucial to influencing this target group.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 1 – Conception

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 2 – Discovery

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

The MCA methodology was applied in the SCORE CCLLs to prioritise the most beneficial EBA solutions for specific climate change hazards. Local and regional stakeholders assessed the potential performance of various measures according to environmental and socioeconomic criteria such as hazard risk reduction, air quality improvement, biodiversity enhancement, and support for recreational opportunities. This method was carried out through the following steps under the coordination of WP7 and the collaboration of CCLLs key representatives and stakeholders: understanding the local adaptation context; identifying a list of preliminary EBA options; conducting a feasibility assessment of these options; defining evaluation criteria; assessment of measures using both unweighted and weighted criteria; and, finally, ranking and prioritizing the options.

Adopting this method across diverse socioeconomic, professional, and cultural contexts of the CCLLs presented challenges, but it proved to be successful overall due to a clear and straightforward methodological approach, supported by visual materials (e.g., posters, infographics) and accessible terminology for complex concepts. The MCA methodology was designed to be adapted to various types of assessments (*ex-ante*, *ex-post* or *interim*), study areas (ranging from specific locations within the municipality to the entire municipality or region), and hazards (e.g., inland and coastal flooding, storm surge, coastal erosion, landslide, droughts and heatwaves).

In general, the MCA workshops had a high stakeholder participation, with its usefulness as an evaluation and decision-making tool being strongly emphasized. The success of this approach was driven by the opportunity to gather valuable input on EBA measures from a diverse group of stakeholders and by fostering a collaborative and creative space for knowledge exchange. Recommendations for improving the application of this method in similar living lab contexts include, among others: implementing a structured sensitivity analysis to test the robustness of the results; ensuring balanced representation of stakeholders from diverse groups; allocating more time for open questions about the assessed measures; foster greater inclusion of both experts and non-experts in problem definition and analysis; and providing more contextual information in advance to non-experts to enhance understanding.

Each CCLL has a set of results from the MCA workshops available on SharePoint and associated infographic highlighting the top three EBAs prioritised during the session. Each workshop explored EBA options to address relevant climate hazards in the study area (related to the SCORE Coastal City Living Lab, CCLL), as it is listed below:

- Oarsoaldea (Spain) – inland and coastal flooding, landslide, and heatwaves
- Piran (Slovenia) – coastal flooding, droughts, and heatwaves
- Sligo (Ireland) – coastal flooding
- Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona (Spain) – inland flooding
- Massa (Italy) – coastal flooding, storm surge, and heatwaves
- Dublin (Ireland) - coastal flooding, storm surge, and heatwaves
- Oeiras (Portugal) – inland flooding
- Gdansk (Poland) – inland flooding and storm surge
- Samsun (Turkey) – coastal erosion
- Benidorm (Spain) – inland and coastal flooding, and coastal erosion

The top three prioritized measures across the CCLLs were:

- Oarsoaldea (Spain) – green spaces, tree plantation, and riparian reforestation
- Piran (Slovenia) – restoration of historic wells and water reservoirs, sustainable permeable pavements, and green spaces
- Sligo (Ireland) – afforestation, peatland restoration, and wetland restoration

- Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona (Spain) – combination of measures (renaturing, restitution of the original riverbed depth, increase in riverbank height), renaturing and stabilization of riverbed and slopes, and restitution of riverbed depth
- Massa (Italy) – floodplain enlargement, riparian reforestation, and high-water channel
- Dublin (Ireland) – floodable park, saltmarsh restoration, and green infrastructure
- Oeiras (Portugal) – planting indigenous vegetation, floodplain enlargement, and maintenance of the river network
- Gdansk (Poland) – water parks and retention ponds, green spaces, and tree plantation
- Samsun (Turkey) – floodplain enlargement, bank restoration/naturalization, and seagrass meadow introduction/restoration
- Benidorm (Spain) – floodable park, riparian reforestation, and tree plantation

Overall, participants highly valued the potential of EBA solutions to reduce hazard risk in the studied areas, while also contributing to the delivery of various socioeconomic and environmental co-benefits. Coastal flooding, inland flooding, and erosion were the most common hazards. Sea-level rise was indirectly considered through related issues like storm surges and erosion, though not explicitly addressed in the MCA. Preferred EBAs varied by hazard:

- For coastal flooding, floodplain enlargement, afforestation, and saltmarsh restoration were top choices.
- For inland flooding, measures included floodable parks and riparian reforestation.
- Green spaces and SUDS were considered effective for both flood types and for heatwaves and drought resilience.

The infographics (see [Piran](#) example) presenting the results of the analysis were developed in their local languages, and these are available for both the public and the participations on social media, [GeoStories](#), and underwent general distribution to wider CCLL networks by facilitators.

External Engagement - Methodology

The [D7.2 Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change](#), which details the methodology followed by SCORE, is available for open use on Zenodo and linked on the SCORE website. The [D7.3 Results from the participatory socioeconomic assessment of EBA interventions](#) is available open-access on Zenodo and linked on the SCORE website for users to review the results of implementing the MCA in the SCORE CCLLs. The MCA process and results are mentioned in D7.5 Policy Guidelines ([link](#)), which details the Multi-criteria Analysis (MCA) tool as an optimal method for integrating knowledge and perspectives from a diverse range of stakeholders, including academia, public administration, the private sector, and civil society. Finally, the MCA process is featured as a useful tool in the POP (KO2.2) template instructions, found on the [Tools and Platforms Page](#) on the SCORE Website. The POP provides recommendations for when within the Living Lab Integrative Process to implement an MCA most effectively, increasing its audience to practitioners of Living Labs.

Conferences and events that shared the MCA methodology were as follows:

- The MCA process was presented at a MIP4Adapt Community of Practice event with participants of the EU Mission Adaptation charter signatories. *This* group on coastal areas and floods is composed of 17 specialised participants all coming from coastal regions or cities (including Nouvelle Aquitaine, Asturias, Troms County, Galway city...). ENT presented as an invited expert at the January 2025 session entitled “Identifying and selecting adaptation options” with a presentation called “SCORE Nature-based Solutions (NBS) selection for coastal areas.” Participants were particularly interested in the MCA process and the EbA catalogue: links to these resources were provided after the session to all participants.
- Shared at the SCORE booth at the EU Week of Regions and Cities conference (2024) and featured in the panel discussion “Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures.”

- Highlighted at the SCORE Final Event at the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025) in both the presentation sessions and at the demonstration sessions.
- ENoLL Open Living Lab Days (2023). The CCLLs of Benidorm, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova i la Geltrú showcased their experience with the prioritization of EbA during the side-event organised by SCORE within the OLLD in Barcelona. The three CCLLs shared their experience with the identification and engagement of stakeholders, as well as presenting the process followed to define the list of EbA to be prioritised during the MCA workshops
- Meulenbergh, C. (2025, April 17) presented at a networking event an abstract presentation, entitled *Co-designed climate adaptive nature-based solutions: Revalorisation of urban parks and historic rainwater collectors*. KR PAN – Fostering research support and activities to improve the performance on European research projects, co-financed by the Republic of Slovenia, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation, and the European Union – NextGenerationEU, *Seas and Coasts for healthy and prosperous societies: Blue Economy, Biodiversity, Climate change*. Centre for Humanities ZRS Koper, Kreljeva 6, Koper, Slovenia.

Finally, the MCA methodology has been shared in [SCORE Feature](#) on the [Nature Based Solutions Platform](#) to disseminate WP7 results to peer learning networks. The CCLLs' vision, main hazards addressed and EbA prioritised have been included in the NBS platform. Additionally, the wider outputs of the SCORE project were featured on this group's [LinkedIn group](#), which has over 46,000 current followers. The MCA has been shared on the [Horizon Results Platform](#), and presented in the SCORE Webinar [The potential of Ecosystem-based Adaptation in coastal areas](#), which has over 500 views on YouTube alone. Additionally, the MCA methodology followed by SCORE is summarised and recommended for use by coastal communities in the MOOC: [Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities](#), which has over 450 enrolments.

External Engagement - CCLL-specific results to be shared with wider community

The results of the MCA were incorporated into local policy briefs in [Sligo](#), highlighting an MCA's strengths and weaknesses for use by policymakers in the Sligo CCLL context. The results of the MCA workshops were translated into infographics in CCLL local languages for easier uptake by a wider range of stakeholders. These were made available to CCLLs for distribution to participants. The graphics were also shared on social media and are now available in [GeoStories](#). See example of an infographic in the Piran example [here](#).

Piran was used as a best-practice example of the MCA, CBA, and EbA catalogue implementation and iterations in a CCLL context for the [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#), where the experience is detailed for future CCLLs to better understand best practices, and its associated MOOC [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#). This best practice case study was also shared as a [blog](#) on the SCORE website.

Additionally, scientific publications with specific CCLL results include:

- The [D7.3 Results from the participatory socioeconomic assessment of EBA interventions](#) is available open-access on Zenodo to review the results of implementing the MCA in the SCORE CCLLs. Although technical, it is a useful summary of all results per CCLL for CCLL teams to utilise when engaging with stakeholder networks.
- Baranczuk et al. 2024. Multicriteria analysis as a method for engaging stakeholders and citizens in activities aimed at supporting climate resilience and adaptation to climate change – Gdansk Coastal City Living Lab case study. <https://sciendo.com/pl/article/10.2478/mgrsd-2023-0049>
- Tiwari, Ananya and Rodrigues, Luís Campos and Caruso, Rochelle and Ensenado, Elena Marie and Makousiari, Elina and Gharbia, Salem, Multi-Criteria Analysis of Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Strategies for Flood Risk Reduction in Irish, Italian, and Turkish Coastal City Living Labs. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831266> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831266>
- Riera-Spiegelhalder, M., Campos Rodrigues, L., & Ferrandis Martínez, A. (2025). A multicriteria analysis to integrate key stakeholders' perceptions in ecosystem-based adaptation to flooding in coastal urban areas. *Documents d'Anàlisi Geogràfica*, 71 (1), 153–179. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/dag.933>

The MCA activities were presented at EBA training schools in February 2025, and at the final SCORE EBA online training school, the MCA/CBA results for Sligo, Vilanova i la Geltrú and Oarsoaldea were shared with participants. The Spanish cases were captured in a [YouTube video](#) for participants and invited stakeholders to view. At the EGU 2024 conference in April, the outcomes of workshops held in Benidorm, Vilanova i la Geltrú, and Oeiras were shared with the scientific community. In Ireland, the findings from the Sligo MCA/CBA process were presented to Sligo County Council during an info session, followed by an online meeting in November 2024 attended by around 20 local stakeholders from the local municipality and wider area. This engagement ensured that the local authority and community representatives were informed about potential adaptation options and had an opportunity to reflect on the relevance of the results to regional planning efforts. Meanwhile, dissemination efforts in Massa were supported by a collaboration with a multimedia company to share MCA activities through radio and television, broadening public reach. Most recently, ENT hosted a webinar on 28 May 2025 to present MCA outcomes for Vilanova i la Geltrú. The session sparked interest from one attendee in exploring how SCORE's findings could be applied to municipalities near Valencia, particularly in response to the severe flooding that occurred in October 2024.

Future Impact and Opportunities

Key recommendations focus on increasing visibility of the results of CCLL-specific MCAs, primarily through incorporation of results into concise policy briefs for policymakers in CCLL areas, similar to what was done in the Sligo CCLL.

The use of the Nature-Based solutions platform was very successful for connecting with academics and practitioners of EBAs. The team has identified the Ocean and Climate platform as a good site for additional visibility for the MCA results, and this will be explored further.

The team will identify upcoming calls relevant to this topic to advertise SCORE's outputs. At present, several SCORE partners are working to apply to a PRIMA call ([1.1.1-2025 Upscaling Nature Based Solutions for sustainable water management to address extreme events in the Mediterranean](#)) to build up on SCORE results.

KER 7.3 - SCORE Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Catalogue: An Educational Catalogue for Coastal Climate Adaptation using Nature-Based Solutions & Ecosystem-based Adaptations

Knowledge Owners: ENT, ZRS, UCD

Current Status: Available on website [SCORE Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Catalogue](#)

Description: The [SCORE Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Catalogue](#) is an online repository of Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EbA) measures suitable to address different climate change hazards (i.e. coastal and inland flooding, coastal erosion, sea-level rise, droughts and heat waves, landslides) in either urban or natural coastal environments. The catalogue involves a case study map along with featured filters, all through which different EbA options can be explored, focusing on European examples.

Navigating the catalogue: By selecting a pinpoint in the map, it is possible to read the description, objectives and benefits related to the measure. There are case study examples related to each EbA, which can be investigated either by pinpointing the pictogram on the map or applying a filter. A pop-up window will show a brief case study description, the link to the full source of information and a picture.

The identification of EbA through the application of filters might be of special interest in case the user needs to explore adaptation options subject to certain conditions. The filters are available under the following categories:

- A. Landscape typology: Urban green, Permeable surfaces, River floodplains, Wetlands, Coastal shoreline, Marine waters.
- B. Climate hazard: Sea-level rise, Coastal flooding, Land and river flooding, Coastal erosion, Storm surge, Droughts and heat wave Landslide.

There are pictograms accompanying each category for easier identification. Landscape category and climate hazard filters can be applied simultaneously in the application for a more advanced search. After applying both filters the map will show the available options.

Novelty: This catalogue is novel as it focuses specifically on *adaptation of coastal areas*, whereas other similar catalogues focus mainly on ecosystem-based approaches or nature-based solutions. Further, the ability to filter by either landscape typology or hazard is novel, as this allows searchers to more easily find the exact examples they are interested in.

Impact & Application: This catalogue is for anyone interested in exploring Ecosystem-based Adaptation measures, and the most relevant context where these can be applied. No previous expertise or knowledge on the topic is requested, and thus the catalogue can provide good introductory material to the concepts of EbAs. As such, this catalogue would be of use to interested citizens, students, facilitators, or policymakers who can navigate to explore potential EbA suitable to address certain hazards under different land typologies. Further, CCLLs of the SCORE project have used the catalogue to inform stakeholders ahead of engagement activities. Other EU Projects engaging in EbAs, citizen science, or environmental education could also benefit from using this resource. The EbA catalogue acts as an introductory tool to better understand the benefits, geographical contexts, and climate hazards under which EbAs can be implemented. As an easy-to-use introductory material, the catalogue can have impacts on a wide range of groups.

- Students can use this tool as a first approximation to the concept and to learn about their potential benefits and applicability. This catalogue would be particularly suited to secondary school students due to the detail displayed on the site. Additionally, as the catalogue provides positive solutions to climate threats, it is a positive material to inspire younger audiences to find solutions.
- Citizens with experience within the field would also likely get the most benefit out of the catalogue. Those who are engaging in citizen science activities or have an interest in local options for EbAs could use the catalogue as a reference.
- Facilitators might use this tool as support material on Climate change adaptation sessions.

Within the public sector, policymakers can use it to know more on adaptation alternatives. For those interested in better understanding EbAs and exploring options more applicable to their locality, the catalogue would be a good resource.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO4.3 - SCORE Game-Based Approaches to Enhance Community Participation in Spatial Decisions, KO7.2 Multi-Criteria Analysis

Priority Target User A: Climate adaptation practitioners, researchers, and academics

Academics, researchers, or other professionals working in the climate adaptation/NBS sphere and engaging in education or community engagement surrounding this topic. This could include urban sustainability and climate change specialists, environmental scientists, etc.

- **Role:** The target users would likely be doing research and/or community engagement work with NBS approaches and other adaptation strategies for implementation in their own regions. This work is important to be explained appropriately to stakeholders within these research areas: as such, these target users would benefit from tools that could support education or outreach activities for their research.
- **Key Message:** Nature-Based Solutions are powerful tools to increase resilience to climate change. This KO could be applied to increase awareness of a variety of NBS solutions, highlighting different case studies of these in practice, allowing for a user to view these options in a way that is easily comparable to future research.
- **Awareness:** This target user would be very aware of EbAs and NBS, but not of this specific catalogue itself. They would be interested to use this KO as an educational tool to increase the knowledge and awareness of their stakeholders (secondary school students, public with limited knowledge on NBS, decision-makers with interest on NBS).
- **Level of Understanding:** This target group would have a high level of understanding on this topic. It will not be necessary to educate these target users on the need for adaptation, but rather the catalogue would support this target user seeking further inspiration or examples. The content is readable and easily accessible.
- **Interest:** There is increasing interest in NBSs and adaptation measures, and target users would be interested in viewing the specific case studies for inspiration or knowledge sharing. In particular, this KO acts as an educational tool which

would be useful for outreach activities related to a target user's research. As this target user group would be using the catalogue for education, they would be engaging with wider communities and other potential users. By transferring this KO to the target users, this opens the possibility to reach more stakeholders within the same ecosystem.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 3 – Engagement

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 4 – Implementation

Project Activities within SCORE

This catalogue has been disseminated extensively within SCORE partners and their networks. The catalogue has been presented during the MCA workshops to the CCLLs and their stakeholders, and it is available on the SCORE website under the following link: <https://score-eu-project.eu/eba-catalogue/>. The catalogue has been used by SCORE partners and iterated according to feedback by subject matter experts at ENT, UCD, ZRS, and ATU.

External Engagement

The EBA catalogue has been promoted at each Ecosystem Based Adaptation Training Schools (2023, 2024, 2025). The EBA catalogue alongside other WP7 results was presented at a MIP4Adapt Community of Practice event with participants of the EU Mission Adaptation charter signatories. This group on coastal areas and floods is composed of 17 participants all coming from coastal regions or cities (including Nouvelle Aquitaine, Asturias, Troms County, Galway city...). WP7 representatives presented as an invited expert at the January 2025 session entitled "Identifying and selecting adaptation options" with a presentation called "SCORE Nature-based Solutions (NBS) selection for coastal areas." Participants were particularly interested in the MCA process and the EBA catalogue: links to these resources were provided after the session to all participants.

The EBA catalogue is featured in SCORE Feature on the [Nature Based Solutions Platform](#) to disseminate WP7 results to peer learning networks. Additionally, the wider outputs of the SCORE project were featured on this group's [LinkedIn group](#), which has over 46,000 current followers. It will be added to the [Climate Adapt tools database](#) and is currently being drafted.

The SCORE EBA Catalogue has been widely promoted and integrated into multiple platforms to enhance its visibility and accessibility. It is featured on the [Horizon Results Platform](#) as a key project output and included in the Citizen Science Playbook (KO4.2) as a practical tool for engaging communities in climate adaptation. It is also highlighted in the D7.5 policy guidelines as an effective resource for showcasing real-world case studies of ecosystem-based adaptation, offering decision-makers concrete examples of nature-based solutions in action.

To support broader learning and context, the EBA Catalogue is featured in the [CCLL GeoStories](#), providing readers with diverse examples of EBA implementations around the world. It has also been spotlighted in several educational webinars, including [The potential of Ecosystem-based Adaptation in coastal areas](#), and the [Adapt4Coast Webinar: Tools to enhance climate change adaptation in coastal areas](#). These events helped raise awareness of the EBA Catalogue's relevance and usability among practitioners and policymakers working on coastal resilience.

The catalogue has further been incorporated into several Massive Open Online Courses, [Ecosystem Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation](#), [Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities](#), and [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#), and the [Serious Games for Participatory Planning](#). Notably, the city of Piran was showcased as a best-practice example of how to implement the MCA, CBA, and EBA Catalogue within a CCLL context. This case was detailed both in the MOOC and on the [SCORE website blog](#), offering valuable guidance for future living labs seeking to replicate successful methods. Most recently, ENT hosted a webinar on 28 May 2025 to present MCA outcomes for Vilanova i la Geltrú, and the catalogue was shared at this event to note its use as a practical and easily accessible tool.

Future Impact and Opportunities

A key recommendation is to collect the CCLL case studies and add them as examples to the EBA Catalogue. Upon project finalisation, the key EBA activities in CCLL will be added to the site, with links to the specific CCLL GeoStories for readers.

interested in further information. In terms of the legacy of the website, the Arcgis URL will continue to be live after SCORE. Finally, MIP4Adapt has agreed to share the EBA catalogue to its platform the [Tools Database](#). It has been approved and is currently being drafted by the team.

KER 7.5 - Cost-Benefit Analysis of Ecosystem Based Adaptation measures in SCORE's Coastal City Living Labs

Knowledge Owners: ENT, Naider, ATU, ZRS, TERO **Current Status:** Open access available in deliverable [D7.4: Campos Rodrigues et al., 2025](#)

Description: This KO presents the key findings from WP7, Task 7.4 (and its corresponding deliverable D7.4: Campos Rodrigues et al., 2025), which focuses on the expert-based socio-economic assessment of adaptation interventions, with a particular emphasis on Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA). Specifically, it compares the costs and benefits of EBA measures across the four WP7 frontrunner CCLs, namely: (i) the evaluation of an existing floodable park in Oarsoaldea (Spain); (ii) the restoration of an intermittent river to alleviate inland flooding in Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain); (iii) the restoration of historic water cisterns and open-access green spaces to address drought and heatwaves in Piran (Slovenia); and (iv) beach and dune valuation and management in the context of coastal erosion in Sligo (Ireland). Task 7.4 builds upon T7.3, which conducted a multicriteria analysis (MCA) of EBA options in the SCORE CCLs (KO7.2). The results from T7.3 influenced the selection of EBA measures for all case studies in T7.4.

The analyses were based on the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) methodology outlined in D7.2, 'Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change' (Etxebarria et al., 2022), which provides an indicative guide for implementing the key stages of a CBA (Figure 1).

Implementing the CBA requires specific technical expertise, but it is a common exercise applied by environmental engineers, civil engineers, landscape architects, or general economists. There is some complexity in using CBA, such as considerations for data limitations, relying on modelling capacities on future projections, and general uncertainty about climate change and predictions / projections around this, for example. To run the CBA in the CCLs, the team had to rely on analysis of technical reports / previous knowledge. For replication of this work, it is a benefit to have someone on board to do this analysis. To support this activity relevant settings, D7.2 was written as a practical and accessible guide, providing CCLs and the public with a clear understanding of the key steps involved in applying CBA methods.

Overall, the case studies were inspired in the CBA methodology but were allowed flexibility, meaning that some analyses performed partial-CBA analysis or, in the case of Sligo, a non-comprehensive comparison between the monetary values of ecosystem services – coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreation – with dune management costs.

Figure 1. Main stages for implementing a cost-benefit analysis

Source: Etxebarria et al. (2022), adapted from USAID Adapt Asia-Pacific (2016).

In terms of novelty, a CBA is a well-known tool. However, the application of the MCA and CBA activities being undertaken in each SCORE frontrunner CCLLs is novel to implementing EBAs in these areas. This knowledge on running a CBA on EBAs is unique as each was facilitated differently depending on their local contexts. As such, there is new knowledge generated through this KO.

Impact & Application: This KO contributes to the expanding body of scientific knowledge on the potential benefits of EBA solutions, both as an alternative to and in combination with traditional hard-based measures. The results from the analysis are expected to be disseminated in technical and scientific reports and journals as well as in conferences and similar events, promoting the discussion about the potential benefits of EBA measures.

The detailed case studies developed offer valuable insights to local authorities and other stakeholders, helping to generate greater interest in learning about and potentially supporting the adoption of the solutions analysed in municipalities. This KO also refers to the CBA general methodological guidelines associated with D7.2 (Etxebarria et al., 2022), which are available for consultation by SCORE and non-SCORE partners, and can be, with necessary adjustments, used for other analyses.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO7.1, KO7.2

Priority Target User A: Public Sector actors and local/regional decision makers

Specific Examples. Local and regional public sector entities would be the key stakeholders interested in utilising CBA as a structured methodology to assess and implement Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA) strategies within their own localities.

Local Public Sector entities could include: Municipal Planning Departments responsible for urban planning, land use, and infrastructure development, City Environmental Agencies that oversee local climate adaptation, green spaces, and sustainability initiatives, Coastal and Water Management Authorities who manage flood prevention, coastal resilience, and water resources, and Transport and Mobility Departments which plan public transport and sustainable mobility strategies.

Regional Public Authorities & Decision-Makers, such as: Regional Climate & Energy Agencies (Support sustainable energy transition and climate adaptation), Metropolitan Governance Bodies (Coordinate planning and policy implementation across multiple municipalities), Regional Development Agencies (oversee economic and environmental projects at the regional level), Environmental & Natural Resource Departments (manage biodiversity, air quality, and ecosystem-based adaptation).

- **Role:** The public sector decision-makers are the ones who are ultimately paying and determining which EBAs to implement and where.
- **Key Message:** The participatory-based nature of using an MCA and CBA in combination allows for the incorporation of the perceptions of different stakeholders about the studied adaptation measures. Decision makers, city planning authorities, and municipalities can then use the results of the MCA to run a CBA to evaluate and decide on the most preferred adaptation interventions to implement. These tools should be used as part of the decision process when planning adaptation strategies to climate change. The detailed case studies developed offer valuable insights to local authorities and other stakeholders, helping to generate greater interest in learning about and potentially supporting the adoption of the solutions analysed in municipalities.
- **Awareness:** Though this target user likely has not conducted a CBA themselves, they have likely heard of it as a process. Implementing the CBA requires specific technical expertise, but it is a common exercise applied by environmental engineers, civil engineers, landscape architects, or general economists, which may work alongside policymakers and decision makers within the public sector.
- **Level of Understanding:** There is some complexity in using CBA, such as considerations for data limitations, relying on modelling capacities on future projections, and general uncertainty about climate change and predictions / projections around this, for example. To run the CBA in the CCLLs, the team had to rely on analysis of technical reports and previous knowledge. For replication of this work, it is a benefit to have someone on board to do this analysis. To support

this activity relevant settings, D7.2 was written as a practical and accessible guide, providing CCLLs and the public with a clear understanding of the key steps involved in applying CBA methods.

- **Interest:** While EBAs are becoming more and more popular, largely the interest in the methodology will depend regionally. For those communities with an interest in EBAs, the CBA methodology can support their decision-making process, including both stakeholder perspectives and a more technical assessment. Public opinion & governance/voting cycles ultimately impact the ability to implement EBAs and therefore use this methodology. The CBA methodology also requires these decision-makers to value the perspectives of the quadruple helix in addition to financial considerations.

Priority Target User B: General public and civil society organisations (CSOs)

The public would contribute to the MCA process and thereby influence the CBA selection as well, which would be facilitated largely by target users such as the public sector facilitators and decisionmakers. Some examples of these participants in the MCA process could be those working in climate action (such as climate action networks, youth climate action groups, environmental NGOs, etc.) or local community groups (environmental advocacy groups, biodiversity conservation organisations, neighbourhood associations, local cooperatives). Further, the general public would be interested in the results of the CBA process if it was used within their area and could influence decision-making.

- **Role:** The general public can play a massive role in putting appropriate pressure on the public authorities/decision-makers if they are educated about their options and have appropriate tools to support their perspectives. They can advocate for the use of this methodology and/or the incorporation of the results of an MCA and CBA (such as the chosen EBA solutions) into their communities.
- **Key Message:** Citizens make active choices and engage in their community's future. The MCA/CBA process allows for facilitators to more accurately gain perspectives from local users on a selection of options. As such, this process is a great method for incorporating citizens into the local decision-making process, specifically in the area of climate action.
- **Awareness:** These target users are not likely to be aware of the CBA specifically used within this context. Generally, they may have little knowledge on EBAs as well, however, with an ever-increasing knowledge of climate change and communities actively feeling the effects of the climate crisis, there is an increasing receptivity towards these solutions.
- **Level of Understanding:** In terms of novelty, a CBA is a well-known tool. However, the application of the MCA and CBA activities being undertaken in each SCORE frontrunner CCLLs is novel to implementing EBAs in these areas. This knowledge on running a CBA on EBAs is unique as each was facilitated differently depending on their local contexts. Some education is needed to explain both the idea of EBAs and/or the CBA process to these target users for this exercise to be effective. The idea that these can be co-created and locally embedded would need to be taught to this user group for them to appropriately engage in the process.
- **Interest:** Whilst the general public and civil society are large groups that can vary in their interest, there are certain climate activists and climate change-affected people due to various climatic hazards (i.e., heat waves, coastal erosion, etc.) that would find this of particular interest. They could be interested in utilising a CBA in similar contexts as well, considering the value of assigning costs/benefits to specific climate solutions to make them more understandable to a wider audience. For the general public to properly understand the results of the CBA within their locality and the implications of this, they must be informed about the potential options for implementation in their locality and the specific challenges these solutions aim to address. Therefore, raising awareness of climate challenges and Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA) solutions is crucial to influencing this target group.

Priority Target User C: Academics, Researchers, and Practitioners of EBA solutions

Academics, researchers, and practitioners specialising in Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA) solutions could utilise the MCA methodology in their own context. This could include economists, sociologists, urban sustainability and climate change

specialists, and environmental scientists working within this space. This could also include other EU projects and initiatives that employ participatory approaches—such as those running Living Labs or implementing NBS/EBA in local areas.

- *Role:* Academics and researchers focussing on EBAs or community based participatory methods.
- *Key Message:* The participatory-based nature of using an MCA and CBA in combination allows for the incorporation of the perceptions of different stakeholders about the studied adaptation measures. For academics focussing on the technical side of EBA assessment or implementation, this is a useful tool to gain new perspectives on a proposed solution. Essentially, following a CBA methodology can support academics in connecting with stakeholders and determining the added value of their research on EBAs in real-world contexts.
- *Awareness:* This target group would be keenly aware of EBAs and may have heard of the concept of a CBA.
- *Level of Understanding:* This target group would be very aware of EBAs and their various impacts but likely have not run a CBA before. Further, they may be familiar with participatory approaches as a concept but may not have implemented them in practice within their research.
- *Interest:* This target group would likely have an interest in this output as it could help them extend the assessment and impact of their research on EBAs within a more localized context.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start	IRL Achieved During SCORE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRL 2 – Discovery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IRL 3 – Engagement

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

The methodological steps and key findings from the analyses conducted in the four study areas are detailed in D7.4 and will be open-access for use by SCORE partners. In brief, the analyses were carried out as follows:

- Errenteria, Oarsoaldea (Basque Country, Spain): An *ex-post* analysis was conducted for the period 2003-2044 to assess the role of an existing floodable park to mitigate flooding in the area, compared to an alternative scenario involving the construction of concrete walls to channel the river. The Net Present Value (NPV) of the intervention was calculated by considering avoided losses, highlighting the adaptation benefits.
- Vilanova i la Geltrú (Catalonia, Spain): An *ex-ante* analysis was conducted to evaluate the impact of an intermittent river restoration strategy for flood mitigation, involving a combination of measures, including raising the height of the right riverbank with a levee in the form of an earthen embankment and widening the riverbed channel at selected cross-sections. The analysis covered the period 2024-2065, and the comparison of costs (investment and maintenance) and benefits (avoided losses) was made through the estimation of the NPV.
- Piran (Slovenia): An *ex-ante* analysis was implemented to compare the costs and benefits of renovating and using historical water collection cisterns during drought periods, in contrast to alternative solutions such as water tanks and water trucks. Additionally, the CBA method was applied to the development of four green spaces in the old town and their role in mitigating the effects of heatwaves, among other benefits. Both analyses were conducted for a 42-year period starting in 2024, and evaluated costs and benefits of the respective measures through the NPV.
- Sligo County (Ireland): The analysis examined three beaches in County Sligo—Enniscrone, Strandhill, and Streedagh—by conducting a monetary valuation of the ecosystem services provided by their beach and dune areas, considering shoreline modelling projections for the period from 2024 to 2044. These services included coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreational benefits. Furthermore, the study provided a comparative overview of the costs associated with dune management and explored potential strategies for effective beach and dune conservation.

Overall, the analyses showed that the assessed measures could serve as viable solutions for addressing local climate adaptation challenges. These measures offer not only hazard risk reduction and economic efficiency but also additional complementary benefits. By incorporating nature-based elements, they have the potential to deliver ecosystem services that are often

overlooked in traditional grey infrastructure. However, achieving more effective climate change adaptation at the local level requires a hybrid approach, blending EBA with both hard and soft strategies.

Sharing results internally with SCORE CCLLs: Dissemination within CCLLs was conducted internally, through the communication of the results with the frontrunner CCLL teams. The team shared the methodology and the results of this work, and discussed the possibility of implementing the assessed measures by municipalities. Further, results then shared with CCLL partners at a CCLL board meeting in 2025, where the results were communicated internally to the followers and a discussion was facilitated for knowledge transfer.

External Engagement

The D7.5 Policy Guidelines ([link](#)) references this deliverable by stating that socio-economic assessment methods are fundamental for making well-informed decisions regarding climate change adaptation, noting that effective decision-making relies on systematic information and data analysed by experts, as well as the incorporation of stakeholders' perspectives. Piran was used as a best-practice example of the MCA, CBA, and EbA catalogue implementation and iterations in a CCLL context for the [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#), where the experience is detailed for future CCLLs to better understand best practices, and its associated MOOC [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#). This best case study was also shared as a [blog](#) on the SCORE website.

A preprint publication on the Sligo results will be available as an open access article on Zenodo after publication - *Assessing the value of coastal dunes and beaches in Northwest Ireland: An Ecosystem Service Valuation Approach* has been resubmitted to the journal International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction.

The CBA methodology followed by SCORE and the results have been shared at a number of events. Primarily, the CBA was highlighted at the SCORE Final Event at the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025) in both the presentation sessions and at the demonstration sessions, as well as at the LITTORAL conference (September 2024), and EBA Training Schools (2025) in conjunction with MCA results. At a [KRPAN](#) networking event in September 2024, Piran partners presented *Preserving, mapping and revalorisation of historic freshwater storage infrastructures to address water scarcity*. Additionally, at final events in frontrunner cities of Sligo (March 2025), Vilanova i la Geltrú (May 2025) and Oarsoaldea (May 2025), the CBA results were presented to key interested stakeholder groups within their respective municipalities.

The CBA has been featured on the [Horizon Results Platform](#). Further, it has been featured in SCORE Feature on the [Nature Based Solutions Platform](#) to disseminate WP7 results to peer learning networks. Additionally, the wider outputs of the SCORE project were featured on this group's [LinkedIn group](#), which has over 46,000 current followers.

Future Impact and Opportunities

Following its publication, D7.4 will be shared across the SCORE website, relevant web repositories, and is recommended to be shared through the communication channels of the contributing organisations, including newsletters and social media platforms. The momentum around the findings should continue to build, with ZRS and TERO expressing strong interest in developing research papers based on the current CBA results, aiming to expand dissemination and raise targeted awareness.

At the same time, ENT was progressing with a scientific publication centered on the Vilanova case study. Their plan was to submit the paper before the end of 2025. Naider, too, was considering turning the Oarsoaldea findings into a journal article, exploring options for scientific dissemination.

Meanwhile, videos summarising key results from the CCLL board meeting were produced and made accessible to all CCLLs, and it is recommended to include these videos into the frontrunner CCLL GeoStories to enhance visibility and engagement. As activities continued, a general reminder was issued to all partners to promote the use and visibility of these outcomes in the short term.

The SCORE partners leading the CBA in the four frontrunners have expertise in the development of this and other methods focusing on the socioeconomic assessment of adaptation measures. This knowledge and expertise are expected to be put into practice in future research calls at the EU, national and regional levels. The results of the CBA conducted in the four CCLL frontrunners can inform future technical projects focused on designing the evaluated measures for real implementation.

3.3.1. Digital Twin & Data Visualisation

KER4.1 - SCORE Catalogue of low-cost sensors viable for citizen science activities

Knowledge Owners: UCD, ATU, MBI

Current Status: Open Access – active on <https://sensors.score-eu-project.eu/> and on [UCD Spatial Dynamics Lab github](#).

Description: The sensor catalogue is an online platform that helps stakeholders involved in community-based environmental monitoring initiatives to collect, structure, manage and publish information and metadata about a variety of low-cost sensing devices designed to measure crucial environmental factors relevant to numerous coastal cities worldwide. Each device entry is linked to specific environmental hazards defined by the initiative(s) scope, as well as to the parameters they aim to measure. The platform then displays a structured catalogue of suitable sensing technologies that have been chosen considering both technical and social aspects, including their affordability (roughly €100-€2,600) and simplicity in assembly and deployment, making them accessible for public involvement. Once the catalogue data is populated, it supports the exploration, comparison, selection and deployment of sensing devices, helping to plan and set-up co-monitoring activities where the sensor data can complement data from institutional sensors by engaging local stakeholders in monitoring efforts.

Usability: [The catalogue](#) is designed around a number of environmental parameters to be monitored which were identified by the SCORE Coastal City Living Labs (CCLL):

- Water levels
- Surface waves topography
- Rainfall
- Erosion
- Water quality
- Air temperature
- Soil moisture
- Atmospheric pressure
- Wind speed

The catalogue itself is currently hosted on a website to enable the CCLLs to select their own sensors and access resources/manuals specific to each sensor. The web platform is easy-to use and allows for users to determine the sensors that would be best fit for purpose for their specific environmental monitoring goals and needs. There are two main components of the catalogue:

1. *Database* – The back end where the catalogue is built that allows stakeholders (e.g. manager roles, CCLL core team) to add new sensors or adjust the information and parameters of the catalogue.
2. *Digital tool* - The main front-end of the catalogue that prioritises ease of use for a non-expert to discover, evaluate options, select and build proposals based on a budget, etc.: it displays the catalogue for use by those interested in searching for relevant sensors based on specific environmental hazards, monitored parameters, operational complexity, cost, etc.

Impact & Application: The low-cost sensor catalogue is a valuable resource for those involved in community-based environmental monitoring and citizen science activities focused on climate mitigation and resilience. This could most likely be the following:

- **Municipalities/Local Government/NGOs** - environmental scientists, planners, climate change officers, community-facing staff.
- **Academic/Research** - researchers working with; citizen science, smart cities, low-cost sensing technology, and environmental science.

The low-cost sensor catalogue can facilitate a wide range of applications, from municipal environmental monitoring and urban planning to academic research in citizen science, smart cities, low-cost sensing technology, and environmental science. It has the potential to empower communities, improve decision-making, and advance understanding of environmental issues in both urban and rural settings. Notably, the utilisation of the catalogue will expedite the process and the uptake of citizen science activities.

Impacts of partaking in citizen science activities for sensing are as follows:

- **Urban Planning:** Planners can integrate sensor data into their urban development plans to create more sustainable and resilient cities. For example, data on heat islands can inform decisions about green space allocation and tree planting; to mitigate urban heat.
- **Climate Change Adaptation:** Climate change officers can use sensor data to assess the impact of climate change on their regions and develop adaptation plans. For instance, monitoring sea level rise and storm surges can inform strategies to protect coastal areas.
- **Community Engagement:** Community-facing staff can involve local residents in data collection and analysis, fostering citizen science projects. This engagement can raise awareness about environmental issues and build a sense of community ownership in sustainability efforts.
- **Smart Cities Development:** Data from low-cost sensors can contribute to the development of smart cities by providing real-time information for city management and improving the quality of life for residents.
- **Validation of Low-Cost Sensing Technology:** Researchers can use this tool to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of low-cost sensing technology in real-world settings, contributing to the advancement of sensor technology.
- **Data Integration:** Data from these sensors can be integrated with other datasets, such as satellite imagery or official monitoring station data, to enhance the scope and accuracy of research in environmental science, climate change, and urban studies

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO5.1 SCORE ICT Platform, KO5.2 SensorThings API ALT, KO5.3 ICT Visualisations - GeoStories, Surveys, etc., KO5.4 SensorThings Application

Priority Target User A: Other EU-Funded projects with citizen science components

Academics or researchers working with; citizen science, smart cities, low-cost sensing technology, and environmental science. Examples of projects targeted are the CitiObs project, Urban ReLeaf, TwinAir, ScienceUs, iCHANGE, HERITACT.

- **Role:** To use the catalogue to make informed decisions on the best sensors to use, and gain knowledge/examples on past usage to educate future users/citizens.
- **Key Message:** The low-cost sensor catalogue can facilitate a wide range of applications, such as academic research in citizen science, smart cities, low-cost sensing technology, and environmental science. It has the potential to improve decision-making, and advance understanding of environmental issues in both urban and rural settings to maximise the impact of environmental research. Notably, the utilisation of the catalogue will expedite the process and the uptake of citizen science activities.
- **Awareness:** This target user would likely be very aware of citizen science activities and use of sensors, but not of the catalogue itself.

- *Level of Understanding:* This target user likely has strong expertise in citizen science activities, and the use of various different sensors for coastal monitoring but may need additional activity ideas or further details about how sensors can best be utilised.
- *Interest:* This target user is likely actively seeking information on sensors and would be interested in determining the best options for their specific means or projects.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 3 – Engagement

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 4 – Implementation

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

WP4 developed and shared the low-cost sensors catalogue framework as a foundational resource to support evidence-based decision-making across all 10 CCLLs, through facilitated multi-stakeholder workshops, engaging local authorities, academia, and citizens to co-select sensors aligned with local hazards and monitoring priorities. The team further promoted stakeholder-driven sensor selection strategies, balancing citizen engagement goals through use of this tool (e.g. low-cost, high-volume sensors), and actively involved local authorities, communities, and researchers in shaping the criteria and decision-making process behind localised sensor deployment.

This sensor catalogue was developed into a platform that was directly used by CCLL teams to purchase selected sensors for their particular needs. This method to engage stakeholders developed by UCD was piloted in Dublin CCLL and further successfully tested in other CCLLs, which included workshops for hands-on assembly, troubleshooting, and onboarding, with training provided to stakeholders to ensure knowledge transfer and local ownership. Iterative feedback loops took place with the Dublin CCLL where stakeholders helped refine the SCORE Catalogue, onboarding and deployment process for broader rollout to all 10 CCLLs.

The pilot activities in CCLLs demonstrated how SCORE sensor catalogue could be sustainably scaled, making the results actionable in both community-led and institutional settings. All CCLLs have used the catalogue to select their sensors. Either the core team selected the relevant sensors depending on the parameters they need to monitor, or they consulted with their wider stakeholder networks to identify the most useful sensors depending on the CCLLs wider priorities and goals (i.e. numerous, cheap sensors to engage a large number of citizens, or fewer, more expensive sensors to provide higher quality data to assist with institutional sensor networks). As such, this provides real-life examples of the use of the sensors in the work of the CCLLs.

Using the catalogue of low-cost sensors, workshops were carried out with leading CCLLs of Dublin, Sligo, Oeiras, Vilanova, and Massa. The first of these workshops was held in Dun Laoghaire during May 2023. Representatives from public administration (local authorities, utilities, etc.) and academia (UCD, ATU Sligo) from both Sligo and Dublin CCLLs came together to shortlist sensors that addressed the most pressing hazards in their local areas. The groups (approximately 30 attendees) identified a list of sensors to be purchased with the available budget using the catalogue web platform and identified the stakeholders to be engaged, any barriers, management strategies, etc. The results of this workshop were analysed, and the CCLL core team decided on the final set of sensors to be purchased and groups to be involved in their deployment.

The framework used for DIY citizen science workshops in the SCORE project demonstrated the potential for meaningful public engagement and knowledge creation in scientific research utilising tools such as the low-cost sensors catalogue. The selection and deployment of sensors, along with troubleshooting techniques, were designed to ensure a comprehensive approach to citizen science activities. These workshops served as valuable platforms for collaboration between public administration, academia, and local stakeholders, fostering a sense of connection and responsibility towards the scientific community and addressing local environmental challenges effectively. Further pilot activities for sensor selection and onboarding were then planned with the core CCLL teams in Dublin, Sligo, Oeiras, Vilanova, and Massa. By the end of these activities, the goal was to have refined the sensor onboarding process to enable citizens to actively participate in assembling and deploying sensors independently or through workshops, with the aim of extending this resource to all 10 CCLLs involved in the SCORE project.

The low-cost sensors catalogue was used across the project to support citizen science activities and provide data to their wider CCLL networks. The catalogue provided them with opportunities for sensor selection and extended the impact of these activities in tangible ways. Across the CCLLs, the following activities took place:

- **Vilanova:** Vilanova involved schools and the community in using low-cost sensors to monitor weather and environmental conditions. Activities included deploying sensors in schools and rural properties during the forest fire prevention campaign, as well as presenting wetland restoration sites to the local community. During European Green Week 2023, workshops and visits to sensor installations were organized for educational purposes. The sensors used included Smart Citizen Water/soil stations, Weather stations, Hobo, Art Sewer, and Smart LNB.
- **Oarsoaldea:** In Oarsoaldea, citizen science activities focused on deploying sensors in schools for environmental monitoring, including meteorological stations, water quality sensors, and climate monitoring sites.
- **Benidorm:** Benidorm conducted citizen science activities primarily with high school students experimenting with low-cost sensors such as weather stations and video cameras. These sensors were installed in various strategic locations, including hotel rooftops and the marina. Efforts to involve citizens through social networks and direct engagement were made. The team also worked on engaging citizens for the deployment of water level sensors, Lidar, and the CoastSnap platform.
- **Dublin:** In Dublin, the main activities involved recruiting community groups, local schools, and academic partners to participate in the SCORE project. Key participants included Dalkey Tidy Towns, Birdwatch Ireland, and several local schools. The stakeholders were engaged in multiple workshops for sensor selection, onboarding and troubleshooting workshops. Smart Citizen Kits, Weather Stations were deployed at public buildings and citizen homes. Citizens and students also assembled and deployed Smart Pebbles for tidal and erosion studies, as well as weather stations and air quality monitors. Data from these sensors were displayed on the SCORE CCLL Geosurvey and analyzed by Dún Laoghaire–Rathdown County Council, enhancing local understanding of weather patterns, air quality, and tidal processes.
- **Gdansk:** Gdansk organized workshops and meetings with stakeholders to deploy various sensors, such as art sewers, optical rain sensors, weather stations, pluviometers, moisture sensors, PLS level sensors, and Hobo. Local water management companies and educational institutions supported sensor installation and data collection.
- **Massa:** Massa deployed various low-cost sensors, including weather stations, video cameras, smart pebbles, smart LNB, and hydrometers. These sensors were used to monitor weather conditions and capture visual data to assess environmental changes and support early warning systems.
- **Piran:** Piran early on focused on engaging local high school students and community groups in utilizing sensors for environmental monitoring and early warning systems. Despite some challenges in broader citizen engagement, they planned to conduct more workshops with stakeholders. Eventually the sensors have been installed on premises of and will be maintained by the municipal environment and waste disposal company, which are near sites of environmental interest throughout the municipality and the sensor network will consist out of weather stations as wells as several sea level gauges.
- **Samsun:** In Samsun, a citizen science event was held where high school and university students examined a weather station using low-cost sensors as part of the SCORE Project in May 2024. Activities also included collaboration with Meteorological Engineering students to plan educational initiatives for high schools, integrating information about citizen science and sensors. The sensors used included soil moisture sensors, water/soil stations, RLS, Smart Pebbles, wave gauges, and general low-cost weather sensors.
- **Sligo:** Sligo engaged citizens in environmental monitoring through the deployment of low-cost sensors and educational activities aimed at raising awareness and collecting valuable environmental data. The team deployed smart pebbles, CoastSnap, kite aerial images, and Smart Citizen Kits for water quality sensors.
- **Oeiras:** In Oeiras, the main activities involved the selection and public procurement of seven hydrological sensors and the establishment of four meteorological stations through stakeholder engagement. Interestingly, it was through this work that the catalogue was iterated, as selected sensors from the catalogue were not accessible to the Portuguese CCLL. To remedy this, the Oeiras CCLL worked with UCD to update the catalogue to include sensors that were applicable to their own context, thereby expanding the options available within the catalogue. A collaborative workshop in 2023 identified optimal sensor locations, leading to the successful deployment of these sensors. The sensors, which included water level and water detection sensors as well as meteorological stations, transmitted data to the Oeiras Municipality LoRa network server to enhance community resilience against hydrological hazards.

External Engagement

The work to create the sensors catalogue has been captured in the following publications:

- Ahmed, T., Creedon, L., Gharbia, S. *Low-Cost Sensors for Monitoring Coastal Climate Hazards: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis*. (2023). *Sensors* 23(3), 1717. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23031717>
- *Report on low-cost sensors viable for citizen science activities is available on zenodo*: <https://zenodo.org/records/11242082>

The Sensors Catalogue and the subsequent work done by the SCORE CCLLs has been shared at multiple conferences. This includes ICoGB, 3rd International Conference on Green Buildings, (26-04-2025, **Authors:** Harish Daruari; Chiara Cocco, José P. Gómez Barrón, Francesco Pilla, “Empowering Urban Coastal Communities through Citizen Science: A Framework for Low-Cost Sensor Management and Deployment in Living Labs” (Publication under review)) and EGU 25, European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly (Harish Daruari; Saul Crowley; Chiara Cocco; José P. Gómez Barrón, “Building Equitable Air Quality Networks: Low-Cost Sensors and Community-Led Monitoring in Dublin” <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu25-1073>). Further dissemination of the catalogue to interested participants took place at ENOLL OpenLivingLab Days (2023), EU Week of Regions and Cities (2024), the SCORE Ecosystem Based Adaptation Training Schools (2023-2025), European Maritime Day (2025), and SCORE Final Event at European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (2025).

Additionally, the sensors catalogue has been shared across all [CCLL GeoStories](#) to give context to sensor selection activities, and is particularly highlighted in a Dublin GeoStory. The Sensors Catalogue is also available on the [Horizon Results Platform](#), and was featured in webinar [Engaging and empowering citizens with low-cost sensors for monitoring climate change hazards](#) (March 2024). A Press release was released in December 2023 on the citizen science activities, featuring the work of developing and using the catalogue - [D4.4 Citizen Science Press Release](#). Finally, the catalogue is detailed in several SCORE Online Learning Massive Open Online Courses - [Ecosystem Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation](#), [Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities](#). A best-practice story on how the sensors catalogue was used and adapted by the Oeiras CLL was shared in [an online blog](#), the [D2.4 Lessons Learned Deliverable](#) and its associated MOOC [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE’s 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#).

Future Impact and Opportunities

Next steps for the Sensors Catalogue:

Steps to ensure the Sensors Catalogue is available for future use have been taken. The sensor catalogue is available for public use via a web platform for future access and reference, which is hosted permanently on a UCD Spatial Dynamics Lab domain. With the catalogue being open and maintained online by UCD, data for sensors included in the catalogue that have an automatic onboarding connection already set, can be accessed through the SensorThings API (See KO 5.2). This allows that new citizen scientist or future projects using a sensor device from the SCORE catalogue to onboard it and to have available the sensor data to develop their own web maps and data visualization tools, apart from the SCORE CCLLs Sensors Map. The sensors catalogue web application codebase is publicly available for anyone to use and modify for their own project requirements on the [UCD Spatial Dynamics Lab github](#) at this link: [SCORE Sensor Catalogue](#), which will continue to be managed by the Spatial Dynamics Lab GitHub.

The sensors catalogue application will be further developed by UCD to complete its fully integration and connection with a STA/STA+ instance, so the sensor devices data and metadata entries in a deployed catalogue are automatically transfer to any set API (STA/STA+) instance. The sensor catalogue app database model will be updated to align with STA/STA+ data models, the information entered and managed through a sensors catalogue will be used to set the STA entities required by other applications, especially the Sensors Onboarding, and Sensors Registration and Data Uploader to work. The STA instance thus acts as the central hub where catalogue definitions are operationalized into live sensor deployments and data collection workflows.

Then the sensor catalogue app is planned to work as a one of the components of an information system for community-based environmental monitoring and citizen science initiatives. This system will build and connect components for sensing devices data management including their onboarding and registration, sensor data transfer, geospatial and data visualization, all powered by the OGC SensorThings API (STA/STA+) integration at the core data infrastructure for storing, accessing, and managing environmental sensor data.

Based on the development plans explained above, any citizen science initiative, living lab or citizen observatory looking for a technology stack to be deployed for having their own community-based environmental monitoring information system, can use it from exploring and curating sensing technologies, to onboard them and to create sensor data streams endpoints for mapping and data visualizations. Additionally, other projects focused on enhancing citizen science that are already using the STA/STA+ open standard in their work, such as CitiObs project where UCD is also involved, can benefit from this development.

The UCD team is preparing tutorials about the different functionalities of the catalogue, and any new integration with other applications. Also guides for content management, oriented to stakeholders in charge to create and edit devices entries. The tutorials are currently being drafted and should be produced in the next few months following project completion.

Integration with wider Information System for Community-based Environmental Monitoring and Citizen Science

The Sensors Catalogue is being integrated within a broader sensor data information system that includes several components: Sensors Database and Application Programming Language (API), Sensors Onboarding, Sensors Registration and Data Uploader and Sensors Map. This interconnected system enables users to select suitable sensors via the SCORE Sensor Catalogue, onboard them through an Onboarding or Registration App instance, and then view the live-streamed data from the deployed sensors on the SCORE CCLLs Sensors Map for example. At the core of the system components integration is API component that is using the Open Geospatial Consortium standard SensorThings API (OGC STA), extended with STA+ to target citizen science specific needs.

The WP4 team is currently advancing the integration of the Sensor Catalogue into the wider SCORE Information System to enhance community-based environmental monitoring and citizen science efforts. This work is focused on creating a unified, interoperable ecosystem that connects sensor hardware, data ingestion, metadata management, and user interaction tools. The Sensors Catalogue will be integrated more fluidly with the wider SCORE ICT platform (KO5.1), with links to the SensorThings API ALT (KO5.2), the ICT Visualisations - GeoStories, Surveys, etc. (KO5.3), and SensorThings Application (KO5.4). Following this integration, the platform will continue to be available after SCORE. The figure below shows the different elements of the platform that are currently being integrated.

At present, the system remains partially fragmented. Some sensors are yet to be onboarded, and various data streams are not yet fully integrated into visualisation platforms. However, significant progress has been made, and a cohesive system is expected to be operational in the coming months, requiring minimal manual configuration.

The Sensor Catalogue functions as the entry point for registering and managing diverse sensing devices used across CCLL. This catalogue is being linked directly to the system's core, the SensorThings API (KO5.2) which includes dedicated extensions for citizen science use cases. This API serves as the foundation for all data exchange and interoperability. An important advancement is the use of metadata based on OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) standards. This enables structured sensor descriptions,

data ownership definitions, licensing, and user management, laying the groundwork for scalable, transparent, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices.

From the Sensor Catalogue, data is processed through several interconnected applications:

- **Sensor Onboarding Tool:** This web-based tool will provide a step-by-step interface for adding sensors, with visual guides, deployment recommendations, and configuration tips. It is particularly useful for community-managed devices such as Smart Citizen Kits and weather stations. The onboarding tool also supports integration with third-party APIs, enabling automatic data transfer from commercial platforms directly into the SensorThings API.
- **Sensor Registration and Data Uploader (KO5.4):** This lightweight application, also developed under Work Package 5, allows users to manually register sensors and upload data—especially useful for offline or non-networked sensors (e.g., HOBO sensors or RT water level sensors). Users can download data locally (e.g., as CSV files) and upload it into the system via a simple interface connected to the central database.
- **Event Reporting Application:** A mobile-friendly tool is being designed to document environmental events, such as storms or flooding. Users can upload photos, add descriptions, and capture geolocation data via their mobile devices. This application extends the concept of “sensors” to include user-generated content as valuable data points.

All three tools are being integrated with a centralised user management system (KO5.1 SCORE ICT Platform) that accommodates institutional accounts (e.g., CCLLs) and individual contributors (e.g., citizen scientists). This ensures traceability, accountability, and secure access control.

Once fully integrated, these components will feed directly into a unified data stream environment. The system will support advanced visualisations, dashboards, and interactive maps—moving beyond static time series to include event notifications and real-time insights. These enhancements will be driven by middleware APIs and linked visualisation layers currently under development.

In the coming weeks, access credentials and usage instructions will be distributed to all CCLLs, enabling them to begin using the full suite of tools far beyond the end of the project, adapted to their own needs and contexts.

KER 5.1 - SCORE Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Platform

Knowledge Owners : UNIPI, TERO

Current Status: Available for browsing by everyone at <https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/#/>. Data upload and content creation (Geostories, Dashboards) allowed only to project partners.

Description: The SCORE ICT Platform (SIP) is an integrated digital platform that acts to collect and share data within the project communities, researchers, and stakeholders of Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) within the SCORE project. The platform can be used for three key purposes:

- **Data repository:** The SIP can be utilised as an internal SCORE data catalogue, for sharing datasets and resources between teams and departments. Resources can be enriched with metadata that provides details about data contents and their lineage – how it was produced, acquired and processed, who is the author, the licensing, the meaning of its structure and content, etc. This allows for easy data exchange and allows data owners to adjust permissions or restrict access to the data sources. A user would not require an account on the SIP for public resources. For the creation of content, CCLLs and any other stakeholder will need an account that can be created by administrators.
- **Data collection:** Data can be collected via sensors or other sources and brought to the platform through a novel interface, SensorThings API. This allows the platform to address the heterogeneity of collected data formats and standardise the data to ensure data interoperability. When data is collected from APIs (through sensors, for example) it is then processed through this interface and uploaded in a readable format onto the SIP. This allows for easy access to different types of data. This element is detailed in KO5.2 - Data Harvestor and SensorThings API.
- **Data visualisation:** The SIP also supports the coordination and visualisation of the data. As such, more visually dynamic representations of the data can be achieved through platform elements such as GeoStories, Dashboards, and Maps.

Individuals or groups can upload datasets for use by wider platform users. Users can add metadata that has been shared by others and assign data to specific CCLs. Subsequently, maps and other visual tools within the SIP (i.e., maps, GeoStories, Dashboards, GeoApps) can be deployed to visualise the data. These visualisations, datasets or other outputs can be shared to other publishing platforms (blogs, etc) for wider distribution. *This element is detailed further in KO5.3 - SCORE ICT Platform Digitalisation Tools.*

As a platform within SCORE, the SIP works to 1) integrate knowledge about the efficacy of NBS/EBA (Nature-Based Solutions, Ecosystem-Based Adaptation) against extreme events, sea level rise and coastal erosion risks; and 2) provide data to support the development of digital twin solutions for instant monitoring/control of climate resilience and smart city early warnings in case of extreme events. Further, the help page provides all the basic knowledge required to use and navigate the platform's pages and tools, allowing for easy use by partners.

Novelty: The SIP offers a uniquely open source, deeply customisable and secured infrastructure to host and serve spatial and documental resources, produced and exchanged within the research project. It can be, at the same time, the official portal to the project's datasets (Spatial Data Infrastructure, SDI) exposed over standard services (Open Geospatial Consortium, OGC; International Organization for Standardization, ISO; INSPIRE), and as an internal data repository that supports both UI (User-Interface) tools and REST API (REpresentational State Transfer, Application Program Interface) interfaces for complete resource management.

Technical Elements:

- Hardware and software – The platform is implemented on a general-purpose state-of-the-art cloud server. The platform is developed using industry-standard OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) open-source software. This means the source code can be used without license fees, freely analysed for quality and safety checks, and extended and modified by anyone.
- Data – The SIP collects data from the past (historical time series data), the present (real-time raw data from sensors) and the future (processed data from climate models and city simulators developed by the partners) for early warning systems and long-term climate change and socio-economic risk assessments based on pre and post EBA intervention data. The value and effective usage of any dataset depends on this meta-information. The same datasets can be shared with the public thanks to the fine-grained access control, making the same repository an open-data catalogue for sharing.
- SensorThings API & Data Harvester (KO5.2 – See linked KO's for more details): This is the novel interface that allows the platform to address the heterogeneity of collected data formats and standardise the data to ensure data interoperability.

The Platform – All the basic SIP functionalities related to the sharing of SCORE project data will be kept operational for several more years. However, it is important to note that after the conclusion of the project, the platform will remain without maintenance and that events may occur that could limit its life, including 1) the need to perform mandatory updates of the software development system; 2) the occurrence of incompatibilities with the software following hardware updates; 3) the need to implement urgent interventions to fill security holes in the system. In all these cases, the platform may no longer be operational. However, thanks to its flexible architecture, the platform lends itself to upgrades rather easily, and thus it will be possible to introduce new features and carry out further developments.

Impact & Application: SIP Platform will ensure long-term data storage and will therefore represent an efficient tool for sharing knowledge on EBAs generated through the SCORE project. As such, the SIP Platform will ensure long-term data storage and will therefore represent an efficient tool for sharing knowledge on EBAs. The SIP can be used as a case study for other projects interested in creating similar platforms. This SCORE platform is specific to SCORE but can be used as a case study for the development of other platforms to be used by other projects or initiatives. Thus, concerning the CCLs using or adopting this technology beyond SCORE, it turns out that: i) the SIP will live beyond the end of the SCORE project as a data marketplace pending no need for large updates; ii) the adoption of this technology by other CCLs in the framework of some future projects is definitely feasible at no cost. The open-source code to create a similar platform is available on [GitHub](#).

Linked Knowledge Outputs:

- **KO5.2 - SensorThings Application Programming Interface (API) and Data Harvesters:** This output, interconnected with the SCORE ICT Platform, focuses on solving the challenge of collecting sensor data from diverse formats. It uses Data Harvesters to pull data from various sources and the SensorThings API to standardise spatial data, ensuring interoperability and supporting the collection of data from sources including citizen science activities. This system is crucial for bringing heterogeneous data into a unified format for use within the SCORE project.
- **KO5.3 - Visualisation Suite for Project Data Communication and Sensor Data Collection:** As an element of the larger ICT Platform, this KO is dedicated to the hosting, sharing, and visualisation of project data. It provides specific tools within the platform such as Maps, Dashboards, and GeoStories to create dynamic, interactive representations of data. These tools are designed to be user-friendly, facilitating the communication of project activities, results, and knowledge on topics like EBAs both internally among partners and externally to wider audiences
- **KO5.4 - SCORE Citizen Science Sensor Data Upload Application:** This is a mobile-friendly web application designed to simplify the process of connecting, uploading, and managing sensor data for both technical and non-technical users, such as citizen scientists. The application is key to standardising heterogeneous sensor data by mapping it automatically to the SensorThings API model, which enhances data interoperability and facilitates the integration of community-generated data. Although it does not provide visualisations itself, it plays a vital role in enabling consistent data flow into the SIP and adhering to technical data standards.

Priority Target User A: Practitioners working in climate adaptation, city planning, and/or data management

Specific Examples.

- **Role:** This target user would likely work in the climate office of a municipality or hold a data management role. Their responsibilities would include developing and implementing climate action strategies. They are identified as researchers or practitioners who need to manage or visualise large amounts of data within a locality, particularly relevant to those in city planning or climate action offices within municipal or regional governments.
- **Key Message:** The SIP offers a uniquely open source, deeply customisable and secured infrastructure to host and serve spatial and documental resources, produced and exchanged within a municipality or research project.
- **Awareness:** *These target users may use multiple data platforms already. However, they likely do not have an integrated platform that works in the specific way the SIP does*
- **Level of Understanding:** *To utilise the features of the existing SIP, this target user would require minimal training to navigate the site, as it is user-friendly and readable. However, to utilise a SIP designed to be fit-for-purpose for a specific locality, which will be integrated with the Digital Twin (KO8.1), technical skills are necessary, and they would require some training to use it. Generally, any user would need some technical skills to know how to upload data for a project and should have some training on how to use the site effectively. [A user guide](#) exists to assist with uploading data and creating GeoStories.*
- **Interest:** A user is likely searching for a way to integrate large amounts of data for climate studies or projects relevant to their municipality.

Priority Target User B: Other EU Projects, academics, and researchers that need to manage or visualise large amounts of data for projects

- **Role:** This group includes researchers, academics (such as urban sustainability and climate change specialists, geographers, environmental scientists), and individuals involved in other large-scale EU projects, such as the Interreg AMMIRARE project. They would likely be seeking a method to manage large amounts of data for a project or research study

- *Key Message:* The SIP offers a uniquely open source, deeply customisable, and secured infrastructure to host and serve spatial and documental resources. This infrastructure is produced and exchanged within a large research project. The platform's innovative and beneficial nature addresses the target users' needs.
- *Awareness:* Users in this category would likely be familiar with ICT platforms in general, but not specifically with that of the SIP
- *Level of Understanding:* To utilise the features of the existing SIP, this target user would require minimal training to navigate the site as it is user-friendly and readable. To utilise a SIP designed to be fit-for-purpose for a specific locality, technical skills are necessary. This is because the SIP will be integrated with the Digital Twin and would require some training to use. A user would need some technical skills to know how to upload data for use by a project and should have some training on how to use the site effectively. However, training on the benefits of the SIP (such as data visualisation or data management) should be minimal, as they would be familiar with the uses of such a platform.
- *Interest:* The target user would likely be seeking a method to manage large amounts of data for a project or research study. As such, they may be seeking out options for ICT platforms.

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start

- IRL 2 – Discovery

IRL Achieved During SCORE

- IRL 4 - Implementation

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) actively engaged with the SCORE Information Platform (SIP) by collecting sensor data, testing the Sensor Data Uploader Application (KO5.4), and creating visualisations such as GeoStories and dashboards to showcase local climate adaptation efforts. These activities were supported by tools enabling data sharing, community engagement, and enhanced communication strategies. The SIP and its components, including KO5.4, were tested and refined through pilot projects with CCLLs, ensuring real-world applicability and responsiveness to user needs.

External Engagement

The SIP has been detailed in a key publications: Paranunzio, R., Anton, I., Adirosi, E., Ahmed, T., Baldini, L., Brandini, C., ... & Gharbia, S. (2024). A new approach towards a user-driven coastal climate service to enhance climate resilience in European cities. *Sustainability*, 16(1), 335. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16010335>

The SIP was discussed at the EGU General Assembly in 2022 and captured in the following publication: Anton, I., Paranunzio, R., Gharbia, S., Baldini, L., Ahmed, T., Giannetti, F., Brandini, C., Ortolani, A., Meulenberg, C. Adirosi, E., Hawke, S., Pilla, F., Iglesias Rodriguez, J.G. (2022). Challenges in retrieving and using climate services' data for local-scale impact studies: insights from the SCORE project. EGU General Assembly 2022. <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU22/EGU22-5469.html>

The SIP's open-source nature means it can be deployed and hosted freely by anyone, facilitating potential use by external parties. Third-party projects can be granted authorised access to the SIP API. The SIP was developed using GeoNode, an open source web-based application and development environment for geospatial information systems (GIS) and spatial data infrastructures (SDI). GeoNode is available on GitHub repository ([link](#)). The SIP has been featured in the webinar [Collecting and managing environmental data: the SCORE ICT Platform](#), the [Horizon Results Platform](#) and has been featured in SCORE Online Learning's Massive Open Online Courses - [Ecosystem Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation](#), [Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities](#), and [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#). GeoStories developed by the CCLLs have been disseminated to local actor and promoted on social media. Given the SIP's open access to visualisation, a Geostory is a powerful tool for disseminating the actions and narrative of the CCLLs — and, consequently, of the platform itself. GeoStory is a MapStore tool integrated in GeoNode that provides the user a way to create inspiring and immersive stories related to CCLLs by combining text, interactive maps, and other multimedia content like images and video or other third-party contents.

Future Impact and Opportunities

The SIP is the only system for data management for climate resilience that integrates a number of products and allows for real-time data collection and works in conjunction with the SCORE Digital Twin (KO8.1). As such, a business plan is under development for the SIP, alongside other SCORE technologies. Specifically, the outline of the business plan will encompass these technologies, such as the connection to the Data Harvesters and SensorThings API (KO5.2), and its connection to the Digital Twin (KO8.1), and the visualisation suite for project data communication and sensor data collection (KO5.3), which is an element of the SIP. ATU, MBI, TERO, UCD and UNIPI partners held several meetings over the last year of the project to discuss next actions.

It was concluded that in the long term, the proposed business model could focus on selling services related to the core software, including providing a tailored SIP designed for a specific locality or project. Customisation and integration services will utilise the underlying technologies (Data Harvesters and SensorThings API).

However, in order to further the potential of the applications, and increasing the TRL and IRLs, further larger-scale EU projects will be highly beneficial to continue the development. The intended customers for this business initiative are anticipated to include city administrations, research institutes, and other institutions dealing with territory management, environmental protection, climate change policies, and similar areas. The key objective to continue the work of the SIP is to continue research and iteration of this resource through additional project opportunities. Partners will identify future calls to advertise the use of the SIP for future EU projects and research initiatives, and promotion is planned on the Horizon Results Platform and relevant EU Calls (CL6-2025-02-COMMUNITIES-03).

KER 8.1 – SCORE Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System

Knowledge Owners: MBI, CNR-ISAC, ATU, Tero, UCD, UNIPI
Current Status: Available as a service for externals (KTP8.1a) and as a completed output accessible for frontrunner CCLLs (KTP 8.1b) and as a service for fellow CCLLs (KTP8.1c)

Description:

System Architecture: The SCORE Digital Twin system is composed of two main blocks, the User Scenario Evaluation (USE) subsystem and the Early-Warning Support (EWS) subsystem.

The User Scenario Evaluation (USE) subsystem is employed for running simulations enabling what-if and long-term analyses on scenarios built by users combining real, ground-truth data from a coastal city, and hypothetical data, e.g., regarding weather events, sea state, and solutions based on Ecosystem-based Adaptations (EBAs) implemented within the urban study area. At present, there is a library of scenarios that could occur. Users can select from these scenarios to visualise potential outcomes from these simulations. In the validation process, these can be compared to real-life scenarios to better train the system through machine learning.

The EWS subsystem, on the other hand, is intended to run continuously without any inputs from the users, since it must monitor the current weather situation. By leveraging on real-time data from sensors distributed over the study area and on weather forecasts, through making use of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML)-based algorithms, it can make projections of the city's floodings risk. This way, it can raise alerts to support existing early warning systems in areas. This extends the ability of existing early warning systems as it can calculate the potential risk to inhabitants or possible economic damages at particular location. This action can be specified to a very particular area and give detailed projections (such as water level) dependent on the resolution of the map. The users can only check the status of the simulation, look at the system outputs, and make few other operations. The intended user of this system would likely be municipalities interested in visualising the impact of events on their local area.

The final version of the system will consider not only risks related to flooding due to rain and river discharge, but also the effects of coastal erosion on various timescales. The here-described, first released version of the DT-EWS system does not yet include functionalities related to erosion, since they depend on other project activities that have not been completed at this stage, yet.

The main novelties of the SCORE DT-EWS can be summarised as follows:

1. The system is conceived as a software framework that integrates different physical (e.g., hydraulic, sea state, coastal erosion) models implemented in the digital domain, with human and financial risk maps, and with data from real-time sensors, that can be employed to monitor and make projections on the short, as well as on the long term. The system allows for a holistic approach considering different aspects of climate-change related events on coastal cities, as the hydrogeological impact, as well as the effects on the local infrastructures and on the community as a whole.

Figure 1. Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the DT-EWS system. a): Example of a city map view on the GUI with flooded areas; b) Color-coded map of the risk calculation in the flooded areas.

2. The SCORE DT-EWS is oriented to offering the possibility of simulating the adoption of EBAs, to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change by encouraging “green” approaches to the problem, specifically tailored to the relevant coastal city ecosystem.
3. It is the product of co-design and co-creation with coastal cities through the Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL) model. Authorities, stakeholders and citizens supported the developers in formulating the system requirements, focusing on the specific needs of coastal cities. As a further step, system review iterations will be carried out accepting feedback from the users.
4. It is equipped with a user-friendly graphical user interface (GUI) that makes users’ operations and results analysis easy. Some screenshots of the GUI are reported in Fig. 1.

System Minimum Required Inputs: The USE and EWS subsystems, in general, require different input data. However, there is a minimum set of data required by both subsystems to properly run consistent and complete simulations and ensuring the minimum functionalities that correspond to the outlined system requirements. These data are represented by the real maps of the study area identified for a coastal city. More specifically:

1. The city digital elevation model (DEM), digital terrain model (DTM), or digital surface model (DSM), preferably with high spatial resolution. Maps with grid cells of 2 m x 2 m are needed to get outputs on flooding with a good degree of detail, but 5 m x 5 m can be also acceptable, depending on the case. These maps are provided in the form of .shp files or similar, that can be viewed with tools like Q-GIS. It is also important that buildings are clearly distinguishable from the ground. In addition, baseline data include the baseline financial exposure and hazard maps calculated on the study area.

2. A map with the actual land use and cover of the study area, containing information on the Manning coefficient and terrain porosity.
3. Geometry of the rivers flowing through the city area, i.e., a .txt or .csv file with coordinates of each river course centre, bed width, Manning coefficient, bed elevation.

For those interested in developing a DT-EWS assessing climate scenarios in their area, the system would need to be provided with a large amount of data. The users must provide these data as maps or other kind of documents and upload them on the SCORE ICT Platform (SIP) as standalone files, that will be employed by the DT-EWS. Of course, the users must also update the provided maps in case there is any major change in the data previously stored on the SIP. Once this data is obtained, it will take time to adapt the system to read the data for this specific area. This can be time consuming as there isn't always a lot of high uniformity in the parameter or units of measurement. However, this process is very flexible; the most demanding step would be interfacing with sensors data and weather forecasting.

User Scenario Evaluation (USE) Subsystem Input Data: The user-defined scenarios are composed by users assembling a heterogeneous set of data from different sources. In addition to the above-listed data, the system also requires:

1. *Climate and weather data:* the users can decide what kind of weather events to simulate, e.g., by inserting values for parameters like rain rate, river flow, and sea state. Alternatively, they can employ pre-set events related to long-term models, elaborated agreeing to the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) models adopted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), and hard-coded in the system. These models are related to the projections on greenhouse gas concentration in the coming decades.
2. *EBA:* the user can choose from an EBA palette prepared for the SCORE project, including 33 possible EBAs. Once the type of EBA solution is selected, the user can trace polygons on the study area map, selecting the zones for realising EBAs, to simulate its impact in the what-if analysis associated to the scenario and the set parameters.

EWS Subsystem Input Data: To ensure its correct operation, in addition to the above-listed baseline data, the system automatically takes the following data:

1. *Real-time data from sensors:* the system needs data streams from stations distributed in the study area, sensing relevant parameters like rain rate, river levels, sewage network discharge, and so on. They are crucial for monitoring the actual hydraulic situation of the city.
2. *Weather forecasts:* beyond data from measurements, to be able to make projections on the flooding risk, the system must know the expected weather evolution, that can have an impact on the current hydraulic situation.

System Outputs

USE Subsystem Outputs: The USE subsystem output is composed of several maps corresponding to different times within the simulation set time frame. The maps report the eventual flooding and related water level in the study area, produced by the conditions set by the user for the simulation. In addition, the recalculated financial hazard maps developed through SCORE are also produced showing the estimated amounts of damages that the simulated events can virtually cause. When a simulation finishes, the system generates a human-readable report that can help the user in understanding whether the output is consistent. This way, a user can decide if the newly produced maps are worth to be stored and further analysed, or if they can be discarded.

EWS Subsystem Outputs: Flooding maps and the associated human and financial damages; it is important noticing that these maps represent projections made by the system, based on the real-time information it gets from weather forecasts and sensors.

2. Alerts of imminent flooding in case the water levels calculated by the system projections can put at risk inhabitants or cause major economic damages. These alerts are shown on the screen, if the user has opened a GUI, and can also be sent to designated users by mail or through other message services. This can potentially support existing warning systems: determining who should receive these alerts is something that will be discussed with stakeholders in future engagement workshops.

3. Warnings, that are not related to simulation outcomes and expected risks, but to the data sources. Indeed, the EWS subsystem also regularly performs a check on the consistency of the received data. It warns the user in case, e.g., there is a data feed that does not fit with other data streams, or in case of any mismatch with what is expected. In such a case, the EWS simply raises a warning to let the users be aware of the data inconsistency so that, if needed, they can exclude that sensor from the system inputs and, eventually, proceed to an in-situ check of the sensor conditions.

Users could configure different permissions for users of the DT and/or EWS. The EWS is an "add on" feature that can be removed for certain permissions.

CCLL Specific Outputs: The frontrunner CCLLs of Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova have the Digital Twin developed fully for use in their areas.

Impact & Application: Government bodies, municipalities, and citizens associations could adopt the SCORE DT-EWS to develop warning systems that are adjusted for their local conditions, and carry out simulations on the impact of extreme weather events and possible countermeasures, to support with scientific evidence their city planning or adoption of policies. Environmental management companies could use this KO as a software tool to provide studies and offer possible strategies to public or private entities interested in increasing resilience against climate change. The Research and Development community can adopt the DT-EWS to perform studies and scientific analyses for research purposes. Further, the DT could prove to be a very good system when it comes to science communication on these events, and citizen learning.

Linked Knowledge Outputs: KO5.1 SCORE ICT Platform

Impact Assessment

IRL at Project Start	IRL Achieved During SCORE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRL 2 - Discovery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRL 4 – Implementation

Knowledge Transfer Plans and Impact Assessments: To fully address the knowledge transfer potential of the DT-EWS, three separate KTPs and Impact Assessments have been dedicated to the different iterations of this system. For example, the full DT-EWS service, from development to deployment, would be of interest to target users outside of SCORE. The SCORE DT-EWS has been successfully deployed in the frontrunner cities of Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova, and individual KTPs have been developed for each alongside their impact assessments. Additionally, follower cities have materials created for use in the DT-EWS through the project, and therefore the creation of a DT-EWS in these contexts would require a different pathway to exploitation.

To appropriately address this potential, the impact assessment for KER8.1 has been further split into the following sections:

8.1a – DT-EWS full service for future cities

8.1b- DT-EWS completed output for frontrunner CCLLs of Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova

8.1 c- DT-EWS service for fellow CCLLs of Benidorm, Dublin, Sligo, Oeiras, Gdansk, Piran, Samsun

KER 8.1a – Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System – for non-SCORE users developing new Digital Twins

Priority Target User A: Academics and practitioners working in the research and development community, with a focus on EU projects, looking to develop new Digital Twins for their locality.

The Research and Development community, that will find in the DT-EWS a valuable tool for performing simulations and analyses.

- Role:** This group includes researchers, academics (such as urban sustainability and climate change specialists, geographers, environmental scientists), and individuals involved in other large-scale EU projects. They would likely be seeking to develop a Digital Twin in their own contexts or use existing DT structures to address a variety of challenges.

- *Key Message:* A researcher would want to use a Digital Twin like the SCORE DT-EWS to simulate and analyse the real-time and long-term impacts of climate-related events on coastal cities, enabling data-driven insights, scenario testing, and evidence-based decision-making. The system's innovative and beneficial nature can address the target users' needs across a variety of research and project objectives.
- *Awareness:* Users in this category would likely be familiar with Digital Twins in general, but not specifically with that of the SCORE DT-EWS.
- *Level of Understanding:* A researcher would need an understanding of environmental modelling, geospatial data, and climate-related processes, along with basic technical skills to interpret simulation results and configure scenario inputs. To use the system once deployed, a researcher would likely have the necessary skills to interpret the outputs of the system.
- *Interest:* Someone working in an EU project would be interested in the Digital Twin because it offers a practical, science-based tool for assessing climate risks, testing nature-based solutions, and supporting policy development aligned with EU goals on climate adaptation, urban resilience, and citizen engagement. As such, they may be seeking out options for partners with this specific tool or skillset to develop such a platform.

Priority Target User B: Government Bodies and public authorities, specifically those working as technical specialists, in civil protection, city planning, or climate adaptation within these institutions

Specific Examples.

- *Role:* Technical figures, policymakers and city planning authorities. Technical specialists play a key role in assessing risks, planning infrastructure, and implementing strategies to protect communities from climate-related hazards such as flooding and coastal erosion.
- *Key Message:* This digital environment allows policymakers, urban planners, and emergency responders to evaluate different adaptation measures before implementation, enhancing climate resilience planning.
- *Awareness:* These professionals are increasingly aware of the need for integrated, data-driven tools to respond to the growing complexity of climate threats and meet EU climate resilience targets. However, they may not have employed a DT system previously.
- *Level of Understanding:* Based on surveys conducted with this group through the SCORE frontrunner cities, target users may have had a low level of understanding of Digital Twins before engaging with the SCORE team, but all had already have encountered Early Warning Systems. They typically possess strong technical knowledge in urban planning or environmental risk management and can interpret model outputs and spatial data with moderate to advanced proficiency.
- *Interest:* Decision makers within municipalities are increasingly being required to better adapted to future climate change as well as implement green(er) solutions in regard to climate adaptation. They may be seeking tools to assist with projecting future scenarios within their locality to improve decision making. In particular, the financial assessments and risk assessments integrated into the DT-EWS would be of particular interest to this target group.

Priority Target User C: Industrial Actors, including insurance providers, large corporations impacted by climate change (e.g., housing corporations, tourism sectors), and related stakeholders

- *Role:* Industrial actors are key stakeholders in managing economic risks and ensuring business continuity, with a vested interest in understanding and mitigating the impacts of climate change on infrastructure, assets, and local communities.
- *Key Message:* The DT-EWS provides predictive insights into climate-related risks, such as flooding or erosion, helping companies make informed decisions about investments, risk management, and adaptation strategies.

- **Awareness:** These actors are increasingly aware of the financial and operational vulnerabilities posed by extreme weather events and the regulatory pressures to implement sustainable and resilient practices.
- **Level of Understanding:** While they may not have deep technical expertise, they rely on clear, visual outputs and actionable data that can inform risk assessments, insurance modelling, and strategic planning.
- **Interest:** Industrial actors may be particularly interested in tools that offer location-specific risk projections, quantify potential financial damages, and support scenario analysis to inform policy compliance, risk reduction, and business resilience efforts.

Impact Assessment

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

During SCORE, the WP8 team implemented a multi-step, co-creation process to deploy and iterate the DT-EWS in each frontrunner CCLL (see 8.1b below). This included initial training and demonstration sessions with local target users, a feedback phase using surveys and discussions to gather insights on usability and relevance, and a final presentation of the adapted system. The process was tailored to each city to maximise engagement and impact. During the validation phase, there was an interaction with the CCLL to identify real validation cases (flooding), the in-situ sensors (to obtain the data needed to define the validation scenarios of the USE and to calibrate the EWS library with real event scenarios), and sometimes the characteristics of the territory (and related data, e.g., DEM). This hands-on experience has directly informed the early development of a service offering for a full DT-EWS service. It demonstrated the importance of a structured, user-centred deployment model that includes onboarding, iterative adaptation based on local feedback, and post-deployment support. These learnings shape a scalable, service-based approach to designing, deploying, and refining Digital Twins in new cities—ensuring relevance, usability, and long-term value for municipal and industrial clients.

External Engagement

The SCORE DT-EWS system has been actively shared at numerous external events across Europe throughout the project's lifetime. Its first major exposure began through the SCORE Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Training Schools, running from 2023 to 2025, where the system was introduced as part of the curriculum to build capacity among researchers and practitioners. In 2024, the system was showcased at the EU Week of Regions and Cities, where it featured both at a dedicated booth and during a panel discussion, engaging a diverse audience of policymakers and stakeholders. Later that year, in September, it was presented at URBIS24 – URban Insights from Space in Frascati, Italy, with a focus on the exploitation of satellite data to evaluate Digital Twins of coastal urban areas. The system's capabilities were further highlighted in 2025 at the EGU General Assembly in Vienna, where a satellite mapping analysis of the November 2023 flood in Prato, Tuscany was presented. Finally, the DT-EWS was a central feature of the SCORE Final Event at the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference, where a live demo was offered at a booth, accompanied by a moderated discussion session and a dedicated engagement table for in-depth interactions with attendees. Later in June 2025, the system was further presented at the EGU Leonardo Conference in Bologna, where its application in satellite-based flood mapping of the November 2023 Tuscany flood was further explored.

Further, the DT-EWS was highlighted in the SCORE webinar [The SCORE Digital Twin – Application of smart technologies against climate change](#) and on the [Horizon Results Platform](#). The DT-EWS has been featured in SCORE Online Learning's Massive Open Online Courses, including [Ecosystem Based Approaches: Introduction to Implementation](#), [Coastal Monitoring for Resilient Communities](#), and [Navigating Living Labs: Lessons Learned from SCORE's 10 Coastal City Living Labs](#). Massa's experience with the DT-EWS was shared in a blog on SCORE's site, [Massa's Digital Twin: Real-Time Resilience for Flood-Ready Cities](#).

Future Impact and Opportunities

Publications: Two scientific publications on the SCORE DT-EWS system are in progress: one currently under review with *Heliyon*, focusing on satellite-based flood mapping during a rainfall event in Tuscany, and another in preparation for submission to the *IEEE IoT Journal*, detailing the development of a Digital Twin of coastal cities to enhance climate resilience.

Further Research opportunity scoping: The key recommendation is that the consortium actively seek opportunities to participate in upcoming EU-funded projects, leveraging the experience, tools, and partnerships developed through SCORE.

Continued involvement in future consortia would not only sustain momentum around the DT-EWS but also open new pathways for collaboration, co-development, and wider deployment across diverse coastal and urban contexts. By aligning with emerging calls related to climate resilience, digital innovation, and nature-based solutions, the consortium can position itself as a strong candidate for further research, innovation, and impact at the European level.

The team has already attempted multiple proposals, including four that were submitted previously without success, one with an accepted outline proposal under negotiation for the full proposal (European Space Agency (ESA) ARTES 4.0, LIMITS Demo Project), and one submitted and under evaluation (HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-02 in the ELIAS (European Lighthouse of AI for Sustainability) Consortium as the project ai-Powered digitAl twiN fOr enviRonmentAl iMPact evaluation (PANORAMA)). Some eligible members of the SCORE consortium are also working at the development of an Innovation Action proposal in the PRIMA-MED PRIMA-CALLS-2025-SECTION 1, Thematic Area 1-Water management in the Nexus, Topic 1.1.1-2025. Identification of other calls of interest to the team include the following: HORIZON-CL5-2025-06-D1-04: The attribution to climate change, and improved forecasting of extreme and slow-onset climate- and weather-related events and their impacts, HORIZON-CL5-2025-05-Two-Stage-D1-05: Adaptation to Climate Change: Effectiveness and Limits, and HORIZON-CL6-2025-03-GOVERNANCE-11: Enhancing sustainability and resilience of agriculture, forestry and rural development through digital twins.

Additionally, the WP8 team, led by MBI, recently contacted the Municipality of Pisa Technician of the offices working on environmental management and data management, who responded very positively to the proposal of a possible extension of the SCORE DT-EWS to their city. In particular, they are interested in a digital tool supporting activities related to the environmental impact estimation of new construction projects. A first meeting was held in March 2025, where some points have been set regarding the future collaboration on this topic. These activities can be included in the framework of the above-mentioned call ELIAS. MBI, in particular, is reaching out to other municipalities, like Pisa (Italy), to present the system and offer the possibility to deploy it for a better system validation and improvement, with the perspective of making the DT-EWS a product that can be purchased by those municipalities.

Business Development: The Innovation Board has recommended the finalisation of the business plan for the SCORE DT—EWS, recognising its strong potential for real-world application and long-term impact. This recommendation has been accepted but postponed by the owners, as it was determined that further innovation action would be necessary before the DT-EWS is fully ready for commercialisation, so this is the priority action at this stage of development. However, the partners have agreed that a finalised business plan should be developed to outline a clear pathway for exploitation, detailing how the DT-EWS can be offered as a full service, including an assessment of potential clients, covering design, deployment, user engagement, and iterative adaptation in new urban contexts as it stands at this time. This ensures that the knowledge and tools developed during SCORE can be effectively scaled and adopted beyond the initial frontrunner cities, supporting wider climate resilience and adaptation efforts across Europe.

KER 8.1b – Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System for frontrunner CCLs of Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova

Priority Target User A: Government Bodies and public authorities, specifically those working as technical specialists, in civil protection, city planning, or climate adaptation within these institutions.

Public Authorities responsible for decision-making in coastal cities aiming at developing resilience against climate change in the frontrunner cities of Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova.

Massa: Municipality of Massa, Carrara Municipality, Montignoso municipality, municipal union, province of Massa Carra, Port Authority, ARPAT, Authority of Bacino

Oarsoaldea: Oarsoaldea development agency management board, communications and tourism board, Gipuzkoako Foru Aldundia environmental department, Eusko Jaurlaritza Basque Country government (business development agency, water agency, emergency and meteorology management agency, energy agency, and tourism agency), Ministry of transport and mobility pasaia port authority, ministry of environment services in the Province de Gipuzkoa, Euroregion cross boarder European agency, Añarbeko Urak (water management public company)

Vilanova: Barcelona Provincial Council, Catalan Government (Catalan Climate Change Office, CADS Sustainable Development Advisory Council, ACA - Catalan Water Agency, DG Coasts), Natural and coastal environment service - Garraf County Council, Ministry for Ecological Transition, Gava City Council, Calafell City Council, Sitges City Council

- *Role:* Technical figures, policymakers and city planning authorities within frontrunner CCLLs that can exploit simulations for planning and deploy solutions focused on urban adaptation to climate change.
- *Key Message:* This digital environment allows policymakers, urban planners, and emergency responders to evaluate different adaptation measures before implementation, enhancing climate resilience planning.
- *Awareness:* Following the work of engaging with these target users through various SCORE activities, these target users should now be more aware of Digital Twins and their use within their roles. Additionally, based on user feedback surveys, this target audience largely have worked previously with Early Warning Systems.
- *Level of Understanding:* Target users may have had a low level of understanding of Digital Twins before engaging with the SCORE team, but all had already have encountered Early Warning Systems. Through SCORE activities, they would have received an amount of technical training and support to appropriately set up and employ their DT-EWS in their locality, though they may need additional support for its upkeep.
- *Interest:* Decision makers within municipalities are increasingly being required to better adapted to future climate change as well as implement green(er) solutions in regard to climate adaptation. They may be seeking tools to assist with projecting future scenarios within their locality to improve decision making. In particular, the financial assessments and risk assessments integrated into the DT-EWS would be of particular interest to this target group.

Impact Assessment

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

For each frontrunner CCLL, the WP8 team hosted a multi-step approach to the deployment and iteration of the DT-EWS adapted to each context. Key steps of this process included:

- Step One: Deployment of the DT-EWS in the local context, as well as a meeting with key target users with an initial system presentation, a live demo/training session, and a final support discussion. These users would then have access to “play” with the system to better understand its functionalities and potential ahead of providing feedback in Step Two.
- Step Two: A feedback session was held with target users to gather their insights on how the DT-EWS was used and the opportunities it presented within their specific local contexts. These sessions primarily involved participants from municipalities in the frontrunner CCLLs and focused on evaluating the system’s usability. The feedback collected enabled the WP8 team to refine and adapt the DT-EWS to better meet the needs of these frontrunner cities. During the session, participants completed a DT-EWS survey developed by ERINN. The responses were carefully reviewed, and where feasible, the feedback was integrated into the system and taken into account for the overall impact assessment. Moreover, during the system validation phase, there was an interaction with the CCLLs to identify real validation cases (flooding), the in-situ sensors (to obtain the data needed to define the validation scenarios of the USE and to calibrate the EWS library with real event scenarios), and sometimes the characteristics of the territory (and related data, e.g., DEM). Step Three: A final presentation of the deployed DT-EWS was presented to the frontrunners to show the final iteration of the DT-EWS and provide support on how to use it.

These activities varied slightly based on the frontrunner CCLL’s context to maximise interaction and subsequent impact. See details below on each different experience and the results of this work.

Massa Coastal City Living Lab

Step One: Deployment of the DT-EWS. Massa CCLL was used as the “frontrunner of the frontrunners” to first test this iterative process to then adapt it to the other frontrunners. The deployment of the DT-EWS had an additional engagement session to iterate the DT with specific target users, i.e., the local coordinator of the Civil Protection and members of the Environment

Management office of the Municipality to provide feedback ahead of iterating to share with a wider range of stakeholders, and these two user engagement sessions allowed for feedback from these users to tailor the system to their needs more clearly. Massa's experience demonstrated the value of a co-design approach, where feedback loops between developers and users helped refine the system's usability and effectiveness. It was the very first live system demonstration in SCORE, since Massa represented the pilot case for the three WP8 frontrunners. The meeting took place in April 2024 and was divided into three parts:

- A presentation employing a slide deck to outline the user architecture, reporting the description of the USE and EWS subsystem, the GUI, the used inputs, and examples of simulation outputs
- The live demo of the system, showing the procedure to create a scenario and launch a simulation from the system's GUI
- A discussion with the users to collect their first feelings and impressions about the DT-EWS system, to ask them some questions that could lead to a system fine-tuning, and to answer their eventual questions as well

A second meeting for system operation explanation, on users' request, took place on 09/07/24. The people attending these meetings, beyond SCORE WP8 people (MBI, CNR-ISAC, UCD) and the CCLL core team members were the same as in the first meeting.

Step Two: Feedback session with stakeholders. From a usability point of view, the system deployed on Massa has been validated by collecting users' feedback in an on-purpose scheduled feedback session on 20/09/2024. From the point of view results consistency, the system has been validated trying to use satellite SAR images regarding past flood events, but the availability of data was scarce, therefore pieces of information provided by the Municipality about flood consequences have been considered. The meeting was organized according to three parts:

- a. A technical session aimed at collecting feedback from users about some technical features of the DT-EWS system: MBI presented again the DT-EWS system highlighting some issues found after the installation in Massa. The current version of the DT-EWS system for Massa was installed and the stakeholders had the opportunity to "play" with the system. Therefore, the technical part of the session was a kind of request for clarification on certain aspects of DT, input Data, interface features and speed of processing.
- b. Open discussion about the possible use of a tool like DT-EWS in the context of duties of the municipality. The rest of the discussion was led by CNR (in presence) and was about the utility and significance of the system for environmental planning and for the user. The possibility of using the system within well-consolidated protocols for managing emergencies was discussed. Basically, the discussion followed the main points of the questionnaire.
- c. Consolidate the results in a questionnaire developed by ERINN. The DT-EWS Officers were aware of the Participants were requested to fill a questionnaire translated into Italian, with particular attention to the vernacular of public administration. Replies were handwritten. Respondents did not ask for clarifications.

Outcomes from the session: The officers of Massa Municipality were aware of the DT-EWS system and tried to use it before the meeting. Some technical aspects, such as the interface were appreciated, and overall, the system was considered to follow a logic to be usable within the duties, but some familiarity with similar systems (e.g. GIS systems according to the respondents) has been found. Definitely the participants reported that the DT has a value and leaving out the considerations regarding the costs of the system to be supported by the municipal administration should it wish to adopt it, the DT system lends itself to being used often and integrated into existing systems (e.g. GIS tools). The responses favoured aspects of the DT of support planning (also with the simulation of EBAs) also for risk reduction. A significant usefulness is seen, especially compared to existing administration tools. The interpretation we can give is that the law explicitly requires municipalities to follow co-design approaches (in Italian participatory planning) and the use of graphic representations is certainly helpful in managing co-design events, although, after all, the system will increase their workload.

The use of EWS has been considered as less impacting (this conclusion follows also from the open discussion), although Civil Protection is mentioned among potential users although for facilitating some post-event activities. In this case the interpretation is that the alarm management procedures are very prescriptive towards municipalities which would find themselves managing

an additional source of information to be compared to the sources of official data and information managed by higher level administrations. For this reason, EWS outputs should be handled by trained specialists, also because of confidentiality issues.

Step Three: A final presentation of the deployed DT-EWS. The Massa core team took advantage of the three-day event for the EBA Training School held in February 2025, to present the system to a larger audience, composed by different stakeholders, like administrators, professional organizations, associations interested in environmental protection, and simple citizens.

Oarsoaldea Coastal City Living Lab

Step One: Deployment of the DT-EWS. The Oarsoaldea system was deployed in November 2024 followed by an initial user meeting to showcase the version of the DT-EWS for their use. The participants were then allowed to “play” with the system and provide feedback via the DT-EWS surveys in Spanish.

Step Two: Feedback session with stakeholders. The team then had a feedback session with the WP8 team on the 24th March 2025 to discuss their feedback and usability of the system. The involved users expressed their overall satisfaction regarding the system usability, asking to add some more features that could improve it like, e.g., more details about the parameters related to the simulated EBAs.

Oarsoaldea survey results: The survey respondents included sustainability technicians, urban ecology coordinators, and a representative responsible for urban regeneration, mobility, and energy within the Oarsoaldea Development Agency. Three participants operated at the regional level, while one respondent worked at the municipal level. One participant specified that they were from a consultancy and not a civil servant.

All respondents confirmed that their municipalities or regions currently use an Early Warning System, with weather alerts being universally employed. Flood alerts were also noted by three participants, and one mentioned marine weather alerts. However, when asked if they typically use similar tools to the DT-EWS, two respondents stated they did not, while others acknowledged that early warning functions are managed at the regional level by multiple agencies. None of the respondents had prior experience using a DT: while some noted the use of GIS, satellite imagery, and small climate risk models, they indicated that a tool of this scale did not exist at their disposal. All respondents found value in utilising a DT, citing its potential to enhance municipal planning, empower technicians, and support climate adaptation strategies. Specific benefits highlighted included better decision-making, improved planning, enhanced situational awareness, and faster analyses.

Two respondents found integration to be somewhat difficult, while two were neutral. Despite this, all but one respondent considered the system realistic for users, though the required level of expertise ranged from intermediate to expert. Typical users were identified as municipal technicians, researchers, emergency coordinators, and environmental agency personnel. The impact on workload was mixed—one respondent felt it would add to their workload, while three considered it neutral. Most anticipated using the tool occasionally rather than frequently. While some respondents were very open to this technology, others expressed neutral or somewhat resistant views. Necessary support included technological assistance, maintenance, and budget considerations. The system’s design was regarded as logical and intuitive by all respondents, with minor improvements suggested. All four participants found the system’s complexity to be “just right.” Respondents saw significant potential in the Digital Twin’s ability to simulate scenarios and aid decision-making at local and regional levels. They envisioned its use for planning, raising awareness, and promoting EBA projects. However, for public engagement, they noted the need to simplify the message before making the tool widely accessible. While two respondents confirmed that their departments could use the Early Warning Support System, another felt it was not appropriate for their role, and one stated they lacked the authority to implement it. Potential users of the DT-EWS included local and regional administrations, civil protection agencies, emergency managers, and policymakers.

All respondents were uncertain about confidentiality requirements. In their final remarks, participants expressed positive feedback, describing the tool as highly promising and potentially valuable in their work. Given access, all respondents indicated they would continue using the Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System.

Step Three: A final presentation of the deployed DT-EWS. Oarsoaldea hosted its final event on 30th May, and the final results of the DT-EWS were made available to the wider CCLL on this date. The team is currently assessing the success of this session and scheduling follow up meetings with interested stakeholders.

Vilanova Coastal City Living Lab

Step One: Deployment of the DT-EWS. The Vilanova DT-EWS was deployed in November 2024 followed by an initial user meeting to showcase the version of the DT-EWS for their use. The participants were then allowed to “play” with the system and provide feedback via the DT-EWS surveys in Spanish.

Step Two: Feedback session with stakeholders. In the feedback session meeting with stakeholders, Ester T. Arroyo, from Vilanova Municipality, used the digital twin system creating scenarios. She found the system really user friendly and easy to use. She also tried to upload other project data and they were perfectly represented on the map of the graphical user interface. She does not believe that the Vilanova City Council will be using the user scenario evaluation subsystem because they do not have technical officers that do this kind of urban planning. She thinks that this tool is more suitable for the activities of the *comarca* government. Monitoring is also very important for companies working in the city area, especially in the port. She believes that the part related to simulations can be more interesting for education purposes and for communications of the plans of the municipality to the population.

She affirms that the most interesting point for her municipality lies in the early warning support system to monitor how the hydraulic situation of the city evolves and that can help the population.

The early warning system actually in use for Villanova is the same that covers a broad area of application, including 800 different cities. This means that the resolution is not very high and sometime the system gives wrong alerts. A system like the SCORE digital twin is more interesting because it can give local information. According to her, every early warning support system should be local to be really interesting and useful, possibly giving the possibility of modulating the alert areas as the SCORE digital twin early warning support system does. That would be more interesting if the alert messages would be sent not only to the administrations, but also to other entities that have competence on very small areas (like a school and the nearby parking lots), to alert, e.g., school directors and other users that can reach other people with the alerts, making more impactful the system and its outputs. She stressed the importance of having a system that should be always tailored to the local situation.

Step Three: A final presentation of the deployed DT-EWS. On the 22nd of May 2025, a final presentation to these users on the deployed systems took place. In this event, the system has been presented to a large audience of stakeholders with a live demo, and some slides reporting about the system validation have been presented.

Future Impact and Opportunities

Based upon the feedback sessions with frontrunners, the SCORE DT-EWS is seen as a valuable and innovative tool that could fill a gap at the municipal and regional levels, aiding decision-making and planning. While integration challenges and training needs exist, the stakeholders expressed enthusiasm for its potential applications and future use. The key recommendation to increase the usability and impact of this system for the frontrunners is to determine a clear pathway for continued purchase of these entities for use beyond SCORE. Conversations among the development team and frontrunner CCLLs have begun to determine how access will continue beyond the project.

As detailed in KTP8.1a, it's recommended at this stage to achieve this by prioritising further research and innovation actions to increase the TRL, especially for the EWSS in the frontrunner contexts as it was noted that reliability should be increased and certifications explored. This could be achieved through perhaps more for private companies proposing actions to the council. Additionally, the Vilanova CCLL has been included in the PRIMA call for next steps (PRIMA-MED PRIMA-CALLS-2025-SECTION 1, Thematic Area 1-Water management in the Nexus, Topic 1.1.1-2025). This proposal brings in the partnerships of Samsun, Piran, Vilanova, Massa CCLL.

The Vilanova team wants continually monitored KPIs and other municipalities included that not in SCORE (Milan & Pisa) to increase impact. There is opportunity to study the DT-EWSS in different contexts: for example, Pisa has expressed interest to use this tool in a different way, potentially as an environmental certification tool.

KER 8.1c – Digital Twin – for follower CCLs

Priority Target User A: Government Bodies and public authorities, specifically those working as technical specialists, in civil protection, city planning, or climate adaptation within these institutions.

Public Authorities responsible for decision-making in coastal cities aiming at developing resilience against climate change in the follower cities: some targeted groups include:

- *Benidorm: Town Hall Beach area (Areas playas del ayuntamiento), Town Hall Civil Engineering area (Area ingenieria civil del ayuntamiento), Smart Office (Distrito Digital), Local Police of Benidorm, General Directorate of Coasts (Dirección General de Costas)*
 - *Dublin: Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council, Office of Public Works (OPW), Smart Dun Laoghaire (Innovation collaborator group), Geological Survey Ireland (GSI), Dublin Bay Biosphere Partnership, Irish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)*
 - *Sligo: Sligo County Council, National Parks and Wildlife Service, Geological Survey Ireland, Environmental Protection Agency, Department of Environmental Climate and Communications, Office of Public Works, Climate Action Regional Office – CARO*
 - *Oeiras: Oeiras Municipality (Environmental Department, Strategy for Science and Technology, Civil Protection), Portuguese Sea and Atmosphere Institute [Instituto Portugues Mar e Atmosfera (IPMA)], Portuguese Environment Agency [Agencia Portuguesa do Ambiente (APA)], Authority of Lisbon Port (APL) [Administração do Porto de Lisboa, S.A.], Territorial Intelligence Office (GIT), Department of municipality construction (DOM), Lisbon Metropolitan Area (AML), Intermunicipality water and sanitation facilities (SIMAS), Regional Development Commission of Lisboa and Tagus Valley [CCDRLVT], Social Action Department [Departamento Ação Social], Firemen corporations (CBV Algés, Dafundo, Oeiras, and Paço de Arcos)*
 - *Gdansk: Municipal Office of Gdansk, Department of the Environment, Institute for Meteorology and Water Management, Operational Center for Flood Protection, Regional Water Management Board, Water Gdansk, Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection, Energa (Energy Distribution Company), Saur Neptun Sewage Company, National Forests [Lasz Państwowe], Education Schoolboard [Kuratorium Oświaty], Tri-city Landscape Park [Trójmiejski Park Krajobrazowy], Port of Gdansk, Gdansk Development Office [Biuro Rozwoju Gdańska], Operational Centre - Flooding Protection [Centrum Operacyjne Ochrony Przeciwpowodziowej], Gdansk Infrastructure [Melioracje Gdańskie], Gdansk Road and Greenery Management [Zarząd Dróg i Zieleni], Voivodeship Crisis Management [Wojewódzkie Centrum Zarządzania Kryzysowego], Maritime Office, RZGW - Regional Panel for Water Management*
 - *Piran: Piran municipality, National Environmental Agency, Piran public space and waste management service, Piran civil protection service, Piran civil working body for spatial planning, Piran municipal environmental office*
 - *Samsun: Samsun Municipality, Samsun Governorship, Ondokuzmayis Municipality, Samsun Provincial Directorate of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change, State Hydraulic Works Samsun Office, Turkish State Meteorological Service Samsun Office*
- *Role:* Technical figures, policymakers and city planning authorities within the follower CCLs that can exploit simulations for planning and deploy solutions focused on urban adaptation to climate change.
 - *Key Message:* This digital environment allows policymakers, urban planners, and emergency responders to evaluate different adaptation measures before implementation, enhancing climate resilience planning.
 - *Awareness:* These target users are likely not well aware of Digital Twins but may have worked previously with Early Warning Systems.
 - *Level of Understanding:* Target users may have a low level of understanding of Digital Twins but may already have encountered Early Warning Systems, as was seen in the frontrunner cities. As such, this target group would require an

amount of technical training and support to appropriately set up and employ a new DT-EWS in their locality, as iterated through lessons learned from the frontrunner engagement sessions.

- *Interest:* Decision makers within municipalities are increasingly being required to better adapted to future climate change as well as implement green(er) solutions in regard to climate adaptation. They may be seeking tools to assist with projecting future scenarios within their locality to improve decision making. In particular, the financial assessments and risk assessments integrated into the DT-EWS would be of particular interest to this target group.

Impact Assessment

Internal Activities Increasing Impact

To build a SCORE DT-EWS, several key actions must be completed to provide the necessary data and inputs for the full system, including gathering high-resolution digital elevation and land-use maps, collecting river and hydraulic data, integrating real-time sensor feeds, and incorporating climate and weather information. Many of these foundational steps have already been initiated or partially completed in some SCORE follower cities during the project, meaning these cities have made significant progress along the pathway to full DT-EWS deployment. Consequently, the service package offered to these follower cities would differ from that designed for entirely new cities (8.1a), reflecting their advanced stage of readiness.

The progress of the DT-EWS development in the frontrunner cities was regularly shared during consortium meetings, including the 2024 general assembly in Gdansk and in the 2025 online session, to keep follower cities informed about the deployment of frontrunner DT-EWS systems. A key milestone in this knowledge sharing process occurred in May 2025, when WP8 partners and representatives from the frontrunner cities held a knowledge transfer session with follower cities. During this event, frontrunners shared their experiences and insights with follower cities, enabling them to assess their own interest and readiness for implementing a DT-EWS. The WP8 team also outlined the current service offerings, required data inputs, and steps involved in the deployment process. This exchange helped spark interest among follower cities and supported them in evaluating the feasibility of planning a Digital Twin within their own contexts.

Furthermore, individual meetings were conducted to explore these feasibility considerations in greater detail, discussing potential barriers, opportunities, and necessary actions to facilitate successful implementation. For example, as a follower CCLL, Sligo primarily produced results data to support the creation of real-time inputs for the future development of the Digital Twin for the Sligo CCLL. This included coastal erosion analysis using Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Digital Surface Models (DSM), shoreline and waterline assessments based on 25 years of satellite imagery, and future projections generated through machine learning models incorporating sea-level and wave data to produce different RCPs scenarios. Additionally, a citizen science photobooth was installed to facilitate local image uploads, helping to address gaps in satellite monitoring for a continuous real-time data stream.

Future Impact and Opportunities

The key priority for the DT-EWS is to ensure a production-ready system. At this time, a follower city would be collaboration in a demonstrator capacity. This would be beneficial as MBI alongside LaMMA and Pisa partnerships (to provide necessary components) seek to deploy the DT-EWS in as many cities as possible to increase the use cases. This is most feasible through acquiring further EU-funded research grants.

Funding considerations for followers: Follower CCLLs will need to actively consider funding acquisition to achieve this. This funding could come from internal sources within their municipalities or partner organisations, or be secured through external avenues such as participation in future projects and funding programs, including EU calls. Exploring diverse funding mechanisms will be essential to ensure the continued development, deployment, and maintenance of the Digital Twin system, enabling CCLLs to fully benefit from its capabilities for climate resilience and urban planning.

Service Offering: WP8 is currently preparing a service offering for follower cities to support the completion of the DT-EWS development beyond the SCORE project. Since many initial system components are already in place, this service will require fewer inputs compared to the full deployment outlined in KTP8.1a. The necessary data and elements exist but still need to be uploaded and integrated into the system—this represents the next crucial step. For follower cities that have not yet engaged in

individual meetings with the WP8 team to assess their feasibility, such discussions are recommended as a first step to evaluate their interest and opportunities for implementing a Digital Twin in their area

Recommended service: The process of iteration followed in the Fronrunner CCLLs has been an effective method for engaging with stakeholders to increase usability of the system within their contexts. We would thus recommend the following key steps taking place:

- One-on-one meetings are held with the DT-EWS development team to assess the feasibility of implementing the SCORE DT-EWS.
- An initial session is conducted to demonstrate the DT-EWS to target users and allow them hands-on experience with the system.
- A feedback session gathers input from stakeholders to inform system improvements.
- A final event showcases the adapted DT-EWS to users and offers support for its deployment in their specific context.

KO #	Knowledge Output Title	
KO5.2	SensorThings Application Programming Interface (API) and Data Harvesters	As the key element of data collection within the SIP, the Data Harvesters and SensorThings API address the challenge of multiple sensor data in different formats, which were single-use applications for specific purpose and had specialised user interfaces. The SensorThings API sensor interface allows the platform to deal with the heterogeneity of data formats and communication methods and protocols, comply with standards and specifications relevant to spatial data such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), standardise the spatial data collected from various networks, ensure data interoperability, and build a citizen science platform to support activities. It consists of eight entities that are linked to each other: thing, location, sensor, observed property, observation, datastream, historical location, and feature of interest.
KO5.3	Visualisation Suite for Project Data Communication and Sensor Data Collection	This KO refers to the visualisation suite for project data communication and sensor data collection, which is an element of the larger SCORE ICT (Information and Communication Technology) Platform, or SIP for short, (see KO5.1). The SIP is an integrated digital platform that acts to collect and share data within the project communities, researchers, and stakeholders of Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) within the SCORE project. This KO refers specifically hosting, sharing, and visualization of data, which includes digital content produced within the project, ranging from event photos and documents to sensor outputs. This does not include the large datasets used as inputs (e.g., those from climate modelling or datasets available at CCLLs), as this would represent an unnecessary duplication, nor the datasets produced by the of the project, as these are hosted on Zenodo multi-disciplinary open repository (maintained by CERN). This KO refers to the elements of the SIP that are capable of hosting, managing, and displaying these various types of data.
KO5.4	SCORE Citizen Science Sensor Data Uploader App	The SCORE Sensor Data Uploader App is a mobile-friendly web application that allows users—both technical and non-technical—to connect, upload, and manage data collected from sensor devices. Recognising that sensor devices from different manufacturers output data in varying formats, the application serves as an intermediary that maps incoming data to the SensorThings API standard. Any sensor device could be compatible with the application, and the application is designed to collect data from sensors that are unable to communicate data via wireless or wired networks (data is saved on an integrated device storage). Its innovative edge lies in its user-centric design combined with backend integration to the SensorThings API

		<p>OGC standard, ensuring the standardisation and interoperability of heterogeneous data. This makes it particularly valuable for citizen science projects and for integrating community-generated data with professional sensor networks. An automated data process that cleans, validates, and enriches raw inputs prior to integration is essential. The application simplifies complex data submission processes into an accessible web interface, thereby expanding participation in environmental and urban data collection efforts.</p>
KO6.1	Exposure database and vulnerability curves for the Coastal City Living Labs, Massa, Vilanova and Oarsoaldea	<p>Description: The overarching goal of this work is to develop quantitative risk assessments for the CCLLs - Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrù, and Oarsoaldea. Building this quantitative risk assessment requires two preliminary components, which are the focus of this KO: 1) the development of the exposure datasets and 2: the vulnerability curves. These exposure datasets combine multiple open-access datasets from different sources. Typically, a single dataset (i.e., a roadmap) won't have sufficient information on all the individual assets (i.e., the height of the buildings, the materials used, etc.), therefore multiple datasets containing the necessary information are collated using statistical and downscaling techniques. Vulnerability curves allow us to establish mathematical relationships between hazard intensity (i.e., depth of flooding) and losses for the different types of assets. For example, the vulnerability curve would tell us for this specific building, if there is 1 meter of flood water depth, we could anticipate 20% damage and therefore €350,000 in damage.</p>

CONCLUSION

The communication and dissemination activities have been carried out in line with the Grant Agreement and the strategy, and the objectives defined in deliverable D9.1 Plan for the exploitation and Dissemination of project Results (PEDR).

During the project lifetime, all partners successfully participated in the communication activities and dissemination of the first significant results of the project. These efforts have resulted in a high level of visibility, both at the local/regional level and at the European level, including recognition from the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change.

A wide range of activities were carried out across the Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs), engaging diverse stakeholders such as citizens, students, policymakers, businesses, and local authorities. In the last year, particular attention was given to finalization of the project activities, dissemination of key achievements and the publications of the final project results, resulting in an intensive dissemination and knowledge management strategy.

In the final months of the project, the WP9 team strengthened project outreach by launching a 'Key Achievements' page on the website, producing a final brochure, press release, and media kit, creating additional video content, and maintaining a strong presence on social media. Several policy briefs and recommendations were also developed and published in collaboration with WP7.

All partners were actively engaged, contributing through events, publications, and ongoing collaboration with local stakeholders. Various events were organised at the national and international level, including: several citizen science activities across the 10 Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs), local final events organised by some CCLs to mark the project's conclusion, one Training School, two international workshops and one final event.

The final round of knowledge collection was completed, with the development of KTPs for all KERs, supporting their implementation through the end of the project and afterwards. Close collaboration between WP9, the CCLs, and other work packages (WP2, WP6, WP7, WP8) ensured impactful communication, exploitation, and dissemination of SCORE results, securing their long-term value.

ANNEX 1 – KPI ANALYSIS

Dissemination or communication activity	Tool / Activity	When (and where, if relevant)	KPI	Target - M48	Results - M48	Evaluation - M48				Partner(s) in charge
						High (>100%)	Good (≤ 100%)	Moderate (≤ 75%)	Low (<50%)	
Events to be organised by the project partners	EBA Training Schools	2023, 2024, 2025	Number of training schools	30	30	>30	≤30	≤23	<15	ATU, UCD and CCLLs
			Number of participants/session	30	113	>30	≤30	≤23	<15	
	International technology workshops	2024, 2025	Number of workshop organised	2	3	>2	≤2	≤2	<1	TBD
			Number of participants/workshop	30	82	>30	≤30	≤23	<15	
	Webinars	2024, 2025	Number of webinars	2	10	>2	≤2	≤2	<1	Euronovia
			Number of participants/webinar	40	64	>40	≤40	≤30	<20	
Final Info Day	M48	Number of participants	1000	60	>1000	≤1000	≤750	<500	Euronovia	
Citizen science activities and workshops in each CCLL	M6-M24	Number of activities	10	107	>10	≤10	≤8	<5	ATU, UCD and CCLLs	
Participation in external events and conferences	Scientific conferences	Whole project duration	Number of conferences	10	52	>10	≤10	≤8	<5	All
			Number of face to face contacts	100	6240	>100	≤100	≤75	<50	
	Exhibition fairs in technology and Open Innovation events	2024, 2025	Number of participation/exhibition	3	5	>3	≤3	≤2	<2	Euronovia
	Science popularization event	Whole project duration	Number of participation/exhibition	1	19	>1	≤1	0	-	Euronovia, ALL
Dissemination or communication activity	Website	M3-M6	Number of visits/month	1000	2747	>1000	≤1000	≤750	<500	Euronovia
			Number of news/month	2/month = 96	168	>96	≤96	≤72	<48	
	Flyer	M6	Number of flyers distributed	2000	1530	>2000	≤2000	≤1500	<1000	Euronovia
	Project videos/ Interview videos	M48	Number of videos	10	40	>10	≤10	≤8	<5	Euronovia
			Number of views	50 000	41870	>50000	≤50000	≤37500	<25000	
	Massive Open Online Courses created from lectures and workshops	M36	Number of videos	30	74	>30	≤30	≤23	<15	ERINN
	Final brochure	M48	Number of brochures distributed	2000	207	>2000	≤2000	≤1500	<1000	Euronovia
	LinkedIn page	Whole project duration	Number of followers	3000	1727	>3000	≤3000	≤2250	<1500	All
			Number of post	300	297	>300	≤300	≤225	<150	
	Twitter account	Whole project duration	Number of followers	2000	415	>2000	≤2000	≤1500	<1000	All
			Number of tweet	300	404	>300	≤300	≤225	<150	
	Facebook page	Whole project duration	Number of followers	500	186	>500	≤500	≤375	<250	Euronovia, ERINN, ATU
	Instagram account	Whole project duration	Number of followers	500	286	>500	≤500	≤375	<250	CCLLs
	Final media press kit	At the end of the project		1	1	>1	≤1	0	-	Euronovia
	Newsletter	Every 6 month, starting M6	Number of newsletter	8	8	>8	≤8	≤6	<4	Euronovia
			Number of registered for updates	1000	595	>1000	≤1000	≤750	<500	
	Press releases	M6, M30 and M42	Number of press releases	3	5	>3	≤3	≤2	<2	Euronovia, ATU
	Article in specialized magazines	M24 and M36	Number of articles	2	3	>2	≤2	≤2	<1	Euronovia, ALL
	Media coverage	Whole project duration	Number of external articles	100	105	>100	≤100	≤75	<50	All
	Decision-support guidelines for management of residual coastal risk (WP6)	M48	Number of set of guidelines produced	2	4	>2	≤2	≤2	<1	RED
Policy recommendations to assist decision making in climate change adaptation at the local, national and EU level (WP7)	M47		0	11	>0	-	-	-	TERO	
Publications	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals	Whole project duration	Number of publications	30	56	>30	≤30	≤23	<15	All
	Conference proceedings	Whole project duration	Number of conference proceedings	10	28	>10	≤10	≤8	<5	All
	Special issue/special collection in a peer-reviewed journal	M48	Number of special issue	1	1	>1	≤1	0	-	All

ANNEX 2 – LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

56 Journal articles

- Giannetti, F.; Reggiannini, R. Opportunistic Rain Rate Estimation from Measurements of Satellite Downlink Attenuation: A Survey. *Sensors* 2021, 21, 5872. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21175872>
- Gharbia, S.; Riaz, K.; Anton, I.; Makrai, G.; Gill, L.; Creedon, L.; McAfee, M.; Johnston, P.; Pilla, F. Hybrid Data-Driven Models for Hydrological Simulation and Projection on the Catchment Scale. *Sustainability* 2022, 14, 4037. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14074037>
- Toledo, I.; Pagán, J. I.; López, I.; Aragonés, L. Causes of the different behaviour against erosion: Study case of the Benidorm Beaches (1956–2021), *Marine Georesources & Geotechnology*, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1064119X.2022.2084003>
- Espinosa, L.A.; Portela, M.M. Grid-Point Rainfall Trends, Teleconnection Patterns, and Regionalised Droughts in Portugal (1919–2019). *Water* 2022, 14, 1863. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14121863>
- Saggese, F.; Lottici, V.; Giannetti, F. Rainfall Map from Attenuation Data Fusion of Satellite Broadcast and Commercial Microwave Links. *Sensors* 2022, 22, 7019.
- Meulenbergh, C.J.W.; Hawke, S.M.; Cavaion, I.; Kumer, P.; Lenarčič, B. Understanding interdisciplinarity through Adriatic maricultures and climate change adaptation. *Visions for Sustainability*, 2022, 18, 6945, 11-36. <https://doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/6945>
- Espinosa, L.A.; Portela, M.M.; Matos, J.P.; Gharbia, S. Climate Change Trends in a European Coastal Metropolitan Area: Rainfall, Temperature, and Extreme Events (1864–2021). *Atmosphere* 2022, 13, 1995. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13121995>
- Tiwari, A.; Rodrigues, L.C.; Lucy, F.E.; Gharbia, S. Building Climate Resilience in Coastal City Living Labs Using Ecosystem-Based Adaptation: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability* 2022, 14, 10863. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141710863>
- Barańczuk, J.; Zeleňáková, M.; Abd-Elhamid, H.F.; Barańczuk, K.; Gharbia, S.S.; Bliščan, P.; Meulenbergh, C.J.W.; Kumer, P.; Golus, W.; Markowski, M. Prediction of Actual from Climatic Precipitation with Data Collected from Northern Poland: A Statistical Approach. *Sensors* 2023, 23, 1159. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23031159>
- Ahmed, T.; Creedon, L.; Gharbia, S.S. Low-Cost Sensors for Monitoring Coastal Climate Hazards: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Sensors* 2023, 23, 1717. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23031717>
- Riera-Spiegelhalder, M.; Campos-Rodrigues, L.; Enseñado, E.M.; Dekker-Arlain, J.d.; Papadopoulou, O.; Arampatzis, S.; Vervoort, K. Socio-Economic Assessment of Ecosystem-Based and Other Adaptation Strategies in Coastal Areas: A Systematic Review. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 2023, 11, 319. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11020319>
- Riaz, K.; McAfee, M.; Gharbia, S.S. Management of Climate Resilience: Exploring the Potential of Digital Twin Technology, 3D City Modelling, and Early Warning Systems. *Sensors* 2023, 23, 2659. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23052659>
- Abd-Elhamid, H.F.; Zeleňáková, M.; Barańczuk, J.; Gergelova, M.B.; Mahdy, M. Historical Trend Analysis and Forecasting of Shoreline Change at the Nile Delta Using RS Data and GIS with the DSAS Tool. *Remote Sens.* 2023, 15, 1737. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15071737>

- Kumer P., Meulenber C., & Kralj E. (2023). Challenges for planning climate change resilience through the co-creation living lab approach in the Mediterranean coastal town of Piran . *Journal for Geography*, 17(2), 89-106. <https://doi.org/10.18690/rg.17.2.2737>
- Sapienza, F., Bacci, G., Giannetti, F., Lottici, V., Vaccaro, A., Serafino, G., ... & Facheris, L. (2023). A Feasibility Study on Opportunistic Rainfall Measurement From Satellite TV Broadcasts. *URSI RADIO SCIENCE LETTERS*, VOL. 4, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.46620/22-0033>
- Antonini, A.; Melani, S.; Mazza, A.; Baldini, L.; Adirosi, E.; Ortolani, A. Development and Calibration of a Low-Cost, Piezoelectric Rainfall Sensor through Machine Learning. *Sensors* 2022, 22, 6638. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22176638>
- Emilio Laino, Gregorio Iglesias, Scientometric review of climate-change extreme impacts on coastal cities, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 242, 2023, 106709, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106709>.
- Emilio Laino, Gregorio Iglesias, Extreme climate change hazards and impacts on European coastal cities: A review, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 184, 2023, 113587, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113587>.
- Beden N, Soydan-Oksal NG, Arıman S, Ahmadzai H. Delineation of a Groundwater Potential Zone Map for the Kızılırmak Delta by Using Remote-Sensing-Based Geospatial and Analytical Hierarchy Processes. *Sustainability*. 2023; 15(14):10964. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151410964>
- Kralj E, Kumer P, Meulenber CJW. Coastal Flood Risk Assessment: An Approach to Accurately Map Flooding through National Registry-Reported Events. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*. 2023; 11(12):2290. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11122290>.
- Laino, E., Iglesias, G. High-level characterisation and mapping of key climate-change hazards in European coastal cities. *Nat Hazards* 120, 3623–3659 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-06349-4>.
- Paranunzio R, Anton I, Adirosi E, Ahmed T, Baldini L, Brandini C, Giannetti F, Meulenber C, Ortolani A, Pilla F, et al. A New Approach towards a User-Driven Coastal Climate Service to Enhance Climate Resilience in European Cities. *Sustainability*. 2024; 16(1):335. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16010335>.
- Espinosa LA, Portela MM, Moreira Freitas LM, Gharbia S. Addressing the Spatiotemporal Patterns of Heatwaves in Portugal with a Validated ERA5-Land Dataset (1980–2021). *Water*. 2023; 15(17):3102. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15173102>.
- Santos JF, Tadic L, Portela MM, Espinosa LA, Brleković T. Drought Characterization in Croatia Using E-OBS Gridded Data. *Water*. 2023; 15(21):3806. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15213806>.
- Kumer, P., Kralj, E., & Meulenber , C. (2023). Tourism Gentrification in a Small Mediterranean Town: Impacts and Implications for Urban Climate Resilience. *Journal for Geography*, 18(2), 105-122. <https://doi.org/10.18690/rg.18.2.3416>.
- Ignacio Toledo, José Ignacio Pagán, Isabel López, Luis Aragonés, Jorge Olcina, Nature-based solutions on the coast in face of climate change: The case of Benidorm (Spain), *Urban Climate*, Volume 53, 2024, 101816, ISSN 2212-0955, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2024.101816>.
- Quadros Aniche, L., Edelenbos, J., Gianoli, A., Caruso, R., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., Pyl Wissink-Nercua, C., Undabeitia, A., Enseñado, E. M., & Gharbia, S. (2024). Contextualizing and generalizing drivers and

- barriers of urban living labs for climate resilience. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 34(5), 490–523. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.2097>.
- Peker İB, Gülbaz S, Demir V, Orhan O, Beden N. Integration of HEC-RAS and HEC-HMS with GIS in Flood Modeling and Flood Hazard Mapping. *Sustainability*. 2024; 16(3):1226. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16031226>.
 - Emilio Laino, Gregorio Iglesias, Multi-hazard assessment of climate-related hazards for European coastal cities, *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 357, 2024, 120787, ISSN 0301-4797, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120787>.
 - Espinosa LA, Portela MM, Gharbia S. Assessing Changes in Exceptional Rainfall in Portugal Using ERA5-Land Reanalysis Data (1981/1982–2022/2023). *Water*. 2024; 16(5):628. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16050628>.
 - Ariman S, Soydan-Oksal NG, Beden N, Ahmadzai H. Assessment of Groundwater Quality through Hydrochemistry Using Principal Components Analysis (PCA) and Water Quality Index (WQI) in Kızılırmak Delta, Turkey. *Water*. 2024; 16(11):1570. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16111570>.
 - Angeloni, Sabina & Adirosi, Elisa & Sapienza, Fabiola & Giannetti, Filippo & Francini, Franco & Magherini, Lucio & Valgimigli, Alessio & Vaccaro, Attilio & Melani, Samantha & Antonini, Andrea & Baldini, Luca. (2024). Enhanced Estimation of Rainfall From Opportunistic Microwave Satellite Signals. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*. PP. 1-1. 10.1109/TGRS.2023.3349100.
 - Nalukurthi NVSR, Abimbola I, Ahmed T, Anton I, Riaz K, Ibrahim Q, Banerjee A, Tiwari A, Gharbia S. Challenges and Opportunities in Calibrating Low-Cost Environmental Sensors. *Sensors*. 2024; 24(11):3650. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24113650>.
 - Tiwari, Ananya and Rodrigues, Luís Campos and Caruso, Rochelle and Ensenado, Elena Marie and Makousiari, Elina and Gharbia, Salem, Multi-Criteria Analysis of Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Strategies for Flood Risk Reduction in Irish, Italian, and Turkish Coastal City Living Labs. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831266>.
 - Emilio Laino, Roberta Paranunzio, Gregorio Iglesias, Scientometric review on multiple climate-related hazards indices, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 945, 2024, 174004, ISSN 0048-9697, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174004>.
 - Ignacio Toledo, José Ignacio Pagán, Isabel López, Luis Bañón, Luis Aragonés, Analysis of the factors affecting erosion in the beach-dune system of Guardamar del Segura, Spain, *CATENA*, Volume 243, 2024, 108212, ISSN 0341-8162, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2024.108212>.
 - Emilio Laino, Gregorio Iglesias, Beyond coastal hazards: A comprehensive methodology for the assessment of climate-related hazards in European coastal cities, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 257, 2024, 107343, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2024.107343>.
 - Ignacio Toledo, José Ignacio Pagán, Isabel López, Jorge Olcina, Luis Aragonés, Storm surge in Spain: Factors and effects on the coast, *Marine Geology*, Volume 476, 2024, 107373, ISSN 0025-3227, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2024.107373>.
 - Ignacio Toledo, José Ignacio Pagán, Luis Aragonés, Manuel Benito Crespo, Doing nothing is no solution: Coastal erosion management in Guardamar del Segura (Spain), *Marine Policy*, Volume 169, 2024, 106340, ISSN 0308-597X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106340>.
 - Laura Quadros Aniche, Jurian Edelenbos, Alberto Gianoli, Elena Marie Enseñado, Elina Makousiari, Marta Irene DeLosRíos-White, Rochelle Caruso, Spela Zalokar, Boosting co-creation of Nature-based Solutions within Living

- Labs: Interrelating enablers using Interpretive Structural Modelling, *Environmental Science & Policy*, Volume 161, 2024, 103873, ISSN 1462-9011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103873>.
- Emilio Laino, Ignacio Toledo, Luis Aragonés, Gregorio Iglesias, A novel multi-hazard risk assessment framework for coastal cities under climate change, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 954, 2024, 176638, ISSN 0048-9697, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176638>.
 - Emilio Laino, Gregorio Iglesias, Extreme weather events and environmental contamination under climate change: A comparative review of ten European coastal cities, *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health*, Volume 45, 2025, 100606, ISSN 2468-5844, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2025.100606>.
 - Ignacio Toledo, Emilio Laino, Gregorio Iglesias, Antonio Palazón, Luis Aragonés, Local authorities or national frameworks? A global review on coastal protection policies, *Environmental Development*, Volume 53, 2025, 101119, ISSN 2211-4645, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2024.101119>.
 - Aktürk G, Çitakoğlu H, Demir V, Beden N. Meteorological Drought Analysis and Regional Frequency Analysis in the Kızılırmak Basin: Creating a Framework for Sustainable Water Resources Management. *Water*. 2024; 16(15):2124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16152124>.
 - Beden, Neslihan & Göksu, Nazire & Soydan Oksal, Nazire Göksu & Demir, Vahdettin & Ariman, Sema & Haliloğlu, Şule & Ahmadzai, Hayatullah. (2024). Geospatial Application on Mapping Groundwater Potential Zones in Samsun, Türkiye. 11. 21-30.
 - Figueiredo, R., Rangel-Parra, R., Bussi, G., Ceresa, P., Coccia, G., & Martina, M. L. V. (2024). A semi-quantitative multi-hazard risk assessment framework for European coastal urban areas. *Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/19475705.2024.2378994>.
 - Riera-Spiegelhalder, M., Campos Rodrigues, L., & Ferrandis Martínez, A. (2025). Una anàlisi multicriteri per integrar les percepcions dels actors clau en l'adaptació basada en ecosistemes per a inundacions en zones urbanes costaneres. *Documents d'Anàlisi Geogràfica*, 71(1), 153–179. <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/dag.933>.
 - Espinosa LA, Portela MM, Ocampo-Guerrero N. Beyond Temperature Peaks: The Growing Persistence and Intensity of Tmin and Tmax Heatwaves in Portugal's Changing Climate (1980/1981–2022/2023). *Atmosphere*. 2024; 15(12):1485. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos15121485>.
 - Ignacio Toledo, José Ignacio Pagán, Isabel López, Luis Aragonés, Manuel Benito Crespo, Study of the factors affecting the vegetation of the dune system of Guardamar del Segura, Spain, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 262, 2025, 107587, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2025.107587>.
 - Saket Oskoui I, Portela MM, Almeida C. Enhancing Reservoir Design by Integrating Resilience into the Modified Sequent Peak Algorithm (MSPA 2024). *Water*. 2025; 17(2):277. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w17020277>
 - Espinosa LA, Portela MM. Red-Hot Portugal: Mapping the Increasing Severity of Exceptional Maximum Temperature Events (1980–2024). *Atmosphere*. 2025; 16(5):514. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos16050514>.
 - Barańczuk, J., Masik, G., Barańczuk, K. & Meulenberg, C.J.W.. (2024). Multicriteria analysis as a method for engaging stakeholders and citizens in activities aimed at supporting climate resilience and adaptation to climate change – Gdansk Coastal City Living Lab case study. *Miscellanea Geographica*, 29(2), 2024. 68-73. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mgrsd-2023-0049>.
 - Abd-Elhamid, H., Abdelfattah, M., Zeleňáková, M. *et al.* Monitoring coastal changes in Port Said, Egypt using multi-temporal satellite imagery and GIS-DSAS. *Model. Earth Syst. Environ*. 11, 56 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-024-02266-y>.

- Calleo, Y., Pilla, F. and Di Zio, S. (2025), Spatial Scenarios With Real-Time Spatial Delphi and Asymptotic Consensus Analysis: An Application to Ten European Coastal Cities. *Futures & Foresight Science*, 7: e70013. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ffo2.70013>
- R. Nebuloni, F. Giannetti, F. Sapienza, V. Lottici, E. Adirosi, G. Roversi, E. Covi, C. Gianoglio, M. Coll, C. De Michel, A Review of Technical Aspects and Challenges in Opportunistic Rainfall Estimation Using Satellite and Terrestrial Microwave Links, *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, 2025. (accepted)
- Demir, V., Beden, N., Oksal Soydan, Flood Modelling in Samsun's Engiz Stream: Assessment of River Cross-Section Adequacy Using HEC-RAS, *Turkish Journal of Remote Sensing*, doi: 10.51489/tuzal.1617697. (accepted)

1 preprint:

- Bendoni, M., Caparrini, F., Cucco, A., Taddei, S., Anton, I., Paranunzio, R., Mocali, R., Perna, M., Sacco, M., Vitale, G., Corongiu, M., Ortolani, A., Gharbia, S., and Brandini, C.: Multiscale Modeling for Coastal Cities: Addressing Climate Change Impacts on Flood Events at Urban-Scale, *EGUsphere* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-270>, 2025.

6 Conference abstracts

- Ahmed, T., Creedon, L., Anton, I., and Gharbia, S.: The use of low-cost sensors for monitoring coastal climate hazards and developing early warning support against extreme events. , EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-8825, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-8825>
- Anton, I., Paranunzio, R., Gharbia, S., Baldini, L., Ahmed, T., Giannetti, F., Brandini, C., Ortolani, A., Meulenberg, C., Adirosi, E., Hawke, S., Pilla, F., and Iglesias Rodriguez, J. G.: Challenges in retrieving and using climate services' data for local-scale impact studies: insights from the SCORE project, EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-5469, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-5469>
- Riaz, K., McAfee, M., Anton, I., and Gharbia, S.: Conceptualising the management of climate extreme events through the GIS-based digital twin system, EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-7343, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-7343>.
- Giannetti, F.; Vaccaro, A.; Sapienza, F.; Bacci, G.; Lottici, V.; Baldini, L. Multi-Satellite Rain Sensing: Design Criteria and Implementation Issues, *2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC)*, Gran Canaria, Spain, 2022, pp. 1-4, <https://doi.org/10.23919/AT-AP-RASC54737.2022.9814405>.
- Riera Spiegelhalder, M. and Campos Rodrigues, L.: The contribution of participatory decision making in the planning of ecosystem-based adaptation, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-1285, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-1285>.
- Katarzyna Barańczuk, Jacek Barańczuk, Effects of climate change on ice cover in lakes in Europe – future scenarios, in *3rd International Conference Lakes and Reservoirs: Hot Spots and Topics in Limnology Book of Abstract*, 24 - 26th September 2024, Gdańsk.

28 Conference proceedings:

- Adirosi, E.; Facheris, L.; Giannetti, F.; Sapienza, F.; Bacci, G.; Vaccaro, A.; Mazza, A.; Ortolani, A.; Baldini, L. On the influence of the vertical variability on the Earth-to-satellite communication link rain retrievals, *2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC)*, Gran Canaria, Spain, 2022, pp. 1-4, <https://doi.org/10.23919/AT-AP-RASC54737.2022.9814224>

- Giannetti, F.; Vaccaro, A.; Sapienza, F.; Bacci, G.; Lottici, V.; Baldini, L. Multi-Satellite Rain Sensing: Design Criteria and Implementation Issues, 2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC), Gran Canaria, Spain, 2022, pp. 1-4, <https://doi.org/10.23919/AT-AP-RASC54737.2022.9814405>.
- Beden, N.; Oksal, N. G. S.; Ariman, S.; Haliloglu, S.; Ahmadzai, H. City Living Labs for Sustainability and Resilience of Climate Change. In *Proceeding Book, 3rd International Conference on Applied Engineering and Natural Sciences; Konya, Turkey, 2022*, ISBN: 978-625-00-0830-0
- Zelenakova, M.; Abd-Elhamid, H.; Barańczuk, K.; Barańczuk, J. Assessment and adaptation to climate change and sea level rise impacts on Egypt's northern coasts in 2022 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **1252** 012009.
- Nagy, P.; Zeleňáková, M.; Barańczuk, K.; Barańczuk, J. Hydrologic Regime of the Torysa River Basin. In *Book of Abstracts and Articles, 17th International Symposium on Water Management and Hydraulic Engineering (WMHE2022)*; Gdansk, Poland, 2022, ISBN: 978-83-7348-874-8
- Beden, N., Ariman, S., Soydan Oksal, N. G., Haliloğlu, Ş., & Ahmadzai, H. (2023). The Impact and Control of Climate Change in European Coastal Cities: A brief summary of SCORE Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11222402>
- F. Sapienza et al., "Rainfall Field Reconstruction by Opportunistic Use of the Rain-Induced Attenuation on Microwave Satellite Signals: The July 2021 Extreme Rain Event in Germany as a Case Study," 2022 IEEE 2nd Ukrainian Microwave Week (UkrMW), Ukraine, 2022, pp. 523-528, [doi: 10.1109/UkrMW58013.2022.10037149](https://doi.org/10.1109/UkrMW58013.2022.10037149).
- Eparkhina, D. and Nolan, J. (Eds). (2023). Proceedings of the 10th EuroGOOS International Conference 'European Operational Oceanography for the Ocean we want – Addressing the UN Ocean Decade Challenges'. 3-5 October 2023, Galway, Ireland
- F. Sapienza, G. Bacci, F. Giannetti, A. Vaccaro and V. Lottici, "Tropospheric Propagation Modeling for Opportunistic Rain Sensing using Current and Future Broadcast and Broadband Satellites," 2023 XXXVth General Assembly and Scientific Symposium of the International Union of Radio Science (URSI GASS), Sapporo, Japan, 2023, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.23919/URSIGASS57860.2023.10265526.
- Ignacio Toledo, José Ignacio Pagán, Isabel López and Luis Aragonés, Regeneración o mantenimiento. ¿Son la solución a la erosión costera?: Caso de estudio Playa de Poniente (Benidorm) in Proceedings of the XVI Jornadas españolas de Ingeniería de Costas y Puertos, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.4995/CyP.2024.677501>
- F. Sapienza, F. Giannetti, G. Bacci, A. Vaccaro, N. Davini, E. Adirosi, S. Angeloni, L. Baldini, S. Melani and A. Ortolani, Performance comparison of different types of broadcast satellite receivers for opportunistic rain estimation, Proceedings of the 4th URSI AT-RASC, Gran Canaria, 19– 24 May 2024. <https://www.ursi.org/proceedings/procAT24/papers/0667.pdf>.
- F. Sapienza, F. Giannetti, and A. Vaccaro, A Poor's Man Approach to Solar Radio Emission Characterization, Proceedings of the 4th URSI AT-RASC, Gran Canaria, 19– 24 May 2024. <https://www.ursi.org/proceedings/procAT24/papers/1054.pdf>
- Riaz, K., McAfee, M., and Gharbia, S.: Assessing Shoreline Dynamics under Macro to Meso-tidal Conditions through Integrative low-cost Remote Sensing Technique, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-17702, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17702>, 2024.
- Bacci, Giacomo & Scognamiglio, Giovanni & Rucci, Andrea & Vaccaro, Attilio & Serafino, Giovanni & Sapienza, Fabiola & Giannetti, Filippo & Lottici, Vincenzo & Adirosi, Elisa & Angeloni, Sabina & Baldini, Luca & Melani,

- Samantha & Ortolani, Alberto. (2024). Rainfall Estimation by Opportunistic Use of Communications Satellite Signals: Facts and Myths Revealed. 10.46620/URSIATRASC24/NNGA4387.
- F. Sapienza, F. Giannetti and A. Vaccaro, "Measurement of Solar Noise Temperature in Ku-Band Using a Satellite Broadcast Receiver," *2024 IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation and INC/USNC-URSI Radio Science Meeting (AP-S/INC-USNC-URSI)*, Firenze, Italy, 2024, pp. 1451-1452, doi: 10.1109/AP-S/INC-USNC-URSI52054.2024.10686464.
 - Brandini, C., Bendoni, M., Caparrini, F., Cucco, A., Taddei, S., Perna, M., Ortolani, A., Anton, I., Paranunzio, R., and Gharbia, S.: Assessing the impacts of coastal and riverine urban floods in the future climate, results from the SCORE project., EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-19910, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-19910>, 2024.
 - JACEK BARAŃCZUK, KATARZYNA BARAŃCZUK, MARTINA ZELEŃÁKOVÁ, Hany F. Abd-Elhamid, climate change and the occurrence of floods in gdańsk, 17th International Symposium on Water Management and Hydraulic Engineering. [WMHE 2022 conference Gdansk Tech.pdf](https://www.wmhe2022.com/conference/GdanskTech.pdf)
 - Toledo, I., Pagán, J.I., López, I., Aragonés, L. (2024). Nature-Based Approaches to Protect the Shoreline in Urban Environments: The Case of Benidorm (Spain). In: He, B., Jupesta, J., Cirella, G.T., Pignatta, G. (eds) *Urban Climate Change Adaptation*. CCES CCES 2022 2023. Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65088-8_2
 - Beden, Neslihan & Göksu, Nazire & Soydan Oksal, Nazire Göksu & Demir, Vahdettin & Ariman, Sema & Haliloğlu, Şule & Ahmadzai, Hayatullah. (2024). Geospatial Application on Mapping Groundwater Potential Zones in Samsun, Türkiye. 11. 21-30.
 - Mar Riera Spiegelhalter, Luís Campos Rodrigues (ENT); Rafel Ocaña Barbero, Gemma Roset i Juan, Ester Toledo, Proyecto europeo SCORE de adaptación al cambio climático en zonas costeras, CONAMA - National congress on environment, <https://www.fundacionconama.org/wp-content/uploads/conama/comunicaciones/8024/COMUNICACION-DIFUSION-DE-PROYECTOS-SCORE-CONAMA-2024.pdf>
 - Enseñado Elena Marie, Kammerer Lukas, Den Dekker Janneke, Lionggo Indriany, Aamot Tiril, Quadros Aniche Laura, Vanelli Francesca, Makousiari, Elina, Nercua Wissink Charmae, Caruso Rochelle, Vervoort Koen, Marta de los Rios White, Paz Asier Undabeitia, Soloaga Sara, Tiwari Ananya, Anton Iulia, Gharbia Salem, Towards a methodology for monitoring and evaluating living labs: Insights from the early stages within the SCORE Project, in European Network of Living Labs. (2024, avril 9). Proceedings of the OpenLivingLab Days Conference 2023. OpenLivingLab Days 2023 (OLLD), Barcelona. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948803>.
 - Í. de Sena, C. Cocco, V. Brůža, P. Lenicolais, S. Crowley and F. Pilla, "EbAcraft: Engaging Local Communities in Learning About Ecosystem-Based Adaptation for Coastal Cities in Europe," 2023 IEEE 19th International Conference on e-Science (e-Science), Limassol, Cyprus, 2023, pp. 1-9, doi: 10.1109/e-Science58273.2023.10254941.
 - Demir, V. , Beden, N., Ariman, S., Oksal Soydan, G.,Ahmadzai, H., Flood Modeling Using EasyFit and HEC-RAS: A Case Study of Kızılırmak Delta, Dynamic Evolution of Atmospheric, Ecological, and Hydrological Systems in Circum-Mediterranean Regions, Proceedings of the 3rd MedGU, Istanbul 2023 (Volume 1), <https://link.springer.com/book/9783031867768> (accepted)
 - Demir, V., Ariman, S., Beden, N., Oksal Soydan, G., Haliloğlu, Ş., Ahmadzai, H., Homogeneity and Trend Analysis of Seasonal Precipitation Data: A Case Study in Kızılırmak Delta (Samsun, Bafra), Turkey, Dynamic Evolution of

Atmospheric, Ecological, and Hydrological Systems in Circum-Mediterranean Regions, Proceedings of the 3rd MedGU, Istanbul 2023 (Volume 1), <https://link.springer.com/book/9783031867768> (accepted)

- F. Sapienza, F. Giannetti, V. Lottici, E.M. Sciortino, A. Piras, A Feasibility Study on Opportunistic Tropospheric Sensing for Meteorological and Geophysical Applications using Microwave Satellite Downlinks, International Conference on Electromagnetics in Advanced Applications - IEEE APWC, September 8-12, 2025 (accepted)
- F. Sapienza, F. Giannetti, G. Manara, G. Bacci, and A. Vaccaro, The potential of opportunistic rainfall sensing to complement conventional sensors: The 2017 flash flood in Leghorn (Italy) as a case study, URSI Asia-Pacific Radio Science Conference, August 17-22, 2025 (accepted)
- F. Sapienza, F. Giannetti, E. Adirosi, and L. Baldini, Precipitation field reconstruction and tracking using opportunistic rain sensors: the summer 2021 catastrophic event in Germany as a case study, International Conference on Opportunistic Sensing of Precipitation OpenSense, June 25-26, 2025 (accepted)
- R. Nebuloni, F. Giannetti, F. Sapienza, V. Lottici, G. Scognamiglio, A. Vaccaro, E. Covi, C. De Michele, C. Gianoglio, and M. Colli, Comparison between terrestrial and satellite microwave links as opportunistic rainfall sensors, International Conference on Opportunistic Sensing of Precipitation OpenSense, June 25-26, 2025 (accepted)

2 Editorials:

- Hawke, S.M.; Spannring, R. Editorial: Critical inter-disciplinary and inter-species approaches to water sustainability and climate change issues, *Visions for Sustainability*, 2022, 18, 7115, 3-10. <https://doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/7115>
- Anton, I.; Paranunzio, R.; Gharbia, S. Changes of the Coastal Zones Due to Climate Change. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 2023, 11, 2158. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11112158>

1 Special issue:

- Giannetti F, Lanza LG. Special Issue "Rain Sensors". *Sensors*. 2023; 23(15):6934. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23156934>

1 Book chapter:

- Espinosa, L.A., Portela, M.M., Matos, J.P. (2023). ERA5-Land Reanalysis Temperature Data Addressing Heatwaves in Portugal. In: Semião, J.F.L.C., Sousa, N.M.S., da Cruz, R.M.S., Prates, G.N.D. (eds) INCREaSE 2023. INCREaSE 2023. Advances in Sustainability Science and Technology. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-44006-9_7

ANNEX 3 – LIST OF EVENTS

53 scientific conferences:

- Presentation of the SCORE project at the EUSPACE Summer School (19-23 July 2021 - online) by MBI
- Presentation at the Water Resources and Wetland 2021 International Conference (9-11 September 2021 – Tulcea, Romania) by UG
- Exhibition booth at the High-level Conference on Citizen Engagement in EU Missions (21 March 2022 – Paris, France) by ENoLL
- Presentation of the SCORE project at the XVI Spanish Conference on Coastal and Port Engineering (11-12 May 2022 – Vigo, Spain) by UA
- Presentation at the 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (30 May 2022 - 04 June 2022 - Gran Canaria, Spain) by UNIFI
- Poster presentation at the World Conference on Climate Change & Sustainability (Climate Week 2022, 14 June 2022 – Frankfurt, Germany) by HIS
- Presentation at the 39th IAHR World Congress (19-24 June 2022 – Granada, Spain) by IST-ID
- Presentation at the 3rd International Conference on Applied Engineering and Natural Sciences (ICAENS) (20-23 July 2022 - Konya, Turkey) by SAMU
- Presentation at the IV Symposium Ibero-African-American on Risks (21-23 July 2022 - online) by IST-ID
- ATU Sligo led a workshop about the SCORE project at the Education with Sustainability Conference (15-17 August, 2022 - Sligo, Ireland)
- Presentation at the 11th European Conference on Weather Radar in Meteorology and Hydrology (ERAD) (29 August – 2 September 2022, Locarno, Switzerland) by CNR and UNIFI
- Presentation at the Limnology conference 'natural and anthropogenic changes in lakes and water reservoirs (14-15 September 2022 – Ruciane Nida, Poland) by UG
- Presentation at the 17th International Symposium on Water Management and Hydraulic Engineering (16 September 2022 – Sopot, Poland) by UG
- Chair of a thematic panel on the state of water and flooding at the Climate Change Forum (11 October 2022 – Gdansk, Poland) by UG
- Presentation at ATMOS'22, 10th International Symposium on Atmospheric Sciences (18-21 October 2022 – Istanbul, Turkey) by SAMU
- Presentation at the 15th edition of the international conference 'Air and Water - Components of the Environment' (17-18 March 2023 – Cluj Napoca, Romania) by UG
- Presentation at the EGU General Assembly 2023 (23-28 April 2023 – Vienna, Austria) by UG and TUKE
- Poster presentation and organisation of a joint session with the CoCliCo project at the 6th European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) 2023 (19-21 June 2023 – Dublin, Ireland) by ATU and IHS
- Presentation of the SCORE project and NBS at the SRI Congress (26-30 June 2023 – Panama City, Panama & Virtual) by ATU
- 2 Presentations of the SCORE project results at the 12th World Congress of EWRA on Water Resources and Environment (27 June – 1 July 2023 – Thessaloniki, Greece) by IST-ID
- Presentation of SCORE results at the INternational CongReSS on Engineering and Sustainability in the XXI cEntury – INCREaSE 2023 (5 – 7 July 2023 – Faro, Portugal) by IST-ID
- Presentation at the May Robinson Climate Conference (6-7 July 2023 - Ballina, Ireland) by ATU

- Presentation of a tutorial entitled "Opportunistic Use of Microwave Satellite Signals for Early Flooding Detection and Real-Time Rainfall Field Reconstruction" at the Workshop "Disaster Risk Reduction and Management" at the URSI General Assembly and Scientific Symposium (GASS) (August 2023 – Sapporo, Japan) by UNIPi
- 2 Presentations of SCORE results at the 40th IAHR World Congress. Rivers – Connecting Mountains and Coasts (21 – 25 August 2023 – Vienna, Austria) by IST-ID
- Presentation of project results at the 10th Conference on Applied Coastal Research (4-6 September 2023 – Istanbul, Turkey) by UCC
- Presentation at the Water Resources and Wetland 2023 International Conference (16 September 2023 – online) by UG
- Presentation at the Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability (CCES) conference (17-18 September 2023 – online) by UA
- Presentations at the European Global Ocean Observing System (EuroGOOS) International Conference (3-5 October 2023 – Galway, Ireland) by ATU
- Presentation at the 2nd World Conference on Climate Change and Sustainability (16 October 2023 – Rome, Italy) by UG
- Presentation at the 4th IAHR Young Professionals Congress (22-24 November 2023 – online) by IST-ID
- Session convening and oral presentations at the SCORE session "The contribution of participatory decision making in the planning of ecosystem-based adaptation" organized at the EGU General Assembly 2024 (15 April 2024 – Vienna, Austria) by ENT, ATU, CNR, UCC, UCD and LAMMA
- Presentation at the 6th Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (15-18 May 2024 – Marrakesh, Morocco) by UA
- Presentation on precipitation measurements an emergency managements at the URSI AT-Rasc Conference (19-24 May 2024 - Gran Canaria, Spain) by UNIPi
- Three presentations at the 8th IAHR Europe Congress (4 - 7 June 2024 - Lisbon, Portugal). Two by IST-ID and one by IST-ID, TUKE, and UG
- Workshop and exhibition booth at the Littoral 2024 "European Coastal Challenge Summit" (24 September 2024, Constanta, Romania) by ATU
- Presentation at the 3rd International Conference "Lakes and Reservoirs: Hot Spots and Topics in Limnology" (25 September 2024, Gdansk, Poland) by UG
- Presentation at the EUNICOAST on-line conference, contributed 'Climate adaptation in coastal Piran considering implementation of nature-based solutions and revalorization of cultural heritage protected urban infrastructure' (27 September 2024 - Online)
- Exhibition booth at the 10th European Conference on sustainable cities and towns (1-3 October 2024, Aalborg, Denmark) by NAIDER
- Presentation at the XXXI Congreso Latinoamericano de Hidráulica (1 - 4 October 2024 - Medellin, Colombia) by IST-ID
- Presentation at the 16th EMUNI Conference, with 'Historic fresh-water sources in the coastal Mediterranean Town of Piran' (10 & 11 October 2024 - Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS
- Presentation at the Precipitation Processes - Estimation and Prediction (PrePEP) conference (16-21 March 2025) by UNIPi
- Poster presentation at the 17th International Conference 'Air and water components of the environment' (21 March 2025 - Cluj-Napoca, Romania) by UG
- Three presentations and one poster presentation at the EGU 2025 (27 April - 2 May 2025, Vienna, Austria) by TUKE, LAMMA, RED, and ENT

- Side event and exhibition booth at the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA, 16-18 June 2025, Rimini, Italy) by the SCORE consortium
- Presentation at the EGU Leonardo Conference on Earth's Hydrological Cycle From Science to People: Expecting the Unexpected in Flood and Drought Risk Management Science Progress and Engineering Practice (20 June, Bologna, Italy) by CNR
- Three presentations at the EMCEI 25 (23 -26 June 2025, Reggio Calabria, Italy) by RED, SAMU and UA
- Presentations at the International Conference on Opportunistic Sensing of Precipitation (25-26 June 2025 - Offenbach, Germany) by UNIFI
- Presentation at the 41st IAHR World Congress (IAHR 2025) (22-27 June 2025, Singapore) by IST-ID
- Presentation at the 19th International Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management (CUPUM, 23-27 June 2025, London, UK) by UCD
- Presentation at 13th World Congress on Water Resources and Environment (EWRA 2025) (24-28 June 2025, Palermo, Italy) by IST-ID

Two additional events will be attended by the SCORE partners shortly after the end of the project:

- Two presentations at the International Congress on Engineering and Sustainability in the XXI Century (INCREaSE 2025) (1-4 July 2025, Faro, Portugal) by IST-ID
- Presentation at the ICUC12 – 12th International Conference on Urban Climate (7-11 July 2025, Rotterdam, the Netherlands) by IHS

5 exhibition fairs in technology and open innovation events

- Exhibition booth and workshop at the Earth Technology Expo (13-16 October 2021 – Florence, Italy) by MBI, CNR and LAMMA
- Exhibition booth at the Open Living Lab Days 2022 (20-22 September 2022, Turin, Italy) by ENoLL
- Workshop, roundtable and exhibition at the Open Living Lab Days conference (21-23 September 2023, Barcelona, Spain) by ATU, ENoLL, HIS, ERINN, UG and EUR
- Promotion of the project at the Diputació de Barcelona Booth at the Smart City Expo World Congress (9 November 2023 – Barcelona, Spain) by VNG.
- Presentation at the Smart City Expo World Congress (5-7 November 2024 - Barcelona, Spain) by UCD

18 International forums

- Presentation of the SCORE project at the Foro de las Ciudades (14 June 2022 – Madrid, Spain) by NAIDER and ENT in collaboration with the CCLLs of Oarsoaldea, Benidorm and Vilanova i la Geltrú
- Presentation of the latest results and findings of SCORE to representatives of the European Commission at the 1st Clustering event of the ClimateChangeMitigation.eu (28-29 March 2023) by ATU
- Presentation at the Oceans Visions Biennial Summit (4-6 April 2023 – Atlanta, Georgia) by ATU.
- Presentation of the latest results and findings of SCORE to representatives of the European Commission at the Ocean Visions Biennial Summit 2023 (5 April 2023) by ATU.
- Presentation of the project and of the CCLL framework at the Waves of Change Forum (5-6 June 2023 – Biarritz, France) by NAIDER
- Presentation at the SEA-EU Talent Communications – Climate Change (10 October 2023 – online) by UG
- Presentation at the MonGOOS (Mediterranean Oceanographic Network for the Global Ocean Observing System) General Assembly and Workshop on Ocean Forecasting and its applications in the Mediterranean Sea: present status, gaps and ways forward (14-16 November 2023 - Tangier, Morocco) by LAMMA.

- Presentation of Sligo CCLL's results to the EFRAG Sustainability Reporting Technical Expert Group (March 2024 – online) by ATU.
- Poster presentation of the Adapt4Coast cluster at the Third Forum for the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change organised by the EU Commission (May 2024 - Brussels, Belgium) by ATU.
- Presentation of the SCORE project and its approach to the study of coastal extreme events at the 55th International Liège Colloquium on Ocean Dynamics (27 - 31 May 2024 - Liège, Belgium) by LAMMA
- Presentation at the XIX International Colloquium of Tourism Geography (6-7 June 2024 - Cullera, Spain) by ENT.
- Contribution to the scientific and technical workshop of the Digital Ocean Forum 2024 (12 June 2024 – Brussels, Belgium) by MBI.
- Presentation of the project and of the CCLL framework at the Waves of Change Forum 2024 (28 June 2024 – Biarritz, France) by NAIDER.
- Workshop and exhibition booth at the European Week of Regions and Cities (7-10 October 2024, Brussels, Belgium) by ATU, EUR, ERINN, VNG, MBI
- Presentation at the 3rd CHESS workshop 'Freshwater consumption in the region of Istria' (14 October 2024 - Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS
- Presentation at the AMIS project kick-off meeting (22 October 2024 - Lucca, Italy) by LAMMA
- Exhibition booth at the European Maritime Days (21-23 May 2025) by ERINN
- Presentation at the CoCliCo Policy Event "Coastal zones are under pressure from climate change: transformational adaptation is needed" (24 June 2025 - Brussels, Belgium) by ATU and TERO

31 National, regional, and local events

- Presentation of the SCORE project and results at the XVI Jornadas Españolas de Ingeniería de Costas y Puertos (11-12 May 2022 – Vigo, Spain) by UA
- Presentation of the project at the Foro de las Ciudades (14 June 2022 – Madrid, Spain) by NAIDER and ENT in collaboration with the CCLLs of Oarsoaldea, Benidorm and Vilanova i la Geltrú
- Presentation of the project at the presentation event of the Oarsoaldea Development Agency 2021 activity report (21 June 2022 – Oarsoaldea, Spain) by OAE
- Presentation of the project at during the presentation event of the Barcelona's Metropolitan Strategic Plan (20 September 2022 - Espai far, Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain) with the attendance of several local municipalities by VNG
- Presentation of the project at the VI Jornada de Governança del Litoral del Garraf (17 November 2022 – Vilanova, Spain) by UA
- Two presentations at the XII Congreso Ibérico de Gestión y Planificación del Agua (26-28 January 2023, Murcia, Spain) by IST-ID
- Project presentation, stakeholder briefing & discussion on practical engagement (27 January 2023 - Dunmoran Beach, Sligo, Ireland) by SCC.
- Oral presentations at the 16° Congresso da Água (21-24 March 2023 – Lisbon, Portugal) by IST-ID.
- Project presentation and discussion with the local stakeholders on the solution to protect the sand dunes in Streedagh (19 April 2023 - Streedagh Beach, Sligo, Ireland) by SCC and ATU.
- Presentation of the SCORE project to the Minister of Environment, Climate and Communications, Eamon Ryan (5 May 2023 – Sligo, Ireland) by ATU.
- Presentation at the seminar “Monitoring and protection of the territory between adaptation and innovation” (27-28 June 2023 – Ancona, Italy) by LAMMA.

- Presentation on sand management for the beach sustainability at the Sitges City Council (15 September 2023 – Sitges, Spain) by VNG.
- Presentation at the Ilešičevi dnevi, Podnebne spremembe in izzivi geografije (22-23 September 2023 - Ljubljana, Slovenia) by ZRS.
- Presentation at the Social innovation workshop on freshwater consumption (26 September 2023 – Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS.
- Presentation at the Primera mesa de Playas Costa del Sol (27 September 2023 - Málaga, Spain) by UA.
- Presentation of SCORE activities during a meeting between the VNG City Council and the Sitges City Council (4 October 2023) by VNG.
- Presentation of SCORE activities at the Jornada de trEBAll PEMB (3 November 2023, Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain) by VNG.
- Presentation at the 9º Seminário do Núcleo Regional do Norte. Fenómenos hidrológicos extremos: os desafios das próximas décadas (16 November 2023 – Porto, Portugal) by IST ID.
- Presentation at the VII Jornada de Governança del litoral del Garraf (22 November 2023 - Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain) by VNG.
- Discussion and problem formulation of Slovenian coastal fresh water consumption at the 2nd CNESS workshop (20 February 2024 – Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS.
- Presentation of SCORE activities at the 24th Annual Assembly of the Vilanova i la Geltrú Municipality (7 March 2024) by VNG.
- Presentation of SCORE’s climate objectives and Piran’s CCLL, results and objectives at the EMUNI University (18 March 2024 – Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS.
- Presentation of results from SCORE’s student pilot workshops in Piran at Tartini House (5 April 2024 – Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS.
- Presentation at the XVII Jornadas Españolas de Ingeniería de Costas y Puertos (8-9 May 2024 – Ibiza, Spain) by UA.
- Poster presentation at the Soluciones Basadas en la Naturaleza: una apuesta de futuro /Nature-based Solutions: a commitment to the future (8-10 May 2024 - Pamplona, Spain) by ENT.
- Lecture 'Nature-based solutions and ecosystem-based adaptations from the SCORE project and the coastal city living lab approach' at the True Blue Summer School (12 June 2024 – Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS.
- Presentation at the SHYFEM meeting (20-21 June 2024 – Venice, Italy) by LAMMA.
- Presentation at the workshop “Le modificazioni della costa in un clima che cambia” (25-26 June 2024 – Livorno, Italy) by LAMMA.
- Participation in a roundtable with regional stakeholders in Nature-based Solutions, ecosystems and cultural and natural heritage protection to share the lessons learned from Piran CCLL (20 March 2025, Piran, Slovenia) by ZRS
- Presentation at the XIII Congreso Ibérico de Gestión y Planificación del Agua (24 - 26 April 2025 - Salamanca, Spain) by IST-ID
- Presentation at the "Monitorare per proteggere: la sfida delle coste" (16 May 2025 - Livorno, Italy) by UNIPI

19 science popularisation events*

**This list does not include popularisation events organised by the SCORE project*

- Presentation of the SCORE project and distribution of project flyers to attendees of the Sligo Engineering & Technology Expo (28 April 2022 – Sligo, Ireland) by ATU. In addition, a full page was dedicated to present the SCORE project in the catalogue of the Expo (page 186 - https://issuu.com/itsligo/docs/sligo_eng_tech_expo_2022_edition).
- SCORE was selected to participate in the FAIR live exhibition as part of the 1st edition of the New European Bauhaus Festival (9-12 June 2022 – Brussels, Belgium). A SCORE mobile exhibition booth was on display in 4 different locations around the city during the 3 days of the festival.
- UCD organised an exhibition booth and the workshop “Geodesign game for families” during the UCD Festival (11 June 2022 – Dublin, Ireland)
- UNIPI attended the Bright researchers Night 2022 (20 September 2022 – Pisa, Italy) with an exhibition booth.
- ATU promoted the SCORE project at the Sligo Science Festival (13 November 2022 – Sligo, Ireland)
- Project promotion at the ATU Sligo Engineering Fair (5 March 2023 – Sligo, Ireland) by ATU
- Project promotion at the ATU Sligo Engineering Expo (4 May 2023 – Sligo, Ireland) by ATU. A full page was dedicated to present the SCORE project in the catalogue of the Expo (page 30 - https://issuu.com/atlantictchnologicaluniversity/docs/sligo_eng_tech_expo_catalogue_2023/2).
- Participation in the EU Green Week with several activities (field trips with local farmers, seabed cleaned) and targeting various audiences to raise awareness of climate risks and marine pollution (May and June 2023, Samsun, Turkey) by SAMU
- Project promotion at the Climate change talk - Spanish Armada, Streedagh Beach (17 September 2023 – Sligo, Ireland) by ATU
- Participation in the Clean Coasts Roadshow in County Sligo to highlight funding opportunities for communities, integrate Nature-based solutions for climate resilience, and showcase coastal projects currently taking place in the region (20 January 2024 - Sligo, Ireland) by ATU and SCC
- Organisation of experiments with the EBAs and sensors to be implemented in Benidorm targeting high school students during the 'Quiero ser ingeniera' (26 March 2024 – Alicante, Spain) by UA
- Participation of ZRS Koper at the Local Festival of Saint George and terraces site visit with students (19-21 April 2024 – Piran, Slovenia)
- Organisation of a Climate Walk during the Podnebni sprehod na Piranu (28 April 2024 – Piran Slovenia) by ZRS
- Presentation of SCORE low-cost sensors at an event organised by VNG during the Green Week (7 June 2024, Vilanova i la Geltrú, Spain)
- Participation in the Noite Europeia dos Investigadores – NEI Oeiras 2024 (27 September 2024, Oeiras, Portugal) by IST-ID and Oeiras
- Participation in the Horhor Stream and Coastal Waste Cleanup Event (October 2024, Samsun, Turkey) by SAMU
- Organisation of experiments with the low-cost sensors and nature-based solutions targeting high school students during the 'Quiero ser ingeniera' (10 April 2025 – Alicante, Spain) by UA
- Presentation during the Oeiras Civil Protection Week (9 May 2025, Online) by Oeiras
- Participation in the Pomeranian Night of Scientists – Scientists at Schools (June 2025, Gdansk, Poland) by UG

ANNEX 4 - KNOWLEDGE OUTPUTS

KO 1.1 - Mapping of baseline exposure and risks of climate change impacts on SCORE's Coastal Cities Living Labs.

Knowledge Owners : UCC

Current Status: Open-Access as part of D1.4 ([link](#))

Description: This KO is composed of several high-level (i.e., high resolution) baseline maps outlining the risks faced by each of SCORE's ten coastal cities living labs to the extreme impacts of sea level rise and climate-related events (i.e., coastal erosion, coastal flooding, land flooding, landslides, heatwaves, cold spells, strong winds, droughts, heavy rainfall, heavy snowfall) due to climate change.

The methodology to develop these models is not novel or unique to SCORE, however, it is a necessary first step in the further development of climate adaptation strategies. The maps are used to outline climate-change-related hazards in an easily digestible way for each CCLL.

The maps have been developed using the following:

- A systematic literature review (10,000+ articles at the global level and 1000+ specifically linked to the CCLLs) on the extreme impacts of climate change on ten European coastal cities.
- A comprehensive overview of the key hazards and impacts of climate change on the study cities as identified via the literature review and the local expertise of the CCLL partners.
- Key hazards include storms, coastal and land flooding, coastal erosion (Sligo and Dublin CCLLs), coastal flooding (Piran CCLL), and coastal flooding and land flooding (Gdansk and Oeiras CCLLs).
- GIS software to map the key hazards
- A high-level, semi-quantitative assessment of exposure and vulnerability for the study cities
- The bespoke semiquantitative approach is based on the application of a combination of popular index-based and indicators methods. The methodology is developed to adapt to the available information through existing indicators.
- The assessment involves the evaluation of two parameters of vulnerability (sensitivity and adaptive capacity) and exposure, that are measured through indicators and then scored as low, medium or high on the vulnerability scale.
- The mapping of coastal exposure and vulnerability indicators for the cities
- Vulnerability indicators include, measuring of different land uses within the low-elevation coastal zone, population statistics, identification of natural protected areas, existence of local coastal adaption plans, and sea-level rise projections.

CCLL Specific Outputs: The maps differ for each CCLL due to the ability to disaggregate at a community level. Benidorm, Oeiras, Oarsoaldea and Massa's baseline maps disaggregate the relevant hazards into sub-areas (i.e., different municipalities). For the other six CCLLs (Sligo, Dublin, Vilanova, Piran, Samsun and Gdansk), the map has been developed more holistically because there was not sufficient data to disaggregate further. In addition to the maps, there are lists of past-climate events, which are useful for a deeper analysis of the risks.

Target & End Users:

- Governments (national & local) are the primary stakeholder group, this group includes policymakers, urban planners, and environmental/climate departments. Those relevant for each CCLL are listed below:
 - Benidorm: Town Hall Civil Engineering Area, General Directorate of Coasts.
 - Dublin: Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Council, Office of Public Works (OPW), Irish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA).
 - Gdansk: Municipal Office of Gdansk, Department of the Environment, Regional Directorate for Environmental Protection.
 - Massa: Municipality of Massa, Tuscany Region Settore Difesa del Suolo.
 - Oarsoaldea: Local government (4 municipalities), Basque Country government agencies.
 - Oeiras: Oeiras Municipality, Portuguese Environment Agency.

- Piran: Piran Municipality, National Environmental Agency.
- Samsun: Samsun Municipality, Samsun Provincial Directorate of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change.
- Sligo: Sligo County Council, Department of Environmental Climate and Communications.
- Vilanova: Gava City Council, ACA - Catalan Water Agency.
- Academicians, researchers, and scientists, specifically Civil Engineers, Survey Engineers, and Environmental Engineers.
- Industry: Various sectors like climate technology, environmental consulting, sensor and software development, civil engineering, insurance, tourism, agriculture, fisheries, and urban infrastructure. Examples include Techworks Marine and sensor providers like DANALTO in Dublin, which contributed technological expertise; tourism operators and Hidraqua, a water utility in Benidorm; and agricultural and fisheries representatives like the Irish Farmers Association and BIM (Seafood Agency) in Sligo. Other local partnerships ranged from hospitality associations in Massa, to innovation-focused SMEs in Piran, and environmental consultancies in Gdańsk.

Potential Application & Impact

This knowledge output provides scientific support to help European coastal cities develop medium- to long-term climate adaptation and resilience plans. Its impact is highly context-specific, as each map is tailored to the unique conditions of individual CCLLs. In cities like Piran, Samsun, Sligo, Massa, and Oarsoaldea, where baseline assessments were previously unavailable or inaccessible, this work is especially valuable, laying the foundation for future climate strategies and policies. While cities like Dublin, Vilanova, Benidorm, Oeiras, and Gdańsk already had climate plans and assessments in place, the maps still enhance existing planning efforts. Although understanding the underlying flood modelling is helpful, the final products are user-friendly and accessible to non-experts, supporting wider stakeholder engagement.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

Academic scientific articles published:

- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2023). Extreme climate change hazards and impacts on European coastal cities: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 184, 113587. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113587>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2023). Scientometric review of climate-change extreme impacts on coastal cities. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 242, 106709. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106709>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2024). High-level characterisation and mapping of key climate-change hazards in European coastal cities. *Natural Hazards*, 120(4), 3623-3659. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-06349-4>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2024). Multi-hazard assessment of climate-related hazards for European coastal cities. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 357, 120787. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120787>
- Laino, E., Paranzio, R., & Iglesias, G. (2024). Scientometric review on multiple climate-related hazards indices. *Science of The Total Environment*, 174004. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174004>
- Laino, E., Iglesias, G. (2024). Beyond coastal hazards: A comprehensive methodology for the assessment of climate-related hazards in European coastal cities. *Ocean Coast Manag* 257, 107343. DOI: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2024.107343>
- Laino, E., & Iglesias, G. (2025). Extreme weather events and environmental contamination under climate change: A comparative review of ten European coastal cities. *Curr Opin Environ Sci Health* 2025, 45:100606. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2025.100606>

KO 2.4 – Coastal City Living Lab Monitoring and Evaluation Framework

Knowledge Owners: <i>Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies, Erasmus University Rotterdam</i>	Current Status: Open-Access as part of D2.3 (link) and available on the IHS website (link)
---	--

Description: A key innovation of the SCORE Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL) Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) framework lies in its integrated, participatory approach applied across ten diverse CCLLs within the SCORE project, which seeks to strengthen climate resilience in European coastal cities. Unlike conventional M&E models, this framework is specifically tailored to the

Living Lab context, blending established evaluation methods with participatory M&E principles to ensure relevance and adaptability across varied settings. Its dual focus on process (implementation) and effect (outcome and impact) during the whole project cycle provides a comprehensive view of both how initiatives are executed (problem definition, ideation and co-design prototype and pilot, testing and evaluation) and what they achieve. The embedded stakeholder engagement in evaluating progress and effectiveness represents a significant advancement, fostering a more inclusive, reflective, and context-sensitive evaluation process rarely seen in traditional frameworks.

By providing a structured assessment, the framework addresses the current lack of a standardized evaluation approach, which limits cross-project learning, scalability, and broader impact. As it stands, the SCORE CCLL M&E framework is particularly suited for projects operating within Living Lab (LL) environments—especially those focused on climate resilience and urban innovation. However, its flexible, principle-based design means it is not limited solely to SCORE or coastal contexts, and could potentially be applied to any LL setting, regardless of thematic focus or geographic location.

Importantly, while it is grounded in LL-specific processes, the framework’s emphasis on participatory evaluation, process-effect duality, and stakeholder engagement makes it adaptable to other innovation-driven or community-based projects beyond the LL model. This opens up the possibility for its use in a wider range of initiatives, including non-EU-funded efforts and urban transformation programs in general.

With further refinement and adaptation, the framework could evolve into a universal evaluation tool that not only enables cross-project comparisons but also guides participants—particularly those unfamiliar with LL concepts—through the development, implementation, and evaluation phases. In doing so, it would provide a structured, replicable model to support the expansion and institutionalization of LLs, ultimately strengthening their role in building climate resilience and fostering urban innovation across diverse contexts.

M&E criteria and indicators: Criteria and indicators were categorized into three evaluation phases: baseline (initial evaluation), interim (progress through different phases and activities), and impact assessment (final evaluation).

Data collection tools: The CCLL data collection process utilized a combination of online surveys, meetings, and workshops to enable a structured assessment across baseline, interim, and endline phases. Likert-scale questionnaires provided quantifiable comparisons, while written feedback offered contextual insights. Survey links and Miro boards will be added in the IHS webpage.

CCLL specific outputs: The evaluation results and sustainability plans of CCLLs are detailed in the public document Deliverable 2.3: Evaluation Outcomes and Sustainability Plans of CCLLs. This report presents key findings on CCLL outcomes and long-term viability. A link to this public document will be added in the IHS webpage.

Target & End Users

The target users include CCLL and LL practitioner/s, networks e.g., ENOLL, as well as academic and research communities engaged in initiatives related to CCLLs and LLs.

Potential Application & Impact

The scientific community, including academic and research institutions, can benefit from the CCLL M&E framework through its application in similar LLs and comparative analysis over time, contributing to broader research. From a practical perspective, LL practitioners can implement the framework in comparable settings, gaining valuable insights and fostering continuous learning to enhance their methodologies.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

At the network level, the European Network of Living Labs serves as a key platform for knowledge dissemination, enabling the sharing of lessons learned and best practices. This framework can be shared in the Water and Oceans Working Group.

The aim is to effectively communicate and disseminate the CCLL M&E framework among SCORE CCLLs to facilitate its adoption and long-term use through email communication, meetings, and dedicated events, ensuring broad accessibility and

engagement. To maximise impact, knowledge transfer strategies will include integration into online toolkits and initiatives (such as ENoLL working groups and the IHS website) that promote long term sustainability.

KO 3.1 - Procedural Guide for Identifying and Using Climate and Marine Data Services and Datasets for Baseline Characterization and Projections

Knowledge Owners : LaMMA, CNR, ATU **Current Status:** Open Access, as part of D3.1 & D3.2 –
[D3.1 Package of procedures for baseline characterization and projections](#)
[D3.2 Data usage document for the Reference datasets for baseline characterization and projections](#)

Description: This KO provides users with procedures and sample data on climate and marine conditions suitable for characterising current climate conditions and making future projections, with a specific focus on coastal cities. Specifically, the main goals of this KO are:

- To provide **information on available climate services** across Europe (listed below), along with the main requirements for the identification and selection of datasets of interest to the project (i.e., e.g., users' needs, variables, accessibility and available spatiotemporal resolution and coverage, available documentation). Those requirements are tailored to the CCLLs as a whole.
- 1. To provide a list of the **most appropriate datasets** to be used for **SCORE** activities.
- To provide a step-by-step procedure for accessing the identified datasets and handling data and information through specific use cases/examples.
- To provide a **general overview and description of a set of selected datasets and variables** in terms of usability, structure, interfaces and access, data format and metadata.

This KO aims to be a valuable resource providing a comprehensive overview of available climate and marine datasets. However, it is important to note that this KO, especially the section describing how to access and handle the datasets, is not intended to replicate information already available on official climate service websites and platforms. Instead, it serves as a **tailored data usage document for SCORE project activities**. In other words, this KO aims to provide requirements and delineates an approach to collect climate data and information from the key climate services and initiatives available across Europe which are of interest for SCORE activities.

This KO provides the **first step toward a larger goal: developing regional and local projections and models for the CCLLs**. As such, these data are to be subsequently analysed and processed for local scale analysis. For this purpose, **open, free and reliable climate data** are essential.

Key Climate Services identified:

The climate services represent a single online point access to a wide range of climate and marine datasets across Europe otherwise sparsely accessible and available. Thus, they complement capabilities existing at the national level and provide comprehensive climate information for a variety of different purposes and studies. The ones selected for the which fit the project requirements are:

- **EFAS (European Flood Awareness System):** Provides 6-hourly flood forecasts and monthly seasonal streamflow outlooks.
- **EMODnet (European Marine Observation and Data Network):** Offers marine data across various themes like bathymetry, biology, chemistry, and physics.
- **CORDEX (Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling):** Provides regional climate downscaling experiments and simulations.
- **Copernicus Datasets:** Includes marine biogeochemistry data, ocean surface wave time series, and water level change time series.
- **CFSv2 (Climate Forecast System Version 2):** A coupled model providing atmospheric, oceanic, and land surface data.

Data Accessibility, format and licensing:

- Data is generally accessible through APIs, FTP, or data viewers.
- Formats include GRIB2, NetCDF-4, ASCII, and compressed files.

- Licenses vary across datasets, with some being freely available while others may have specific restrictions.

A use case: Coastal Flooding in Ireland

The Irish case study focuses on the impact of climate change on coastal flooding at a local scale in Ireland and its relevance to other Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs) within the SCORE project. Here's a breakdown of the case study:

- **Problem:** Ireland lacks meteocean datasets for future climate projections. Currently, fixed ratios of increase are assumed for variables like water level per year and percentage change of wind height in the medium and long term. The case requires the knowledge of meteorological and hydrogeological models, with input data such as water level, mean sea level change, wave features, and wind.
- **Solution:** Utilising the **Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)** and its Climate Data Store (CDS). The CDS provides datasets on sea level rise, storm surges, and tidal variations, which are crucial for assessing flood risk in coastal areas. This data enables the evaluation of current and future risks based on different climate scenarios, helping to predict extreme weather events.
- **Benefits:** Stakeholders and end users can access climate and marine data to understand the impact of storm surges and sea levels on the Irish coastline. The data supports long-term planning and enables decision-makers to develop adaptive measures for future climate scenarios. The CDS data helps local authorities, urban planners, and communities implement effective flood risk management and adaptation strategies.
- **Impact:** The impact indicators provided by the C3S assist end users in decision-making and taking actions to improve climate resilience. Outputs from this activity are planned for inclusion in the national Climate Change Sectoral Adaptation Plan for Flood Risk Management, flood risk management plans, and erosion risk management plans.
- **Accessibility:** Use cases and demonstrator projects in the C3S can be accessed through the "Sectoral Impact" page.

In essence, the case study demonstrates how **easily accessible climate and marine data** and products can help understand the impact of storm surges and sea level rise, leading to better climate resilience and adaptation measures.

Target & End Users : It has to be stated that in the framework of the SCORE project, data extracted from the services and datasets are meant to be handled and processed by expert users who have the specific skills to interpret the results and transfer information to the different range of stakeholders. Given that, the primary end users expected to benefit from this KO are as follows:

- Research communities working on climate adaptation: the methods designed through this approach are useful to produce climate scenarios as well.
- Municipalities of coastal cities that are managing climate risks: The visualisation outputs generated by these methods would benefit local communities, as they will be both easily accessible and easy to understand.
- Environmental scientists and technical experts analysing climate data or developing climate models of their own.
- Civil protection agencies such as national or UN disaster risk reduction organisations for preparedness for extreme weather events.
- Local and national environmental agencies.

Potential Application & Impact

The purpose of transferring this knowledge output is to empower municipalities, researchers, and stakeholders in European coastal cities to make evidence-based decisions that enhance climate resilience and sustainable coastal management. By providing a comprehensive framework of curated and bespoke datasets, alongside practical guidance for their application, this knowledge aims to bridge the gap between raw climate data (useful) and actionable insights (usable). During the SCORE project, the KO facilitates:

1. Localized hazard assessments, such as coastal flooding, erosion, and urban climate impacts.
2. The development of early-warning support and infrastructure planning tailored to regional vulnerabilities.
3. Collaboration across Coastal City Living Labs (CCLs) to implement co-created adaptation solutions that integrate scientific rigor with community input.

Beyond SCORE, the intended impact of this knowledge is multi-faceted:

1. Policy Influence: Establishes a standardized approach for utilizing climate services, aiding policymakers in aligning local actions with broader climate goals, such as those outlined in the Paris Agreement.

2. Capacity Building: Enhances the technical capabilities of end-users, ensuring sustained use and adaptation of datasets and tools in addressing emerging climate challenges.
3. Scalable Solutions: Provides a replicable model for other regions globally, promoting resilience in diverse coastal contexts.
4. Informed Decision-Making: Ensures that future urban planning, hazard management, and sustainability initiatives are grounded in high-quality, actionable climate data.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures: Due to the interconnected nature, any communication, dissemination or exploitation activities will not focus solely on this KO but will encompass the results of the entire WP3 in a broader, more holistic framework.

- Organizing workshops and training sessions for end-users within the CCLLs
- Publishing findings in peer-reviewed journals: [link](#)
- Presenting findings at conferences: [link](#)
- Engaging stakeholders through SCORE’s online platform for real-time dataset access.
- Supporting local government initiatives with targeted consultations and user guides.

KO 3.3 - Package for the statistical analysis tools, data and user-guide for urban-scale models.

Knowledge Owners: ATU; **Current Status:** Open access, as part of D3.5-3.8:

CNR; LaMMA

- User Guide 1: [D3.6 User document for statistical analysis tools for urban-scale hazards and data samples](#) .
- Associated functions: [D3.5 Package for the statistical analysis tools for urban-scale hazards](#)
- User Guide 2: [D3.8 - Short-term hazard modeling](#) Associated Functions: [D3.7 - Package of short-term hazard modeling](#)

Description: This KO includes the **processing tools, procedures, and accompanying user guide useful to produce data for urban-scale models.**

Urban-scale models are computational representations of cities that simulate various aspects of urban life, including: *infrastructure* (e.g., roads, bridges, buildings, and transportation networks), the *environment* (e.g., climate, air quality, and water resources), the *economy* (e.g., land use, business activities, and population distribution), and *social dynamics* (e.g., demographics, migration patterns, and social interactions).

These models are used for a variety of purposes, including climate change adaptation, as they **assess the vulnerability of cities to climate change and help develop adaptation strategies**. To achieve this, they require specific, local and tailored data — **data that this KO aims to provide.**

This KO provides essential tools for urban hazard analysis, focusing on extreme value analysis (EVA) and urban scale hydraulic modelling. This analysis is crucial for creating flood maps and conducting risk assessments, ensuring its relevance for disaster preparedness and coastal resilience.

Specifically, the aim of this KO is to provide

1. A set of **urban-scale statistical based analysis tools and procedures, along with a user guide**, to support the analysis of historical data and future projections for quantities related to extreme weather events, such as wave height or precipitation levels (Guidebook 1)
2. Hydraulic models at urban scale (Guidebook 2)

These tools can be used to estimate trends in these parameters, identify suitable distributions and return periods and group homogeneous conditions. Based on these statistical tools, procedures for short-term hazard modelling can be performed to simulate flood water extent and depth on coast and land and thus to assess areas at risk. User guides serve as comprehensive instructional bases for the tools and procedures available.

Guidebook & Statistical Tools 1: Construction of urban-scale scenarios

The first user guide includes a brief theoretical explanation of the statistical analysis tools, instructions for using these tools, and a description of the datasets that can be generated. The main areas covered in the document include:

- Time series trend analysis: a straightforward analysis often used to estimate trends in key parameters based on linear models.
- Extreme value modelling based on extreme value theory: an analysis of historical timeseries and future projections for key parameters used to estimate the likelihood of the occurrence of extreme values.
- Clustering techniques for the multivariate data analysis: this analysis is aimed at grouping homogenous conditions for coastal hazard occurrence in the CCLLs, enabling the identification of typical conditions associated with various hazards, such as coastal flooding.
- Analysis of the weather circulation types over a defined region (in this case, the CCLLs areas): this method associates major coastal hazards in the CCLLs with relevant atmospheric characteristics, helping to understand the conditions linked to weather events like floods, storms, and waves.

As described, these elements provide a **statistically based and standardised procedure to analyse historical time series and projections**. The datasets used as inputs in this KO are derived from previous SCORE activities, and consist of time series of key parameters, which are either observed and measured in the past (historical) or modelled to forecast future trends (projections). The procedures are **accompanied by step-by-step examples**, that allow users with relevant expertise to apply each of them to their own case studies and data using a variety of functions, written in the R coding language, as practical tools. These tools support the estimation of trends in key parameters in coastal urban areas (e.g., sea level, wave height, wind speed, rainfall, sea temperature) and related extreme values, and they facilitate identifying suitable distributions and return periods. In detail, this KO provide 4 functions for the time series and extreme value analysis (TimeSeriesAnalysis.r, General_EVA.r, River_discharge_EVA.r, Calculate_threshold.r), one for the data clustering techniques (DataClustering.r) and a set of files containing the weather circulation types.

Guidebook 2: Hydraulic Models

The second user guide provides a **theoretical overview of the “last-mile” hydraulic models used to assess short-term hazards**. It includes a detailed explanation of their application, the associated methodology, and the results from the analysis conducted in the WP3 frontrunner cities (CCLLs) i.e., Massa (Italy), Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), Oarsoaldea (Spain) and Samsun (Turkey).

The main topics covered in this document are:

1. **Hydraulic Modelling at Urban Scale**: This section outlines the parameters, models, and tools employed to assess the impacts of flood and sea-level dynamics, including tides, storm surge, and wave-induced sea level changes, at the urban scale.
2. **Case Studies and Results**: This section presents the results of applying the “last-mile” hydraulic models to the four WP3 frontrunner cities across various RCP scenarios and temporal horizons. The analysis demonstrates how these models can be used to predict urban-scale flood risks under different climate conditions.

This document also describes the tools (models, scripts) and data files used for short-term hazard modelling and flood mapping with high spatiotemporal resolution, under different radiative forcing scenarios.

Case studies accompany the hydraulic modelling section, highlighting the practical application of these models in generating urban-scale flood scenarios. Additionally, the guide includes links to resources detailing the installation, compilation, and execution of the urban-scale flood models, such as HEC-RAS, XBeach, and coupled models, available in various languages.

Novelty: This KO demonstrates the capability of an integrated modelling framework to assess impacts of future climate change scenarios at the fine spatial resolution of the coastal cities based on extreme value analysis of projected relative sea level rise (RSLR) and river discharge. EVA is not a new process, however, **novelty lies in the inclusion of the well-consolidated EVA procedure within a new high-resolution multi-scale model that transfers atmospheric information at the synoptic (large) scale to the urban scale of coastal cities under different climate change scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) and temporal horizons**. These results can be used both for validation and intercalibration in the Digital Twin development (WP8). Additionally, integration of EVA and integrated hydraulic modelling into the digital framework: SCORE-ICT Platform (SIP) (WP5), and use of these data outputs in Early Warning Support System (EWSS) is a valuable advancement.

Next Steps: The time series, hazard maps and outputs produced in this task are among the main sources of data production stored in the SCORE ICT Platform - SIP - (WP5) for the entire project and a fundamental component to drive models in Digital Twin (DT) and EWSS (Early Warning Support System) in WP8 for Samsun, Massa, Oarsoaldea and Vilanova CCLLs.

CCLL Specific Outputs: This KO provides maps simulating the extent and depth of flooded areas in four WP3 frontrunners CCLLs (Samsun, Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrú, and Oarsoaldea).

Target & End Users:

KO3.3 provides tools, data, and a user guide focusing on extreme value analysis and hydraulic modelling to help Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) generate locally tailored climate data. This is particularly useful for the CCLLs of Samsun, Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrú, and Oarsoaldea. Local governments, such as the Municipality of Massa, Samsun Municipality, Vilanova i la Geltrú City Council, and the Oarsoaldea Development Agency, can use this information to enhance local climate adaptation plans.

This document would be useful for researchers and academics who are working on climate resilience in coastal cities beyond SCORE.

Potential Application & Impact

The impact of KO3.3 is substantial for fostering data-driven climate resilience, particularly within CCLLs. It provides tools, data, and methodology allowing local authorities in CCLLs like Samsun, Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrú, and Oarsoaldea to generate high-resolution, tailored climate data. This empowers them to enhance local climate adaptation plans, improve flood management policies, and make informed infrastructure decisions, strengthening urban resilience.

The KO also impacts the academic community by providing resources for teaching and research in advanced extreme value analysis and hydraulic modelling. Environmental scientists and agencies can use the tools for hydraulic risk assessment, hazard monitoring, and predictive modelling, improving disaster preparedness. NGOs can leverage the outputs for vulnerability assessment and evidence-based awareness campaigns and policy advocacy. The free, open-access nature and transferable methodology extends its potential use within SCORE and to other coastal areas.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

- Conference Poster: [link](#)
- PICO presentation: [link](#)
- Preprint: [link](#)

KO 3.6 - Testing Package & User Document to Improve Coastal Hazard Assessment & Long-Term Shortline Evolution.

Knowledge Owners: UCD, LaMMA, CNR, ATU; **Current Status:** Open Access - [D3.11 - Packages of Testing Tools](#) and [D3.12 - User Documentation for Testing Tools and Data](#)

Description: Coastal cities are at the forefront of climate change impacts that endanger their infrastructure, ecosystems, and communities. Rising sea levels, more intense storm events, coastal erosion, and urban flooding required immediate, data-driven solutions. Addressing these complex issues, predictive models and tools have been developed (in WP3 tasks) to analyse short- and long-term evolution of the coastline and flood scenarios. This KO integrates the developed findings, models, and tools to **establish a final set of cohesive tools, aimed at testing and validating the models' effectiveness in simulating real-world conditions and supporting decision-making in coastal risk management.**

This Testing Package consists of multiple testing tools and models combined to analyse and predict coastal hazards. Specifically, these tools were designed to validate and improve models produced (previously in the WP3 tasks) for coastal hazard assessment and long-term shoreline evolution using real-world data and earth observations that allow users to explore various hazard scenarios. The user document acts as a guide manual for using these tools developed for coastal hazard assessment, such as flood hazard forecasting, extreme climate event modelling, coastal erosion, and urban resilience under various climate scenarios.

The package tools include:

Historical And Current Shoreline Dynamics Analysis tools (Google Earth Engine (GEE), Coastsat toolkit, and Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS)) integrated to analyse historical and current shoreline changes, exploring the erosion and accretion patterns over time. These tools were tested in a case study of Dublin (Ireland) shoreline.

- [Google Earth Engine \(GEE\)](#): Advanced algorithm retrieves and processes satellite data from platforms (Landsat and Sentinel2). This algorithm enables water/land classification and shoreline detection, allowing for efficient shoreline vectorization and generate of GeoJSON files for integration with spatial analysis. The extracted shoreline vectors are then analysed for coastal erosion trends using transect-based measurements in DSAS.

- [Coastsat Toolkit](#): A Python-based open-source toolkit that integrates with GEE, enabling users to extract shoreline time-series data for any coastal region. Users can define their region of interest (ROI), process satellite imagery, and generate GeoJSON files for further analysis.
- [Digital Shoreline Analysis System \(DSAS\)](#): A dedicated tool for quantifying shoreline changes and erosion/accretion rates. DSAS integrates satellite-derived shoreline data to perform transect analysis and predict future shoreline trends using weighted linear regression (WLR) for long-term analysis.

Future Shoreline Evolution Modelling tools (COSMOS-COAST, XBeach) predicts future coastline trends influenced by natural processes and human activities by integrating multiple climate modelling aspects to address varying temporal scales. The models are implemented in specific case studies, such as Benidorm (Spain) and Massa (Italy).

- [COSMOS-COAST model](#): A computational tool designed to simulate long-term shoreline evolution. By integrating sediment transport dynamics, satellite-derived shoreline data, and sea-level rise projections, the model predicts shoreline behaviour over time. Its robust algorithm captures the interplay of erosion, accretion, and sedimentary processes to generate long-term forecasts.
- [XBeach](#): An open-source hydrodynamic model designed for simulating extreme wave conditions and associated morphodynamics.

Flood extent in historical event validation tool Remote sensing data provided by Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), a radar technique used to create high-resolution images of the Earth's surface utilizing microwave signal, are employed to detect flood extent in the study area. It is not a tool, but an instrument (a form of radar) used to collect data. SAR images are widely used in literature for different purposes. This tool was applied in a historical flood event of Marina di Massa (Italy), and some historical flood event of Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain) and Oarsoaldea (Basque Country, Spain).

Flood extent in climatological scenarios validation tools (XBeach and FUNWAVE-TVD) simulate flood risks in urban coastal areas through multiple climatological aspects. These tools were tested in a case study of Massa.

- [XBeach](#): An open-source hydrodynamic model designed for simulating extreme wave conditions and associated morphodynamics.
- [FUNWAVE-TVD \(fully nonlinear Boussinesq wave model - Total Variation Diminishing\)](#): A fully nonlinear Boussinesq wave model specifically selected for its capability to provide accurate phase-resolving simulations of wave dynamics, making it particularly suited to addressing the challenges of coastal inundation and complex wave interactions.

These tools work together to test, validate, and refine climate resilience models, ensuring accuracy and adaptation in real-world conditions.

The key novelty of testing package presented on:

- Integrated approaches by combining multiple tools to offer a comprehensive analysis of shoreline evolution, and flooding.
- Validation with real data using satellite imagery from different missions making the analysis patterns more accurate and reliable.
- Advanced coastal flood models which provide a systemically physics simulation of how climatological aspects interact with flooding.
- Adoptability and scalable solution which can be applied to different coastal cities with varying conditions.

Testing package builds upon earlier WP3 tasks (D3.7, D3.8, D3.9, and D3.10). The models developed in the previous deliverables are tested and validated using the methodologies and testing tools described in D3.11 and D3.12.

CCLL Specific Outputs: The testing tools for Shoreline Analysis have been applied to the following case studies:

- Dublin (Ireland) shoreline dynamics analysis using Google earth engine, DSAS, and Coastsat.
- Benidorm (Spain) and Massa (Italy) shoreline evolution analysis using a hybrid approach combining XBeach and COSMOS-Coast.

The testing tools for Flood Extent Analysis have been applied to the following case studies:

- Massa (Italy), Vilanova i la Geltru (Spain) and Oarsoaldea (Basque Country, Spain) in historical flood event using a SAR data - based method and the computation of validation coefficients (still in progress).
- Massa (Italy) coastal flood assessments in Climatological Scenarios using XBeach and FUNWAVE-TVD.

Target & End Users: CCLLs technical staff, stakeholders, and researchers: This document is mainly intended to support technical staff, stakeholders, and researchers from CCLLs in using and validating models and tools designed for flood hazard assessment, extreme event modeling, and long-term coastal dynamics in urban coastal environments. The documentation provided can serve as a reference for a broader scientific community interested in validation methods for flood hazard assessment, extreme event modeling, and long-term coastal dynamics in urban coastal environments as it provides technical details on the testing tools.

Potential Application & Impact

- Technical staff and stakeholders in Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) can use this KO to assess the models' applicability, accuracy, and effectiveness in simulating real-world conditions across various climate conditions. The validation tools are specifically designed to bridge the gap between theoretical modeling and practical application, ensuring the efficacy of the models in forecasting flood events and predicting coastal changes.
- By ensuring these tools undergo rigorous testing, users (including local governments and municipalities) can confidently use them to plan for new strategies and mitigate the risks associated with climate change, sea-level rise, storm surges, and other coastal hazards. Consequently, this KO demonstrates its support for effective decision-making in coastal risk management, which is one of the SCORE project goals.
- Scientific community involved in flood hazard assessment, extreme event modeling, and long-term coastal dynamics can be interested by this KO, as validating climatological models for flood extent at a local scale presents significant challenges, especially due to the limited availability of comprehensive literature databases, unlike those for large-scale models.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

- Oral presentation titled "Compound Coastal Flood and impact-based Risk Assessment in the Context of Climate Change: Using a Multimodel Approach to Enhance Coastal Resilience" scheduled at EGU25 conference (<https://www.egu25.eu/>).

KO 3.7 - Constructing Severity Heat Maps to Assess Temporal Changes in Extreme Rainfall (Portugal)

Knowledge Owners: IST-ID, ATU

Current Status: Published Open-Access:

Espinosa, L.A.; Portela, M.M.; Gharbia, S. (2024). Assessing Changes in Exceptional Rainfall in Portugal Using ERA5-Land Reanalysis Data (1981/1982–2022/2023). *Water*, 16(5), 628. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16050628>

Description: This Knowledge Output (KO) provides an in-depth analysis of exceptional rainfall events in Portugal over a 42-year period, spanning from 1981 to 2023. Utilising the publicly available ERA5-Land reanalysis dataset, which offers high-resolution and continuous daily rainfall data, the study examines the frequency and intensity of extreme rainfall events. The analysis focuses on rainfall that exceeds key empirical thresholds, specifically the 95th, 99th, 99.5th, and 99.9th percentiles. These empirical percentiles are statistical measures that divide a dataset into 100 equal parts. In this context, they represent rainfall amounts that exceed a certain percentage of all recorded values: the 95th percentile is only exceeded by 5% of observations; the 99th, 99.5th, and 99.9th percentiles indicate increasingly rare and intense rainfall events. This approach allows for a detailed assessment of how exceptional rainfall patterns have evolved spatially and temporally across the region.

A significant innovation in this KO is the development of a severity heat map, which visually represents the temporal evolution of combined characteristics of exceptional rainfall events. This map integrates both the frequency and cumulative intensity of extreme rainfall, highlighting regions where rainfall severity has increased. By distinguishing between areas of heightened rainfall frequency and those with increased cumulative rainfall, the heat map provides a nuanced view of how extreme weather impacts have shifted over time. This tool is particularly valuable for identifying high-risk areas and informing climate adaptation strategies.

The KO advances beyond existing research by leveraging the ERA5-Land dataset, which addresses many limitations of traditional meteorological datasets, such as data incompleteness and the uneven spatial distribution of weather station

networks. The ERA5-Land dataset's high spatial resolution and consistent temporal coverage ensure a more accurate and comprehensive analysis of rainfall dynamics. The study's validation against established observational records from the two main sources of hydrometeorological ground-based records in Portugal further supports the reliability of its findings. These records are obtained from IPMA (Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera) and SNIRH (Sistema Nacional de Informação de Recursos Hídricos), both of which provide freely available data.

Overall, this KO contributes to a deeper understanding of rainfall patterns in Portugal and offers practical tools for climate risk assessment. The severity heat map enhances the ability to communicate and visualise rainfall impacts effectively, aiding in disaster preparedness and urban planning. This map uses a color-coded scale to represent severity, with red areas indicating the highest severity where both the number of occurrences and cumulative rainfall have increased, green areas showing the lowest severity with lower values compared to the past, orange areas representing an increase in cumulative rainfall, and yellow areas indicating an increase in occurrences. By highlighting the evolving nature of extreme rainfall and regional variations, the KO underscores the need for adaptive strategies in response to changing climate conditions and supports informed decision-making in managing water resources and infrastructure.

Target & End Users

Academic and Research Community: Environmental scientists, climate researchers, and hydrologists can utilise this KO to enhance their understanding of rainfall patterns and extreme weather events. The high-resolution data and severity heat map provide valuable resources for academic studies and research projects focused on climate change, meteorology, and hydrology. These insights may also prove valuable to other regions facing similar climate challenges, thus extending the utility of the severity heat maps beyond Portugal's borders.

Government Bodies and Policy Makers: National and local government agencies, such as the Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere (IPMA) and the Ministry of Environment and Climate Action, can leverage this KO to inform policy-making and climate adaptation strategies. The severity heat map can aid in identifying high-risk areas and prioritising resource allocation for infrastructure improvements and disaster preparedness.

Urban and Regional Planning Authorities: City planning authorities and regional development agencies can use the insights from this KO to guide urban development and zoning decisions. The detailed analysis of exceptional rainfall patterns can inform the design of drainage systems, flood defences, and other critical infrastructure to mitigate the impacts of extreme weather events. The outputs of this methodology are indeed applicable at a regional planning scale due to the high-resolution spatial data provided by ERA5-Land, which has a resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.10^\circ$ per pixel. This level of detail allows for precise analysis and insights relevant to specific regions within any country.

Potential Application & Impact

Academic and Research Community: Researchers can use this KO to study the impact of climate change on rainfall and extreme weather, integrating high-resolution data and severity maps into climate models. This KO can enhance academic research, improve climate predictions, and contribute to global climate change awareness and policy advocacy.

Government Bodies and Policy Makers: Anyone from agencies such as IPMA and the Ministry of Environment and Climate Action can utilise this KO to develop targeted climate adaptation strategies and allocate resources to high-risk areas identified by the severity heat map. Meteorologists, and climatologists at IPMA could use the heat maps for detailed analysis of rainfall patterns and extreme weather events (and can be adapted to different variables). The Minister of Environment and Climate Action could use these heat maps for drafting and implementing environmental policies related to climate change adaptation. The KO can inform more effective policies, enhancing community resilience, infrastructure preparedness, and disaster response.

Additionally, Planning authorities can use this KO to guide urban development, and improve drainage systems based on detailed rainfall analysis. The KO can help create climate-resilient cities, reducing flood risks and damages, supporting sustainable growth, and protecting the environment.

Overall, transferring this KO to the end users can raise climate change awareness, enhance preparedness for extreme weather, and foster resilient, sustainable communities.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

Publication: Espinosa, L.A.; Portela, M.M.; Gharbia, S. (2024). Assessing Changes in Exceptional Rainfall in Portugal Using ERA5-Land Reanalysis Data (1981/1982–2022/2023). *Water*, 16(5), 628. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16050628>

GeoStories: Present in the Oeiras CCLL GeoStories in [English](#) and [Portuguese](#).

Conferences: European Researchers' Night in Portugal 2024 in Portugal, the XXXI Congreso Latinoamericano de Hidráulica from IAHR in Medellín, Colombia 2024, and will be presented in April 2025 at the XIII Congreso Ibérico de Gestión y Planificación del Agua in Salamanca, Spain. This upcoming event will also include heat maps for temperature (not only for rainfall) based on this methodology, showcasing the wide-ranging applicability of this KO.

Policy Brief: A Policy Brief regarding this methodology and outputs was already produced by IST-ID and already included in SCORE website ([link](#)).

KO 5.2 - SensorThings Application Programming Interface (API) and Data Harvesters

Knowledge Owners : UniPi, TERO

Current Status: The SensorThings API server is published as open-source software and can be deployed and hosted for free by anyone. Data collectors are up and running and constantly updated, managed on a TERO server, and will be hosted within the same system at the UNiPi once the SIP is finalised. Data collectors will continue to run until the end of the project's lifetime

Description: As the key element of data collection within the SIP, the Data Harvesters and SensorThings API address the challenge of multiple sensor data in different formats, which were single-use applications for specific purpose and had specialised user interfaces.

The SensorThings API sensor interface allows the platform to deal with the heterogeneity of data formats and communication methods and protocols, comply with standards and specifications relevant to spatial data such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), standardise the spatial data collected from various networks, ensure data interoperability, and build a citizen science platform to support activities. It consists of eight entities that are linked to each other: thing, location, sensor, observed property, observation, datastream, historical location, and feature of interest.

Data Collectors: The data collectors are small pieces of software which allow the collection of data from the various webpages provided by the CCLLs that hold information of interest for use in the SIP (such as weather data, etc.). These harvesters have similar functionalities but are programmed to be specific per webpage/site. As such, they aren't an output or a product.

Data collectors can include those from CCLL sensor networks or professional sensors, though they have not yet been used for SCORE sensors to date. They can be scheduled to run to collect real time data with different sampling rates, read data with different structures and data formats, connect to third party APIs that are both public and private, and can integrate the process that is responsible for the transformation and publication of heterogenous data to the standard format that is supported by the SensorThings API.

Data collectors are configured and deployed on a case-by-case basis depending on the requirements and technical characteristics of each network.

Data collectors pull data from data sources, then push the data to the SensorThings API servers. In cases where data from the citizen sensors deployed at CCLLs cannot be automatically sent to the API, data collectors act as a solution to this issue. For instance, citizens can act as a data source to push data towards the servers.

- Data is pulled by data collectors via an ETL process, and then this is pushed into the API server.
- For the citizen sciences, we want to pull/push the data to the SensorThings API.
- Data can also be manually uploaded to SensorThings API via specialized web applications

Target & End Users :

A user would need technical knowledge in order to use this KO, and it would need to be used in conjunction with the SIP for functionality. Target and End Users capable of utilizing and benefitting from the technologies developed under the SensorThings API and the Data Collectors are:

1. Academics/Researchers: The community of scientists/researchers, specifically those in architecture, urban planning, civil and environmental engineering, telecommunications and sensing engineering, climatology and atmospheric sciences, including SCORE technical partners.
2. Industry: Industry and SMEs with technical and development capability, such as sensor devices and sensor network manufacturers, data analytics, architecture and urban planning companies.
3. R&I projects: Researchers and Innovators, specifically those working in EU-funded projects.

Potential Application & Impact

The main advantage is the capability to collect heterogeneous data and produce it in a unified format. Applications include utilisation by the scientific/research community to develop tools, allowing Industry and SMEs to adjust the API and develop data collectors for their own technologies. R&I projects can apply these technologies in numerous sectors like environmental, health, and transport. The API is used to collect data for SCORE's DT-EWS system. As part of a wider system like the SIP, it provides potential for decision making and planning, although it needs tailoring for each case.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

Completed actions include a webinar of the SIP and promotion of the open-source technology through CCLLs and other events. This KO is strongly embedded into KER 5.1 SIP and will be clustered alongside relevant DEC activities, including the SCORE final event. UniPi and associated partners have determined that if a new project is identified and the SIP is a component, the SIP can be embedded into project activities.

KO 5.3 - Visualisation Suite for Project Data Communication and Sensor Data Collection

Knowledge Owners : UNIPI, TERO, LaMMA

Current Status: The visualisation tools on the SIP platform are accessible to web visitors at <https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/>. Content creation is currently limited to those SCORE CCLL members with a login to the SIP.

Description: This KO refers to the visualisation suite for project data communication and sensor data collection, which is an element of the larger SCORE ICT (Information and Communication Technology) Platform, or SIP for short, (see KO5.1). The SIP is an integrated digital platform that acts to collect and share data within the project communities, researchers, and stakeholders of Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs) within the SCORE project. The SIP is currently online and able to be accessed at (<https://platform.score-eu-project.eu/>).

This KO refers specifically hosting, sharing, and visualization of data, which includes digital content produced within the project, ranging from event photos and documents to sensor outputs. This does not include the large datasets used as inputs (e.g., those from climate modelling or datasets available at CCLLs), as this would represent an unnecessary duplication, nor the datasets produced by the of the project, as these are hosted on Zenodo multi-disciplinary open repository (maintained by CERN). This KO refers to the elements of the SIP that are capable of hosting, managing, and displaying these various types of data.

The SIP was purposely created to meet the requirements and needs of project activities concerning data hosting, managing, and visualization. The SIP consists of two main parts:

- **A Data Hub**, which includes the SCORE database (DB) that will host all project data, along with relevant services such as metadata management and interfaces for data access.

- **A Sensor Service**, specifically designed to collect and download data from the broad set of sensors installed within the project.

The SIP platform is hosted on a dedicated server, made available by UNIPI's IT systems and services team, that can be accessed through a web client application, i.e., using a simple browser. The SIP provides the project with a valuable tool for sharing all relevant information, documents, and results, both internally and externally.

Graphical User Interface

The web client Graphical User Interface (GUI) for accessing the platform's resources is designed to be user-friendly for both technical and non-technical users. It employs design patterns and components based on user-centred design principles. Most functionalities are grouped into a few views and pages for ease of use. Different levels of permission are implemented for content creators, project personnel, and general web visitors:

- **Web visitors** have only view permissions. The application provides tools for navigation, filtering, and drilling down into detailed resource information.
- **Content creators** have access to various tools for creating, editing, and managing resources, as well as their related metadata and permissions.

The catalogue and the resources

The *catalogue* represents the central functionality of SIP. It serves the purpose of exploring and viewing the published resources and provides the tools for viewing and downloading (web visitors) or managing it (resource creators). A *resource* is the central concept of the catalogue. It represents an item with a connected data source, metadata information, owner and a shared/published status within the platform's catalogue. While a resource is an abstract concept, the actual items that users can manage and navigate on the SIP are *concrete resources*. A concrete resource is a type of resource with specific characteristics:

- **Document:** generic resource like a document, a photo, an audio file without geospatial information (not anchored geographically)
- **Spatial Dataset:** generic resource with geospatial information (georeferenced data).
- **Timeseries:** a dataset with temporal support.

The concrete resources mentioned above are simple resources. Simple resources directly map to a data source (filesystem, database, etc.), either local or remote. Simple resources can be combined to create more complex resources using specialized tools available in the SIP platform. Below are three key tools that SIP provides:

- **Maps:** multiple spatial datasets can be combined and styled to compose a rich interactive map.
- **Dashboards:** a virtual board where multiple widgets and maps can be positioned to create live views on specific datasets, tailored to create reports, decision support tools, and so on.
- **Geostories:** a vertically scrolling composition of media, maps and documents that can communicate an organic representation of a story based on geographical features.

The visualization tools for each of these resources are the central point of this KO, providing the project with a shared, free, and tailored instrument for gathering and sharing data, both for internal use and for the external dissemination of project data and activity documentation.

CCLL Specific Outputs: Each CCLL has a personal and dedicated GeoStory page available on the SIP to highlight and showcase their project outputs. For example, see Massa CCLL's [GeoStory](#).

Target & End Users : Web visitors (view only, including those learning about CCLLs and quadruple helix stakeholders). Content creators (access to creation/editing tools; currently CCLL Core Team, potentially other projects/academics needing to manage/visualise large local data). Outputs (GeoStories, Maps, Dashboards) are of interest to local governments/municipalities.

and the general public. Specific potential users include CCLL Networks, Municipalities and local governments (especially CCLLs), and Other projects and academics (academia, environmental scientists)

Potential Application & Impact: CCLLs can use this KO for communication activities, easily sharing digital resources like links on social networks or for presentations. Municipalities and local governments can use the information and outputs for communication activities, sharing documents, maps, or datasets. This enhances local climate adaptation plans by enabling more tailored and informed communication and dissemination activities, such as sharing knowledge on EBAs. Other projects and academics can work more efficiently by centralising and visualising heterogeneous data, retrieving information quicker, and leveraging experience from CCLLs.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

An exploitation pathway has been considered by partners in conjunction with the SIP and Digital Twin. A joint commercial initiative among partners is in preliminary phase. The KO was made available to an audience of stakeholders and individuals aware of SCORE activities at an EBA School event.

KO 5.4 - SCORE Citizen Science Sensor Data Uploader Application

Knowledge Owners : TERO

Current Status: The application is online, fully operational, mobile responsive, and available for use by SCORE project partners and CCLLs. The underlying open-source server implementation of the SensorThings API is available on GitHub.

Description: The SCORE Sensor Data Uploader App is a mobile-friendly web application that allows users—both technical and non-technical—to connect, upload, and manage data collected from sensor devices. Recognising that sensor devices from different manufacturers output data in varying formats, the application serves as an intermediary that maps incoming data to the SensorThings API standard. Any sensor device could be compatible with the application, and the application is designed to collect data from sensors that are unable to communicate data via wireless or wired networks (data is saved on an integrated device storage).

Its innovative edge lies in its user-centric design combined with backend integration to the SensorThings API OGC standard, ensuring the standardisation and interoperability of heterogeneous data. This makes it particularly valuable for citizen science projects and for integrating community-generated data with professional sensor networks. Entities who run professional sensor networks can use the OGC SensorThings API to gather community-generated data in a standardised format for subsequent processing and analysis. An automated data process that cleans, validates, and enriches raw inputs prior to integration is essential. The application simplifies complex data submission processes into an accessible web interface, thereby expanding participation in environmental and urban data collection efforts.

User Experience (UX) Flow

- 1. Registration and Verification**
 - a. User selects account type (Individual / CCLL / Team)
 - b. Enters registration details
 - c. Verifies account via email
 - d. [Success] → Dashboard Access
- 2. Device/Sensor Registration**
 - a. Users selects a sensor from predefined list
 - b. Provides a name
 - c. Selects sensor location on map
 - d. [Sensor saved]
- 3. Dataset Uploads**
 - a. User selects sensor from map
 - b. Drag-and-drop data file (e.g. CSV)

- c. Maps file columns to sensor parameters
- d. Selects timezone for data
- e. Confirms upload
- f. [Upload success]

4. Status Tracking

- a. View status dashboard
- b. See total rows, imported rows, issues (if any)

Key Characteristics:

- **User-Friendly Interface:** Intuitive dashboards for device registration, dataset uploads, and status tracking.
 - **Device Registration:** Users select their device from a list of available sensors, provide a recognisable name for the device and select the location where the sensor is or will be installed.
 - **Dataset Upload:** Users select one of their registered sensors on the map, upload the data file (e.g. CSV) via a “drag-and-drop” interface, map the columns within their uploaded file to the corresponding measurements monitored by the sensor and finally select the appropriate timezone relevant to when the sensor data was recorded.
 - **Status Tracking:** Users can monitor the status of the data import process (e.g Submitted, Processed, Failed) and get detailed information on the total number of observations being imported to the system.
- **Standardized Data Harmonization:** Automatically maps heterogeneous sensor data to the SensorThings API model, ensuring compatibility with global geospatial standards and addressing fragmentation in environmental monitoring. The entity that manages the SensorThings API can determine if the data will be available publicly or privately.
- **Automated Data Processing:** Implements advanced data entry tools (e.g., timezone alignment, data column mapping), reducing manual errors.
 - **Data column mapping:** Users are not required to pre-process data files or eliminate redundant data from sensor logs, which carries the risk of data loss.
 - **Timezone alignment:** The system requires the date-time value of the observations to be expressed in Universal Time Coordinated (UTC). The app automatically aligns the time zone of the data, eliminating the need for users to perform the conversion manually.

See below some images of how the application looks to a user, from the landing page (Figure 1) to the sensor data upload form (Figure 2). The app does not provide any visualisations of sensor data. The data is stored in the SensorThings API, and how the data appears in the API is seen in Figure 3.

Figure 1 31. Landing page of the application

Figure 2 32. Sensor data upload form

```

@iot.count: 4000
- values:
  - @iot_sdtLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/1"
    @iot_id: 1
    resultTime: "2024-09-15T11:35:00Z"
    result: 14.25
    Datastream@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/1/Datastream"
    FeatureOfInterest@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/1/FeatureOfInterest"
    Object@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/1/Objects"
    ObservationGroup@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/1/ObservationGroups"
    Subject@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/1/Subjects"
  - @iot_sdtLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/2"
    @iot_id: 2
    resultTime: "2024-09-15T11:40:00Z"
    result: 14.25
    Datastream@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/2/Datastream"
    FeatureOfInterest@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/2/FeatureOfInterest"
    Object@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/2/Objects"
    ObservationGroup@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/2/ObservationGroups"
    Subject@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/2/Subjects"
  - @iot_sdtLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/3"
    @iot_id: 3
    resultTime: "2024-09-15T11:45:00Z"
    result: 14.25
    Datastream@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/3/Datastream"
    FeatureOfInterest@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/3/FeatureOfInterest"
    Object@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/3/Objects"
    ObservationGroup@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/3/ObservationGroups"
    Subject@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/3/Subjects"
  - @iot_sdtLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/4"
    @iot_id: 4
    resultTime: "2024-09-15T11:50:00Z"
    result: 14.25
    Datastream@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/4/Datastream"
    FeatureOfInterest@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/4/FeatureOfInterest"
    Object@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/4/Objects"
    ObservationGroup@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/4/ObservationGroups"
    Subject@iot_navigationLink: "https://localhost:8082/PROST-Server/v1.0/observations/4/Subjects"
  
```

Figure 3. Sensor data sample from SensorThing API

The application enhances data interoperability and enables real-time or manual data handling—closing the gap between citizen-generated and system-compatible data. It contributes significantly to SCORE’s goals by enabling consistent data integration from diverse sources into the SCORE ICT Platform (SIP) (KO5.1).

Target & End Users : It is noted that to deploy and operate the application, the target users should have some level of technical expertise. When collecting community data, a clear methodology for data cleaning, validation, and quality control must also be established. The application must be read alongside KO5.1 (the SIP) and KO5.2 (Data Harvesters and SensorThings API) as they are interconnected for full functionality. KO5.4 integrates community-generated data with professional sensor networks.

- Academics/Researchers: Supporting open and replicable science through accessible data collection.
- Citizen Scientists: Enabling non-experts to contribute meaningful environmental data.
- Public Authorities: Local and regional governments collecting community-based data.
- CCLL Partners: Coastal City Living Labs utilising the app for sensor deployment and community engagement.
- Smart City Planners & Urban Developers: Collecting fine-grained spatial data from communities.
- Environmental NGOs and Advocacy Groups: Monitoring and visualising citizen-reported data.

Potential Application & Impact

The result has broad, holistic impacts that extend beyond individual user groups. By enabling both technical and non-technical users to upload sensor data through a mobile-friendly interface and mapping it to the SensorThings API standard, the application significantly simplifies data submission and bridges community-generated and professional datasets.

Its overall impact includes:

- Democratising environmental data collection, expanding access and participation in scientific and civic processes.
- Enhancing data standardisation and interoperability, supporting cross-sector collaboration and open science.
- Strengthening evidence-based decision-making in public governance and urban planning.
- Empowering local and coastal communities to take part in climate action and resilience initiatives.
- Fostering sustainable development, aligning with broader environmental and policy goals like the EU Green Deal.
- Enabling data-driven advocacy, equipping NGOs and civil society with tools for monitoring and influencing environmental policy.

While user-friendly, effective deployment requires some technical capacity and must be accompanied by robust data quality protocols. The tool works in conjunction with other SCORE components (KO5.1 and KO5.2) to deliver its full value.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

The KO was made available to CCLLs in conjunction with KO4.1 to facilitate citizen science activities. It enables the uploading of uncertified and unvalidated data from low-cost sensors in the catalogue to the SensorThings API server. This KO can be utilised in EU research projects focusing on environmental monitoring data, citizen science activities and open standards, either independently or in conjunction with the SCORE Catalogue of low-cost sensors viable for citizen science activities (KO4.1). Further funding opportunities will be identified, and the application will be promoted to future consortiums, with the objective of further improving and enhancing its functionality. It is a recommendation to provide training sessions at conferences or events for interested users of the app to increase usage within future activities.

KO 6.1 – Exposure database and vulnerability curves for the Coastal City Living Labs, Massa, Vilanova and Oarsoaldea

Knowledge Owners : Red Risk

Current Status: Open-Access : [D6.3 Exposure database and vulnerability curves for the frontrunner CCLLs](#)

Description: The overarching goal of this work is to develop quantitative risk assessments for the CCLLs - Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrú, and Oarsoaldea. Building this quantitative risk assessment requires two preliminary components, which are the focus of this KO

- 1) the development of the exposure datasets ;
- 2) the vulnerability curves.

Exposure datasets are, by definition, geospatial datasets, i.e., digital maps, where the exposure information is associated with spatial coordinates. This activity includes collating:

- 1) The different types of assets in the pre-identified region (i.e., buildings, road networks, rail networks, population size)
- 2) Their geographical distribution;
- 3) The key features (e.g., building occupancy types, main construction materials, road classes) that determine their vulnerability to natural hazards (i.e., flooding);
- 4) Estimating the amount and/or value of assets that potentially could be affected by natural hazards using different sources that can include construction cost data, construction market survey data, and analyses of technical documentation, reports, and scientific literature.

This above asset information is combined with a hazard component, which assesses the probabilities of different hazards occurring in a region (e.g., probabilities of flood water depths being exceeded at different locations within a city).

These exposure datasets combine multiple open-access datasets from different sources. Typically, a single dataset (i.e., a roadmap) won't have sufficient information on all the individual assets (i.e., the height of the buildings, the materials used, etc.), therefore multiple datasets containing the necessary information are collated using statistical and downscaling techniques.

Vulnerability curves allow us to establish mathematical relationships between hazard intensity (i.e., depth of flooding) and losses for the different types of assets. For example, the vulnerability curve would tell us for this specific building, if there is 1 meter of flood water depth, we could anticipate 20% damage and therefore €350,000 in damage.

Output: Geospatial dataset (shape file) and vulnerability curves. These outputs are specific to the CCLLs. This methodology is commonly used to produce these regionally specific outputs. Municipalities have their own database and expertise to access and assess these files.

Timeline: Risk assessments should be updated every few years (a reference time span of 5 years can be considered, although this depends of the specificities of each CCLL) as their accuracy is impacted by the types and frequency of hazards as well as the configuration and evolution of the built environment. Consequently, the vulnerability curves and particularly the exposure databases would need to be revised periodically to update the risk assessment.

CCLL Specific Outputs: CCLL Massa, Oarsoaldea and Vilanova can download their exposure database and vulnerability curves from Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/7494631>

The exposure datasets are in Geopackage (GPKG) format and may be opened using QGIS. The vulnerability curves are provided as CSV files. Notably, the exposure and vulnerability models are used to perform the quantitative risk assessments later in WP6, being the "end product", will likely be more useful for CCLLs. Notwithstanding, the exposure and vulnerability models may still be interesting for more technical users within the CCLLs.

Target & End Users :

Local governments, authorities and general decision-makers: Designing an effective adaptation strategy requires these preliminary models/datasets to be developed. Policymakers and decisions makers are becoming more aware of the need to manage natural hazard risks. Example stakeholders are listed below.

- **Massa:** Municipality of Massa, Carrara Municipality, Montignoso Municipality, Municipal Union, and the Province of Massa Carrara. Civil Protection Associations are also listed as civil society stakeholders.
- **Oarsoaldea:** Local government (4 municipalities) and the Oarsoaldea Development Agency Management Board, communications and tourism departments. Regional/Provincial government includes Gipuzkoako Foru Aldundia (province government) Environmental Department. The survey responses from Oarsoaldea mention a role in Regional public administration at the Provincial level.
- **Vilanova:** Calafell City Council and Sitges City Council (neighbouring municipalities). Regional government includes the Barcelona Provincial Council and Catalan Climate Change Office. Neighbouring Gava City Council is also listed.

Insurance companies: These assessments are common for insurance companies to develop risk transfer products, however, the utilisation of these risk assessments by insurance companies will differ from country to country. For example – in Italy, it is not so common to insure buildings against climate hazards, while in the USA it is very normal. As climate change continues, the utilisation of these assessments by insurance companies is anticipated to grow.

Academicians, researchers, and scientists: Researchers and academics in fields such as environmental science, urban planning, and risk management are interested in the methodology and findings for further study and research. This data can contribute to advancing scientific knowledge. Examples identified in the sources within Massa, Oarsoaldea, and Vilanova include:

- Massa: Istituto Istruzione Superiore Meucci di Massa, Consorzio LaMMA, Tuscany Region Settore Difesa del Suolo, National Research Council of Italy - various institutes (ISAC CNR, IBE CNR, ISMAR CNR), University of Florence Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, and the University of Pisa Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra.

- Oarsoaldea: AZTI - Marine Science & Technology, BC3 - Basque Centre for Climate Change, EHU/UPV - University of Basque Country, Aranzadi Zientzia Elkartea - Science Association, CEDEX - Public Works Studies & Experimentation, CEIT, Elhuyar - Advanced Knowledge Application, MU - Mondragon University, Tecnalia - Science & Technology, TECNUN, University of Cantabria - Instituto de Hidráulica, and the University of Deusto.
- Vilanova: Josep Miro, CEM Sea Study Centers, and Obsea UPC Vilanova Underwater Observatory.

Potential Application & Impact

The exposure and vulnerability models, developed alongside other risk assessment tools, offer public authorities a more proactive and integrated approach to climate adaptation. By enabling holistic planning that considers grey, green (EBA), and hybrid solutions, these models support more cost-effective and resilient strategies—for example, combining lower physical barriers with nature-based interventions instead of relying solely on expensive infrastructure. While not directly transferable across all CCLLs or cities, these assessments serve as best practice examples for broader regional or national application. They also foster cross-sector collaboration, particularly between academia, public authorities, and the finance and insurance sectors, ultimately helping quantify and strengthen the financial resilience of coastal cities.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Measures

Because the Knowledge Outputs & KERs from WP6 act in a cumulative capacity, any knowledge transfer actions for the other KERs will by definition include the transfer of this KO.

ANNEX 5 – IMPACT READINESS LEVELS

IRL Level	SRL	TRL	Description of IRL
IRL 1: Conception	SRL 1	TRL 1	Generation and/or identification of new knowledge awaiting validation through experimentation or peer-review
		TRL 2	Research concepts or proposals generated following identification of stakeholder knowledge and evidence needs
		TRL 3	Research knowledge requiring further definition to allow evaluation of the potential value chain Anticipated research outputs require further development to enable progress along the value chain
IRL 2: Discovery	SRL2	TRL 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping and analysis of the stakeholders' landscape in order to grasp the value chain of the envisioned research outputs Definition of knowledge outputs and strategic planning of knowledge transfer activities in order to create value
	SRL3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Successful communication of research to key target audiences at a medium/late stage of the project Research agenda and process are co-designed with the potential stakeholders
IRL 3: Engagement	SRL4	TRL 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of and/or participation in multi-stakeholder events with a common agenda Successful outreach and systematic, planned involvement of various media channels
	SRL5		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific knowledge circulates along various channels in a stakeholder sensitive language
	SRL6		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early systematic exploration with specific stakeholders about requirements, barriers, opportunities for potential application
IRL 4: Implementation	SRL7	TRL 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The basis for research application is established through an iterative co-creation process Consolidation and validation of 'actionable' results of research by stakeholders in practice
	SRL8	TRL 7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First implementation efforts can be demonstrated as single one-off events in a concrete societal context of application Societal and political stakeholders are engaged in research evaluation and support learning feedback loops for researchers
IRL 5: Uptake	SRL9	TRL 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrable uptake of research results and their advancement through policy influence and/or entering an enduring partnership with stakeholders Sustainability of the multi-stakeholder process is planned for in previous stages and appears highly probable Beneficial outcomes on target stakeholder groups are verifiable Research leverages additional research funding and/or a change in the visibility and the positioning of the research organisation

<p>IRL 6: Sustained Change</p>		<p>TRL 9</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrable scale-up and follow-ups both in regional and sectoral terms; emergence of spin-offs • The initiators/researchers are recognised as innovators and are consulted for advice for replication of good practices • Long term research contracts/further commissioned work with Departments/Agencies for sustained policy influence • The application of research in different contexts generates additional demand with funding organisations for further innovative research • Beneficial outcomes are measurable and introduce not merely a change in practice/policy but moreover a sustainable change in mindsets, culture and/or regulation
---	--	--------------	---

